

**ANNUAL SCIENTIFIC REPORT
(Year II)**

**CENTER FOR CARBON RESEARCH IN TROPICAL AGRICULTURE
(CCARBON)/USP**

**RESEARCH, INNOVATION AND DISSEMINATION CENTERS
(CEPID)- FAPESP**

**AUGUST
2025**

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(CEPID)- FAPESP**

Annual Scientific Report (Year II) submitted to The São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP), as part of the requirements for the activities performed in Process: 2021/10573 - Period from September 1st 2024 to August 31th 2025.

**AUGUST
2025**

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ABSTRACT

Brazil is one of the world's largest producers and exporters of food, feed, fiber, and (bio)fuels. Estimates indicate that the country will need to increase food production by 40% to meet global demand by 2050. At the same time, tropical agricultural systems must play a key role in carbon (C) sequestration and the reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, thus contributing to climate change mitigation and adaptation. Therefore, the challenge is to increase agricultural production while ensuring environmental, social, and economic sustainability. In this context, the Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture (CCARBON/USP) was established at ESALQ/USP, one of the most respected agricultural schools in the world. The objective of this report is to present all activities carried out during the second year of CCARBON/USP's operations, covering the period from September 1st, 2024, to August 31st, 2025. The report is divided into three main sections: (i) research, (ii) innovation, and (iii) dissemination, highlighting scientific achievements, technological advances, and outreach initiatives that reinforce CCARBON/USP's role in building sustainable low-carbon agricultural systems. Briefly, CCARBON/USP advanced its research agenda by reorganizing and expanding the initial five thematic research areas into seven multidisciplinary and innovative research chains: (i) Ecosystem Restoration and Conservation, (ii) Forestry, (iii) Blue Carbon, (iv) Integrated Systems, (v) Bioenergy, (vi) Sustainable Livestock, and (vii) Annual Crops. In addition, three cross-cutting areas were consolidated: (i) Measurement, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) technologies, (ii) Climate change impact modeling and assessment, and (iii) Green finance, economic models, public policies, innovations, and governance. Together, these research efforts have generated significant scientific results, enhancing knowledge on soil carbon, biodiversity, climate-smart agricultural practices, and sustainable food systems. In addition, the center also celebrates new public-private projects that provide additional funding and support for the research activities and infrastructure of the center. The center also strengthened its position within the innovation ecosystem by establishing research, development, and innovation (R&D&I) partnerships with national and international institutions, private companies, and public organizations. These initiatives aim to accelerate the development of scalable technologies and practical solutions for low-carbon agriculture, including MRV systems, digital tools, and sustainable production practices. By fostering collaboration across sectors, CCARBON/USP ensures that scientific advances are effectively translated into innovative tools and strategies that can support Brazil's leadership in tropical agriculture and contribute to global sustainability transitions. Dissemination has also been key to ensuring that the knowledge and innovations generated by CCARBON/USP reach diverse audiences and generate real impact. Throughout this period, the center organized scientific events, technical workshops, and training activities, while also participating in national and international conferences. In addition, CCARBON/USP engaged in communication efforts with farmers, policymakers, and society at large, promoting awareness of low-carbon practices and strengthening networks for cooperation. These dissemination strategies not only expand the adoption of sustainable practices but also support evidence-based policymaking and position the center as a global reference in science-driven solutions for climate change mitigation. Such efforts have taken place across multiple levels: at the municipal level, through direct support to local governments and producers; at the state level, by establishing partnerships with research institutions and public agencies; at the national level, via engagement with ministries, federal programs, and policy dialogues; and at the international level, through collaboration with global research networks, contributions to multilateral organizations, and active participation in COP climate negotiations. Altogether, these initiatives demonstrate that CCARBON/USP's activities are deeply aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 2 – Zero Hunger, SDG 12 – Responsible Consumption and Production, SDG 13 – Climate

Action, and SDG 15 – Life on Land. By advancing research, innovation, and dissemination simultaneously across scales, the center reinforces its mission of building sustainable low-carbon agricultural systems that contribute both to Brazil’s leadership in tropical agriculture and to the global sustainability transition.

1 INTRODUCTION

In its second year of operation, CCARBON/USP has achieved significant advances in research, innovation, and dissemination, consolidating a solid foundation for the center's continued development. On June 6, 2025, the University of São Paulo (USP) celebrated the inauguration of the administrative center of the Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture (CCARBON/USP), located on the “Luiz de Queiroz” campus (Esalq/USP) in Piracicaba. Figure 1 illustrates images from inauguration of the CCARBON/USP's building

Figure 1. A) Unveiling of the inaugural plaque; B) CCARBON/USP Directors, ESALQ USP Director, and USP Rector; C) Headquarters (external view); D) Welcoming visitors (internal view).

The highlight of the ceremony was the unveiling of the inaugural plaque bearing the names of USP’s Rector, Professor Carlos Gilberto Carlotti Junior, Vice-Rector Professor Maria Arminda do Nascimento Arruda, and the Center’s Coordinator, Professor Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri.

In addition to the previously mentioned authorities, the ceremony was attended by dozens of guests and dignitaries, including the Directors of Research, Innovation, and Outreach at the center—Maurício Roberto Cherubin, Pedro Henrique Santin Brancalion, and Tiago Osório Ferreira, respectively. The installation of the new administrative hub

marks a milestone in strengthening the initiatives of CCARBON/USP, whose mission is to develop and coordinate innovative solutions to mitigate climate change through tropical agriculture, fostering synergies among academia, the productive sector, public policies, and civil society.

CCARBON/USP's building is composed of administrative offices, meeting rooms, co-working spaces and a gourmet cafeteria. Since the inauguration, the space has been used daily by administrative staff, coordinators, post-docs, students and research partners and many visitors.

In the area of research, CCARBON/USP has focused on deepening knowledge about the role of tropical agriculture in carbon capture and the mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions. This effort has resulted in the publication of several relevant scientific articles, the training of qualified human resources, and the strengthening of strategic partnerships. The five originally structured research areas — soil, plant, animal, atmosphere, and digital tools — were reorganized and expanded into seven strategic, multidisciplinary, and innovative research chains: (i) Ecosystem Restoration and Conservation, (ii) Forestry, (iii) Blue Carbon, (iv) Integrated Systems, (v) Bioenergy, (vi) Sustainable Livestock, (vii) Annual Crops. In addition, three cross-cutting areas were developed: (i) Measurement, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) technologies, (ii) Climate Change Impact Modeling and Assessment, (iii) Green Finance, Economic Models, Public Policies, Innovation, and Governance.

Research activities involve 55 researchers, along with 222 undergraduate and graduate students, as well as postdoctoral researchers, promoting a collaborative and integrated scientific environment. Several studies have been conducted to better understand the role of tropical agricultural systems in climate change mitigation and carbon sequestration, resulting in the publication of 59 scientific papers in high-impact journals. These efforts have led to the publication of articles in high-impact international scientific journals and to CCARBON/USP's recognition as a reference center in low-carbon tropical agriculture. Strategic partnerships with national and international institutions continue to be established, strengthening the collaboration network and driving the development of innovative research projects.

On the innovation front, strategic actions include the promotion of: (i) R&DI partnerships with world-class players in the sector, (ii) Innovation ecosystems, (iii) Discoveries and technologies, (iv) Entrepreneurship, and (v) Public-private partnerships. Innovation activities have been developed in synergy with research projects, aiming to

optimize the use of knowledge and technologies generated to solve practical challenges in the agricultural sector. Although results are still in an early stage, CCARBON/USP remains committed to advancing these initiatives, which hold significant potential to impact low-carbon tropical agriculture and climate change mitigation.

As part of its mission to disseminate knowledge, CCARBON/USP is implementing a comprehensive Scientific Dissemination Plan (SDP), aimed at promoting engagement and awareness on carbon and environmental issues. Actions include the production of documentaries, organization of events, creation of a multilingual project website, training courses for teachers, student competitions, and online courses for rural producers. In addition, CCARBON/USP has begun building an international collaboration network, producing podcasts, e-books, and webinars, as well as publishing scientific papers and technical bulletins. The plan also includes advocacy actions to influence public policies and decision-making processes, such as virtual meetings with government bodies and participation in international forums.

2 GOVERNANCE

The governance structure of CCARBON/USP is organized in a multi-level system that integrates coordination, management, scientific advice, and innovation fostering. At the highest level, the coordination is led by Carlos Eduardo Cerri and Maurício Cherubin, who are responsible for the overall strategic direction of the center. Supporting this coordination, the Management Committee includes researchers such as Pedro Brancalion, Heitor Cantarella, João Luis Carvalho, Carlos Eduardo Cerri, Maurício Cherubin, Tiago Ferreira, Leidivan Frazão, and Mateus Gerolamo, ensuring that strategic decisions and internal management processes are aligned with the objectives of the institution.

In addition to internal governance, the International Scientific Advisory Board brings together globally recognized experts, including Martial Bernoux (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations), Mercedes Bustamante (University of Brasília), Rachel Creamer (Wageningen University), Douglas Karlen (United States Department of Agriculture), Rattan Lal (Ohio State University), Jacques Marcovitch (FEA/USP), Luiz Martinelli (CENA/USP), Francisco Mello (Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture), Pete Smith (University of Aberdeen), and Thais Vieira (ESALQ/USP). This board provides external perspectives and scientific guidance, reinforcing the international credibility and quality of CCARBON/USP's activities. To

stimulate innovation and promote the development of new initiatives, the Fostering Innovation Board, which includes Eduardo Bastos, plays an important role in expanding the center's impact beyond the academic sphere.

The governance structure also relies on an administrative staff composed of Lucila Colcchio, Marcelo Melo, and Eden Vilarinho, who are responsible for supporting operational and managerial activities. Furthermore, the institutional mission is operationalized through three nuclei. The Research Nucleus (NRD) is directed by Maurício Cherubin, with Jessica Campoli serving as project manager, ensuring the scientific coordination of research activities. The Dissemination Nucleus (NDI), directed by Tiago Ferreira, has Juliana Ramiro as dissemination manager, and counts on the support of staff members such as Nayana Alves and Mariana Pollo, who contribute to the administrative and operational activities of the nucleus. Finally, the Innovation Nucleus (NIT), directed by Pedro Brancalion, is dedicated to promoting innovative practices, with the position of innovation manager still to be defined.

Through this integrated structure, CCARBON/USP ensures the articulation between research, dissemination, and innovation, supported by strong coordination, an active management committee, international scientific advice, and a dedicated innovation board, thus consolidating its role as a leading institution in tropical agriculture and sustainability. Figure 2 illustrates CCARBON/USP's Governance.

Figure 2. CCARBON/USP's Governance

The gender distribution of collaborators at CCARBON/USP indicates a relatively balanced composition. According to the data, 7 of the team is male and 5 is female. Although men constitute a slight majority, the figures demonstrate that CCARBON/USP has advanced toward gender balance within its staff. This distribution reflects the center's commitment to diversity and inclusion, ensuring that both male and female professionals are represented in its research, dissemination, and innovation activities. Figure 3 presents the gender of CCARBON/USP collaborators.

Figure 3. Gender of CCARBON/USP collaborators

During its second year of operation, CCARBON/USP held four meetings of its Management Committee: the 7th on November 28, 2024; the 8th on February 20, 2025; the 9th on May 22, 2025; and the 10th on August 21, 2025. These meetings play a key role in aligning the Center's strategic vision, monitoring progress across research and outreach initiatives, and ensuring that decisions are taken collectively and transparently. They also serve as a space to evaluate the impact of CCARBON/USP's actions, strengthen institutional partnerships, and identify emerging opportunities to enhance the Center's contribution to science, innovation, and society.

On August 25th, 2025, the second meeting of the *International Scientific Advisory Board* was held, starting at 10:00 AM and ending at 12h00AM. The meeting was organized in a hybrid format, with in person and videoconferencing participation. The participants were: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri (CCARBON/USP), Maurício Roberto Cherubin (CCARBON/USP), Pedro Brancalion (CCARBON/USP), Douglas Karlen (USDA–Agricultural Research Service), Francisco Mello (Instituto Interamericano de

Cooperación para la Agricultura – IICA), Jacques Marcovitch (FEA/USP), Mercedes Maria da Cunha Bustamante (Universidade de Brasília), Rattan Lal (Ohio State University) and Martial Bernoux (Food and Agriculture – FAO). In addition, the members of the Management Committee João Luis Nunes Carvalho (The Brazilian Center for Research in Energy and Materials – CNPEM), Heitor Cantarella (Agronomic Institute – IAC) and, Leidivan Frazão (Federal University of Minas Gerais- UFMG), as well as CCARBON's staff Jessica Suarez Campoli (CCARBON/USP), Juliana Ramiro (CCARBON/USP), Lucila Colichio (CCARBON/USP) also attended in the meeting.

The objective of the meeting was to present the progress of CCARBON in its second year of activities. The Director of CCARBON, Professor Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, gave a general overview of the center activities and governance. The other directors then complemented the presentation. Innovation Director Pedro Brancalion presented some of the activities on the CCARBON/USP innovation front from the first years of the Center's development. Among the innovation strategies, he highlighted international partnerships and promoted private partnerships. The Research Director, Professor Maurício Roberto Cherubin, presented the new research structure of CCARBON/USP. He explained that the five original research areas — soil, plant, animal, atmosphere, and digital tools — were reorganized and expanded into seven strategic, multidisciplinary, and innovative research chains: (i) Ecosystem Restoration and Conservation, (ii) Forestry, (iii) Blue Carbon, (iv) Integrated Systems, (v) Bioenergy, (vi) Sustainable Livestock, and (vii) Annual Crops. In addition, three cross-cutting areas were established: (i) Measurement, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) technologies, (ii) Climate Change Impact Modeling and Assessment, and (iii) Green Finance, Economic Models, Public Policies, Innovation, and Governance. Professor Cherubin also highlighted CCARBON/USP's scientific production, with over 60 publications, as well as the consolidation of public–private partnerships aimed at strengthening investments in research.

In the sequence, The CCARBON/USP Director Carlos Eduardo Cerri highlighted that CCARBON/USP developed multiple activities of dissemination (events, digital media, publications, podcast and advocacy). Finally, it presented the actions of the center in different levels of society from municipal to international. Finally, space was opened for discussions and members of the International Scientific Advisory Board asked questions and made general suggestions for the next year's activities.

3 RESEARCH

The sectoral chains defined in CCARBON/USP's research strategy have evolved over time. Initially, as presented in Figure 6, they were organized in a broader and more conceptual manner, with emphasis on the main research components (soil, plant, animal, atmosphere, and digital tools) and their respective lines of action.

Figure 6. Research action strategy from CCARBON/USP

Starting in 2025, with the advancement of projects and the expansion of scientific and strategic demands, the center adopted a new multidimensional research matrix, structured around:

Two Main Thematic Pillars:

- Carbon Removal (Sequestration of Carbon)
- Greenhouse Gases (GHG) Emission Reduction

These pillars guide all the center's actions, being applied integrally across the seven sectoral research chains (Figure 7):

Sectoral Chains:

a) Ecosystem Restoration and Conservation

Focus on strategies to restore degraded ecosystems with the aim of increasing carbon stocks (in soil and biomass), recovering biodiversity, and improving ecosystem services.

b) Forestry

Focus on forest systems (such as planted forests and agroforestry systems — SAFs) and their potential to sequester carbon (in soil and biomass) and reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

c) Blue Carbon

Focus on the potential of coastal ecosystems (especially mangroves) to sequester carbon and provide other ecosystem services.

d) Integrated Systems

Focus on the potential of integrated systems, such as crop-livestock, crop-livestock-forest, and livestock-forest systems, to promote carbon sequestration and reduce GHG emissions.

e) Bioenergy

Focus on the potential of energy crops and agro-industrial residues for bioenergy production (biogas, bioethanol, solid biomass), contributing to carbon sequestration and emissions reduction.

f) Sustainable Livestock

Focus on animal management practices with lower GHG emissions (such as methane), improved feed efficiency, animal welfare, and integration with managed and regenerative pasture systems.

g) Annual Crops

Focus on the potential of sustainable management practices adopted in major annual crops to reduce emissions and increase resilience.

Transversal Research Areas:

The Transversal Research Areas were designed to support, integrate, and enhance the scientific impact of the Sectoral Chains, providing analytical, methodological, and strategic tools that enable a systemic and evidence-based approach. These areas are not tied to a single production chain but span the entire thematic matrix of CCARBON/USP, fostering the articulation of data, policies, finance, and innovation.

They are essential for evaluating, monitoring, and enabling the adoption of sustainable technologies and practices aimed at carbon sequestration and the reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in tropical agriculture.

Below are the three transversal areas:

h) MRV Technologies (Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification Technologies)

Development of technologies for monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV), including new methodologies for carbon analysis, flux towers, remote sensing, modeling, mapping, certification, traceability, scenario analysis, and life cycle assessment (LCA).

i) Modeling Impact Assessment due to Climate Change

Development and application of models to assess the impacts of climate change on natural and socio-economic systems.

j) Green Finances, Economic Models, Public Policies, Innovations, and Governance

Investigation of sustainable financial mechanisms, economic models for the green transition, and the role of public policies and governance in promoting innovations that foster sustainable development. Figure 7 illustrates this new structure.

Figure 7. CCARBON/USP's Research Sectorial chain

This new structure aims to integrate production chains and strategic themes into a systemic and interconnected approach, focusing on increasing the scientific and technological impact of CCARBON/USP in promoting a low-carbon tropical agriculture. This evolution reflects the maturation of the research strategy, which transitioned from an initial conceptual framework to a clear operational structure with well-defined sectoral chains, specific technologies, cross-cutting methodologies, and explicit consideration of co-benefits.

CCARBON/USP team currently brings together 55 researchers and 222 students (Figure 8), forming a diverse and multidisciplinary network that spans national and international institutions. The researchers affiliated with CCARBON/USP come from diverse backgrounds, reflecting a broad network of national and international scientific collaboration. The majority are associated with the University of São Paulo (USP), which accounts for 41 researchers (75%), but 25% come from other key University and research Institutions across the country and abroad (Figure 8).

Figure 8. CCARBON/USP' team formed by researchers (internal and external from USP) and students.

The gender composition of researchers affiliated with CCARBON/USP shows a predominance of male researchers (44) while female researchers represent 11. Figure 9 presents this composition.

Figure 9. Gender composition of CCARBON/USP researchers

CCARBON/USP currently has 222 participants engaged in its Scientific Initiation Program, MSc., Ph.D. students, and Postdoctoral researchers. The largest proportion corresponds to Ph.D. candidates (36%), followed by MSc. candidates (23%) and postdoctoral researchers (24%). Additionally, 17% are undergraduate students participating in the Scientific Initiation Program. This reflects CCARBON/USP's engagement in fostering research capacity at multiple stages of higher education and professional development. Figure 10 illustrates this distribution.

Figure 10. CCARBON/USP Scientific Initiation Program, M.Sc., Ph.D. students and Postdoctoral researchers (PD)

Figure 11 shows the institution distribution among CCARBON/USP's students (Scientific Initiation Program, M.Sc. and Ph.D.) and Postdoctoral researchers. The

majority, representing 68%, are affiliated with the University of São Paulo (USP), which highlights the central role of the university in fostering research and training within the program. Meanwhile, 32% of the participants come from other institutions, including both national and international universities (Argentina, France and Italy), reflecting the collaborative and multidisciplinary nature of CCARBON/USP's activities. This balance underscores USP's strong leadership while also emphasizing the network of external partnerships that enrich the center's research environment.

Figure 11. Institution distribution among CCARBON/USP's students and Postdoctoral researchers

Figure 12 shows the gender distribution among CCARBON/USP's students (Scientific Initiation Program, M.Sc. and Ph.D.) and Postdoctoral researchers. The data reveal that men represent the majority (approximately 55%), while women account for 45% of the total. This distribution highlights the current gender profile of the academic participants engaged in research and training activities within the center.

Figure 12. Gender distribution among CCARBON/USP's students and Postdoctoral researchers

Figure 13 illustrates the distribution of scholarships linked to CCARBON/USP. Most students (66%) are supported by non-budgetary scholarships, funded by external agencies or specific projects. Meanwhile, 19% of participants carry out their activities without any scholarship, and 15% receive budgetary scholarships, financed by the university's internal resources. These figures highlight the crucial role of external partnerships in sustaining and expanding the center's research activities, while also pointing to the need for strengthening institutional budgetary support.

Figure 13. Distribution of scholarships linked to CCARBON/USP

Figure 14 illustrates the scientific output of CCARBON/USP between 2023 and 2025. In 2023, the center began its activities with only 1 published paper, but in 2024 there was a significant increase to 19 papers, reaching a cumulative total of 20 publications. In 2025, the growth accelerated further, with 41 papers published in that year alone, achieving a cumulative total of 61 publications over the period analyzed. This progression highlights the rapid consolidation of CCARBON/USP as an academic reference, demonstrating not only quantitative growth but also the center's ability to structure and expand its research lines in a short time, reinforcing its contribution to scientific and technological advances in tropical agriculture and in climate and sustainability agendas.

Figure 14. Papers of CCARBON/USP between 2023 and 2025

These papers (Figure 14) correspond to those that include affiliation to CCARBON/USP and/or acknowledgment of the FAPESP process n° 2021/10573-4. However, throughout the report, several additional results related to CCARBON/USP research are also presented, even though they do not explicitly mention the center's affiliation or the FAPESP process number in the acknowledgments. The complete list of all publications reported in is listed in Section 5.1 Publications – Scientific Papers. In the following section, each research chain will be presented in detail, along with the main activities and achievements developed during CCARBON/USP's second year of operation.

3.1 Sectorial chain: Ecosystem Restoration and Conservation

Research Sector Chain Coordinator: Pedro Henrique Santin Brancalion

3.1.1 Part 1: General

The research activities of the supply chain “ecosystem conservation and restoration” covered a broad range of fields, providing a comprehensive analysis of the various opportunities to both reduce GHG emissions and to remove them from the atmosphere. Three projects focused on understanding carbon stocks in different forest types and degradation conditions, including veredas in Minas Gerais state, with a focus on soil carbon dynamics, and different types of native forests in São Paulo state, targeting both degraded forests in Botucatu and conserved forests at Caetetus (Seasonal Semideciduous Forest) and Assis (Cerradão woodland) Ecological Stations – this latter project has also used the 10-ha permanent plots established in both ecological stations to develop innovative approaches to monitor carbon and biodiversity through remote sensing. Together, these projects will characterize reference ecosystems to be used as benchmarks for carbon stocks in alternative land uses. Two projects focused on the assessment of varied reforestation and restoration approaches to recover carbon stocks, biodiversity, and ecosystem services. The first is an ambitious project that established nearly 800 plots (30x30 m) across five reforestation methods (naturally regenerating forests, restoration plantings, tree monocultures with and without regeneration, and agroforests) and three reference systems (agropastoral lands, degraded forests, conserved forests), distributed in broader environmental conditions in the Atlantic Forest. The other evaluated the effectiveness of grazing exclusion as a management strategy to restore Caatinga (Ceará), evaluating soil health and carbon stocks. Five initiatives focused on the assessment of soil biota and its impacts on carbon dynamics, including the evaluation of (i) microbial necromass using HPLC in soil samples collected from diverse biomes and land-use types; (ii) the role of methanotrophy in carbon sequestration at different stages of forest succession, pastures, and conserved forests in the Amazon (Rondônia); (iii) soil microbial

diversity in amazonian agroforestry systems and its influence on the development of açai palm; (iv) the contribution of earthworms, ants and termites to soil carbon and nitrogen stabilization, and soil hydrophysical properties; and (v) microbial dynamics of biocrusts and their role in carbon sequestration in the Caatinga. Finally, four projects focused on the manipulation of soil properties through the addition of (i) silicate rock powders (diabase, phonolite, and granite), (ii) biochar produced with sewage sludge, and sterile residues from mining; these projects have evaluated the impacts of these treatments in soil carbon stocks and biota, as well as in vegetation growth. Fulfilling CCARBON/USP's mission, these experiments have assessed native ecosystems and soil types across several Brazilian regions and critical ecosystem processes governing carbon fluxes, as well as emerging technologies to leverage the contribution of tropical agriculture to mitigate climate change. Most of these projects are in an early to intermediate stage of development, but have already resulted in bold scientific contributions, with 15 papers published in leading academic journals and 6 MSc thesis and 10 PhD dissertations defended. We also highlight the valuable contributions of these projects to capacitate a new generation of researchers to better integrate conservation and production across productive landscapes.

3.1.2 Part 2: Carbon removal

(A) Principal Investigator: Pedro H. S. Brancalion

Technology: Afforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: reforestation - assessment of carbon stocking and biodiversity co-benefits across reforestation methods and conditions

Summary of achievements: (i) We concluded the establishment of 867 30 x 30 m plots across five reforestation methods (naturally regenerating forests, restoration plantings, tree monocultures with and without regeneration, and agroforests) and three reference systems (agropastoral lands, degraded forests, conserved forests), distributed in broader environmental conditions in the Atlantic Forest. We measured the carbon stocks in different pools (aboveground and belowground living biomass, dead wood, coarse debris, litter, fine roots, and soil), tree diversity, soil water infiltration and several climatic, edaphic, and landscape drivers of forest development. We found that monoculture tree plantations had the highest total carbon stock in vegetation ($\sim 350 \text{ Mg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$ in 20 years), which was even higher than that found in conserved and degraded remnants ($\sim 300 \text{ Mg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$) and more than double of agroforests, naturally regenerating forests, and restoration plantings ($\sim 150 \text{ Mg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$ in 20 years). The drivers of carbon stock recovery varied across reforestation methods, with method-specific relationships with climate, soil, and landscape variables. Based on these relationships, we built equations to predict over time the carbon stock per pool for each reforestation method. Regarding tree diversity, conserved forests maintained the highest average Shannon diversity, but naturally regenerating forests and restoration plantings approached diversity levels of degraded forests. Species composition of naturally regenerating forests most closely resembled conserved forests. Restoration plantings and agroforests showed the highest compositional overlap across sites, reducing overall richness. (ii) As far as we are concerned, our database is the most comprehensive assessment of tropical reforestation performance. We explored how diversity and carbon varied across these methods through

varied perspectives, which resulted in five publications, including synthesis and review papers about this research topic. (iii) we will conclude the analysis on carbon and tree diversity recovery to prepare and submit research papers, as well advance with the analysis of soil carbon stock recovery.

Team members: PIs: Pedro H. S. Brancalion, Ricardo R. Rodrigues and Renato F. Lima (ESALQ/USP), Paulo G. Molin (CCA/UFSCar), Lourens Poorter, Marielos Peña-Claros, Frans Bongers (Wageningen University and Research); PAs: Marisa Piccolo (CENA/USP), Miguel Cooper (ESALQ/USP), Ricardo Viani (CCA/UFSCAR), Silvio Ferraz (ESALQ/USP), Simone Vieira (NEPAM/UNICAMP), Vinicius Castro-Souza (ESALQ/USP), Joannes Guillemot (CIRAD)

Students:

Post-docs: Angélica Resende (ESALQ/USP, FAPESP: 2019/24049-5), Pedro Krainovic (ESALQ/USP, FAPESP: 22/07712-5), Fábio Matos (ESALQ/USP, FAPESP: 2024/07707-7), Laura Simões (ESALQ/USP, FAPESP: 25/01346-5) – none of these were directly funded by CCARBON/USP or received a support letter

PhD: Amanda Cook (ESALQ/USP, FAPESP 2025/06714-2, directly funded by CCARBON/USP), Gabriela Albuquerque, José Guedes, Frederico Miranda (all ESALQ/USP, CAPES, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a support letter)

MSc: Ary Toledo: (ESALQ/USP, CAPES, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a support letter)

Results: Papers published:

Brancalion, Pedro H. S., Fangyuan Hua, Francis H. Joyce, Alexandre Antonelli, and Karen D. Holl. "Moving Biodiversity from an Afterthought to a Key Outcome of Forest Restoration." *Nature Reviews Biodiversity* 1, no. 4 (2025/04/01 2025): 248-61. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s44358-025-00032-1>.

Brouwer, Rens, Marielos Peña-Claros, Frans Bongers, Lourens Poorter, Joannès Guillemot, Danilo R. A. Almeida, Catherine Torres de Almeida, Angélica F. Resende, Laura H. P. Simões, Natália M. Ivanauskas, Renato A. Ferreira de Lima, Vinicius Castro Souza, Cássio A. P. Toledo, Miguel Cooper, José Guedes Fernandes Neto, Mathieu Decuyper, Paulo G. Molin, Ricardo R. Rodrigues, and Pedro H. S. Brancalion. "Functional Recovery of Tropical Forests: The Role of Restoration Methods and Environmental Conditions." *Biological Conservation* 309 (2025/09/01/ 2025): 111269. <http://dx.doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111269>.

Chazdon, Robin L., Nico Blüthgen, Pedro H. S. Brancalion, Viola Heinrich, and Frans Bongers. "Drivers and Benefits of Natural Regeneration in Tropical Forests." *Nature Reviews Biodiversity* 1, no. 5 (2025/05/01 2025): 298-314. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s44358-025-00043-y>.

dos Reis Oliveira, Paula C., Gabriel Arantes Ferreira Gualda, Gustavo Fiedler Rossi, Antônio Fernando Monteiro Camargo, Solange Filoso, Pedro Henrique Brancalion, and Silvio Frosini de Barros Ferraz. "Forest Restoration Improves Habitat and Water Quality

in Tropical Streams: A Multiscale Landscape Assessment." *Science of the Total Environment* 963 (2025/02/01/ 2025): 178256. <http://dx.doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.178256>.

Simões, Laura H. P., Marielos Peña-Claros, Joannès Guillemot, Rens Brouwer, Frans Bongers, Lourens Poorter, Catherine T. de Almeida, Danilo R. A. Almeida, Miguel Cooper, Mathieu Decuyper, José G. Fernandes Neto, Matheus S. Fuza, Renato A. F. Lima, Juliano van Melis, Paulo G. Molin, Angélica F. Resende, Ricardo R. Rodrigues, Vinicius C. Souza, Ari F. de Toledo, Cássio A. P. Toledo, and Pedro H. S. Brancalion. "Recovery of Tree Species Functional Composition in Eucalypt Plantations with Natural Regeneration Differs among Canopy Strata." *Forest Ecology and Management* 594 (2025/10/15/ 2025): 122952. <http://dx.doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2025.122952>.

PhD dissertations defended: Rens Brouwer, Laura Simões, Frederico Miranda

(B) Principal Investigator: Fernando Dini Andreote

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Soil Biology

Summary of achievements: Activities Performed During the Period: Completion of PhD course credits. Assessment of microbial necromass using HPLC in soil samples collected from diverse biomes and land-use types. Integration and preliminary analysis of obtained results. Work Plan for the Next Period: Selection of representative areas for soil collection. Subsequent soil characterization, DNA extraction, sequencing, and microbial ecology analysis. Continued data analysis and initiation of writing the first research article.

Team members: Fernando Dini Andreote, PI, Brazilian Supervisor, (ESALQ/USP). Rafael Santana Mendonça, PhD Candidate, Graduate Program Soil and Plant Nutrition (ESALQ/USP). The scholarship is not directly funded by, but received a support letter from CCARBON/USP. The scholarship is funded by CAPES (process number 88887.952516/2024-00).

Technology: Soil carbon, Enhanced weathering

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Enhanced weathering for organic and inorganic carbon removal

Summary of achievements: (i) During this period, we carried out soil collection, setup, and conduction of the first experiment of the research project. The study involves the application of three silicate rock powders (diabase, phonolite, and granite) at doses of 0.0, 1.5, 7.5, and 15.0 Mg ha⁻¹. Pots were maintained without plants, and a standardized solution of 15 root-exuded compounds (artificial rhizosphere) was periodically applied. Soil samples were collected at 1 and 3 months for biochemical and physical analyses. Enzymatic activity (β -glucosidase and dehydrogenase), microbial biomass carbon (MBC), water retention capacity, and soil penetration resistance were evaluated. (ii) Preliminary results indicate that rock powders enhance enzymatic activities and microbial biomass carbon compared to controls. Notably, the soil treated with rock powders

exhibited higher resistance to penetration under the same bulk density, suggesting increased particle cohesion or aggregate stability. (iii) The next phase will investigate whether the observed improvement in soil aggregation is mediated by microbial activity, particularly through the contribution of applied carbon sources and microbial necromass. The experiment will run until month 12, with additional soil sampling scheduled at months 6, 9, and 12. Analyses of microbial community structure and function will be conducted throughout these timepoints. Carbon tracing and fractionation studies (aimed at determining the role of microbial residues in aggregate formation) will be carried out after the final sampling, to capture the cumulative effects over time.

Team members: Fernando Dini Andreote, PI, Brazilian, (ESALQ/USP) Rafael Lima Oliveira, PhD student, Brazilian, (ESALQ/USP) (i) No (ii) Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo (FAPESP, grant number 2025/00432-5) (iii) Yes, a CCARBON/USP cover letter was used in the scholarship submission process.

(C) Principal Investigator: Leidivan Almeida Frazão

Technology: Soil carbon, Wetland restoration

Key questions addressed/Research area: Carbon monitoring in human-modified vereda (palm swamp) areas of the Brazilian Cerrado

Summary of achievements: Wetlands are ecosystems that play a vital role in maintaining biodiversity and providing essential ecosystem services. Veredas (palm swamps) are a type of phytophysiology in the Brazilian Cerrado characterized by hydrophilic plant communities associated with the palm *Mauritia flexuosa* L.f. These environments play a fundamental role in maintaining hydrological balance and hold great ecological importance, as well as a unique social significance. Although veredas are legally recognized as Permanent Preservation Areas (APPs), human occupation and land use in their natural areas have led to the degradation and exhaustion of these environments. This project is part of the PELD-VERE research site (CNPq Process 445976/2024-1). During the first six months of activity, veredas at different stages of anthropogenic disturbance (preserved, moderately disturbed, and under degraded conditions) were identified, and sampling sites were established to monitor soil carbon dynamics. The next step was to assess the dynamics of total and microbial soil organic carbon across different altitudinal gradients of veredas impacted by climatic and anthropogenic actions, as well as to determine the amount of carbon stored in soil profiles in response to these climatic and anthropogenic changes.

Team members: Leidivan Almeida Frazão (PI), (UFMG); Jaqueline de Cassia de Oliveira (Post-doc), (UFMG), Marco Antônio Couto Barbosa (IC), (UFMG)

(D) Principal Investigator: Rodrigo E. Hakamada

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Alternative multi-functional forest system to restore degraded lands

Summary of achievements: Under the umbrella of "ReflorestaSP" project, we are studying mixed species plantation to restore degraded lands achieving objectives of

restoring of ecosystem services by using native species and at the same time produce forest products, by inserting fast growing trees in part of the area.

Team members: Rodrigo Hakamada, PI (ESALQ/USP), Pedro Brancalion, PI (ESALQ/USP), Desiree Lopes, PhD (ESALQ/USP), Tiago Marcilio Pinto, MSc (ESALQ/USP).

Results:

Conference paper:

Pinto, T. M. G., Brancalion, P. H. S., Hakamada, R. E. (2025). Does the use of eucalyptus in the Legal Reserve impact the growth of native species and the accumulation of biomass in the restoration?. Congresso de Plantações Florestais, IPEF.

Domingos, A. G. M. M., Barbieri, J. G. B., Brancalion, P. H. S., Campoe, O. C., Hakamada, R. E. (2025). Atlantic forest biomass production after 20 years of forest restoration by different methods. Congresso de Plantações Florestais, IPEF.

(E) Associate Research: Antonio Carlos de Azevedo

Technology: Enhanced weathering

Key questions addressed/Research area: Carbon Dioxide Removal using Enhanced Rock Weathering

Summary of achievements: (i) We concluded one PhD thesis, One PhD student (Thairis) is in an international training (Marrocos); Finished the contract with Newcastle University (UK) funded by Grantham Foundation to establish a field experiment to do measurements in carbon capture with ERW; Hosted the V Brazilian Stonemeal Congress in Piracicaba; (ii) Published one paper as co-author of Dr. David Manning and is preparing a second one; Hosted the V Brazilian Stonemeal Congress in Piracicaba (300 people from 20 Brazilian States); Submitted a proposal to Imperial College-Aucani-USP for a meeting between the two universities in this theme, Invited poster at the American Geophysical Union annual meeting (iii) Advancement in the methods and mechanisms of CDR with ERW; expecting approval of proposals submitted.

Team members: Antonio Carlos de Azevedo (PA), Students: Luis Fernando Vieira da Silva/PhD, finished/ PPG SNP ESALQ, not funded by CCARBON/USP, CAPES 88887513846/2020-00 Thairis Gomes Santos/ PhD, ongoing/ PPG SNP ESALQ, not funded by CCARBON/USP, CAPES 888878223512023-00 Mariana Faria Mendes MSc, ongoing/ PPG SNP ESALQ, not funded by CCARBON/USP, CAPES 88887175829202500 Juliana Costa do Nascimento/ PhD, ongoing/ PPG SNP ESALQ, not funded by CCARBON/USP, CAPES

Results:

Publication:

Precipitation of amorphous iron and aluminum during the weathering of rock dust in soil columns, DOI 10.1590/1678-992X-2023-0219 ; Soil carbon management and enhanced rock weathering: The separate fates of organic and inorganic carbon, DOI 10.1111/EJSS.13534; Changes in soil bacterial community structure in a short-term trial

with different silicate rock powders, 10.1186/S40538-024-00586-W; A scientometric review of research on sapolite in Brazil from 1990 to 2022, DOI 1590/1807-1929/AGRIAMBI.V29N1E280446

Thesis:

Contribuição do sapolito na estimativa do intemperismo aprimorado de rocha: revisão exploratória e estudo de caso, Luis Fernando Vieira da Silva

(F) Associate Research: Arthur Prudêncio de Araújo Pereira

Technology 1: Afforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Recovery of areas undergoing desertification in the semi-arid region

Summary of achievements: Brazil has the most populous semiarid region in the world, covering an area of 982,566 km². Agricultural use in the region, such as livestock grazing on extensive pastures, has been causing significant changes to the soil, especially when land-use change (LUC) involves the conversion of native forest (Caatinga). However, the impacts of LUC on soil health are still poorly studied in the region. Chemical, physical, and biological indicators are rarely integrated through tools that generate soil quality indices. A holistic assessment is urgently needed, as the semiarid region is predominantly covered by the Caatinga biome, a biodiversity hotspot unique to Brazil. The effectiveness of grazing exclusion (GE) as a soil management strategy in areas degraded by overgrazing is poorly documented for the semiarid. Therefore, the hypothesis that GE restores soil quality/functions, and that this influence increases with GE time, will be tested. Soil samples will be collected at the Irauçuba Desertification Nucleus (Ceará). Three scenarios will be evaluated: (i) Native Caatinga (NC), (ii) Degraded Pasture (DP — area adjacent to NC, converted to pasture), and (iii) Grazing Exclusion (area of DP under natural recovery, fenced off from animals for 21 years). We will assess physical properties (bulk density, porosity, and aggregate stability), chemical properties (macro- and micronutrient contents and acidity attributes), and biological properties (total organic carbon, microbial carbon, glomalin content, enzymatic activity, and microbial diversity through DNA sequencing). Univariate and multivariate analyses will be applied to analyze the data.

Team members: Arthur Prudêncio de Araujo Pereira, Maurício Roberto Cherubin, Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega, Ruggeri Mikahaknem M. Santos e Katriny Kellen da Silva Negreiros (estudantes de mestrado)

Technology 2: Biochar

Key questions addressed/Research area: Use of biochar in the restoration of degraded soils

Summary of achievements: Project approved under call 02/2021 Funcap-Cagece, with a multi- and interdisciplinary team that will carry out five studies aimed at demonstrating that sewage sludge used to produce biochar is promising for improving the physical, chemical, and biological quality of the soil when mixed with a second biomass source and processed through the hydrothermal process.

Team members: Arthur Prudêncio de Araujo Pereira, Francisco Luan Almeida Barbosa (estudante de doutorado)

Results: Barbosa, F.L.A., Santos, J.M.R., Mota, J.C.A. et al. Potential of biochar to restoration of microbial biomass and enzymatic activity in a highly degraded semiarid soil. *Sci Rep* 14, 26065 (2024).

(G) Associate Research: Iraê Amaral Guerrini

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management, Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Quantification of carbon and ecosystem services in natural forest and in restoration areas.

Summary of achievements: We have two projects in this line. The first project, about natural recovery of different Semideciduous Seasonal Atlantic Forest fragments, at UNESP Campus in Botucatu, was evaluated in 2017, with the defense of a doctoral and a master's student and reevaluated in 2022 by another doctoral student. The results are still being published, comparing the different preservation states of the fragments with the quantification of carbon in the systems, measured by an innovative methodology from UNESP, and the biodiversity of flora, fauna, micro-, and macroorganisms in the soil, in addition to comparisons with satellite and drone surveys. The results indicate that better-preserved fragments have higher amounts of C and bird biodiversity. Soil macro- and microorganism levels are being evaluated with partial results. The next steps are to complete these soil biodiversity surveys, continue the assessment of small and medium-sized animals, and repeat the Carbon surveys in 2027 and every 5 years. A similar study under Mediterranean conditions was also carried out on the island of Sardinia, Italy, and continues to be evaluated in terms of soil biodiversity. Another project is to carry out surveys to quantify carbon and ecosystem services in natural areas of the Amazon and other biomes with the aim of generating carbon credits.

Team members: PIs: Iraê Amaral Guerrini, Renata Batista Fonseca and Bruno Rossini (FCA-UNESP-Botucatu), Celso Marino and José Raimundo Sousa Passos (IB-UNESP-Botucatu); Gian Franco Capra and Antonio Ganga (UNISS-Università degli Studi di Sassari, Sardinia, Italy); PAs: Alessandro Zabotto (FCA-UNESP-Botucatu). Students: Post-doc: Deicy C. L. Sivisaca (FCA-UNESP; BMV Program); PhD: Deicy C. L. Sivisaca (FCA-UNESP; SENESCYT-Ecuador); Ludmila Ribeiro Roder (UNISS-Università degli Studi di Sassari, Sardinia, Italy); Sérvio Túlio Pereira Justino, Leonardo José Silva da Costa, Mellina Nicácio da Luz and Rafael Barroca da Silva (all FCA-UNESP, CAPES, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a support letter) MSc: Felipe Góes de Moraes, Jaqueline Pinheiro da Silva, Ludmila Ribeiro Roder, Matheus Fontes Souza (all FCA-UNESP, CAPES, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a support letter) I.C.: Magda Santos, Pietro Brown, Maria Fernanda Vieira Mendes, Mariana Varoni Alves, Roberta Selingardi, Nildaiane Luzia de Sales (all FCA-UNESP-Botucatu, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a support letter).

Results:

GUERRINI, IRAÊ AMARAL; DA SILVA, JAQUELINE PINHEIRO ; LOZANO SIVISACA, DEICY CAROLINA ; DE MORAES, FELIPE GÓES ; PUGLLA, CELSO ANIBAL YAGUANA ; DE MELO SILVA NETO, CARLOS ; BARROCA SILVA, RAFAEL ; PEREIRA JUSTINO, SÉRVIO TÚLIO ; RODER, LUDMILA RIBEIRO ; JAMES, JASON NATHANIEL ; CAPRA, GIAN FRANCO ; GANGA, ANTONIO . Evaluating carbon stocks in soils of fragmented Brazilian Atlantic Forests (BAF) based on soil features and different methodologies. *Scientific Reports*, v. 14, p. 1, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-60629-y>

SIVISACA, DEICY CAROLINA LOZANO ; PUGLLA, CELSO ANIBAL YAGUANA ; PASSOS, JOSÉ RAIMUNDO DE SOUZA ; Fonseca, Renata Cristina Batista ; GANGA, ANTONIO ; CAPRA, GIAN FRANCO ; GUERRINI, IRAÊ AMARAL . Atlantic forest regeneration dynamics following human disturbance cessation in Brazil. *Environments*, v. 11, p. 243, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments11110243>

RODER, LUDMILA RIBEIRO ; GUERRINI, IRAÊ AMARAL ; LOZANO SIVISACA, DEICY CAROLINA ; YAGUANA PUGLLA, CELSO ANIBAL ; GÓES DE MORAES, FELIPE ; PINHEIRO DA SILVA, JAQUELINE ; BATISTA FONSECA, RENATA CRISTINA ; UMBELINO, MARIA TEREZA ; JAMES, JASON NATHANIEL ; CAPRA, GIAN FRANCO ; GANGA, ANTONIO . Atlantic rainforest natural regeneration in fragmented formations affected by increasing human disturbance. *JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT*, v. 325, p. 116521, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116521>

Roder, Ludmila Ribeiro; Guerrini, Iraê Amaral; Ganga, Antonio; Silva, Rafael Barroca; Farris, Emmanuele; Alfredo, Lorena Chagas; Keller, Thomas; Capra, Gian Franco. The influence of soil physical-chemical properties and land uses on organic carbon stocks in contrasting Mediterranean pedosystems. *Catena*, 2025 (Submitted).

Justino, Sérgio Túlio Pereira; Silva, Rafael Barroca; Sivisaca, Deicy Carolina Lozano; Roder, Ludmila Ribeiro, Sales, Nildaiane Luzia; Selingardi, Roberta; Alves, Mariana Varoni; Ganga, Antonio; Capra, Gian Franco; Guerrini, Iraê Amaral. Above- and below-ground carbon stock in the Atlantic Forest at different levels of anthropogenic disturbance. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 2025. (Submitted).

Silva, Rafael Barroca; Justino, Servio Tulio Pereira; Costa, Leonardo José Silva; Luz, Mellina Nicácio; Silva, Maicon dos Santos; Sales, Nildaiane Luzia; Alves Mariana Varoni; Selingardi, Roberta; Fritz, Gabriel Fratta; Souza, Matheus Fontes; Roder, Ludmila Ribeiro; Paganini, Enzo Antonio Lecciole; Rossini, Bruno Cesar; Capra, Gian Franco; Ganga, Antonio; Marino, Celso Luis; Guerrini, Iraê Amaral. Enzymatic activity and other soil characteristics as indicators of preservation degree of Brazilian Atlantic Forest. *Forest, Ecology and Management*, 2025 (Submitted).

PhD dissertations defended:

Deicy Carolina Lozano Sivisaca; Sérgio Túlio Pereira Justino; Ludmila Ribeiro Roder; Rafael Barroca da Silva.

MSc dissertations defended:

Jaqueline Pinheiro da Silva;

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management, Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Use of organic residues in forest fertilization

Summary of achievements: This research line is about the use of organic residues to increase soil carbon stock, soil fertility and plant growth. This line of work presents four main projects. The first one involves the application of different doses of sewage sludge to restore a degraded area by planting native Atlantic Forest species at Suzano Company in Itatinga-SP. The results showed increased soil fertility and carbon, as well as greater initial growth of the species compared to chemical fertilizer treatments. New measurements and sample collections will be carried out this year. The second project (Edital PITE - FAPESP/SABESP - Processo 13/50413-0) involves the production of organic compost using sewage sludge produced at Sabesp's ETE in Botucatu, São Paulo, testing eucalyptus bark, sugarcane bagasse, and rice husks as carbon sources. The products resulting from composting were tested in forest seedlings production, eucalyptus and other crops growth. Results are being published yet. The third project is about the application of sewage sludge in forest restoration area, trying to get a faster growth of native species with less herbicides, fertilizers, etc. It is in progress and we will have publications next year. The fourth one is about the use of sewage sludge in urban soils from Italy and Brazil and the research is in progress.

Team members: PIs: Iraê Amaral Guerrini, Roberto Lyra Villas Bôas, Dirceu Maximino Fernandes (all FCA-UNESP); Pedro H. S. Brancalion, José Leonardo M. Gonçalves (ESALQ-USP); Joannes Guillemot, Agnès Robin (CIRAD); Gian Franco Capra and Antonio Ganga (UNISS-Università degli Studi di Sassari, Sardinia, Italy); PAs: Caio Carbonari, Magali Ribeiro da Silva; Maura Seiko Tsutsui Esperancini (all FCA-UNESP); José Raimundo Sousa Passos (IB-UNESP-Botucatu). Students: PhD: Livia Mara Lima Goulart and Marianne Fidalgo de Faria (Capes; FCA-UNESP); Enzo Antonio Lecciolle Paganini (UNISS-Università degli Studi di Sassari, Sardinia, Italy); MSc: Laura Oliveira Cleto da Silva; Aline Cássia da Fonseca; Camila R. Pergentino da Silva; Pedro H. P. Nalesso (all FCA-UNESP; Capes, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a support letter);

Results:

SILVA, LAURA OLIVEIRA CLETO DA ; FONSECA, ALINE CÁSSIA DA ; LOZANO SIVISACA, DEICY CAROLINA ; BOAS, ROBERTO LYRA VILLAS ; SILVA, MAGALI RIBEIRO DA ; CAPRA, GIAN FRANCO ; GANGA, ANTONIO ; GUERRINI, IRAÊ AMARAL . Composted Sewage Sludge as a Substrate for Commercial Seedlings of *Peltophorum dubium* (Spreng.) Taub.. *Environments*, v. 11, p. 7-14, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments11010007>

PAGANINI, ENZO ANTONIO LECCIOLE ; SILVA, RAFAEL BARROCA ; RIBEIRO RODER, LUDMILA ; GUERRINI, IRAÊ AMARAL ; CAPRA, GIAN FRANCO ; GRILLI, ELEONORA ; GANGA, ANTONIO . A systematic review and meta-analysis of the sustainable impact of sewage sludge application on soil organic matter and nutrient content. *Sustainability*, v. 16, p. 9865, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16229865> PhD dissertations defended: Livia Mara Lima Goulart and Marianne Fidalgo de Faria (FCA-UNESP);

MSc dissertations defended:

Laura Oliveira Cleto da Silva; Aline Cássia da Fonseca; Camila R. Pergentino da Silva; Pedro H. P. Nalesso (all FCA-UNESP);

(H) Associate Research: Lucas William Mendes

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil Microbial Diversity in Amazonian Agroforestry Systems and Its Influence on the Development of *Euterpe oleracea* Mart.

Summary of achievements: This project focuses on the study of the soil microbiome in agroforestry systems (AFS) and its role in promoting agricultural sustainability in tropical ecosystems. Soil degradation resulting from forest-to-farmland conversion—particularly through slash-and-burn practices—has led to biodiversity loss, declining soil fertility, and increased carbon emissions. In this context, AFS have emerged as a key strategy for ecosystem recovery, supporting nutrient cycling, organic matter accumulation, and the enrichment of microbial biodiversity. This project aims to advance the understanding of the taxonomic and functional diversity and composition of microbial communities in AFS soils through amplicon and metagenomic sequencing. It also seeks to correlate rhizosphere microbiome structure with plant performance, identifying microorganisms with plant growth-promoting potential. In parallel, soil carbon dynamics will be evaluated through the integration of enzymatic assays, microbial activity profiling (Biolog), and metagenomic analyses, using *Euterpe oleracea* (açai palm) as a model species in mesocosm experiments. The project integrates research on soil fertility, belowground biological processes, and climate mitigation, offering innovation potential in the sustainable use of soil biodiversity in Amazonian agroforestry systems. Its outcomes may guide the development of more resilient agricultural practices aligned with both climate change mitigation and tropical ecosystem conservation.

Team members: Lucas William Mendes, PI (CENA-USP). Student: Izadora de Cássia Mesquita da Cunha. Project: Diversidade microbiana do solo de sistemas agroflorestais amazônicos e sua influência no desenvolvimento de *Euterpe oleracea* Mart. (submitted to FAPESP, under review). YES - We received CCARBON/USP 's supporting letter.

(I) Associate Research: Miguel Cooper

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management, Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Contribution of earthworms, ants and termites to soil carbon and nitrogen stabilization, and soil hydrophysical properties

Summary of achievements: Project: "Contribution of soil fauna to mitigate global warming: the role of the invertebrate ecosystem engineers in the stabilization of soil carbon in the neotropical region" (Project initiated in July 2025): Soils represent one of the largest carbon reservoirs in the biosphere, playing a key role in climate regulation and, therefore, a central element in global warming. This habitat is home to a vast diversity of organisms responsible for various functions that originate from numerous ecosystem services. Earthworms, ants and termites represent more than 80% of the soil macrofauna community and are considered ecosystem engineers due to their ability to significantly

alter the habitat. These organisms affect several soil functions, including the decomposition of organic matter, soil structuring and nutrient cycling. Due to their lifestyle habits, these invertebrates significantly affect the turnover of soil organic matter, thus potentially altering soil carbon sequestration rates. However, there is little information on the relevance of these organisms in carbon sequestration, especially in tropical environments, while studies on the impact of these invertebrates on soil carbon stabilization mechanisms are non-existent. This information is essential for understanding the role of these organisms in climate change, especially considering their high sensitivity to changes in land use and management. Additionally, this information would make these organisms a target for studies on soil quality and policies for soil conservation and native and agricultural ecosystems, especially in Brazilian biomes that are highly modified, such as the Atlantic Forest, and under constant threat of deforestation, such as the Amazon rainforest.

Team members: Miguel Cooper, PI, (ESALQ/USP) George Brown, PA, (Embrapa Florestas) Wilian Carlo Demetrio; Post-doc; (ESALQ/USP); not directly funded by CCARBON/USP; FAPESP 2025/01236-5; yes, received a support letter from CCARBON/USP.

(J) Associate Research: Renato A. Ferreira de Lima

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Biomass Reference Measurement Sites: Combining ground data and remote sensors for monitoring forests in the state of São Paulo

Summary of achievements: (i) In this research line we made substantial progress on the project including the maintenance and marking of the permanent forest plots in two sites (Caetetus and Assis Ecological Stations), where trail clearing, perimeter marking, and plot infrastructure restoration were carried out to enable safe and precise access for fieldwork. In parallel, four campaigns of tree-by-tree censuses were conducted in the two plots with two four teams, encompassing the measurement of diameter at breast height (DBH) and total height for all surviving trees and new recruits in 20x20 m subplots. Mapping and tagging of recruits, as well as collection of voucher specimens for taxonomic identification, were also executed. (ii) So far, 3.9 ha in Assis and 3.0 ha in Caetetus were measured, out of a total of 10.24 ha in each site. Besides these results, a major highlight of the period was the successful coordination of multi-team fieldwork under challenging logistical conditions, ensuring high-quality and consistent data collection across all sites. (iii) In the next period, efforts will focus on completing tree censuses in the two sites and start the census in the rainforest plot. We will also conduct the airborne and terrestrial LiDAR scanning aligned with ground measurements to support calibration of satellite-derived biomass estimates.

Team members: PIs: Renato A. Ferreira de Lima, (ESALQ/USP), Natália Macedo Ivanauskas (IPA, SEMIL), Ricardo Ribeiro Rodrigues (ESALQ/USP), Alexandre Adalardo de Oliveira (IB/USP) and Matheus Pinheiro Ferreira (ESALQ/USP). No students with direct CCARBON/USP funding or support.

(K) Associate Research: Simone Raposo Cotta

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Microbial dynamics of biocrusts and their role in carbon sequestration in the Caatinga

Summary of achievements: Biological Soil Crusts (BSCs) are widespread in dryland ecosystems, forming a thin but essential living layer on the soil surface. These crusts comprise diverse microbial communities closely associated with soil particles and play a crucial role in enhancing soil structure through the exudation of exopolysaccharides, which promote particle aggregation and surface stabilization. In desertification-prone areas, BSCs offer a promising nature-based solution for restoring soil health and resilience. We hypothesize that microbial succession during BSC maturation enhances carbon uptake and stabilization in Caatinga soils. To test this, we will evaluate changes in community composition and function across different stages of crust development, integrating field observations and mesocosm experiments. Our analyses will focus on the role of BSCs in promoting soil multifunctionality and stabilizing microbial necromass. The project is currently in its initial phase, with the first sampling campaign scheduled for late July 2025.

Team members: Simone Raposo Cotta, PA, (ESALQ/USP). Laura Camila Cardona Astudillo, PhD student, (ESALQ/USP). (i) No (ii) CAPES, (iii) Not yet. We are currently finalizing the proposal to submit it to FAPESP, with a support letter from CCARBON/USP.

(L) Associate Research: Tsai Siu Mui

Technology: Soil carbon, Crop breeding/physiology, Biochar, Methanotrophy stimulation through use of composed inoculants

Key questions addressed/Research area: This project aims to investigate the role of methanotrophy in carbon sequestration at different stages of ecological succession in restoration areas, pastures, and native forests in the Amazon. The central hypothesis postulates that the increase in methanotrophic bacteria and the reduction in methanogenic archaea promote greater carbon sequestration, favoring the ecological balance throughout forest succession. Another hypothesis tested in this study suggests that model plants will have a positive effect on modulating the microbial community, favoring carbon sequestration. To meet the main goal, soil and litter samples will be collected at different depths (0-10 cm, 10-20 cm, and 20-40 cm) during two seasons (dry and rainy) and two subsequent years. The functional characterization of the microbiota will be conducted through the quantification of functional genes associated with methanotrophy (*pmoA* and *mmoX*) and analysis of CH₄ isotopic composition. In parallel, CH₄ emission measurements will be performed using gas chromatography and soil physicochemical analyses will be conducted to assess their influence on microbial processes. The study will be conducted in areas surrounding pastures, forests, and secondary forests in southern Rondônia. The results of this project will enable an understanding of how ecological succession modulates the microbial communities involved in the methane cycle, contributing to the development of forest management and conservation strategies. The findings are also expected to reinforce the role of secondary forests as potential carbon

sinks, with direct implications for climate change mitigation. Furthermore, the potential of Ipê (*Handroanthus* spp.), Jatobá (*Hymenaea courbaril*), and Copaíba (*Copaifera* spp.) species in modulating microbial communities will be evaluated to determine their abilities to stimulate methanotrophy and promote nutrient cycling, thus favoring carbon sequestration.

Team members: Tsai Siu Mui, PI (CENA/USP), Juan Andrés de Domini (PhD student), Rafael Barti Dextro (Post-doc) (ii) A PhD fellowship from CAPES, but the PhD proposal will also be submitted to FAPESP (iii) It will be submitted with a support letter from CCARBON/USP

Summary of achievements: The project has just started.

3.1.3 Part 3: GHG emission reduction

(A) Associate Research: Antonio Carlos de Azevedo

Technology: Residue management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Use of mine waste to increase the resilience of sandy soils to climate change

Summary of achievements: (i) submitted proposals to FAPESP, Roullien Foundation; Approval of an APR-FAPESP (ii) establish partnership with Dr. Laurent Caner, Univ Poitiers, France (iii) execute the APR FAPESP and possibly the other plans if the proposals happen to be approved.

Team members: Antonio Carlos de Azevedo (PA) Aline Vitti Secco/ MSc/ PPGSNP-ESALQ/ not funded by CCARBON/USP / CAPES 88887.906258/2023-00 Amanda Keitili Martins / MSc/ PPGSNP-ESALQ/ not funded by CCARBON/USP / CAPES 88887.952383/2024-00 Raissa Razera/ MSc/ PPGSNP-ESALQ/ not funded by CCARBON/USP / FAPESP 2022/15186-1; BEPE 2023/12915-5 (Finished) Leonardo Fontoura Crevelim/IC/BIC FAPESP 2024/05622-4; BEPE 2024/21466-2

Results:

Dissertation defended:

Modificação nas propriedades de solo arenoso pela aplicação de resíduos estéreis de mineração; Spatial Variability of Potassium and Agricultural Productivity in Sandy Loam Soil with Rock Dust under Functional Diversity in the Brazilian Cerrado, DOI 10.1007/S42729-024-01766-1; Mineralogical controls over soil K reserves: A case study in Southeastern Brazil (Rio de Janeiro State), DOI 10.1016/J.GEODRS.2025.E00980

(B) Associate Research: Simone Raposo Cotta

Technology 1: Land use change

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil carbon dynamics and biotic responses to land use changes in the Brazilian Amazon

Summary of achievements: Our study aims to investigate how the conversion of Amazon rainforests into agricultural lands and pastures alters soil microbial communities, their interactions with soil fauna, and the consequent shifts in microbial metabolism and

necromass formation. We will also examine how these changes affect the distribution of carbon between the MAOC and POC fractions, assess soil respiration, and track carbon flow through the soil food web. This research will generate valuable insights into the conservation of soil biodiversity and ecosystem functioning in this unique biome. The project has been submitted to FAPESP, and we are currently awaiting the outcome.

Team members: Simone R. Cotta, PA, (ESALQ/USP). María F Chiappero, Post-doc (National University of Córdoba) (i) No (ii) FAPESP-2025/09876-3 [awaiting the outcome] (iii) Yes

3.2 Sectorial chain: Forestry

Research Sector Chain Coordinator: Rodrigo Eiji Hakamada

3.2.1 Part 1: General

Summary of achievements: the supply chain “forestry” is covering various lines of research with the objective of adapting forest management to climatic change, providing results that can be applied in reducing carbon emission and reducing GHG emissions. Two research lines are more focused in a big research platform in a partnership with the Institute of Forest Research and Studies (IPEF), where more than 300 hectares are set with Eucalyptus and Pine plantations along Brazil to understand carbon, water and nutrient cycles. Alternative species to *Eucalyptus* plantation are being studied in two projects. One of them, in the north of Minas Gerais state, has the objective of monitoring soil carbon following the application of biological inputs in response to the needs of the Macaúba and eucalyptus production chains. Another new project aims to assess the combined effects of eCO₂, eTemp, and water scarcity on the metabolism of three economically important and fast-growing tree species in Brazil—eucalypt (*Eucalyptus grandis*), African mahogany (*Khaya anthotheca*), and teak (*Tectona grandis*)—and their interactions with phyllosphere and rhizosphere microbes. Two projects are studying alternative species and mixed plantations. In one of them, we propose an innovative approach that mixes native and fast-growing exotic species to fulfill both conservation and production goals. This project comprehends a strong partnership between

ESALQ/USP, UNESP, São Paulo State Department of the Environment and FAPESP (process 2025/15527-1 approved in June 2025). The second project regarding mixed plantations is the MixFroCarbon project, which started in the beginning of 2025 and the first plot will be set in February 2026 in Itatinga/SP. A lot of efforts are being made to set up new field trials and to study the three that are already set in Forest Research Stations at ESALQ/USP. The project will evaluate environmental adaptation, and carbon balance and stocking of about 30 forest species or mixed models with native and exotic species. The species are: *Eucalyptus grandis*, *E.cloeziana*, *E. pilularis*, *Corymbia citriodora*, *Corymbia torelidora*, *Pinus caribaea*, *Pinus taeda*, *Pinus elliottii*, *Khaya grandifoliola*, Cedro Australiano, Guanandi, Paricá, Kiri Japonês, Macaúba, Bambu listrado, Palmito pupunha, *Gmelina arborea*, Seringueira, *Araucaria angustifolia*, *Tectona grandis*, besides other mixtures of native and exotic species. Finally, we have two projects that are related with forest management, with one of them aiming to help forest managers to adapt decision support systems to Brazilian contexts, emphasizing ecosystem services and carbon sequestration: the other one objectives to evaluate the potential of remote sensing approaches to derive precise estimates of the aboveground biomass and carbon removal of forest plantations. All research lines together sum up 47 papers published, 19 conference abstracts, 1 conference proceedings and 1 book chapters. All of these were produced by 71 persons related to CCARBON/USP's, being about 30% of undergrad, master and PhD students, highlighting the CCARBON/USP 's objective of training new researchers and future decision makers.

3.2.2 Part 2: Carbon removal

(A) Principal Investigator: Rodrigo Hakamada

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Management of Eucalyptus forest coppice

Summary of achievements: Our research is part of a cooperative program within the Institute of Forestry Research and Studies, conducted in conjunction with forestry-based companies (Aço Verde do Brasil, Arauco, Bracell, CMPC, Dexco, Gerdau, Klabin, Lacan, Suzano, Sylvamo, Vallourec, and Veracel), and Brazilian (USP, UNESP, UFRPE, UFES, IFRO, EMBRAPA, UFRN) and international (Colorado State University, US Forest Service, University of Guadalajara) research institutions. The main objective of this line of research is to understand the best management techniques for eucalyptus coppice, as well as the ecophysiological processes that control their response to the environment. One of the main lines of research is the carbon stock and balance in the comparison between tall stem and coppice. The research line, which was implemented in 2021, has so far resulted in 4 master's dissertations (2 defended) and 4 doctoral theses (all in progress), in addition to the training of 15 undergraduate students in forestry engineering.

Team members: Rodrigo Eiji Hakamada, PI (ESALQ/USP), Gardenia Gonçalves, PhD (UNESP), Rosilvam Ramos, PhD (Federal Rural University of Pernambuco, UFRPE), Sara Bandeira, PhD (UFRPE), Graziela Barbosa, PhD (UFRPE), Lucas Cortez, MSc (UFRPE), Pedro Pimenta, MSc (ESALQ/USP), Sarah Almeida, MSc (ESALQ/USP). Researchers: Silvio Frosini de Barros Ferraz e Humberto Eufrades Júnior (ESALQ/USP), Iraê Guerrini e José Luiz Stape (UNESP), Dan Binkley (Colorado State University),

Robert Hubbard (US Forest Service), Gualter Guenther Silva (Federal Univ. of Rio Grande do Norte), José Antônio Aleixo da Silva, Marcone Santos, Rute Berger (UFRPE), Graziela Vidaurre (Federal Univ. of Espírito Santo), Dany Caldeira (Federal Institute of Rondonia), Paulo Guilherme Salvador Wadt (EMBRAPA), Joannes Guilemot and Daniel Poultney (CIRAD), Flávio Mendes (Aço Verde do Brasil), Naiara Fernandes de Souza (Arauco), Gabriela Gonçalves Moreira (Bracell), Elias Frank Araújo (CMPC), Jarbas Borges (Dexco), James Stahl (Klabin), Romulo Costa (Gerdau), Henrique Scolforo and Clayton Alvares (Suzano), José Henrique Rocha (Sylvamo), Mariana Nascimento (Veracel), Breno Bercot Lamas (Vallourec), Paulo Henrique Muller da Silva (IPEF), Bronson P. Bullock and Túlio B. Queiroz (University of Georgia-EUA) Maria Fernanda Vieira Mendes, Pietro Brown (both from FCA-UNESP-Botucatu, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a support letter).

Results:

Scientific papers

Cirilo N.R.M., de Almeida M.N.F., dos Santos V.B., de Souza A.J., da Conceição G.J., da Silva J.G.M., Protázio L.B., Arantes B.S., Campoe O.C., Hakamada R.E., de Medeiros Neto P.N., Neto T.C.C., Guillemot J., Vidaurre G.B.. 2024. Impact of coppice and high stem management on Eucalyptus wood quality. *European Journal of Wood and Wood Products*, 82 : p. 1841-1854. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00107-024-02125-8>

Fernandes, P.G., Alvares, C.A., Queiroz, T.B., Pimenta, P.V., Borges, J.S., Stahl, J., Mendes, F.T., Souza, Amanda, Silva, G.M., Silva, G.G.C., Milhomem, S.B.B., Sousa, R.R., Hakamada, R.E. Contrasting Weather and Stocking Effects on Eucalyptus Initial Coppice Response in Brazil. *Plants*, v. 13, p. 3254, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants13223254>

Gomes da Silva, M.K.A., dos Santos, R.C., Castro, R.V.O., Silva, G.G., Hakamada, R., Minini, D., Santos, L.J., Lopes-Nunes, A.L., Dias Júnior, A.F. The impact of genetics and spacing on productivity and energy stock: perspectives on the expansion of Eucalyptus as a biofuel in Brazil. *New Forests* 56, 39 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11056-025-10110-z>

Oliveira, G. G., Queiroz, T.B., Guerrini, I. A., & Hakamada, R. E. (2023). Exportação de nitrogênio, fósforo e potássio na remoção do toco por Eucalyptus urophylla sob manejo de alto fuste e Talhadia. *Série Técnica IPEF*, v. 26, n. 48. <https://doi.org/10.1867/sertec.v26n48.084>

Oliveira, G. G., Queiroz, T. B., Bullock, B. P., Coelho, J. C., Hakamada, R. E., & Guerrini, I. A. (2025). Full-Tree Biomass, Root Carbon stock and nutrient use efficiency across ages in Eucalyptus stands under seedling and coppice system. *Plants*, 14, 1382. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants14091382>

Oliveira, G. G., Queiroz, T. B., Kupper, A. P., Masullo, L., Hakamada, R. E., & Guerrini, I. A. (2025). Optimizing Forest residue management after harvesting: nutrient export scenarios in Eucalyptus plantations across high forest and coppice systems. *Forestry*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/forestry/cpaf044>

Book chapter:

Hakamada, R. E., Oliveira, G. G., Ferreira, M., & Hartung, P. (2025). Florestas plantadas. In: O mundo Rural Brasileiro (Capítulo 26).

Conference abstracts:

Cortez, L. E. B., Sousa, R. R., Santos, L. P., Oliveira, G. G., Silva, J. C., Milhomem, S. B. B., Barbosa, G. S., Berger, R., Santos, M. M., Hakamada, R. E. (2025). Comparação de produtividade entre os sistemas silviculturais de talhadia e alto fuste: uma revisão sistemática. Congresso Plantações Florestais.

Hakamada, R., Ramos, R., Gonçalves, G., Bandeira, S., Pimenta, P., Souza, N., Silva, M., Franci, A., Costa, R., Stahl, J., Lamas, B., Teixeira, R., Nascimento, M., Dick, G.,

Mendes, F., Berger, R., Mizunati, I., Claudio, E., Tunes, R. (2025). Criteria to select stands for a coppice rotation in Eucalyptus plantation in Brazil. Decisiones, IUFRO. Mendes, M. F. V., Silva, C. A., Oliveira, G. G., Queiroz, T. B., Hakamada, R. E., Fernandes, D. M., & Guerrini, I. A. (2025). Atividade da Arilsulfatase como bioindicadora em sistemas de Talhadia e alto fuste: Avaliação com diferentes clones de Eucalyptus no Mato Grosso do Sul. Congresso de Plantações Florestais, IPEF.

Milhomem, S. B. B., Mendes, F. T., Souza, N. F., Silva, Franci, A. F., Costa, R. D., Stahl, J., Pimenta, P. V., Veroneze, A. J., Siebeneichler, S. C., Ferreira, R. L., Silva, J. A. A., Hakamada, R. E. (2025). Atributos fisiológicos na escala da folha e da árvore em regiões de estresse hídrico elevado. Congresso Plantações Florestais.

Oliveira, G. G., Queiroz, T. B., Franci, A. F., Hakamada, R. E., & Guerrini, I. A. (2025). Interceptação e eficiência do uso da luz em diferentes clones de eucalipto sob sistema de talhadia e alto fuste. Congresso de Plantações Florestais, IPEF.

Oliveira, G. G., Queiroz, T. B., Lamas, B. B., Hakamada, R. E., & Guerrini, I. A. (2025). Fluxo de CO₂ do solo em diferentes clones de eucalipto sob sistema de talhadia e alto fuste. Congresso de Plantações Florestais, IPEF.

Sousa, R. R., Santos, M. M., Barbosa, G. S., Hakamada, R. E. (2025). Influência do clima e da densidade de plantio no potencial hídrico e produção de Eucalyptus. Congresso Plantações Florestais.

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: sustainable production and adaptation of forests under climatic change scenarios

Summary of achievements: this topic has a wide range of objectives, covering studies from natural to planted forest management, all of them aiming to get a better understanding of forest response to climatic change. This line of research has a wide collaboration with the Institute of ESALQ/USP, Forest Research and Studies (IPEF), the Univ. of Lavras, UNESP and CIRAD.

Team members: Rodrigo Eiji Hakamada, PI (ESALQ/USP), Cecilia Chotti MSc (ESALQ/USP), Researchers: Joannes Guillemot (CIRAD), Otávio Campoe (UFLA), Clayton Alcarde Alvares (Suzano), Iraê Guerrini (UNESP), Rildo Moreira e Moreira,

João Carlos Teixeira Mendes (ESALQ/USP), José Leonardo de Moraes Gonçalves (ESALQ/USP), Alexandre Vicente Ferraz (IPEF).

Results:

Leite e Lopes, I., Campoe, O. C., Barros, G. M., Gonçalves, A. F. A., Matzner, G. G. M., Figura, M. A., Alvares, C. A., Cunha, F. L., de Rezende, V. B. S., Stahl, J., Basílio, J. J. N., Félix, H. J. A., Boigues, T. B., Dick, G., de Mattos, E. M., Guillemot, J., Le Maire, G., Cook, R., Albaugh, T. J., ... Laclau, J. (2025). Improved Estimates of Biomass Expansion Factors and Root-To-Shoot Ratios: An Approach for Different Forest Types Across a Climatic Gradient in Brazil. *Global Change Biology*.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.70395>

Cunha, F. L., Campoe, O. C., de Souza, C. R., Leite Lopes, I., Alvares, C. A.; Stape, J. L. (2025). Carbon partitioning as a drought-tolerance strategy in clonal eucalyptus under thermal and water stress. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2025.110719>

Bozo, D., Rubilar, R., Jara, Ó., Asmussen, M. V., Alzamora, R. M., Elissetche, J. P., Campoe, O. C., Pincheira, M. (2025). Modeling the Effects of Climate and Site on Soil and Forest Floor Carbon Stocks in Radiata Pine Stands at Harvesting Age. *Forests*.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/f16071137>

Rajab Pourrahmati, M., Le Maire, G., Baghdadi, N., Alvares, C. A., Stape, J. L., Scolforo, H. F., Campoe, O. C., Nouvellon, Y., Guillemot, J. (2025). Integrating MODIS-derived indices for eucalyptus stand volume estimation: an evaluation of MODIS gross primary productivity. *Frontiers in Remote Sensing*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsen.2025.1588387>

Albaugh, T. J., Maier, C. A., Campoe, O. C., Laviner, M. A., Shively, T. J., Aguiar, V., Peer, K. R., Carter, D. R., Cook, R. L., Rubilar, R. A., Fox, T. R. (2025). Quantifying above- and belowground biomass improved our understanding of site differences and demonstrated the importance of management decisions in sequestering carbon in *Pinus taeda*. *Forest Ecology and Management*.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2025.122901>

Costa, J. R. S., Maciel, J. L. M., Silva, M. R., Campoe, O. C., Maire, G., Alvares, C. A., Marting-Stpaul, N. K., Bittencourt, P., Pereira, L., Cagnoni, L. B., Laclau, J., Nouvellon, Y., Ustulin, S. M. F., Guillemot, J. (2025). Coppice and high forest Eucalyptus stands show similar drought resistance on deep soils. *Tree Physiology*.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/treephys/tpaf089>

Stape, J. L.; Alvares, C. A. (2025). Water table depth contributes to tropical Eucalyptus plantation yields in sandstone-derived landscapes. *Forest Ecology and Management*.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2025.122771>

Morin, X., Toigo, M., Fahse, L., Guillemot, J., Cailleret, M., Bertrand, R., Cateau, E., Coligny, F., García-Valdés, R., Ratcliffé, S., Riote-Lambert, L., Zavala, M. A., Vallet,

P. (2025). More species, more trees: The role of tree packing in promoting forest productivity. *Journal of Ecology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.14460>

Pourrahmati, M. R., Maire, G. L. Baghdadadi, N., Alvares, C. A., Stape, J. L., Scolforo, H. F., Campoe, O. C., Nouvellon, Y., Guillemot, J. (2025). Integrating MODIS- derived indices for eucalyptus stand volume estimation: an evaluation of MODIS gross primary productivity. *Frontiers in Remote Sensing*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsen.2025.1588387>

Zheng, L., Ibáñez, I., Williams, L. J., Zhu, K., Serrano-León, H., Jensen, J., Eisenhauer, N., Verheyen, K. Scherer-Lorenzen, M., Schnabel, F., Kreft, H., Guerrero-Ramírez, N. R., Holscher, D., Paterno, G. B., Irawan, B., Ponette, Q., Messier, C., Paquette, A., Stefanski, A., Mereu, S., Bauhaus, J., Hajek, P., Nock, C. A., Cavender-Bares, J., Parker, W. C., Quosh, J., Ferlian, O., Auge, H., Potvin, C., Yan, E., Yang, B., Zhang, L., Zhao, Z., Sinacore, K., Hall, J. S., Guillemot, J., Robin, A., Brancalion, P. H. S., Sundawati, L., P.B. (2025). Neighbourhood diversity increases tree growth in experimental forests more in wetter climates but not in wetter years. *Nature Ecology and Evolution*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-025-02805-5>

Schnabel, F., Guillemot, J., Barry, K. E., Brunn, M., Cesarz, S., Eisenhauer, N., Gebauer, T., Guerrero-Ramirez, N. R., Handa, T., Madsen, C., Mancilla, L., Monteza, J., Moore, T., Oelmann, Y., Scherer-Lorenzen, M., Schwendenmann, L., Wagner, A., Wirth, C., & Potvin., C. (2025). Tree Diversity Increases Carbon Stocks and Fluxes Above— But Not Belowground in a Tropical Forest Experiment. *Global Change Biology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.70089>

Skiadaresis, G., Leban, J. M., Schnabel, F., Schwarz, J., Guillemot, J., Potvin, C., Bauhaus, J. (2025). Interacting and dynamic effects of species and structural diversity promote annual woody biomass production in a tropical tree diversity experiment. *Forest Ecology and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2025.122844>

Conference abstracts:

Castiglioni, V. G., Galizia, L. F., Pinto, T. M. G., Hakamada, R. E. (2025). Correlation between risk and occurrence of forest fires in Piracicaba/SP between 2002 and 2024. Congresso de Plantações Florestais, IPEF.

Nenartavis, A.C.C., Hakamada , R.E. (2024). Systematic fan-shaped design of Eucalyptus. Simpósio Internacional de Iniciação Científica e Tecnológica da USP.

Pinto, T. M. G., Hakamada, R. E. (2024). Comparison between dendrometric variables in the assessment of the uniformity of *Eucalyptus grandis* at 160 days. Simpósio Internacional de Iniciação Científica e Tecnológica da USP.

Castiglioni, V. G., Galizia, L. F., Hakamada, R. E. (2024). 40 years assessment of forest fire risk in piracicaba by the Monte Alegre formula. Simpósio Internacional de Iniciação Científica e Tecnológica da USP.

Technology: *Afforestation, reforestation and forest management*

Key questions addressed/Research area 3: *innovative silvicultural systems to be used in legal reserve areas.*

Summary of achievements: The Brazilian “Forest Code” requires that a portion of rural properties – ranging from 20% to 80% depending on the biome – must be designated as a “Legal Reserve,” maintained with forest species to both conserve nature and provide forest products for farmers. These areas may contain up to 50% exotic species and be managed without clearcut (only by thinning or partial cuttings). We propose an innovative approach that mixes native and fast-growing exotic species to fulfill both conservation and production goals. This project comprehends a strong partnership between ESALQ/USP, UNESP, São Paulo State Department of the Environment and FAPESP (process 2025/15527-1 approved in June 2025). A lot of efforts are being made to set up new field trials and to study the three ones that are already set in Forest Research Stations at ESALQ/USP.

Team members: Rodrigo Eiji Hakamada PI (ESALQ/USP), Pedro Brancalion (ESALQ/USP), Desiree Lopes, PhD (ESALQ/USP), Tiago Marcilio Pinto MSc (ESALQ/USP). Researchers: Rildo Moreira e Moreira, João Carlos Teixeira Mendes (ESALQ/USP), José Leonardo de Moraes Gonçalves (ESALQ/USP), Alexandre Vicente Ferraz (IPEF).

Results:

Conference papers:

Pinto, T. M. G., Brancalion, P. H. S., Hakamada, R. E. (2025). Does the use of eucalyptus in the Legal Reserve impact the growth of native species and the accumulation of biomass in the restoration?. Congresso de Plantações Florestais, IPEF.

Key questions addressed/Research area 4: *MixForCarbon: understanding potencial forest species adaptation in a wide range of environmental conditions.*

Summary of achievements: this project starts in the beginning of 2025 and the first plot will be set in February 2026 in Itatinga/SP. The project will evaluate carbon balance and stocking of about 30 forest species or mixed models with native and exotic species. The species are: *Eucalyptus grandis*, *E.cloeziانا*, *E. pilularis*, *Corymbia citriodora*, *Corymbia toreliodora*, *Pinus caribaea*, *Pinus taeda*, *Pinus elliottii*, *Khaya grandifoliola*, Cedro Australiano, Guanandi, Paricá, Kiri Japonês, Macaúba, Bambu listrado, Palmito pupunha, *Gmelina arborea*, Seringueira, *Araucaria angustifolia*, *Tectona grandis*, besides other mixtures of native and exotic species.

(B) Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Modeling and monitoring of soil carbon using remote sensing and AI for removal and MRV

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, the research line on Soil Carbon advanced in the quantification and monitoring of soil organic carbon (SOC) in tropical

regions by integrating geospatial data, spectroscopy, proximal sensing, and machine learning. Scalable approaches were developed to link field measurements with remote sensing, enabling high-resolution mapping and MRV systems for climate mitigation. Actions included the consolidation of spectral libraries, improvement of predictive models, and the association of mineralogy, microbiology, and carbon stabilization. This made it possible to identify areas with higher sequestration potential and to align national monitoring protocols with international standards. Highlights: Progress was made in operationalizing SOC monitoring, reducing uncertainties, and supporting carbon removal policies. Tools integrating spectroscopy, remote sensing, and modeling were applied at regional and national scales, impacting agriculture, forests, and restoration areas. Next period plan: The focus will be on expanding uncertainty-based assessments, integrating microbial data into sequestration models, improving spectral transferability, and incorporating results into national MRV and carbon credit platforms.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Nikolaos Tziolas, PA, (University of Florida) Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2022/14935-0 Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17508-9 (CCARBON/USP) Nicolás Augusto Rosin, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2021/10063-6 e BEPE 2023/11467-9 Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/11350-4 Marcos Guedes de Lana, MSc, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES Victoria Sato Pedral, IC, (ESALQ/USP) – Projeto Fosfato e Mineralogia Students: Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2022/14935-0; (iii) Não Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Sim (CCARBON/USP); (ii) FAPESP 2023/17508-9; (iii) Sim Nicolás Augusto Rosin, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2021/10063-6 e BEPE 2023/11467-9; (iii) Não Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/11350-4; (iii) Não Marcos Guedes de Lana, MSc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES; (iii) Não Victoria Sato Pedral, IC, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) –; (iii) Não

Results:

BARTSCH, B.A. et al. Space-time mapping of soil organic carbon through remote sensing and machine learning. *Soil & Tillage Research*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.still.2024.106428

RODRÍGUEZ-ALBARRACÍN, H.S. et al. Soil organic carbon sequestration potential explained by mineralogical and microbiological activity using spectral transfer functions. *Science of the Total Environment*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174652

VAN WESEMAEL, B. et al. A European soil organic carbon monitoring system leveraging Sentinel 2 imagery and the LUCAS soil data base. *Geoderma*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.geoderma.2024.117113

ROSIN, N.A. et al. Spatializing soil elemental concentration as measured by X-ray fluorescence analysis using remote sensing data. *Catena*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.catena.2024.107988

(C) Principal Investigator: Leidivan Almeida Frazão

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management, Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil carbon monitoring following the application of biological inputs in response to the needs of the macaúba and eucalyptus production chains

Summary of achievements: The intensive use of agrochemicals has raised environmental and public health concerns, in addition to increasing production costs. Macaúba, a native palm from the Cerrado biome with high potential for biofuel production and other value-added products, faces challenges during its initial cultivation phase. Low seed germination rates, seedling susceptibility to diseases, and slow early growth have limited the commercial expansion of this promising crop. Considering macaúba's potential to diversify the energy matrix and generate income in marginal areas, overcoming these challenges is essential to enable its large-scale production. In forestry, eucalyptus—the main species cultivated in Minas Gerais—faces challenges related to disease control, the need for more vigorous seedlings, and the pursuit of more sustainable practices. The intensive use of chemical inputs in forestry has raised environmental and economic concerns, pressuring the sector to seek more sustainable alternatives. Given this context, our central hypothesis is that the development of specific and innovative bioinputs can provide effective and sustainable solutions for each of these production chains, simultaneously meeting demands for higher productivity, quality, and environmental sustainability, while contributing to carbon sequestration within these production systems. This project is funded by FAPEMIG (APQ-05304-24) and is currently in its initial development phase. During the first three months, mapping of the areas to be monitored was completed. The next steps consist of: i) evaluating soil microbial carbon dynamics and enzymatic activity in macaúba and eucalyptus cultivation areas following bioinput application; and ii) determining the potential for carbon storage after crop establishment over time, with improved plant health and reduced use of industrial fertilizers.

Team members: Leidivan Almeida Frazão, PI, (UFMG), Jaqueline de Cássia de Oliveira, Post-doc, (UFMG)

(D) Principal Investigator: Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Development of Decision Support Systems for Conflicting Objectives to Improve Governance of Production, Conservation, Restoration, and Sustainable Ecosystem Services (The project aims to evaluate global multicriteria forest plantation management approaches that identify consensus solutions for diverse stakeholders and adapt these decision support systems to Brazilian contexts, emphasizing ecosystem services and carbon sequestration.

Summary of achievements: (i) synthesis of the main activities performed during the period Over the past year, we have been finalizing the formation of our team of scholarship recipients and consolidating the national and international collaboration network that supports this research line. This phase has been marked by the regular

engagement of four researchers from the Department of Forest Sciences at ESALQ/USP—Prof. Rodrigo Hakamada, Prof. Nathália Nascimento, Prof. Matheus Ferreira, and Prof. Sílvio Ferraz—under the coordination of the principal investigator, Prof. Luiz C. E. Rodriguez. Together, we defined and consolidated our roles as supervisors of the students joining this initiative. Priority was given to integrating three fellows supported by a related project funded by FAPESP (Project No. 2021/00833-9: DecisionES – Decision Support for the Provision of Ecosystem Services under Global Change). This support allowed us to onboard two PhD candidates—one in the area of governance, co-supervised by Prof. Nathália, and another in hydrology, co-supervised by Prof. Sílvio—as well as one postdoctoral researcher under the supervision of Prof. Rodriguez. We also initiated the recruitment process for two additional fellowships (a regular PhD and a postdoctoral position) within the scope of the CCARBON/USP program. Unfortunately, these selection efforts will need to be repeated due to the lack of suitable candidates in the initial rounds. Dr. Jordi Garcia-Gonzalo, from the Centre de Ciència i Tecnologia Forestal de Catalunya (CTFC), joined our core team as a representative from a key European partner institution. In the context of this collaboration, we organized a major scientific symposium—DecisionES 2025—which brought together around 100 participants from ten different countries. All abstracts, presentation slides, and full-length videos were made publicly available at: <https://decisiones.github.io>. Additionally, two European fellows—Jean Marques (ISA, University of Lisbon) and Álvaro Cortez (CTFC, Spain)—visited our team to begin collaborative research activities with our fellows. (ii) highlights We achieved the following key milestones: Integration of new fellows supported by the FAPESP project (2021/00833-9); Organization of an international symposium with strong national and global participation; Researcher exchange through the visit of two European collaborators; Dissemination of symposium content via a dedicated website and technical series, and publication of a scientific paper addressing a core topic of this research line. (iii) workplan for the next period The DecisionES 2025 Symposium created valuable opportunities for collaborative work with both national and international institutions. In coordination with the three fellows supported by the related FAPESP DecisionES project, we will identify the most promising collaboration opportunities and draft specific joint work plans. We will also launch a second call to recruit qualified candidates for the remaining postdoctoral and doctoral fellowships under the CCARBON/USP program. Filling these positions is essential to achieving key objectives of this research line. Professor Rodrigo Hakamada is integrating his ongoing research activities with the goals of this research initiative. A more detailed work plan will be developed and aligned with the activities of the soon-to-be-recruited postdoctoral and doctoral fellows. A third significant contribution is also being planned. Dr. Silvana R. Nobre will soon begin work on a related research project recently funded by CNPq (Process: 444215/2024-7, period: July 9, 2025, to July 31, 2029), titled “Integração de Metodologias Científicas na determinação de preços, custos e produtividade para compor recomendação de plantio de Florestas Multifuncionais” (Integration of Scientific Methodologies to Determine Prices, Costs, and Productivity for Recommendations on the Planting of Multifunctional Forests).

Team members: Team members PI, Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez, PI, (ESALQ/USP) PA, Matheus Pinheiro Ferreira Students, and members from related projects This research

line has substantially benefited from fellowships provided by the following related FAPESP project: Projeto FAPESP (021/00833-9) 01/07/2023 a 30/06/2028: Apoio à Decisão para o Fornecimento de Serviços Ecológicos sob Mudança Global - esforço brasileiro (DecisionES - BR). PD Scholarship: Jomil Costa Abreu Sales (2024/14444-2) 01/03/2025 a 28/02/2027: "Apoio à Decisão para o Fornecimento de Serviços Ecológicos sob Mudança Global – esforço brasileiro (DecisionES-BR)" PhD Scholarship: Giulia Domingues Pedro (2024/13393-5) 01/Sep/2024 a 29/Feb/2028: AcquaES - Mensuração de serviços hidrológicos no design e desenvolvimento de sistemas de suporte à decisão para gestores florestais e formuladores de políticas PhD Scholarship: Daniel de Almeida Ferreira (2025/04246-1) 01/04/2025 a 30/09/2028: BiodivES - Mensuração de serviços ecológicos relacionados à biodiversidade no desenho e desenvolvimento de sistemas de suporte à decisão para gestores florestais e formuladores de políticas

Results:

Symposium proceedings:

Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez, Silvana Ribeiro Nobre & Jordi Garcia-Gonzalo Eds. (2025) DecisionES 2025 Proceedings. Série Técnica IPEF, Vol. 27 No. 49 (ISSN 2764-3808)

Presentations at the symposium:

Giulia Domingues Pedro, Matheus Pinheiro Ferreira, Paula Caroline Dos Reis Oliveira, Silvio Frosini De Barros Ferraz. Predicting the effects of land use on stream drying through remote sensing and deep learning algorithm.

Nathália Nascimento, Daniel Ferreira. Prioritizing Areas for Forest Restoration in São Paulo State: Degradation, Connectivity, and Decision-Making

Nathália Nascimento. Spatial Patterns of Fire in the Atlantic Forest of Bahia: Analysis of Driving Factors and Risk Scenarios.

Silvana Ribeiro Nobre, Luísa Ribeiro von Glehn Nobre, Marc Eric McDill, Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez. Integrating Multifunctional Forests into the Rubber Tree Industry in São Paulo, Brazil: A Model for Balancing Resource Availability and Market Constraints.

Silvana Ribeiro Nobre, Marc McDill, Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez. Defining Adequately the Decision Space for Maximizing Carbon Removals in Eucalyptus Industrial Plantations.

Hakamada, R. Criteria to select stands for a coppice rotation in Eucalyptus plantation in Brazil.

Matheus Pinheiro Ferreira. Exploring EnMAP hyperspectral images for distinguishing forest land-cover types in Brazil.

Scientific Papers:

Nobre, S R; McDill, M E; Rodriguez, L C E; Diaz-Balteiro, L. (2024) Reframing Forest Harvest Scheduling Models for Ecosystem Services Management. *Forests*, v. 15, p. 2236, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f15122236>

Delgado-Rodriguez, M.; Diaz-Balteiro, L.; Ribeiro Nobre, S.; Rodriguez, L C E (2025) Optimal Rotation and Ecosystem Services: A Generalization in Forest Plantations. *Forests*, 16, 618. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f16040618>

Pedro, Giulia Domingues; Oliveira, Paula Caroline dos Reis; Ferraz, Sílvio Frosini de Barros. (2025) Avaliação da saúde de riachos por meio de indicadores da paisagem. XXI Simpósio Brasileiro de Sensoriamento Remoto

Ogasawara, M. E. K., Filoso, S., Taniwaki, R. H., & Ferraz, S. F. B. (2025). Influence of restored riparian forest structure and age on channel morphology and health of neotropical streams. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 389, 126095. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.126095>

Almeida, G. S. S., Saito, V. S., Sartori, M., Saulino, H. H. L., da Penha, L. O., et al. (2025). Experimental effects of multiple agricultural stressors on diversity and size structure of subtropical stream macroinvertebrates. *Environmental Advances*, 20, 100630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envadv.2024.100630>

de Paula, F. R., Brejão, G. L., Pérez-Mayorga, M. A., Casatti, L., et al. (2025). Timing since deforestation for pastures implementation in the western Amazon: Impacts on stream water biogeochemistry. *Science of The Total Environment*, 976, 179320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.179320>

dos Reis Oliveira, P. C., Filoso, S., & Ferraz, S. (2025). Evaluating the untapped potential of forest landscape restoration to streams. *Restoration Ecology*, e70073. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rec.70073>

Felippe, B. M., dos Santos Luciano, A. C., Marin, F. R., Ortega-Rodriguez, D. R., et al. (2025). Local atmospheric vapor pressure deficit as microclimate index to assess tropical rainforest riparian restoration success. *Science of The Total Environment*, 973, 179146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.179146>

dos Reis Oliveira, P. C., Gualda, G. A. F., Rossi, G. F., Camargo, A. F. M., Filoso, S., et al. (2025). Forest restoration improves habitat and water quality in tropical streams: A multiscale landscape assessment. *Science of The Total Environment*, 963, 178256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.178256>

Rossi, G., Miralha, L., Ogasawara, M., Ferraz, S., & Oliveira, P. (2024). Characterizing stream temperature hysteresis in forested catchments under restoration practices in Brazil. *AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts*, 2024(1158), H11F-07.

Ogasawara, M. E. K., Mattos, E. M., Rocha, H. R., Wei, X., & Ferraz, S. F. B. (2024). Assessing hydrological response and resilience of watersheds as strategy for climatic change adaptation in neotropical region. *Sustainability*, 16(20), 8910. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16208910>

Meli, P., Ellison, D., Ferraz, S. F. B., Filoso, S., & Brancalion, P. H. S. (2024). On the unique value of forests for water: Hydrologic impacts of forest disturbances, conversion, and restoration. *Global Change Biology*, 30(2), e17162. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17162>

Melo, R. S., Alexandrino, E. R., de Paula, F. R., Boscolo, D., & de Barros Ferraz, S. F. (2024). Promoting bird functional diversity on landscapes with a matrix of planted *Eucalyptus* spp. in the Atlantic Forest. *Environmental Management*, 73(2), 395–407. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-023-01877-y>

Paula, M., David, E., Ferraz, S. F. B., Filoso, S., & Brancalion, P. H. S. (2024). On the unique value of forests for water: Hydrologic impacts of forest disturbances, conversion, and restoration. *Global Change Biology*, 30, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17162>

Tavares, M F; Gallo, P; Nascimento, N; Bauhus, J; Brancalion, P H S; Feurer, M. (2024) Smallholders' perspectives, motivations, and incentives for restoring the Brazilian Atlantic Forest. *Restoration Ecology*, v. 1, p. 1

Metzger, J P; Joly, C; Sparovek, G; Pardini, R; Ruggiero, P; Di Giulio, G; Azevedo, C; Boscolo, D; Brancalion, P H S; Carrascosa, H; Carvalho, R; Ferreira, L S; Gerard, A; Hohlenwerger, C; Igari, A; Krainovic, P M; Morewira, E F; Nascimento, N; Ortega, J; Nlon, M A; et.al . (2024) Guiding transdisciplinary synthesis processes for social-ecological policy decisions. *Perspectives in Ecology and Conservation*, v. 500, p. 424000543.

Berenguer, E; Armenteras, D; Lees, A C; Fernside, P M; Alencar, A; Almeida, C; Aragão, L; Barlow, J; Bilbao, B; Brando, P; Bynoe, P; Finer, M; Flores, B M; Jenkins, C N; Silva Jnr, C; Smith, C; Souza, C; Garcia-Vilacorta, R; Nascimento, N (2024) Drivers and ecological impacts of deforestation and forest degradation in the Amazon. *ACTA AMAZONICA*, v. 54, p. e54es22342.

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Using Active and Passive Sensors from Ground and Orbital Platforms for Estimating Aboveground Biomass and Carbon (The main objective is to evaluate the potential of remote sensing approaches to derive precise estimates of the aboveground biomass of forest plantations)

Summary of achievements: (i) Synthesis of Main Activities Performed During the Period
The research line focused on Active and Passive Sensors from Ground and Orbital Platforms for Estimating Aboveground Biomass and Carbon has greatly benefited from the related FAPESP project (EMU 2022/11591-9), titled “Acquisition of LiDAR Technology Integrated with a Data Management System for Monitoring, Measurement, and Data Access in the Forest Experimental Stations of USP and the Fundação Florestal.” This project invested substantial resources in acquiring multi-user LiDAR equipment—one of the most advanced technologies currently available for non-destructive estimation of aboveground biomass and carbon. Originally conceived by Professor Luiz C. Estraviz Rodriguez and granted to Professor Silvio Ferraz, the project now also benefits from the active collaboration of Professor Matheus Ferreira. The LiDAR system enables highly detailed measurements of forest parameters, including diameters at multiple heights, stem and crown counts, canopy density, trunk taper, branch architecture, and estimates of wood volume, biomass, and carbon. In addition to the LiDAR component, the team has been actively working on multiple fronts involving remote sensing strategies. These include the use of multi- and hyperspectral data collected via various platforms—ranging from satellite to drone-based sensors—complementing the LiDAR data and broadening the

scope of research applications. (ii) Highlights Over the past year, the first round of missions was successfully carried out to achieve wall-to-wall LiDAR coverage of the four forest experimental stations included in the project. These stations are located in the municipalities of Itatinga, Anhembi, Piracicaba, and Rio Claro in the State of São Paulo. Current efforts are focused on user training, equipment testing under diverse conditions, and the development of standard operating procedures. These activities are being organized under the Multiuser Equipment Center, coordinated by Professor Matheus Ferreira, to ensure long-term support and impact for this research line. (iii) Workplan for the Next Period In the upcoming period, priority will be given to refining operational routines and guidelines to enhance data quality and workflow efficiency. A major effort will also focus on developing robust systems to convert the raw LiDAR data into precise estimates of biomass and carbon. These core activities—alongside expanded work involving multi- and hyperspectral data collection and analysis—will be significantly strengthened once the remaining fellowships provided by the CCARBON/USP program (postdoctoral and doctoral) are assigned to support this research line.

Team members: PI, Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez, PI, (ESALQ/USP) PA, Matheus Pinheiro Ferreira, PA (ESALQ/USP)

Results:

Master thesis: Jose Jorge Monteiro Junior

Efeito das mudanças no padrão de precipitação na área total e biomassa da Mata Atlântica e Caatinga Defesa: 26/09/2024 <https://www.teses.usp.br/teses/disponiveis/11/11150/tde-10122024-103914/pt-br.php> <https://doi.org/10.11606/D.11.2024.tde-10122024-103914>

Master thesis:: Leonardo Costa Peres

Uso de medidas não convencionais e aplicação de LiDAR para cálculo de volume de árvores plantadas Data da Defesa: 08/11/2024 <https://www.teses.usp.br/teses/disponiveis/11/11150/tde-03022025-172304/pt-br.php> <https://doi.org/10.11606/D.11.2024.tde-03022025-172304>

Scientific papers:

Almeida, Danilo R. A.; Vedovato, Laura B.; Fuza, Matheus; Molin, Paulo; Cassol, Henrique; Resende, Angélica F.; Krainovic, Pedro M.; Almeida, Catherine T.; Amaral, Cibele; Haneda, Leo; Albuquerque, Rafael W.; Gorgens, Eric; Romanelli, João; Ferreira, Matheus; Salk, Carl; Espinoza, Nikolai; Silva, Carlos; Broadbent, Eben; Brancalion, Pedro H.S. (2025) Remote sensing approaches to monitor tropical forest restoration: Current methods and future possibilities. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, v. 62, p. 188-206.

Li, Qing; Yin, Jia; Zhang, Xiaoxin; Hao, Dalei; Ferreira, Matheus Pinheiro; Yan, Wenhui; Tian, Ye ; Zhang, Da; Tan, Shen; Nie, Sheng; An, Tianyu; Li, Xiaoyao; Huang, Jianxi; Su, Wei; Zeng, Yelu. (2025) Tree-level carbon stock estimations across diverse species using multi-source remote sensing integration. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, v. 231, p. 109904.

Ferreira, Matheus Pinheiro; Santos, Daniel Rodrigues; Ferrari, Felipe; Coelho Filho, Luiz Carlos Teixeira; Martins, Gabriela Barbosa; Feitosa, Raul Queiroz. (2024) Improving

urban tree species classification by deep-learning based fusion of digital aerial images and LiDAR. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, v. 1, p. 128240.

Ferreira, Matheus Pinheiro; Martins, Gabriela Barbosa; Almeida, Thaís Moreira Hidalgo; Silva Ribeiro, Rafael ; Veiga Júnior, Valdir Florêncio; Silva Rocha Paz, Igor; Siqueira, Marinez Ferreira; Kurtz, Bruno Coutinho. (2024) Estimating aboveground biomass of tropical urban forests with UAV-borne hyperspectral and LiDAR data. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, v. 96, p. 128362.

(E) Associate Research: Paulo Mazzafera

Technology: Crop breeding/physiology

Key questions addressed/Research area: Plant growth of economically important tree species under high CO₂

Summary of achievements: Trees play a crucial role in mitigating rising atmospheric CO₂ levels caused by fossil fuel burning. Alongside native forests, Brazil has extensive planted forests dominated by eucalyptus and pine, with increasing cultivation of fast-growing species like African mahogany and teak for various economic purposes. Elevated CO₂ (eCO₂), higher temperatures (eTemp), and reduced water availability — key aspects of climate change — affect planted forests by disrupting nutritional relationships between carbon (C) and nitrogen (N), since increased C allocation to starch and sugars influences the biosynthesis of N-containing compounds via interconnected metabolic pathways. Additionally, eTemp-induced water stress can impact potassium (K) nutrition, which is essential for wood formation in trees. Another largely unexplored aspect is the impact of global warming on the microbiota inhabiting tree leaves (phyllosphere) and roots (rhizosphere). Increased atmospheric CO₂ alters C metabolism and root exudation, the primary drivers of microbial diversity and activity in these microenvironments.

This project aims to assess the combined effects of eCO₂, eTemp, and water scarcity on the metabolism of three economically important and fast-growing tree species in Brazil — eucalypt (*Eucalyptus grandis*), African mahogany (*Khaya anthotheca*), and teak (*Tectona grandis*) — and their interactions with phyllosphere and rhizosphere microbes. Three main experiments will be conducted under controlled conditions to investigate these effects on young plants using transcriptomic, anatomical, and metabolomic analyses, as well as characterizing the rhizosphere and phyllosphere microbiomes. By integrating these approaches, the project seeks to understand how climate change factors influence the physiological and metabolic traits related to wood formation in these species. Given their rapid growth, these trees have significant potential to contribute to atmospheric CO₂ mitigation.

Team members: Paulo Mazzafera, Sara Adrian Lopez Andrade

3.2.3 Part 3: GHG emission reduction

(A) Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Technology: Fertilizer management, Residue management, Land use change, Crop management, Water management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Emission mitigation through soil management, land use, and sustainable practices supported by data and modeling

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, research on reducing agricultural GHG emissions advanced in assessing land management and use practices to mitigate soil- and crop-related fluxes. Remote sensing, predictive modeling, and agro-environmental indicators were integrated to identify critical areas and guide strategies that increase input use efficiency, reduce carbon losses, and maintain soil cover. Methods were developed to monitor the frequency of bare soil — associated with degradation and emissions — alongside improvements in soil physical characterization and the integration of digital mapping with crop growth models. These approaches provided support for conservation practices and more efficient fertilizer management, reducing nitrous oxide emissions and promoting sustainable agricultural systems. Highlights: The research line consolidated a framework linking soil attributes, agricultural management, and GHG emissions, with potential applications in low-carbon agriculture policies and monitoring platforms. Next period plan: The next stage will prioritize integration into MRV systems, expansion of predictive models to different regions, use of climate time series in prospective analyses, and development of technical protocols for national agricultural emissions mitigation programs.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Kabindra Adhikari, PA, (Texas Tech University) Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17876-8 Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2024/11100-0 Borges Marfrann Dias Melo, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00 Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES Miguel Palacio Pelaez Carvalho Neto, IC, (ESALQ/USP) – Projeto IC Mapeamento Calcário/Carbono (FAPESP submetido) Students: Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/17876-8; (iii) Não Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Não Borges Marfrann Dias Melo, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00; (iii) Não Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES; (iii) Não Miguel Palacio Pelaez Carvalho Neto, IC, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP submetido; (iii) Não

Results:

DI RAIMO, L.A.D.L. et al. Sand subfractions by proximal and satellite sensing: Optimizing agricultural expansion in tropical sandy soils. *Catena*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.catena.2023.107604

DOS SANTOS, N.V. et al. Digital soil mapping and crop modeling to define the spatially-explicit influence of soils on water-limited sugarcane yield. *Plant and Soil*, 2024. DOI: 10.1007/s11104-024-06587-w

PELEGRINO, M.H.P. et al. Optimizing soil texture spatial prediction in the Brazilian Cerrado: Insights from random forest and spectral data. *Geoderma Regional*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.geodrs.2025.e00922

SOUSA, G.P.B. et al. Assessing soil degradation in Brazilian agriculture by a remote sensing approach to monitor bare soil frequency: impact on soil carbon. *Soil Advances*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.soilad.2024.100011

(B) Associate Research: Paulo Mazzafera

Technology: Crop management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Fast growing trees can mitigate more CO₂ because their high carbon fixation in the stem

Summary of achievements: The research project is currently underway.

Team members: Paulo Mazzafera, Sara Adrian Lopez Andrade

3.3 Sectorial chain: Blue Carbon

Research Sector Chain Coordinator: Tiago Osório Ferreira

3.3.1 Part 1: General

Summary of achievements: During the evaluated period, the Blue Carbon Research Sector consolidated important advances in research, innovation, and dissemination, reinforcing CCARBON/USP's leadership in tropical coastal ecosystems and climate change mitigation. The activities covered a wide spectrum, from fundamental studies on soil carbon stabilization processes to large-scale restoration projects with possible implications for public policies and carbon markets. (i) Main activities: The successful approval and launch of the MARES (Mangrove Assisted Restoration for Ecosystem Services) project, with approximately US\$ 4.9 million funding, is a large-scale initiative that integrates innovative restoration approaches, using ROOT™ bioengineering technology, optimizing mangrove seedling establishment and soil stability. Considering other 8 ongoing projects, field campaigns were conducted in multiple sites along the Brazilian coast (São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro, Pará, Amapá, Ceará), generating unprecedented datasets on carbon stocks, soil properties, biodiversity, carbon fluxes and nutrient dynamics. Additionally, field experiments were installed aiming to test how the

fertilization of restored mangrove forests would optimize mangrove restoration programs. Parallel to fieldwork, controlled experiments in mesocosms were conducted to assess the impacts of salinity and climate change scenarios on soil carbon stabilization, organo-mineral interactions, and nutrients (e.g., phosphorus) fractionation in mangrove soils. (ii) Highlights for research and innovation: Seven peer-reviewed articles were published in leading journals, such as *Nature Communications*; *Environmental Research*; *Marine Pollution Bulletin*; *Ecosphere*, and *Journal of Environmental Management*. Additionally, at least 30 scientific articles are being produced. These publications provided novel insights into the role of iron oxides in stabilizing soil organic carbon under dynamic redox conditions; the impacts of land use change on mangrove carbon stocks and GHG fluxes and the dynamics of nutrients and pollutants in replanted mangroves. A total of nine projects are linked to the Chain Sector, involving 14 investigators, 5 pos-docs, 9 PhD, 4 Ms and 5 undergraduate students. All these projects are focused on mangrove soil processes, land use change, and ecosystem services recovery. These works not only advanced scientific knowledge but also trained a new generation of researchers in state-of-the-art methodologies, from spectroscopy and isotopic analysis to microbial ecology and remote sensing. Innovation and dissemination efforts were strengthened through the establishment of strategic partnerships with *Fundação Florestal* and other stakeholders, enabling the operationalization of total ecosystems carbon stock monitoring in mangroves for the entire state of São Paulo. Workshops and training activities were conducted for managers, technical staff, and students, reinforcing CCARBON/USP's role as a bridge between academia, government, and society. These actions ensured that results reached both the scientific community and decision-makers, expanding the visibility of CCARBON's work at national and international levels. (iii) Workplan for the next period: Key goals for the next period include: (1) finalizing laboratory analyses of soil and vegetation samples collected during the campaigns; (2) publishing manuscripts on land use change impacts, soil carbon stabilization mechanisms, and restoration practices; (3) strengthening MRV systems by integrating uncertainty analyses, microbial data, and climate time series into predictive models; (4) expanding partnerships with government agencies and international institutions to align national monitoring protocols with international standards; and (5) promoting knowledge dissemination through policy briefs, technical reports, and engagement in global forums such as COP30. Overall, the period was marked by robust scientific production, impactful partnerships, and innovative field and laboratory experiments. These achievements position the Blue Carbon Research Line as a strategic contributor to climate change mitigation, ecosystem restoration, and sustainable development.

Articles

Bernardino, A. F., Mazzuco, A. C. A., Costa, R. F., Souza, F., Owuor, M. A., Nobrega, G. N., ... & Kauffman, J. B. (2024). The inclusion of Amazon mangroves in Brazil's REDD+ program. *Nature communications*, 15(1), 1549.

Bernardino, A. F., Queiroz, H. M., Nóbrega, G.N., Coppo, G. C., Sanders, C.J., Antonio E.B. Silva, Kauffman, J. B., Costa, R.F., Pacheco, C.F., Vassoler, A., Pereira, A.P., Ruiz, F., Ferreira, T.O. (2024) Soil greenhouse gas fluxes partially reduce the net gains in carbon sequestration in mangroves of the Brazilian Amazon. *Environmental Research*, 263, 120102.

Ferreira, T.O., Queiroz, H.M., Ruiz, F., Nóbrega, G., Cherubin, M.R., Sousa Junior, V.S., Barcellos, D., Ferreira, A.D., Otero, X.L. How do soil processes control the provision of ecosystem services in coastal wetlands? *Environmental Research*, 255, 119078.

da Silva, G. R., Lázaro, M. L., Queiroz, H. M., Ferreira, A. D., Ramos, R. A. D., Machado, W. T. V., ... & Nóbrega, G. N. (2024). How do replanted mangroves affect phosphorus dynamics in their soils?. *Journal of environmental management*, 366, 121915.

Kauffman et al., 2024. Conversion of tropical forests to water buffalo pastures in lower Amazonia: carbon losses and social carbon costs. *Ecosphere*, 15: ecs2.70055. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.70055>

Pacheco, C. F., Queiroz, H. M., Mazzuco, A. C. A., Nóbrega, G. N., Ferreira, T. O., & Bernardino, A. F. (2024). Soil greenhouse gas emissions from dead and natural mangrove forests in Southeastern Brazil. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 203, 116487.

Ruiz, F., Bernardino, A. F., Queiroz, H. M., Otero, X. L., Rumpel, C., & Ferreira, T. O. (2024). Iron's role in soil organic carbon (de)stabilization in mangroves under land use change. *Nature communications*, 15(1), 10433.

Projects and participants

- 1) How innovative assisted restoration strategies will increase the ability of Blue Carbon ecosystems to act as carbon sinks? Tiago Osório Ferreira (USP/ESALQ, PI).
- 2) What are the mechanisms and drivers controlling the carbon sequestration and stabilization in Blue Carbon ecosystems? Tiago Osório Ferreira (USP/ESALQ, PI).
- 3) Total Ecosystem Stocks of Mangroves. Angelo Bernardino (UFES, PI)
- 4) Assessment of the soil microbiome and its relationship with carbon dynamics in mangrove environments. Arthur Prudêncio de Araujo Pereira (UFC, PI)
- 5) Changing mangroves: How mangrove restoration affects soils characteristics and the provision of ecosystems services? Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega (UFC, PI)
- 6) Pro-mangue: optimized mangrove recovery program through fertilization for carbon sequestration and ecosystem services. Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega (UFC, PI)
- 7) Carbon emissions associated with land-use changes in mangrove forests. Angelo Bernardino (UFES, PI)
- 8) How does land use change impact the ability of blue carbon ecosystems to act as carbon sinks? Tiago Osório Ferreira (USP/ESALQ, PI).
- 9) Evaluation of carbon stocks and sequestration potential in mangrove ecosystems under restoration and conservation scenarios Tiago Osório Ferreira (USP/ESALQ, PI).

3.3.2 Part 2: Carbon removal

(A) Principal Investigator: Tiago Osório Ferreira

Technology: Afforestation, reforestation and forest management, Soil carbon and Wetland restoration

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: How innovative assisted restoration strategies will increase the ability of Blue Carbon ecosystems to act as carbon sinks?

Summary of achievements: (i) for the evaluation period in this initiative we have approved a research project Mares (Mangrove Assisted Restoration for Ecosystem Services) project which provides a total funding of US\$ 4.011.566,75 for P&D&I and US\$ 948.615,44 for infrastructure (77% from Total Energies and 23% from Qatar Energy) to evaluate an innovative strategy of assisted restoration of mangroves at the southern coast of São Paulo. (ii) publication of 1 scientific paper (Journal of Environmental Management) on how the replantation of mangroves affects the P biogeochemical dynamics in their soils. The study examined how mangrove restoration influences soil phosphorus (P) dynamics and associated ecosystem services on the southeast coast of Brazil, comparing soils from unvegetated areas, mature mangroves, and replanted mangroves aged 7 and 9 years. The key findings reveal that mangrove restoration significantly impacts soil properties and nutrient cycling. As restored mangroves aged, there was a notable increase in total organic carbon (TOC) content, signifying enhanced carbon sequestration potential. Soil pH became more acidic and both pH and redox potential (Eh) exhibited strong seasonal fluctuations—acidification with restoration and distinctive shifts between wet and dry periods (lower Eh and higher pH during the wet season). Phosphorus fractionation analyses showed that organic P forms constituted the principal pool across all sites. Interestingly, unvegetated soils contained the highest concentrations of organic P, while vegetated and restored sites displayed lower levels of exchangeable and mineral-bound phosphorus fractions. Although no strong seasonal trend in P fractionation was observed, and the forest age did not uniformly influence these fractions, the pseudo-total phosphorus (a measure of overall P availability) increased with progressing forest recovery. This points to enhanced nutrient retention capacity as mangroves mature after replanting. These findings underscore that replanting mangroves promotes the accumulation of phosphorus in soils—critical for supporting nutrient cycling and other soil-related ecosystem services. Restoration also altered key soil parameters, including pH, redox conditions, and organic carbon content, which control important soil processes like redox reactions and organic matter degradation and are intricately linked with the cycles of iron, carbon, and phosphorus. While mangrove replanting improves the functions of soil ecosystems, particularly in nutrient regulation and carbon storage, the study emphasizes the ongoing need for further research on how seasonal factors affect nutrient dynamics in these recovering environments. Overall, restoring mangroves enhances the ability of coastal soils to regulate nutrients and store carbon, reaffirming their value for ecosystem services. (iii) Workplan for the next period: to initiate the activities of Mares, which will assess the potential of ROOT technology, a bioengineering method, to optimize mangrove restoration and enhance overall ecological functioning. The ROOT technology aims to improve seedling development, sediment trapping, and soil stability, therefore promoting successful restoration. The project involves independent but interconnected work packages, focused on: (1) synthesizing available data on carbon stocks in mangroves forests in Brazil and identifying degraded mangrove areas along the Brazilian coast for potential use of ROOT system (2) assessing Total Ecosystem Carbon Stocks of mangrove forests following restoration process using ROOT technology; (3) assessing mangrove soil parameters after mangrove restoration, including soil organic matter stability, benthic and microbial community diversity, as well as overall soil health to quantify the rehabilitation of ecosystems services. By studying an innovative restoration approach in

real field conditions, this project aims to contribute to mangrove ecosystems' long-term resilience and sustainability.

Team members: PI: Tiago Osório Ferreira (USP/ESALQ), Maurício Cherubin (USP/ESALQ), Carlos Eduardo Cerri (USP/ESALQ), Pedro Brancalion (USP/ESALQ) PA: Ângelo Bernardino (UFES), Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega (UFC), Hermano Melo Queiroz (USP/FFLCH), Diego Barcellos (UNIFESP), Arthur Prudêncio (UFC), Paulo Guilherme Molin (UFSCAR), Matheus Pinheiro Ferreira (USP/ESALQ), Xosé Luis Otero (USC) Post-doc: Dr. Francisco Ruiz (USP/ESALQ) - funded by FAPESP (2023/06841-9) and received a support letter from CCARBON/USP; Dr. Amanda Duim Ferreira (USP/ESALQ) - funded by FUSP (Project 107 - RCGI). PhD: M.Sc. Rodolfo Fagundes Costa (USP/ESALQ) - funded by CAPES.

Results:

da Silva, G. R., Lázaro, M. L., Queiroz, H. M., Ferreira, A. D., Ramos, R. A. D., Machado, W. T. V., ... & Nóbrega, G. N. (2024). How do replanted mangroves affect phosphorus dynamics in their soils?. *Journal of environmental management*, 366, 121915.

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: What are the mechanisms and drivers controlling the carbon sequestration and stabilization in Blue Carbon ecosystems?

Summary of achievements: (i) For the evaluation period in this initiative, we have approved an IC FAPESP scholarship entitled “Organomineral Interactions in Mangrove Soil under Different Salinity Conditions” (FAPESP: 2025/00609-2), conducted by the undergrad student Tainara Novaes Bispo under the supervision of Dr. Francisco Ruiz. As a part of the project, the student is completing a research internship abroad at the University of Santiago de Compostela in Spain. The role of different iron minerals, especially short-range ordered Fe oxides and iron sulfides (e.g., monosulfide and pyrite) on C stabilization through adsorption and coprecipitation mechanisms will be evaluated by the Master student, Flaviane Caroline Pagoto. A Master’s FAPESP scholarship was approved (FAPESP: 2025/05523-9). Another research activity involves the project entitled "Impact of global warming on the dynamics of soil organic carbon stocks in mangrove ecosystem: assessment of climate change feedback” (FAPESP: 2024/06285-1), conducted by the postdoc Danilo César de Mello. Finally, as a research highlight for we have published the paper “Iron’s role in soil organic carbon (de)stabilization in mangroves under land use change” (Nature Communications) where we show that Fe oxides protect more labile SOC fractions, which would otherwise be vulnerable to biological degradation, with poorly crystalline Fe oxides being the most effective phase for SOC retention. Despite the fragile equilibrium of FeOMI under dynamic redox conditions in mangroves, this balance sustains approximately 8% of total SOC. The LUC scenario studied led to a massive loss of FeOMIs as less crystalline phases were either degraded or transformed into more crystalline ones, losing the efficiency in retaining SOC. (iii) Conducting a mesocosm experiment using mangrove soil samples to simulate conditions of increased salinity. Our aim is to describe the processes of (de)stabilization of Soil Organic Matter (SOM) and predict the fate of Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) in mangrove soils under rising salinity conditions. We will measure CO₂ emissions, assess changes in particulate organic matter (POM) and mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM), soil enzymatic activity, and investigate changes in iron (Fe) biogeochemistry,

focusing on organomineral interactions. Data analysis will include principal component analysis and structural equation modeling to understand the processes contributing to SOM (de)stabilization. Our results will provide insights into how increased salinity may affect organic carbon sequestration and stabilization in these coastal ecosystems, as well as analyze how the biogeochemical processes that govern organic carbon accumulation in mangrove soil respond to climate change.

Team members: PI: Tiago Osório Ferreira (USP/ESALQ), PA: Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega (UFC), Hermano Melo Queiroz (USP/FFLCH), Diego Barcellos (UNIFESP), Xosé Luis Otero (USC). Post-doc: Dr. Francisco Ruiz (USP/ESALQ), Dra. Amanda Duim Ferreira (USP/ESALQ), Dr. Danilo Cesar de Mello (USP/ESALQ) PhD: M.Sc. Rodolfo Fagundes Costa (USP/ESALQ) - funded by CAPES; M.Sc. Antonio Elves Barreto (USP/ESALQ) funded by CAPES. MSc: Flaviane Caroline Pagoto (USP/ESALQ) - funded by FAPESP (2025/05523-9) and received a support letter from CCARBON/USP. IC: Tainara Novaes Bispo (USP/ESALQ) - funded by FAPESP (2024/07430-5) and received a support letter from CCARBON/USP.

Results:

Ruiz, F., Bernardino, A. F., Queiroz, H. M., Otero, X. L., Rumpel, C., & Ferreira, T. O. (2024). Iron's role in soil organic carbon (de) stabilization in mangroves under land use change. *Nature communications*, 15(1), 10433.

Key questions addressed/Research area 3: How does mangrove replanting influence soil biogeochemistry and nutrient cycling? What are the impacts of wetland restoration on phosphorus (P) fractionation and associated ecosystem services such as nutrient retention and carbon sequestration?

Summary of achievements: (i) During the evaluation period, we focused on understanding the impacts of mangrove restoration on soil phosphorus (P) dynamics and associated biogeochemical processes. (ii) The study was conducted in southeastern Brazil (APA Guapi-Mirim, Rio de Janeiro), comparing soils from unvegetated sites, mature mangroves, and 7- and 9-year-old replanted mangroves. Key findings included a marked increase in TOC with forest age (from 8.6% to 17.9%), significant acidification of soils in restored areas, and strong seasonal fluctuations in redox conditions (Eh ranging from 165% in the dry to -46% in the wet season). Although organic P forms were dominant across all sites, unvegetated areas paradoxically showed higher concentrations than restored or mature forests. Nevertheless, restored forests exhibited lower levels of more labile P fractions (e.g., exchangeable P, Fe/Mn-bound P, and apatite-bound P), suggesting increased P retention through organic and mineral associations. (iii) Workplan for the next period: Mesocosm experiments will simulate climate change scenarios and salinity gradients to evaluate the impacts of these scenarios on P retention in mangrove soils. Adsorption experiments will be conducted, and further attention will be given to the temporal evolution of P pools and their association with Fe and C cycling.

Team members: PI: Tiago Osório Ferreira (USP/ESALQ), PA: Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega (UFC), Hermano Melo Queiroz (USP/FFLCH), Xosé Luis Otero (USC). Post-doc: Dra. Amanda Duim Ferreira (USP/ESALQ) PhD: M. Sc. Gabriela Rodrigues da Silva (UFF) - funded by CAPES, M.Sc. Elves Lima Barreto (USP/ESALQ) funded by CAPES.

Results:

da Silva, G. R., Lázaro, M. L., Queiroz, H. M., Ferreira, A. D., Ramos, R. A. D., Machado, W. T. V., ... & Nóbrega, G. N. (2024). How do replanted mangroves affect phosphorus dynamics in their soils?. *Journal of environmental management*, 366, 121915.

(B) Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Modeling and monitoring of soil carbon using remote sensing and AI for removal and MRV

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, the research line on Soil Carbon advanced in the quantification and monitoring of soil organic carbon (SOC) in tropical regions by integrating geospatial data, spectroscopy, proximal sensing, and machine learning. Scalable approaches were developed to link field measurements with remote sensing, enabling high-resolution mapping and MRV systems for climate mitigation. Actions included the consolidation of spectral libraries, improvement of predictive models, and the association of mineralogy, microbiology, and carbon stabilization. This made it possible to identify areas with higher sequestration potential and to align national monitoring protocols with international standards. Highlights: Progress was made in operationalizing SOC monitoring, reducing uncertainties, and supporting carbon removal policies. Tools integrating spectroscopy, remote sensing, and modeling were applied at regional and national scales, impacting agriculture, forests, and restoration areas. Next period plan: The focus will be on expanding uncertainty-based assessments, integrating microbial data into sequestration models, improving spectral transferability, and incorporating results into national MRV and carbon credit platforms.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Nikolaos Tziolas, PA, (University of Florida) Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2022/14935-0 Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17508-9 (CCARBON/USP) Nicolás Augusto Rosin, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2021/10063-6 e BEPE 2023/11467-9 Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/11350-4 Marcos Guedes de Lana, MSc, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES Victoria Sato Pedral, IC, (ESALQ/USP) – Projeto Fosfato e Mineralogia Students: Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2022/14935-0; (iii) Não Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Sim (CCARBON/USP); (ii) FAPESP 2023/17508-9; (iii) Sim Nicolás Augusto Rosin, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2021/10063-6 e BEPE 2023/11467-9; (iii) Não Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/11350-4; (iii) Não Marcos Guedes de Lana, MSc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES; (iii) Não Victoria Sato Pedral, IC, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) –; (iii) Não

Results:

BARTSCH, B.A. et al. Space-time mapping of soil organic carbon through remote sensing and machine learning. *Soil & Tillage Research*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.still.2024.106428

RODRÍGUEZ-ALBARRACÍN, H.S. et al. Soil organic carbon sequestration potential explained by mineralogical and microbiological activity using spectral transfer functions. *Science of the Total Environment*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174652

VAN WESEMAEL, B. et al. A European soil organic carbon monitoring system leveraging Sentinel 2 imagery and the LUCAS soil data base. *Geoderma*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.geoderma.2024.117113

ROSIN, N.A. et al. Spatializing soil elemental concentration as measured by X-ray fluorescence analysis using remote sensing data. *Catena*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.catena.2024.107988

(C) Principal Investigator: Tsai Siu Mui

Technology: Soil carbon, Crop breeding/physiology, Biochar, Methanotrophy stimulation through use of composed inoculants

Key questions addressed/Research area: This project aims to investigate the role of methanotrophy in carbon sequestration at different stages of ecological succession in restoration areas, pastures, and native forests in the Amazon. The central hypothesis postulates that the increase in methanotrophic bacteria and the reduction in methanogenic archaea promote greater carbon sequestration, favoring the ecological balance throughout forest succession. Another hypothesis tested in this study suggests that model plants will have a positive effect on modulating the microbial community, favoring carbon sequestration. To meet the main goal, soil and litter samples will be collected at different depths (0-10 cm, 10-20 cm, and 20-40 cm) during two seasons (dry and rainy) and two subsequent years. The functional characterization of the microbiota will be conducted through the quantification of functional genes associated with methanotrophy (pmoA and mmoX) and analysis of CH₄ isotopic composition. In parallel, CH₄ emission measurements will be performed using gas chromatography and soil physicochemical analyses will be conducted to assess their influence on microbial processes. The study will be conducted in areas surrounding pastures, forests, and secondary forests in southern Rondônia. The results of this project will enable an understanding of how ecological succession modulates the microbial communities involved in the methane cycle, contributing to the development of forest management and conservation strategies. The findings are also expected to reinforce the role of secondary forests as potential carbon sinks, with direct implications for climate change mitigation. Furthermore, the potential of Ipê (*Handroanthus* spp.), Jatobá (*Hymenaea courbaril*), and Copaíba (*Copaifera* spp.) species in modulating microbial communities will be evaluated to determine their abilities to stimulate methanotrophy and promote nutrient cycling, thus favoring carbon sequestration.

Team members: Tsai Siu Mui, PI (CENA/USP), Juan Andrés de Domini (PhD student), Rafael Barti Dextro (Post-doc) (ii) A PhD fellowship from CAPES, but the PhD proposal will also be submitted to FAPESP (iii) It will be submitted with a letter of support from CCARBON/USP

Summary of achievements: The project has just started.

(D) Associate Research: Angelo Fraga Bernardino**Technology:** Soil carbon**Key questions addressed/Research area:** Total Ecosystem Stocks of Mangroves

Summary of achievements: Our group has been conducting field campaigns to determine the total ecosystem stocks (aboveground carbon, belowground carbon, and soil carbon) in mangrove forests within national territory. In recent years, we carried out three campaigns to assess total stocks along the Amazonian coast of Brazil, sampling mangroves in the states of Pará and Amapá. These expeditions, funded by National Geographic, resulted in an unprecedented dataset on mangroves in Northern Brazil, revealing not only regional stock patterns but also providing data on the effects of land-use changes on carbon stocks. In the coming years, we plan to continue these expeditions in under-sampled or previously unexplored areas, in order to expand our dataset on these stocks and refine national models of the biogeochemical controls over them.

Team members: Angelo Bernardino, Co-PI, UFES, Tiago O. Ferreira, PI, ESALQ/USP, Gabriel C. Coppo, Post-doc, UFES Students Vitor Leonardo Rodrigues/PhD student/UFES, BlueShore scholarship Carla F. Pacheco/PhD student/UFES, CNPq scholarship Lethicia Pinto/Master student/UFES, CAPES scholarship

Results: Bernardino, A. F., Mazzuco, A. C. A., Costa, R. F., Souza, F., Owuor, M. A., Nobrega, G. N., ... & Kauffman, J. B. (2024). The inclusion of Amazon mangroves in Brazil's REDD+ program. *Nature communications*, 15(1), 1549.

(E) Associate Research: Arthur Prudêncio de Araújo Pereira**Technology:** Wetland restoration**Key questions addressed/Research area:** Assessment of the soil microbiome and its relationship with carbon dynamics in mangrove environments

Summary of achievements: The research is just beginning. For the next period, the characterization of the soil microbiome is planned through sequencing of the 16S gene and the ITS region of bacteria and fungi, respectively, in addition to the characterization of the microbial necromass in mangrove soils of different lithologies along the Brazilian coast.

Team members: Arthur Prudêncio de Araujo Pereira, Tiago Osório Ferreira, Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega, Raissa Razera

(F) Associate Research: Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega**Technology:** Wetland restoration**Key questions addressed/Research area 1:** Changing mangroves: How mangrove restoration affects soils characteristics and the provision of ecosystems services?

Summary of achievements: Coastal wetlands, such as mangroves and hypersaline flats (apicuns), are globally significant ecosystems that provide a range of ecosystem services, including carbon sequestration, retention of potentially toxic elements, and enhancement of coastal productivity through nutrient cycling. Due to their importance and the growing

concern about the carbon cycle and its impacts on global climate, researchers and public agencies have been pursuing policies and projects aimed at mangrove restoration to mitigate the increase in greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere. This project aims to evaluate changes in the physicochemical characteristics and pedogenetic processes in soils transitioning between apicuns and mangroves, to understand how mangrove colonization affects the provision of ecosystem services. Soils samples and plant biomass has been systematically collected and analyzed in restored mangroves along the Brazilian Coast (Ceará and Rio de Janeiro states), aiming to improve the comprehension of soils' process related to mangrove restoration. This project supported the work of 4 graduate students (1 DSc and 3 MSc), and 4 undergrad students, conducting activities that gave insights regarding nutrient dynamics in restored mangroves that will help to improve management practices for restoring mangroves.

Team members: Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega (UFC), PI Tiago Osório Ferreira (ESALQ/USP), Associate Investigator (AI) Arthur Prudêncio de Araújo Pereira (UFC), AI Luis Ernesto de Arruda Bezerra (UFC), AI Marcela Lopes Lázaro (M.Sc/UFF), CNPq grant, no support letter Gabriela Rodrigues da Silva (M.Sc/UFF), CNPq and FAPERJ grant, no support letter Marie Frantzie Milien (MSc/UFC), CAPES grant, no support letter Tamia Daniela Cabascango Vasquez (MSc/UFC) CAPES grant, no support letter Flávio Monteiro Gondim (Undergrad, UFC) CNPq grant, no support letter José Fernando Caetano da Cunha (Undergrad, UFC) CAPES grant, no support letter Thayná de Ciza Castanhêde Corrêa (Undergrad, UFF) CAPES grant, no support letter Kaio dos Santos Sobreira (Undergrad, UFC) CAPES grant, no support letter Eleyse da Silva Abreu (Undergrad, UFC) CAPES grant, no support letter.

Results: 2 Doctorate thesis (1 ongoing), 2 Masters dissertation, 2 Final monograph for undergraduate course

da Silva, G. R., Lázaro, M. L., Queiroz, H. M., Ferreira, A. D., Ramos, R. A. D., Machado, W. T. V., ... & Nóbrega, G. N. (2024). How do replanted mangroves affect phosphorus dynamics in their soils?. *Journal of environmental management*, 366, 121915.

Technology: Wetland restoration

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Pro-mangue: optimized mangrove recovery program through fertilization for carbon sequestration and ecosystem services

Summary of achievements: Mangroves are coastal ecosystems that play a crucial role in carbon (C) sequestration and pollutant retention, significantly contributing to climate change mitigation. In this sense, mangrove restoration practices have been encouraged worldwide to mitigate the increase in CO₂ in the atmosphere. However, the degradation of these habitats, driven by human activities and climate change, threatens their ability to provide vital ecosystem services (ES). This project aims to investigate the biogeochemical processes in restored mangroves, focusing on the impact of soil fertilization on C sequestration, ecosystem service provision, and ecosystem health. This project aims to understand how management practices typical of degraded and agricultural areas, such as fertilization, can optimize mangrove recovery. The hypothesis to be investigated posits that fertilization can accelerate mangrove recovery compared to unfertilized forests, increasing biomass and C retention capacity, as well as the provision

of other ES. Therefore, field experiments are being conducted in mangrove areas already recovering, where 25 m² plots will be fertilized with 50 kg of N and P/ha/year, comparing plant growth and soil characteristics with unfertilized plots, as well as with degraded and pristine areas. Thus, plant development (biomass analyses) will be monitored throughout the project, as well as the quantification of C stocks, fractionation of organic matter, metals, and P, as well as microbiological analyses (e.g., enzyme activities and stoichiometry, and sequencing fungi and bacteria). This approach will provide valuable data to guide sustainable management practices, contributing to the conservation and restoration of mangroves on a global scale.

Team members: Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega (UFC), PI Tiago Osório Ferreira (ESALQ/USP), Associate Investigator (AI) Arthur Prudêncio de Araújo Pereira (UFC), AI Luis Ernesto de Arruda Bezerra (UFC), AI Maria Vitoria Ricarte (MSc, UFC), CAPES grant, no support letter Md. Najmus Sayadat Pitol (MSc, UFC) CAPES grant, no support letter

(G) Associate Research: Rodolfo Fagundes Costa

Technology: Afforestation, reforestation and forest management, Soil carbon, Wetland restoration

Key questions addressed/Research area: Evaluation of carbon stocks and sequestration potential in mangrove ecosystems under restoration and conservation scenarios

Summary of achievements: During the period, the MARES project (Mangrove Assisted Restoration for Ecosystem Services) advanced in the establishment of a monitoring and carbon quantification system for mangrove forests in São Paulo State, Brazil. In collaboration with Fundação Florestal, the project implemented protocols to assess total ecosystem carbon stocks (soil, aboveground and belowground biomass, and necromass) in both preserved and impacted mangroves, including areas under natural regeneration and active restoration. Highlights include the consolidation of a strategic partnership between CCARBON/USP and the state environmental agency, strengthening governance and technical capacity for coastal ecosystem monitoring. We also promoted capacity-building through workshops with environmental managers and technical staff and trained undergraduate and graduate students. For the next period, we aim to: (i) finalize laboratory analyses of soil samples for total organic carbon (TOC), bulk density and elemental composition; (ii) systematize vegetation data to complete ecosystem C stock estimates; (iii) develop predictive models of C sequestration based on salinity, disturbance level, and restoration status; (iv) prepare technical reports to guide decision-making by Fundação Florestal and other stakeholders. Manuscripts and policy briefs will be submitted in collaboration with CCARBON/USP's dissemination team.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Tiago Osório Ferreira, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega, professor PA (UFC) Hermano Melo Queiroz, professor PA (FFLCH/USP) Matheus Pinheiro Ferreira, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) Diego Barcellos, Professor (UNIFESP) Arthur Prudêncio de Araujo Pereira, professor PA (UFC) Angelo Fraga Bernardino, professor PA, (UFES) Pedro Henrique Santin Brancalion, professor PA (ESALQ/USP) Paulo Guilherme Molin, professor PA (UFSCAR) Maurício Roberto Cherubin, professor PA (ESALQ/USP) Students: Rodolfo Fagundes Costa, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) Position: PhD student (ESALQ/USP) (i)

Scholarship funded by CCARBON/USP? No (ii) CAPES, process number 88887.481406/2020-00; FUSP/RCGI (iii) Received support letter from CCARBON/USP? No

Results: The MARES project was launched 4 months ago and there are no products yet.

3.3.3 Part 3: GHG emission reduction

(A) Principal Investigator: Tiago Osório Ferreira

Technology: Land use change

Key questions addressed/Research area: How does land use change impact the ability of blue carbon ecosystems to act as carbon sinks? How will climate change and deforestation impact blue carbon soil dynamics?

Summary of achievements: (i) studies on the LUC of Amazonian (conversion to pasture and shrimp farming) and SE-Brazil mangroves (death of mangrove forests upon an extreme climate event) and its impacts on GHG emissions; (ii) as a research summary for this initiative we may highlight the publication of 4 scientific papers (2 in Nature Communications, 1 in Environmental Research, 1 in Marine Pollution Bulletin) and 1 conference paper (SSSA 2024). Our research on Amazonian mangroves, which sheds light on their vital role in carbon dynamics and the profound impacts of land use change (LUC). Our data revealed that methane fluxes near the Amazon River mouth are especially high - representing up to 37% of regional mangrove carbon sequestration. However, conversion of mangroves to pastures or shrimp farms transforms these areas from major carbon sinks to greenhouse gas sources, potentially reversing annual sequestration by an average of 8.0 Mg CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ lost. Furthermore, soil organic carbon stability in mangroves depends heavily on iron-organomineral interactions (FeOMIs), which become severely compromised following LUC as key mineral phases degrade, thus reducing carbon-retention capacity. Additionally, a comprehensive carbon stock assessment across 190 Amazon mangrove plots estimated total ecosystem carbon at 468 Mg ha⁻¹, notably surpassing values found in upland biomes and underscoring the global relevance of mangrove conservation. Conversion of mangroves can unleash emissions triple those of traditional Amazon rainforest conversion, indicating the importance of including mangroves in national climate strategies and carbon market mechanisms. Our Land cover study based on data from MapBiomass highlighted that, since 1985, major mangrove losses along Brazil's coast have been driven by varied factors: livestock and agriculture in the north and south, aquaculture in the northeast, and urbanization in the southeast. These findings emphasize the need for region-specific restoration to maximize carbon credit potential and support Brazil's climate commitments. Finally, GHG flux studies comparing intact and dead mangroves in southeastern Brazil found that intact forests emit significantly more CO₂ and CH₄ during warm, dry periods, with GHG emissions dropping during wet seasons. Interestingly, dead mangroves did not become large ongoing GHG sources, even years after die-off, suggesting complex post-disturbance dynamics. Finally, we have approved a FAPESP Postdoc Scholarship entitled "Impact of Extreme Weather on Iron-Mediated Organo-Mineral Interactions in Mangrove Soils" (FAPESP: 2023/06841-9) conducted by Dr. Francisco Ruiz. (iii) For the next evaluation period, the completion, writing, and publication of the following scientific articles related to the doctoral research of student

Rodolfo Fagundes Costa (entitled “The role of iron on carbon stabilization in mangrove soils”) are expected; (i) Land use change and stock losses arising from historic land use change in Brazilian mangroves as a guiding element for carbon pricing; (ii) The role of Fe in carbon stabilization in mangrove soils within different geological surroundings; (iii) Fe speciation in mangrove soils under different geological surroundings accessed by Fe K-edge X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS); (iv) Fe species under contrasting salinity environments and their impact on C stabilization in mangrove soils of the Amazon River Delta; (v) Fe and S speciation in mangrove soils of the Amazon River Delta accessed by X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS).

Team members: PI: Tiago O Ferreira (ESALQ/USP), Alexandre Demattê (ESALQ/USP) PA: Paulo G. Molin (UFSCAR), Angelo Bernardino (UFES), Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega (UFC), Raul Poppiel (ESALQ/USP), Post-doc: Francisco Ruiz (USP/ESALQ) - funded by FAPESP (2023/06841-9) and received a support letter from CCARBON/USP; Dr. Danilo Cesar de Mello (USP/ESALQ) - funded by FAPESP (2024/06285-1) and received a support letter from CCARBON/USP, Dr. Fellipe Alcantara de Oliveira Mello (USP/ESALQ) - funded by FUSP (Project 107 - RCGI). PhD: M.Sc. Rodolfo Fagundes Costa (USP/ESALQ) - funded by CAPES.

Results:

Bernardino, A. F., Queiroz, H. M., Nobrega, G. N., Coppo, G. C., Sanders, C. J., Silva, A. E., ... & Ferreira, T. O. (2024). Soil greenhouse gas fluxes partially reduce the net gains in carbon sequestration in mangroves of the Brazilian Amazon. *Environmental research*, 263, 120102.

Ruiz, F., Bernardino, A. F., Queiroz, H. M., Otero, X. L., Rumpel, C., & Ferreira, T. O. (2024). Iron’s role in soil organic carbon (de) stabilization in mangroves under land use change. *Nature communications*, 15(1), 10433.

Bernardino, A. F., Mazzuco, A. C. A., Costa, R. F., Souza, F., Owuor, M. A., Nobrega, G. N., ... & Kauffman, J. B. (2024). The inclusion of Amazon mangroves in Brazil’s REDD+ program. *Nature communications*, 15(1), 1549.

Pacheco, C. F., Queiroz, H. M., Mazzuco, A. C. A., Nóbrega, G. N., Ferreira, T. O., & Bernardino, A. F. (2024). Soil greenhouse gas emissions from dead and natural mangrove forests in Southeastern Brazil. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 203, 116487.

<https://scisoc.confex.com/scisoc/2024sssa/meetingapp.cgi/Paper/156464>

(B) Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Technology: Fertilizer management, Residue management, Land use change, Crop management, Water management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Emission mitigation through soil management, land use, and sustainable practices supported by data and modeling

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, research on reducing agricultural GHG emissions advanced in assessing land management and use practices to mitigate soil- and crop-related fluxes. Remote sensing, predictive modeling, and agro-environmental indicators were integrated to identify critical areas and guide strategies that increase input

use efficiency, reduce carbon losses, and maintain soil cover. Methods were developed to monitor the frequency of bare soil—associated with degradation and emissions—alongside improvements in soil physical characterization and the integration of digital mapping with crop growth models. These approaches provided support for conservation practices and more efficient fertilizer management, reducing nitrous oxide emissions and promoting sustainable agricultural systems. Highlights: The research line consolidated a framework linking soil attributes, agricultural management, and GHG emissions, with potential applications in low-carbon agriculture policies and monitoring platforms. Next period plan: The next stage will prioritize integration into MRV systems, expansion of predictive models to different regions, use of climate time series in prospective analyses, and development of technical protocols for national agricultural emissions mitigation programs.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Kabindra Adhikari, PA, (Texas Tech University) Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17876-8 Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2024/11100-0 Borges Marfrann Dias Melo, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00 Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES Miguel Palacio Pelaez Carvalho Neto, IC, (ESALQ/USP) – Projeto IC Mapeamento Calcário/Carbono (FAPESP submetido) Students: Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/17876-8; (iii) Não Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Não Borges Marfrann Dias Melo, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00; (iii) Não Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES; (iii) Não Miguel Palacio Pelaez Carvalho Neto, IC, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP submetido; (iii) Não

Results:

DI RAIMO, L.A.D.L. et al. Sand subfractions by proximal and satellite sensing: Optimizing agricultural expansion in tropical sandy soils. *Catena*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.catena.2023.107604

DOS SANTOS, N.V. et al. Digital soil mapping and crop modeling to define the spatially-explicit influence of soils on water-limited sugarcane yield. *Plant and Soil*, 2024. DOI: 10.1007/s11104-024-06587-w

PELEGRINO, M.H.P. et al. Optimizing soil texture spatial prediction in the Brazilian Cerrado: Insights from random forest and spectral data. *Geoderma Regional*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.geodrs.2025.e00922

SOUSA, G.P.B. et al. Assessing soil degradation in Brazilian agriculture by a remote sensing approach to monitor bare soil frequency: impact on soil carbon. *Soil Advances*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.soilad.2024.100011

(C) Associate Research: Angelo Fraga Bernardino

Technology: Land use change

Key questions addressed/Research area: Carbon emissions associated with land-use changes in mangrove forests

Summary of achievements: This line of research aims to determine the total CO₂ emissions associated with the conversion of mangrove forests due to anthropogenic (aquaculture, pasture) and natural (coastal erosion, climate) activities. During the period, we sampled mangrove forests impacted by extreme climate events in the state of Espírito Santo, as well as assessed the impacts of mangrove conversion into shrimp farms and pastures in the state of Pará. These studies generated unprecedented data on forest emission factors associated with these pressures and provide novel information to support mitigation policies aimed at preventing forest loss in the land-use change sector. In the coming years, we will determine emission factors associated with mangrove loss due to coastal erosion along the Amazonian coast.

Team members: Angelo Bernardino, Co-PI, UFES, Tiago O. Ferreira, PI, ESALQ/USP, Gabriel C. Coppo, Post-doc, UFES Students Vitor Leonardo Rodrigues/PhD student/UFES, BlueShore scholarship Carla F. Pacheco/PhD student/UFES, CNPq scholarship Lethicia Pinto/Master student/UFES, CAPES scholarship

Results:

Bernardino et al., 2024. The inclusion of Amazon Mangroves in Brazil's REDD+ program. *Nature Communications*, 15:1549, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-45459-w>;

Ruiz et al., 2024. Iron's role in soil organic carbon (de)stabilization in mangroves under land use change. *Nature Communications*, 15: 10433, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-54447-z>

Kauffman et al., 2024. Conversion of tropical forests to water buffalo pastures in lower Amazonia: carbon losses and social carbon costs. *Ecosphere*, 15: ecs2.70055. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.70055>

3.4 Sectorial chain: Integrated Systems

Research Sector Chain Coordinator: Leidivan Almeida Frazão

3.4.1 Part 1: General

Summary of achievements: The research activities of the supply chain “Integrated Systems” covered a broad range of fields, involving specialists from diverse fields such as soil fertility, microbiology, crop science, ecology, food science and technology, bioproducts, spectrometry, metabolomics, remote sensing, and agroforestry systems. The researchers work across the Brazilian biomes, reflecting the complexity and multidisciplinary nature of integrated production systems, providing a comprehensive analysis of the various opportunities to both reduce GHG emissions and to remove them from the atmosphere. The objective is to structure the chain's actions according to areas — such as agroforestry systems, crop-livestock-forest integration, bioenergy, food, bioproducts, and biodiversity valorization — to reflect the diversity of ongoing production arrangements and to strengthen alignment with scientific priorities, funding opportunities, and public policy instruments. Two projects focused on the mitigation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in tropical systems, indicating the increase in carbon sequestration using forage grasses in tropical deep soils under no-tillage. Eight different projects investigated the topsoil and deep-soil under pasture, conventional and integrated systems across Atlantic, Caatinga, Cerrado and Amazon biomes, revealing that land use systems with long-term spatial-temporal use of grass in well-managed pastures or integrated systems promoted greater SOC storage and stabilization, enhancing soil health. One project focused on the evaluation soil carbon dynamics following the implementation of agrivoltaic systems (Agri-PV) in Brazilian agroecosystems, and preliminary results showed Agri-PV implementation may initially reduce microbial activity, but SMB-C proved to be a sensitive indicator of early soil biological changes associated with photovoltaic systems. One project aimed to investigate the effects of integrated agricultural production systems in the Caatinga biome and the responses of the associated

microbiome to nutrient cycling in a semi-arid environment. Another research line mixed native and fast growth species models and aimed to investigate silvicultural adaptation and carbon cycle and stocking and those integrated systems. Two projects in the related area of functional foods are currently under development, focusing on the use of by-products from the food industry and the production of materials with functional characteristics for application in food formulations. The main findings showed that adopting diversified systems like ICL and ICLF shows potential to mitigate emissions, but highlights significant data gaps and methodological inconsistencies, urging for standardized, comprehensive research across all Brazilian biomes. Another study in different regions, SP, MS, GO, PE, PI e CE, focusing on the co-benefits of IAS, particularly regarding soil health and biodiversity. A critical analysis of soil health research in Brazil further identified national challenges and priorities, revealing that research is concentrated in specific biomes, leaving large, vulnerable areas under-studied. These findings show that integrated systems can partially restore soil health in degraded sandy pastures. Some of these projects are in an early to intermediate stage of development, but the research in the supply chain have resulted in several scientific contributions, with 23 papers published in leading academic journals, 1MSc thesis and 5 PhD dissertations defended and 2 book chapters, and one filed patent.

3.4.2 Part 2: Carbon removal

(A) Principal Investigator: Leidivan Almeida Frazão

Technology: Soil carbon/ Crop breeding/physiology

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Assessment of soil carbon sequestration potential in integrated agricultural production systems within the Cerrado and Caatinga biomes

Summary of achievements: Integrated Crop-Livestock-Forest (ICLF) systems have emerged as an effective strategy for the restoration of degraded pastures, promoting sustainable production while enhancing local biodiversity through the synergistic interaction of productive components. In this research line, the evaluation of land-use intensification systems implemented in the Cerrado and Caatinga biomes is proposed. The experimental approach consists of testing different productive arrangements according to the specific soil and climate conditions of each site. After data collection of GHG emissions and soil for carbon analysis, soil health will be assessed using the BioAs and SMAF tools. Finally, a multilevel analysis will be carried out using the MEAF tool, evaluating the effects of integrated systems on the provision of soil ecosystem services. Some preliminary results demonstrated that the conversion of low-productivity pastures to integrated crop-livestock-forest systems increased soil carbon stocks. Additionally, the integration of pasture and annual crops with forage legumes contributed to the improvement of soil health.

Team members: Leidivan Almeida Frazão, PI, (UFMG) Mauricio Roberto Cherubin, PA, (ESALQ/USP) Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PA, (ESALQ/USP) Jaqueline de Costa de Oliveira, Post-doc (Bayer), (UFMG) Igor Costa de Freitas, Post-doc (CNPq), (UFMG) Marcos Fernando Gonçalves Lessa, PhD (CAPES), (UFMG) Felipe Jorge Viana, PhD (CNPq), (UFMG) Leonardo Máximo Silva (CNPq), (UFMG) Aline Araujo Reis, MSc (CAPES), (UFMG)

Results:**Published:**

Duarte, A. C. S., Oliveira, J. D. C. D., Oliveira, W. R. D., Freitas, I. C. D., Cardoso, Á. D. S., Couto, A. J. S., ... & Frazão, L. A. (2025). Restoring Soil Health with Legume-Based Integrated Farming Systems. *Sustainability*, 17(8), 3340. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17083340>

de Oliveira, J. D. C., de Freitas, I. C., Duarte, A. C. S., Moreira, J. G. F., Couto, A. J. S., Lessa, M. F. G., ... & Frazão, L. A. (2025). Fertility and carbon stocks in Oxisols under Urochloa pastures and Eucalyptus-based agrosilvopastoral systems established in the Brazilian Cerrado. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 253, 106663.

Under review:

Silvopastoral Systems Improve Soil Health Indicators in the Brazilian Semi-Arid Region -- Applied and Environmental Soil Science (under review)

Spatial pattern of litter decomposition and soil carbon and nitrogen stocks in a silvopastoral system in the Cerrado biome - *Journal of Soil Science and Plant Nutrition* (under review)

Technology: Soil carbon/ Crop breeding/physiology

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Productivity indicators and carbon sequestration potential in integrated agricultural production systems

Summary of achievements: In this research line, we aim to analyze the productivity and carbon sequestration potential of forage and tree components in integrated systems established in the Cerrado region. Crop performance is being evaluated throughout the cycle using variables such as dry mass, average height, productivity, and effective yield (system productivity excluding the area occupied by trees). For the tree component, parameters including diameter at breast height and total tree height are being assessed to calculate wood volume and carbon sequestration over the production cycle. We have selected severous experiments in Minas Gerais State, and the next the next steps consist of: i) evaluation of crop and forage production potential; ii) assessment of soil carbon sequestration potential.

Team members: Leidivan Almeida Frazão, PI, (UFMG) Jaqueline de Costa de Oliveira, Post-doc (Bayer), (UFMG) Igor Costa de Freitas, Post-doc (CNPq), (UFMG) Demerson Luiz de Almeida Barbosa, PhD (CAPES), UFVJM Marcos Fernando Gonçalves Lessa, PhD (CAPES), (UFMG) Felipe Jorge Viana, PhD (CNPq), (UFMG) Leonardo Máximo Silva (CNPq), (UFMG)

(B) Principal Investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Impact of soil tillage on greenhouse gas emissions balance in intensified agricultural systems

Summary of achievements: In the last period, it was possible to complete the literature review of the project, as well as its writing and refinements. Numerous readings were carried out on carbon balance calculation. Different sites with long-term experiments that enable the measurement of soil carbon input and greenhouse gas emissions were also analyzed, with the objective of conducting future sampling for the experiment. We were very pleased to identify a suitable site for the experiment, with several years of implementation, located in Itiquira, in the state of Mato Grosso.

For the next period, the preparation of materials for sample collection will be carried out, followed by the sampling in the selected area, corresponding laboratory analyses (gas sample readings using gas chromatography), and the organization of the obtained data, which will subsequently be subjected to statistical analysis.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, Laura Coltro Estella

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Improving pasture management as a “nature-based solution” for soil carbon sequestration in Brazil

Summary of achievements: (i) Summary of Main Activities Conducted During the Period: The project investigates the impacts of converting pastures into regenerative agricultural systems on the quantity and quality of soil organic matter (SOM) in tropical and subtropical regions of Brazil, also assessing the potential for carbon sequestration and mitigation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The study areas encompass different treatments, including conventional pasture, managed pasture, regenerative agricultural systems, crop-livestock integration, agroforestry systems, and no-tillage. Soil sampling was carried out using a grid (1 ha, nine points every 50 m), collecting disturbed, semi-disturbed, and undisturbed samples (up to 1 m depth) for chemical, physical, and microbiological analyses. Measurements included carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) contents and stocks, soil bulk density, aggregate stability, and enzymatic activity (arylsulfatase and β -glucosidase). Analyses of bulk density, chemical and enzymatic properties, as well as the final determination of C and N stocks, were completed for all areas, with only the interpretation and FTIR analyses remaining. (ii) Highlights: Carbon Sequestration and GHG Mitigation: Initial evidence suggests that regenerative agriculture can increase soil carbon stocks, particularly in degraded pasture areas, contributing to GHG emissions reduction. Changes in SOM: The study demonstrates the potential of land-use change to modify SOM composition and stability, enhancing soil health and resilience. Sustainable Strategies: The results will support strategies to expand the adoption of regenerative practices, strengthening the sustainability of Brazilian agriculture and supporting national climate targets. (iii) Work Plan for the Next Period: Manuscript preparation activities will be coordinated, and the results will be published. The insights gained from these data will enable the identification of management practices and system intensification levels most suitable for soil carbon storage, aiming to minimize global warming potential. Based on this information, it will be possible to more accurately recommend mitigation-oriented management practices in cultivated areas, contributing to reducing the negative impacts of agriculture on GHG emissions and promoting sustainable production systems.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI (ESALQ/USP), Daniel Aquino De Borba, PhD (ESALQ/USP)

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Carbon sequestration in Brazilian pasturelands and integrated systems

Summary of achievements: i) The objective of this study was to systematically synthesize evidence regarding changes in SOC stocks following the conversion of low-productivity pastures in Brazil, and to derive system-specific SOC management factors that would assist in national carbon inventories. A systematic search of peer-reviewed literature published up to December 2024 was conducted. Following a comprehensive screening and data extraction process adhering to an established protocol, 50 studies detailing 57 experimental sites in Brazil were incorporated. The log response ratio (LnRR) was employed as the effect size metric to measure the proportional change in SOC stocks. A linear mixed-effects model was developed to evaluate the effects of management system, implementation duration, and soil depth, incorporating study identity as a random effect. ii) The model was validated for publication bias and residual normality. The meta-analysis indicated an average increase in SOC stock of 15.3% (95% CI: 10.4–20.5%) across all interventions relative to low-productivity baselines. Management factors (MF) were derived for specific systems, ranging from 1.12 for Crop-Livestock Systems (CLS) to 1.40 for Crop-Livestock-Forestry Systems (CLFS) after 20 years of management in the 0-100 cm soil profile. Consequently, estimated annual SOC change rates (ΔC) for this scenario ranged from 0.75 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in CLS to 2.42 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in CLFS. Although total carbon stocks increased with management duration, the average annual accumulation rate decreased over long-term scenarios. The restoration of low-yield pasturelands in Brazil represents an achievable strategy for mitigating climate change. The findings extend beyond merely verifying whether these systems sequester carbon to identifying which systems are most effective and the duration of their efficacy. The incorporation of trees is a key factor in the rate of carbon sequestration, and a long-term perspective is crucial for achieving the complete potential of these restored agroecosystems. iii) Compare the estimated MF to with the national greenhouse gas inventories to suggest new methodologies that could include each integrated production system as different factors for C sequestration account. Apply the meta-analysis results to carbon sequestration modeling on scenarios simulations of management systems and climate horizons.

Team members: Carlos E. P. Cerri, PI, (CCARBON/USP); Stoecio M. F. Maia, PI, (IFAL); Leidivan A. Frazão, PI, (UFMG); José I. A. Castro, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) i)No ii)- iii)No

Results: Submitted Doctoral Thesis - Sustainable intensification of Brazilian pastures: soil health assessment and carbon sequestration / Jose Igor Almeida Castro.

(C) Principal Investigator: Fernando Dini Andreote

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil Biology

Summary of achievements: Activities Performed During the Period: Completion of PhD course credits. Assessment of microbial necromass using HPLC in soil samples collected from diverse biomes and land-use types. Integration and preliminary analysis of obtained results. Work Plan for the Next Period: Selection of representative areas for soil collection. Subsequent soil characterization, DNA extraction, sequencing, and microbial ecology analysis. Continued data analysis and initiation of writing the first research article.

Team members: Fernando Dini Andreote, PI, Brazilian Supervisor, (ESALQ/USP). Rafael Santana Mendonça, PhD Candidate, Graduate Program Soil and Plant Nutrition (ESALQ/USP). The scholarship is not directly funded by, but received a support letter from CCARBON/USP. The scholarship is funded by CAPES (process number 88887.952516/2024-00).

(D) Principal Investigator: João Luis Nunes Carvalho

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Land use changes

Summary of achievements: This project is divided into three complementary parts. The first part is based on the question? Do well-managed pastures in the Brazilian Amazon increase the physical and chemical stability of soil organic carbon (SOC) compared to crop succession systems? In this research line, we published a paper in the Journal of Environmental Management, where we evaluated the mechanisms of SOC storage and stabilization in anthropized Amazon soils, as described below. This study assessed an 11-year field experiment to quantify SOC changes and elucidate SOC stabilization mechanisms in areas under anthropic uses in the southern Amazon of Brazil. Our findings revealed that land use systems with long-term spatial-temporal use of grass in well-managed pastures or ICL promoted greater SOC stabilization through intra-aggregate occlusion, mineral sorption, and chemical recalcitrance, representing a good strategy to enhance SOC storage in Amazon anthropized soils. The second part evaluates the main environmental drivers influencing POC and MAOC storage and assesses the long-term SOC changes across the Cerrado, which is being developed in cooperation with Colorado State University. The first objective involves a systematic meta-analysis to assess the effect of distinct agricultural systems, including their direct and indirect controls on the storage of POC, MAOC, and the changes following land use conversion (Δ POC and Δ MAOC). This work provides evidence that POC and MAOC fractions are shaped by both land use systems and environmental drivers (soil texture, pH, NPP, and temperature) in the Cerrado (this study is in the final stages of writing and will be submitted soon. The next step is to advance the validation of the MEMS 3.01 ecosystem model to evaluate the effect of land management on the dynamic of POC and MAOC fractions under the Cerrado conditions.

Team members: João Carvalho (LNBR/CNPEN), Carlos Eduardo Cerri (ESALQ/USP), Ricardo Bordonal (LNBR/CNPEN), Sarah Tenelli (Post-doc) Student: Sarah Tenelli - Processes (FAPESP # 2022/07665-7 and FAPESP # 2023/18299-4)

Results:

TENELLI, S.; NASCIMENTO, A.F.; GABETTO, F.P.; PIMENTEL, M.L.; STRAUSS, M.; BORDONAL, R.O.; CERRI, C.E.P.; CHERUBIN, M.R.; CARVALHO, J.L.N. Well-managed grass is a key strategy for carbon storage and stabilization in anthropized Amazon soils. *JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT*, v. 373, p. 123742, 2025 – <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.123742>

(E) Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Modeling and monitoring of soil carbon using remote sensing and AI for removal and MRV

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, the research line on Soil Carbon advanced in the quantification and monitoring of soil organic carbon (SOC) in tropical regions by integrating geospatial data, spectroscopy, proximal sensing, and machine learning. Scalable approaches were developed to link field measurements with remote sensing, enabling high-resolution mapping and MRV systems for climate mitigation. Actions included the consolidation of spectral libraries, improvement of predictive models, and the association of mineralogy, microbiology, and carbon stabilization. This made it possible to identify areas with higher sequestration potential and to align national monitoring protocols with international standards. Highlights: Progress was made in operationalizing SOC monitoring, reducing uncertainties, and supporting carbon removal policies. Tools integrating spectroscopy, remote sensing, and modeling were applied at regional and national scales, impacting agriculture, forests, and restoration areas. Next period plan: The focus will be on expanding uncertainty-based assessments, integrating microbial data into sequestration models, improving spectral transferability, and incorporating results into national MRV and carbon credit platforms.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Nikolaos Tziolas, PA, (University of Florida) Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2022/14935-0 Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17508-9 (CCARBON/USP) Nicolás Augusto Rosin, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2021/10063-6 e BEPE 2023/11467-9 Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/11350-4 Marcos Guedes de Lana, MSc, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES Victoria Sato Pedral, IC, (ESALQ/USP) – Projeto Fosfato e Mineralogia Students: Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2022/14935-0; (iii) Não Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Sim (CCARBON/USP); (ii) FAPESP 2023/17508-9; (iii) Sim Nicolás Augusto Rosin, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2021/10063-6 e BEPE 2023/11467-9; (iii) Não Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/11350-4; (iii) Não Marcos Guedes de Lana, MSc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES; (iii) Não Victoria Sato Pedral, IC, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) –; (iii) Não

Results:

BARTSCH, B.A. et al. Space-time mapping of soil organic carbon through remote sensing and machine learning. *Soil & Tillage Research*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.still.2024.106428

RODRÍGUEZ-ALBARRACÍN, H.S. et al. Soil organic carbon sequestration potential explained by mineralogical and microbiological activity using spectral transfer functions. *Science of the Total Environment*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174652

VAN WESEMAEL, B. et al. A European soil organic carbon monitoring system leveraging Sentinel 2 imagery and the LUCAS soil data base. *Geoderma*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.geoderma.2024.117113

ROSIN, N.A. et al. Spatializing soil elemental concentration as measured by X-ray fluorescence analysis using remote sensing data. *Catena*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.catena.2024.107988

(F) Principal Investigator: Maurício Roberto Cherubin

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Effects of integrated agricultural systems on soil carbon sequestration across Brazil

Summary of achievements: Research efforts have focused on understanding soil organic carbon (SOC) dynamics within Brazil's integrated agricultural systems (IAS) using a multifaceted approach that includes spatio-temporal assessments, field experiments (SP, MS, GO, PE, PI e CE), and modeling. A key finding from a three-decade assessment in southeastern Brazil revealed that sustainably managed cropland achieved the highest rates of SOC increase. Similarly, in the Cerrado biome, IAS accounted for approximately 40% more SOC stock than business-as-usual systems. However, experimental work has identified limitations, particularly the influence of soil texture on carbon persistence. IAS established in sandy soils demonstrated lower carbon stability compared to perennial systems, attributed to reduced aggregate stability and biomass input. The role of soil macrofauna was also explored, confirming that earthworm activity significantly boosts short-term carbon inputs and its physical protection through aggregation. Future work will aim to deepen the understanding of these mechanisms. Research will also continue to evaluate the impact of different cover cropping systems on SOC, nutrient cycling, and biomass productivity, and to assess SOC stocks in dryland systems using spectroscopic techniques. The overarching goal is to refine IAS design and management to improve climate change resilience and soil security in Brazil.

Team members: Mauricio Roberto Cherubin, PI, ESALQ/USP Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI, ESALQ/USP Stoécio M. F. Maia, PA, Instituto Federal de Alagoas/IFAL Arthur Prudêncio de Araújo Pereira, PA, Universidade Federal do Ceará/UFC Chukwudi Nwaogu, Post-doc, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FAPESP – 2021/11757-1; (iii) No. Lucas Freitas Nogueira Souza, Post-doc, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No. Beatriz da Silva Vanolli, PhD, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FAPESP – 2022/14212-9; (iii) No. Lucas Tadeu Greschuk, PhD, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FAPESP 2023/00438-8; (iii) Yes. Luan Aparecido Ferreira de Campos, IC, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No.

Results:

Publications in Journals

Greschuk, L. T., Villela, J. M., Maia, S. M. F., Junior, C. R. P., Tonucci, R. G., Signor, D., & Cherubin, M. R. (2025). Soil carbon storage in Brazilian drylands: A review. *Catena*, 257, 109144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2025.109144>

Nwaogu, C., Enaruvbe, G. O., Diagi, B. E., & Cherubin, M. R. (2025). Three-decades assessment of land use changes and soil carbon stocks in Southeastern Brazil. *Environmental Research Communications*, 7, 055021. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7620/add66e>

Nwaogu, C., Diagi, B. E., & Cherubin, M. R. (2025). Research trend and conceptualization of low carbon agricultural systems for food security in Brazil and Africa: a systematic and bibliometric analysis. *Discover Sustainability*, 6, 479. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-025-01071-6>

Nwaogu, C., Diagi, B. E., Ekweogu, C. V., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Soil organic carbon stocks as driven by land use in Mato Grosso State: The Brazilian Cerrado agricultural frontier. *Discover Sustainability*, 5, 382. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00592-w>

Book Chapters

Nwaogu, C., Agidi, V. A., Diagi, B. E., & Cherubin, M. R. (2025). Unveiling the Prospects of Regenerative Agriculture in Promoting Soil-C Stocks... Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-81288-0_12 (Book chapter).

Nwaogu, C., Agidi, V. A., Diagi, B. E., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). The role of agriculture and environmental drivers on soil carbon in Brazil... IEEE International Conference. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AGRETA61912.2024.10949013> (Book chapter).

Conference Papers

Vanolli, B. S., Campos, L. A. F., Chudzik, P., Carvalho, I. S., & Cherubin, M. R. (2025). Soil carbon persistence in integrated agricultural systems. Abstract of the Latin American and Caribbean Soil Carbon Research Symposium.

Nwaogu, C., Nwaiwu, E. R., Diagi, B. E., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Soil carbon and land use dynamics in the greater part of Cerrado biome, Brazil. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 557, 03004. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202455703004>

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Agri-PV system: combining solar energy production with food production and climate change adaptation (“AgriPV_Brazil”)

Summary of achievements: This research line focuses on soil carbon dynamics following the implementation of agrivoltaic systems (Agri-PV) in Brazilian agroecosystems. A field experiment was established in Piracicaba (SP), on a Nitisol, with four treatments: (i) Conventional Photovoltaic (PVC), energy generation without cultivation; (ii) Cultivation Applied to Pre-existing PV (APVP); (iii) Conventional Crop (CC), with full-sun cultivation; and (iv) Agri-PV from the Beginning (APVB), combining panel installation and cultivation simultaneously. Soil samples were collected at two stages: before infrastructure deployment (baseline) and after Agri-PV installation. Carbon-focused analyses include total soil organic carbon (SOC) and microbial biomass carbon (SMB-

C). Laboratory analyses for SOC and its fractions are currently underway. Preliminary results for SMB-C (0–10 cm) reveal early impacts of infrastructure deployment. Although the Agri-PV setup (APVB) showed higher SMB-C (312 mg kg^{-1}) than the traditional PV system without crops (PVC: 259 mg kg^{-1}), the difference was not statistically significant. The highest microbial biomass was observed in the control treatment (CC: 539 mg kg^{-1}), under undisturbed ruzigrass cover, suggesting that Agri-PV implementation may initially reduce microbial activity. Nevertheless, SMB-C proved to be a sensitive indicator of early soil biological changes associated with photovoltaic systems. The next phase will include SOC quantification across all treatments and depths to assess carbon stocks and stabilization potential under different shading and land-use scenarios. The Agri-PV project, funded by TotalEnergies through the Brazilian National Agency for Petroleum, Natural Gas and Biofuels (ANP), is developed within the InovaPower program at the Research Centre for Greenhouse Gas Innovation (RCGI), a São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP) center at the University of São Paulo (USP). Therefore, it is associated by CCARBON/USP, but not funded by it.

Team members: Maurício Roberto Cherubin, PI, ESALQ/USP Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PA, ESALQ/USP Moacir Tuzzin De Moraes, PA, ESALQ/USP Tiago Osório Ferreira, PA, ESALQ/USP Angelo Tiago Azevedo, Post-doc, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No. George Rodrigues Lambais; Post-doc, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No. Rafael Braghieri Menillo, PhD, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No. Anaila Amaral de Alencar, MSc, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No. Gabriel de Almeida Mori Muniz, IC, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No. Finalizou (01/05/2024 a 30/04/2025) João Victor Muller Antigo, IC, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No. Matheus Viana Lopes, IC, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No.

Results:

Lambais, G. R., Menillo, R. B., Mello, F. A., Manito, A. R. A., Alencar, A. A., Vieira, B. J., Fedrizzi, M. C., Almeida, M. P., Moraes, M. T., Ferreira, T. O., Cerri, C. E. P., Muniz, G. A. M., Miura, M., Zilles, R., Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Transforming Small Farms: The Intersection of Energy and Food Security through Agri-PV Systems [Paper presentation]. Energy Transition Research & Innovation Conference - ETRI 2024, São Paulo, Brazil.

Menillo, R. B., Lambais, G. R., Dal Pozzo, B. S., Denny, D. M. T., Manito, A. R. A., Alencar, A. A., Vieira, B. J., Fedrizzi, M. C., Almeida, M. P., Moraes, M. T., Ferreira, T. O., Cerri, C. E. P., Muniz, G. A. M., Miura, M., Zilles, R., Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Agri-PV systems to protect soils and tackle the triple planetary crisis [Paper presentation]. Energy Transition Research & Innovation Conference - ETRI 2024, São Paulo, Brazil.

Muniz, G. A. M., Menillo, R. B., Lambais, G. R., Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Agrivoltaics systems: connecting agriculture and energy in a sustainable way. [Paper presentation]. 32º SIICUSP (Simpósio Internacional de Iniciação Científica e Tecnológica da USP), Piracicaba, Brazil.

(G) Principal Investigator: Rodrigo E. Hakamada

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Mixed native and fast growth species models

Summary of achievements: The main objective of the so-called Legal Reserve area, that farmers must have in their properties, is the concomitant preservation and production of forest products. To encourage farmers to restore those areas, we are proposing a research line about multi-functional forests, where native trees are planted mixed with fast growing trees. Among the native trees, an important alternative is the use of native fruit tree species, such as pitanga (*Eugenia uniflora*), cereja real (*Eugenia aggregata*) ou jabuticaba (*Plinia cauliflora*). The objective of this research line is to investigate silvicultural adaptation and carbon cycle and stocking and those integrated system. An experimental area was set in Anhembi station in May 2025, so, there are no results for a while, but many dissertations and theses are already planned to study this system deeply.

Team members: Rodrigo E. Hakamada, PI (ESALQ/USP), José Leonardo de Moraes Gonçalves (ESALQ/USP), João Carlos Teixeira Mendes (ESALQ/USP).

(H) Principal Investigator: Tsai Siu Mui

Technology: Soil carbon, Crop breeding/physiology, Biochar, Methanotrophy stimulation through use of composed inoculants

Key questions addressed/Research area: This project aims to investigate the role of methanotrophy in carbon sequestration at different stages of ecological succession in restoration areas, pastures, and native forests in the Amazon. The central hypothesis postulates that the increase in methanotrophic bacteria and the reduction in methanogenic archaea promote greater carbon sequestration, favoring the ecological balance throughout forest succession. Another hypothesis tested in this study suggests that model plants will have a positive effect on modulating the microbial community, favoring carbon sequestration. To meet the main goal, soil and litter samples will be collected at different depths (0-10 cm, 10-20 cm, and 20-40 cm) during two seasons (dry and rainy) and two subsequent years. The functional characterization of the microbiota will be conducted through the quantification of functional genes associated with methanotrophy (*pmoA* and *mmoX*) and analysis of CH₄ isotopic composition. In parallel, CH₄ emission measurements will be performed using gas chromatography and soil physicochemical analyses will be conducted to assess their influence on microbial processes. The study will be conducted in areas surrounding pastures, forests, and secondary forests in southern Rondônia. The results of this project will enable an understanding of how ecological succession modulates the microbial communities involved in the methane cycle, contributing to the development of forest management and conservation strategies. The findings are also expected to reinforce the role of secondary forests as potential carbon sinks, with direct implications for climate change mitigation. Furthermore, the potential of Ipê (*Handroanthus* spp.), Jatobá (*Hymenaea courbaril*), and Copaíba (*Copaifera* spp.) species in modulating microbial communities will be evaluated to determine their abilities to stimulate methanotrophy and promote nutrient cycling, thus favoring carbon sequestration.

Team members: Tsai Siu Mui, PI (CENA/USP), Juan Andrés de Domini (PhD student), Rafael Barti Dextro (Post-doc) (ii) A PhD fellowship from CAPES, but the PhD proposal will also be submitted to FAPESP (iii) It will be submitted with a support letter from CCARBON/USP.

Summary of achievements: The project has just started.

(I) Associate Research: Arthur Prudêncio de Araujo Pereira

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Integrated Production Systems in the Brazilian Semiarid: An Analysis of the Soil Microbiome

Summary of achievements: Land-use change and the loss of soil organic matter (SOM) in agricultural areas are the activities that most contribute to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in Brazil. In this context, adopting management practices that reduce GHG emissions, such as integrated agricultural production systems (IAPS), is essential to mitigate climate change and ensure sustainable agricultural development. However, although the benefits of IAPS have been demonstrated in some regions, such as the Cerrado and Atlantic Forest biomes, their potential remains almost unexplored in the Brazilian drylands (Caatinga biome). Furthermore, studies exploring the microbiome associated with soil nutrient cycling are scarce in these areas, especially at larger geographical scales. Therefore, this project aims to investigate the effects of integrated agricultural production systems in the Caatinga biome and the responses of the microbiome associated with nutrient cycling in a semiarid environment. The experimental design will be conducted in randomized blocks in all the cities involved in the study. In Betânia do Piauí/PI, a 2x3 factorial scheme will be used, where the first factor corresponds to the integrated management systems (Crop-Forest Integration [CFI] and native vegetation), and the second factor to the three soil sampling depths (0.0–0.10 m; 0.10–0.20 m; 0.20–0.30 m). In Petrolina/PE, the factorial scheme will also be 3x3, with the first factor representing the integrated management systems (Crop-Livestock-Forest Integration [CLFI], monoculture, and native vegetation), and the second factor corresponding to the same three sampling depths (0.0–0.10 m; 0.10–0.20 m; 0.20–0.30 m). For Sobral/CE, the design follows a 4x3 factorial scheme. The first factor will include the integrated management systems (Crop-Livestock-Forest Integration [CLFI 1 year], Crop-Livestock-Forest Integration [CLFI 6 years], monoculture, and natural Caatinga), while the second factor will be the three soil sampling depths (0.0–0.10 m; 0.10–0.20 m; 0.20–0.30 m). The enzymatic activities arylsulfatase (ARS), β -glucosidase (BG), acid (AP) and alkaline (ALP) phosphatase, and urease (U) will be quantified, as well as DNA extraction and sequencing of the samples. The Soil Management Assessment Framework (SMAF) will be adopted to assess soil health, and the Multifunctionality Index will be used as a metric to evaluate the ability of an integrated system to provide multiple ecosystem services simultaneously. Data will be analyzed using analysis of variance (F-test) and mean comparison (Tukey test at 5% probability). Regarding the DNA sequencing data, the raw sequences will be analyzed using the Quantitative Insights Into Microbial Ecology software (v.1.9.1) following the pipelines available at: qiime.org. This project is expected to provide a solid foundation for how conservation practices can improve soil health. Understanding the microbiome associated with nutrient cycling will be fundamental for improving these techniques and may enable viable soil management strategies in the Brazilian semiarid.

Team members: Arthur Prudêncio de Araujo Pereira, Mauricio Roberto Cherubin, Gabriel Nuto Nobrega, Murilo de Sousa Almeida (Estudante de doutorado)

(J) Associate Research: Carlos Alexandre Costa Crusciol

Technology: Soil carbon, Crop breeding/physiology, Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS)

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil carbon, Crop breeding/physiology and BECCS (This line evaluates lime and calcium/magnesium silicate as tools to enhance soil carbon sequestration and reduce GHG emissions in tropical no-till systems, combining field and greenhouse experiments to assess carbon inputs, stabilization, and emission dynamics).

Summary of achievements: Substantial progress was achieved in implementing the long-term field experiment focused on the mitigation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions using lime and calcium/magnesium silicate under tropical no-till systems. The experimental setup was successfully established with soybean–maize rotations (2024–2026) intercropped with *Urochloa ruziziensis*. Soil sampling and installation of GHG monitoring infrastructure, including PVC collars and LI-COR IRGA systems, were completed. Protocols for collecting above- and belowground biomass, root C and N, and plant biochemical components were initiated. Systematic measurements of CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O fluxes during crop cycles began, alongside soil moisture and temperature monitoring. Key achievements during this period include: (i) calibration and reliable operation of the LI-COR IRGA system for high-resolution GHG flux data; (ii) detailed destructive sampling for dry matter and root C and N using LECO elemental analysis; (iii) execution of soil analyses, including total C and N, pH, and organic matter fractionation into particulate (POM) and mineral-associated (MAOM) pools; and (iv) initiation of a controlled greenhouse trial to compare the direct CO₂ release from lime versus silicate reactions in previously unamended soils. For the next phase, the workplan includes completing field campaigns for soybean and maize (2025/2026), maintaining GHG flux measurements, and calculating cumulative emissions and CO₂-equivalent values. Comprehensive evaluations of soil physical, biochemical, and microbiological indicators (e.g., microbial biomass, basal respiration, qCO₂) will be conducted. The carbon balance and conservation index will be estimated based on inputs and losses, and results will be linked to grain yield to determine GHG efficiency per kilogram of production.

Team members: Carlos Alexandre Costa Crusciol, PI (FCA/UNESP); João Henrique dos Santos Ferreira, PhD Fellow (FCA/UNESP); Laura Tarrafel da Silva, IC Fellow (FCA/UNESP); Marcela Pacola Oliveira, Post-doc applicant (FCA/UNESP); Juliano Carlos Calonego, Faculty Member (FCA/UNESP); José Roberto Portugal, Collaborator (FCA/UNESP, not funded by CCARBON/USP). Students: João Henrique dos Santos Ferreira / PhD Fellow / FCA–UNESP (Department of Crop Production) (i) Is the scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP? No (ii) Funding agency and process number: FAPESP – Process nº 2023/18096-6 (iii) Did the scholarship receive a support letter from CCARBON/USP? Yes Laura Tarrafel da Silva / IC Fellow / FCA–UNESP (Department of Crop Production) (i) Is the scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP? No (ii) Funding agency and process number: FAPESP – Process nº

2024/08385-3 (iii) Did the scholarship receive a support letter from CCARBON/USP?
Yes

Results:

This research line is linked to two approved FAPESP projects:

- PhD – FAPESP Process nº 2023/18096-6: Potencial mitigador de gases de efeito estufa com uso de calcário e silicato de cálcio e magnésio em sistema de semeadura direta de longa duração
- IC – FAPESP Process nº 2024/08385-3: Calcário e silicato de cálcio e magnésio no balanço de carbono em semeadura direta de longa duração

Published article: Ferreira, J. H. S., Portugal, J. R., Fróes, M., Bossolani, J. W., Calonego, J. C., Crusciol, C. A. C. (2025). Boosting carbon sequestration by using forage grass in tropical deep soil with no-tillage. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 109750. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2025.109750> No thesis or dissertation has been defended yet under this research line, and additional manuscripts are currently under preparation.

(K) Associate Research: Lucas William Mendes

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Impact of Cover Crops on Soil Health: Microbial Diversity and Phosphorus Dynamics in Sustainable Agricultural Systems

Summary of achievements: This project aims to determine how cover crops alter C and P cycling processes, the soil microbiota, and related ecosystem services through complementary studies. To this end, two short- and long-term field experiments and one controlled pot experiment will be evaluated. The first study will investigate the contribution of cover crops to agricultural sustainability, focusing on soil carbon reservoirs and impacts on soil health and multifunctionality. More specifically, the second study will explore the microbial (soil–plant) feedbacks left by cover crops for a subsequent commercial crop, assessing how cover crops modulate microbial community networks and P-cycling genes such as *pqqC* and *phoC* to enhance P availability. The third study will evaluate how cover crops associated with arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi affect soil P dynamics, shifting P reservoirs in no-till systems managed with these plants over short and long periods. Additionally, a greenhouse experiment will be conducted during an international research stay to analyze microbial recruitment in the rhizosphere of cover crops through metabolite exudation under conditions of high and low P limitation. This project is expected to generate insights into how cover crops modulate the soil microbiome and C and P dynamics, contributing to the development of more sustainable agricultural practices. The PhD candidate Luana do Nascimento Silva Barbosa is developing this research with FAPESP scholarship (2024/17838-1).

Team members: Lucas William Mendes, PI (CENA-USP). Student: Luana Nascimento Silva Barbosa. Project: Impacto de plantas de cobertura na saúde do solo: diversidade microbiana e dinâmica do fósforo em sistemas agrícolas sustentáveis (FAPESP 2024/17838-1). YES - We received CCARBON/USP's supporting letter.

(L) Associate Research: Luís Reynaldo Ferracciú Alleoni

Technology 1: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil chemical and biological attributes and plant nutrition under conventional pasture and integrated crop-livestock-forestry systems

Summary of achievements: (i) synthesis of the main activities performed during the period: the following laboratory analyses were performed, such as determination of dissolved organic carbon contents; fractionation of soil organic matter; mid-infrared spectroscopy using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy; quantification of nitrate and ammonium; analysis of elemental concentrations in pasture and eucalyptus plant tissues; and soil phosphorus fractionation. Additionally, a research scholarship abroad (BEPE) from FAPESP was approved, which began in February 2025 under the supervision of Dr. José Carlos Batista Dubeux Junior, at the University of Florida. During the first half of 2025, the student carried out the including: quantification of carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) in soil organic matter fractions; C and N concentrations in plant tissue (pasture and eucalyptus); and identification of the soil microbial community. The student also conducted three soil biological activity test using soil incubation techniques, as well as fractionation of soil organic matter from samples collected in the United States. (ii) highlights: approval and initiation of an international research internship (BEPE-FAPESP); completion of analyses; and execution of soil incubation experiments focused on biological activity; (iii) workplan for the next period: analyses soil solution samples and conduct a new incubation study to evaluate C-13 dynamics in CO₂. In 2026, the primary focus will be on data analysis, manuscript preparation, and development of the thesis.

Team members: - Luís Reynaldo Ferracciú Alleoni, PI (ESALQ/USP) - Tamires M. Ercole, PhD candidate (ESALQ/USP) (i) Is the scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP? No (ii) Funding agency and process number: FAPESP: 2023/14904-0 - Doctorate/Continuous Flow, and 2024/13958-2 - BEPE - Doctorate/Continuous Flow (iii) Did the scholarship receive a support letter from CCARBON/USP? Yes

Technology 2: Biochar

Key questions addressed/Research area: Variations of ambient temperature impacting chemical and biological attributes of a sediment contaminated with zinc and cadmium and remediated with biochar

Summary of achievements: (i) synthesis of the main activities performed during the period: During this reporting period, the focus was on transforming the chapters of Mariana Pollo's MS dissertation into scientific articles for submission to peer-reviewed journals. The first article, "Do changes in ambient temperature affect cadmium and zinc pools in a contaminated soil amended with biochar?", was submitted to Environmental Pollutants and Bioavailability. The second article, "Temperature sensitivity (Q10) and β -glucosidase activity in a mine tailing sediment amended with sugarcane-straw biochar", was submitted to the Journal of Environmental Quality. The results of the DNA sequencing results for sediment samples enabled the assessment of the bacterial 16S rRNA community, and the third article based on this molecular analysis has been under construction. (ii) highlights: Completion and submission of two manuscripts to international peer-reviewed journals. Receipt and interpretation of microbial community data (16S rRNA), which provided new insights for the third manuscript in development.

(iii) workplan for the next period: Follow up on the peer-review process for the submitted manuscripts and prepare responses to reviewers' comments if necessary. Finalize and submit the third manuscript focused on microbial community responses to temperature variation and biochar amendment.

Team members: - Luís Reynaldo Ferracciú Alleoni, PI (ESALQ/USP). Mariana P. Pollo, MSc student (ESALQ/USP) (i) Is the scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP? No (ii) Funding agency and process number: FAPESP: 2023/04271-0 - Masters/Continuous Flow (iii) Did the scholarship receive a support letter from CCARBON/USP? Yes

Results: “Variations of ambient temperature impacting chemical and biological attributes of a sediment contaminated with zinc and cadmium and remediated with biochar” - Mariana Pezzatte Pollo - Dissertation presented to obtain the degree of Master in Science. Area: Soils and Plant Nutrition – University of São Paulo, Luiz de Queiroz College of Agriculture – Graduate Program in Soils and Plant Nutrition – 2024

Technology 3: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Enzymatic activity and CO₂ emission by soil microbiota as a function of ambient temperature variation in an Oxisol under degraded pasture and under crop-livestock-forest integration

Summary of achievements: (i) synthesis of the main activities performed during the period: The following laboratory analyses were conducted to assess soil properties and quality. The chemical characterization included the determination of pH in 0.01 M CaCl₂, potential acidity, exchangeable cation contents (such as calcium, magnesium, potassium, and aluminum), available phosphorus, and other essential nutrients, with the aim of evaluating soil fertility. Basal soil respiration was measured by quantifying the CO₂ released by microbial activity, serving as an indicator of biological activity. Contents of dissolved organic carbon were quantified. Soil organic matter fractionation was performed to separate the light and heavy fractions, allowing for an assessment of carbon stability and dynamics. Additionally, mid-infrared spectroscopy using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was applied to qualitatively characterize the functional groups present in the soil organic matter. Finally, the enzymatic activities of β-glucosidase, acid phosphatase, and arylsulfatase were determined, which are associated with the carbon, phosphorus, and sulfur cycles, respectively, and serve as bioindicators of soil health and functionality.

(ii) highlights: The execution of advanced analyses for assessing soil quality, such as FTIR spectroscopy. The student also began writing a scientific article based on the research findings. Additionally, the preparation of the FAPESP report contributed to the development of technical and academic writing skills.

(iii) workplan for the next period: Publication of a manuscript to be submitted to a scientific journal.

Team members: Luís Reynaldo Ferracciú Alleoni, PI (ESALQ/USP) - Bruno Stella, Undergraduate Student (ESALQ/USP) (i) Is the scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP? No (ii) Funding agency and process number: FAPESP: 2024/03712–

6 – Undergraduate Research Fellowship (Scientific Initiation) (iii) Did the scholarship receive a support letter from CCARBON/USP? Yes

(M) Associate Research: Newton La Scala Jr.

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Monitoring CO₂ emission and reduction in ecosystems

Summary of achievements: With the improvement of remote sensing tools we have used O-CO₂ and GoSat satellite data to monitor CO₂ exchange over agricultural areas and ecosystems. Our recent results have shown that xCO₂ (atmospheric CO₂ concentration) has significant differences over areas with contrasting management practices. We could improve this over other sites, once management is characterized in ground.

Team members: Newton La Scala Jr.

Results:

ODORIZZI DE CAMPOS, MARCELO ; PELLEGRINO CERRI, CARLOS EDUARDO ; LA SCALA, NEWTON . Atmospheric CO₂, soil carbon stock and control variables in managed and degraded pastures in central Brazil. Remote Sensing Applications-Society And Environment, v. 28, p. 100848-100861, 2022.

(N) Associate Research: Ricardo de Oliveira Bordonal

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil carbon stabilization mechanisms

Summary of achievements:

Team members: 1. Carlos Eduardo Pelegrino Cerri (PI) – ESALQ/USP. 2. Maurício Roberto Cherubin (PI) – ESALQ/USP. 3. João Luís Nunes Carvalho (PI) – LNBR/CNPEN. 4. Ricardo de Oliveira Bordonal (PA) – LNBR/CNPEN. 5. Diego Alexander Aguilera Esteban (Pos-Doc) – LNBR/CNPEN. Bolsa FAPESP (#23/10866-7), concedida com carta de apoio do CCARBON/USP. 6. Sarah Tenelli (Pos-Doc) – LNBR/CNPEN. Bolsa FAPESP (#22/07665-7).

Results:

DOR, M.; BORDONAL, R.O.; GUBER, A.K.; RIVERS, M.L.; KRAVCHENKO, A. Contrasting land-uses affect chemical composition of organic matter in tropical soils: A case study via osmium staining and infrared spectroscopy. JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT, v. 388, p. 126067, 2025. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.126067>

TENELLI, S.; NASCIMENTO, A.F.; GABETTO, F.P.; PIMENTEL, M.L.; STRAUSS, M.; BORDONAL, R.O.; CERRI, C.E.P.; CHERUBIN, M.R.; CARVALHO, J.L.N. Well-managed grass is a key strategy for carbon storage and stabilization in anthropized Amazon soils. JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT, v. 373, p. 123742, 2025. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.123742>

BORDONAL, R.O.; DOR, M.; GUBER, A.K.; CHERUBIN, M.R.; NASCIMENTO, A.F.; TENELLI, S.; LA SCALA, N.; CERRI, C.E.P.; CARVALHO, J.L.N.; KRAVCHENKO, A.N. Synchrotron X-ray tomography to decipher the role of pore structure in driving soil carbon accrual in contrasting land use systems in tropical agroecosystems. *JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT*. 2025. [Submetido/Em revisão].

(O) Associate Research: Rogerio Martins Mauricio

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area: cattle nutrition, silvopastoral systems Associate professor at the Federal University of São João del-Rei (UFSJ) and member of the Global Agenda for Sustainable Livestock (GASL – FAO). Researcher in ruminant nutrition, silvopastoral systems, and natural regeneration of native trees. Works on forage evaluation, GHG reduction, measuring the efficiency of natural resource use in livestock systems, sustainable techniques for ruminant production, and addressing climate change in the tropics.

Summary of achievements: Scientific publications, projects (International atomic energy agency and Global Agenda for Sustainable Livestock), congress (ASAS-CSAS), meetings (IAEA Asutria, GASL Rome). Strong scientific collaboration with Prof Adibe (CENA).

Team members: Rogerio Martins Mauricio, Laura Bertolaso De Vecchi (doutoranda), Scholarship from FAPESP, no support from CCABON

Results: Ovani, V., Pérez-Márquez, S., Monteiro, A., Kruger, A. M., de Mello Tavares Lima, P., Bizzuti, B. E., ... & Abdalla, A. L. (2024). Understanding the impacts of intensity and harvest frequency on *Tithonia diversifolia* for use in tropical silvopastoral systems. *Grassland Science*.

Pérez-Márquez, S., Ovani, V., Meira, V. E., de Azevedo Olival, A., Louvandini, H., de Morais, J. P. G., ... & Abdalla, A. L. (2025). Assessing the impact of *Samanea tubulosa* trees on methane emissions and its potential as a feed supplement for ruminants in silvopastoral systems. *Agroforestry Systems*, 99(6), 135.

(P) Associate Research: Stoécio Malta Ferreira Maia

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil carbon sequestration in integrated systems and pastures in the Brazilian semiarid region

Summary of achievements: Fieldwork was conducted in four locations in Brazil's semiarid region, encompassing various livestock-forest integration systems. The focus was to assess the dynamics of soil C and organic matter.

Team members: Stoécio M.F. Maia, Adviser (IFAL). Crislâny Canuto dos Santos (PhD. UFAL). Thamirys Suelle da Silva (PhD. UFAL). Handerson Brandão Melo de Lima (MSc. UFAL). José Marcone da Silva (MSc. UFAL). None of them were scholarship holders or received direct support from CCARBON/USP.

Results:

Two doctoral and two master's degree papers have been completed. Five articles have been submitted so far. One has been accepted but has not yet been published; the others are under review. In addition, three other papers are being finalized and should be submitted by the end of August.

3.4.3 Part 3: GHG emission reduction**(A) Principal Investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri**

Technology: Land use change/ Crop management/ Soil Carbon and Nitrogen Biogeochemistry

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Use of different land-uses and soil management to soil carbon and nitrogen

Summary of achievements: During the reporting period, two major studies advanced understanding of deep-soil biogeochemistry in the southeastern Amazon. The first examined deep soil nitrogen (N) dynamics across forest, recently deforested, single-crop soybean, and double-crop soybean–corn systems to 8 m depth. We found that deforestation alone—without fertilization—drove significant redistribution of N from surface to deep layers, likely via mineralization and leaching following slash-and-burn. Croplands exhibited similar total N stocks to forests but with distinct nitrate enrichment at 3–6 m depth, suggesting combined effects of land conversion and fertilization. These results clarify initial mechanisms of deep nitrate formation and highlight the long-term legacy of deforestation on N cycling. The second paper investigated deep-soil carbon (C) distribution under native forest, pasture, recently deforested, single-cropped soybean, and double-cropped soybean–maize. Across land uses, 30–40% of C to 8 m was stored in the top metre, with ~50% in the upper 3 m. Forest-to-cropland conversion reduced mineral-associated organic matter C to 1 m depth, while intensification (double cropping) partially restored surface C pools. Pasture promoted particulate organic matter accrual at depth. These findings emphasize the need to sample beyond the conventional 1 m profile to capture full C dynamics under tropical land-use change. In the coming period, we will finalize and submit the manuscript “Short-term deforestation and conversion to cropland systems drive shifts of soil bacterial and fungal communities in the southeastern Amazon” to *Soil Biology & Biochemistry*. This work links land-use change, microbial community composition, and C and N fractions, adding a mechanistic, biological dimension to our previous geochemical findings.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo P. Cerri, Gustavo Vicentini Popin (PhD) Gustavo Vicentini Popin/ former PhD student/"Luiz de Queiroz" College of Agriculture - University of São Paulo FAPESP, Process number 2019/25988-5, No support letter from CCARBON/USP.

Results:**Thesis:**

Popin, G. V., & Cerri, C. E. P. (2024). Land-use change and agricultural intensification: impacts on carbon and nitrogen distribution in soil profiles of the Amazon-Cerrado frontier.

Publications:

Popin, G. V., de Resende, M. E. B., Locatelli, J. L., Santos, R. S., Siqueira-Neto, M., Brando, P. M., ... & Cerri, C. E. (2025). Land-use change and deep-soil carbon distribution on the Brazilian Amazon-Cerrado agricultural frontier. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 381, 109451.

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Spectroscopic Techniques and Modeling Applied to Soil Organic Matter Dynamics in Pasture Systems under Different Brazilian Biomes

Summary of achievements: Soil organic matter (SOM) is a key indicator of soil quality, influencing edaphic properties and playing a crucial role in climate change mitigation. Quantifying and understanding the stabilization mechanisms of SOM is essential for the development of sustainable agricultural systems. Pasture management, combined with soil characteristics and edaphoclimatic conditions of different Brazilian biomes, directly affects SOM dynamics, though these effects remain underexplored. In addition to quantification, assessing the chemical quality of SOM—focusing on functional groups and carbon protection within aggregates—is necessary. Non-destructive techniques, such as laser-induced fluorescence spectroscopy, have proven effective in this context. Integrating these data with existing surveys through modeling allows the simulation of management scenarios in terms of carbon stocks, SOM quality, and soil health. This project aims to understand how different pasture conditions (native, managed, degraded, and integrated) affect SOM and its chemical properties. The association of modeling with functional SOM characterization is strategic to advance the understanding of SOM dynamics in pasture systems and to support Brazil in achieving its Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) goals.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri/Advisor/ESALQ/USP and CCARBON/USP / Kelly Tamires Urbano Daboit/PhD Student/ ESALQ/USP. and CCARBON (i) Is the scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP? Yes (ii) Funding agency and process number : 2025/11644-3 (iii) Did the scholarship receive a support letter from CCARBON/USP? Yes

(B) Principal Investigator: Joao Luis Nunes Carvalho

Technology: Land use change

Key questions addressed/Research area: N₂O emissions

Summary of achievements: In this research, we applied a multiscale approach by integrating high-resolution computed tomography based on synchrotron radiation and ¹⁵N-labelled fertilizers to trace the pathways of N₂O production. The first paper has been written and submitted, and the details are described below: Understanding how soil pore structure controls nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions remains a critical challenge for climate

mitigation in tropical systems. Here, we combine synchrotron-based X-ray computed microtomography (SXRCT), soil hydraulic modeling, and ^{15}N -labelled fertilizers to investigate how soil pore architecture and air-water dynamics regulate N_2O pathways in soils under long-term experiment in the Amazon biome. The experiment includes crop succession, integrated crop-livestock, and well-managed pasture systems. We show that pore architecture, particularly the increase in fraction of 10-30 μm pores and greater global average pore distance, enhances N_2O production by promoting anaerobic microsites for denitrification. At the macro-scale, increased air-filled porosity and inter-aggregate pores (30-80 μm) facilitate gas diffusion, enabling N_2O produced in micro-scale zones to reach the atmosphere. The integrated crop-livestock system exhibited the highest N_2O emissions due to favorable structural and biochemical conditions, while pasture maintained lower emissions. These findings highlight the key role of soil pore heterogeneity in modulating N_2O pathways across tropical land use systems. In the next steps of the FAPESP project, we will make progress in: i) analyzing and discussing the effects of anthropogenic land use in the Amazon on soil structure, using a multiscale approach based on conventional and synchrotron radiation tomography techniques; ii) developing and submitting a proposal for a research internship abroad (BEPE), with the aim of quantifying and correlating N_2O emissions with the distribution of particulate organic matter (POM) in different systems (crop succession, crop-livestock integration and pasture), using X-ray microtomography.

Team members: João Carvalho (LNBR/CNPEN), Carlos Eduardo Cerri (ESALQ/USP), Ricardo Bordonal (LNBR/CNPEN), Thais Nascimento Pessoa (Post-doc FAPESP # 2023/11900-4)

Results:

PESSOA, T.N.; FERREIRA, T.R.; OLIVEIRA, A.B.; BORDONAL, R.O.; NASCIMENTO, A.F.; CHERUBIN, M.R.; CERRI, C.E.P.; CARVALHO, J.L.N. Micro-scale pore architecture drives nitrous oxide emission pathways in Amazon anthropized soils. COMMUNICATIONS EARTH & ENVIRONMENT. Under consideration.

(C) Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Technology: Fertilizer management, Residue management, Land use change, Crop management, Water management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Emission mitigation through soil management, land use, and sustainable practices supported by data and modeling

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, research on reducing agricultural GHG emissions advanced in assessing land management and use practices to mitigate soil- and crop-related fluxes. Remote sensing, predictive modeling, and agro-environmental indicators were integrated to identify critical areas and guide strategies that increase input use efficiency, reduce carbon losses, and maintain soil cover. Methods were developed to monitor the frequency of bare soil—associated with degradation and emissions—alongside improvements in soil physical characterization and the integration of digital mapping with crop growth models. These approaches provided support for conservation practices and more efficient fertilizer management, reducing nitrous oxide emissions and promoting sustainable agricultural systems. Highlights: The research line consolidated a

framework linking soil attributes, agricultural management, and GHG emissions, with potential applications in low-carbon agriculture policies and monitoring platforms. Next period plan: The next stage will prioritize integration into MRV systems, expansion of predictive models to different regions, use of climate time series in prospective analyses, and development of technical protocols for national agricultural emissions mitigation programs.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Kabindra Adhikari, PA, (Texas Tech University) Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17876-8 Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2024/11100-0 Borges Marfrann Dias Melo, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00 Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES Miguel Palacio Pelaez Carvalho Neto, IC, (ESALQ/USP) – Projeto IC Mapeamento Calcário/Carbono (FAPESP submetido) Students: Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/17876-8; (iii) Não Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Não Borges Marfrann Dias Melo, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00; (iii) Não Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES; (iii) Não Miguel Palacio Pelaez Carvalho Neto, IC, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP submetido; (iii) Não

Results:

DI RAIMO, L.A.D.L. et al. Sand subfractions by proximal and satellite sensing: Optimizing agricultural expansion in tropical sandy soils. *Catena*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.catena.2023.107604

DOS SANTOS, N.V. et al. Digital soil mapping and crop modeling to define the spatially-explicit influence of soils on water-limited sugarcane yield. *Plant and Soil*, 2024. DOI: 10.1007/s11104-024-06587-w

PELEGRINO, M.H.P. et al. Optimizing soil texture spatial prediction in the Brazilian Cerrado: Insights from random forest and spectral data. *Geoderma Regional*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.geodrs.2025.e00922

SOUSA, G.P.B. et al. Assessing soil degradation in Brazilian agriculture by a remote sensing approach to monitor bare soil frequency: impact on soil carbon. *Soil Advances*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.soilad.2024.100011

(D) Principal Investigator: Maurício Roberto Cherubin

Technology: Crop management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Crop management

Summary of achievements: We did a comprehensive systematic review assessing GHG fluxes in Brazilian climate-smart systems. It found that adopting diversified systems like ICL and ICLF shows potential to mitigate emissions, but highlights significant data gaps and methodological inconsistencies, urging for standardized, comprehensive research across all Brazilian biomes.

Team members: Mauricio Roberto Cherubin, PI, ESALQ/USP Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI, ESALQ/USP

Results:

Bieluczyk, W., et al. 2025 Greenhouse gas fluxes in Brazilian climate-smart agricultural and livestock systems: A systematic and critical overview. Journal of Cleaner Production 464, 142782 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.142782>

(E) Principal Investigator: Paulo Sergio Pavinato

Technology: Fertilizer management, Residue management, Crop management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil/Crop/Fertilizer Management to Improve P and S Efficiency in Annual Crops for improving C sequestration

Summary of achievements: This project includes both short-term and long-term experiments. Short-term experiments will evaluate the effectiveness of crop species, as well as the most promising P and S management strategies and bio-based fertilizers aiming at sustainable cash crop production and active C allocation in soil. Long-term field experiments (LTE) will assess the impact of cover crops on soil profile quality and health within crop rotations. LTEs trials are already established in some regions of Brazil, with additional experiments to be established in collaboration with institutions and partners. This project provides an opportunity to introduce innovative P and S solutions (e.g., new cover crops, bio-based fertilizers, fertilizer placement) to enhance nutrient use efficiency and assess soil C protection and accumulation, contributing to improved soil health. Methodology: Soil samples will be collected from field studies conducted in collaboration with research institutions and universities across Brazil. Specific experiments include: 1. Dois Vizinhos-PR (UTFPR): Ongoing since 2009, evaluating cover crop effects on P dynamics, P speciation, and crop yield. 2. Arapiraca-AL (UFAL): Established in 2022, focusing on P solubility in semi-arid conditions with maize as the cash crop. 3. Paraguay: Field P calibration experiments in collaboration with UFRGS, evaluating yield and P availability. 4. Fundação ABC, PR: Evaluating chemical-biological changes from crop/soil management in LTEs. 5. Fundação MS: Trials assessing microorganism effects on P solubilization and nutrient availability. 6. Fundação MT: LTEs in Itiquira-MT since 2010, studying P levels in depth and comparing furrow vs. broadcast fertilization. In all field studies, crop yield, shoot growth, and P/S uptake will be evaluated, along with soil P speciation. In select studies, rhizosphere soil will be analyzed for organic acids, enzymes, and effective species exudation. Deliverables: The results will deepen our understanding of how different P sources affect availability over time and how annual crops absorb these forms of P, linking these mechanisms to biogeochemical and geochemical nutrient cycles. Technical recommendations for improved nutrient management practices will be disseminated through WP7.

Team members: Paulo Sergio Pavinato – PI, (Esalq/USP) Lucas W. Mendes – PA, Cena/USP Maria Carolina Quecine – Esalq/USP Jose Leonardo Gonçalves - Esalq/USP Tiago Tezotto – Esalq/USP Carlos Antônio C. Nascimento – Esalq/USP Hudson Wallace Carvalho – Cena/USP Laercio R. Sartor – UTFPR, Dois Vizinhos PR Tales Tiecher – UFRGS, Porto Alegre RS Valdevan R. dos Santos – UFAL, Arapiraca AL Douglas Gitti – Fundação MS, Dourados MS Gabriel Barth – Fundação ABC, Castro PR Larissa

Bortolo – Fundação MT, Rondonópolis MT Students: Millena Raquel Queiroz – MS, Esalq/USP – scholarship CAPES Wellington Rosa Soares – MS, Esalq/USP – no scholarship Andre L. de F. Espinoza – DR, Esalq/USP - scholarship CAPES Fernanda Miotti – DR, Esalq/USP - scholarship CAPES Matheus B. N. Pereira – DR, Esalq/USP - scholarship CAPES Mikaella Meira Monteiro – DR, Esalq/USP - scholarship CAPES Valdeci J. F. Pinheiro – DR, Esalq/USP - scholarship CAPES

(F) Principal Investigator: Thais M. F. S. Vieira

Technology: Reduce food loss and waste, and shift to sustainable healthy food

Key questions addressed/Research area: Development of low-carbon processes for the recovery of bioactive compounds from agro-industrial residues, encompassing the entire process from clean-technology extraction to the application of new ingredients in food systems.

Summary of achievements: (i) Synthesis of the main activities performed during the period - During the reporting period, the project focused on the development of low-carbon processes for the valorization of Brazilian agro-industrial residues through the extraction, combination, and application of natural antioxidants. Preliminary experiments with oilseed residues (e.g., avocado) were performed but showed limited antioxidant effectiveness in lipid systems, which led to a redirection of the research. The work was then concentrated on cashew peduncle (*Anacardium occidentale* L.) residues, and aqueous extraction conditions were optimized. The extracts were characterized (vitamin C content, total phenolic content and antioxidant capacity by ABTS and FRAP assays), and a simplex-centroid experimental design was applied to evaluate synergistic combinations of the cashew extract with quercetin and α -tocopherol. (ii) Highlights - A major achievement was the successful microencapsulation of cashew juice by spray drying (110 °C inlet temperature; 75 °C outlet), using maltodextrin as carrier material. The obtained microparticles presented favorable techno-functional properties ($A_w = 0.15$; solubility $\approx 81\%$; hygroscopicity ≈ 113 g H₂O/100 g). Scanning Electron Microscopy confirmed spherical morphology, and stability assays demonstrated significantly higher retention of phenolic content in encapsulated samples compared to the free juice during storage. These results confirm the potential of microencapsulation as a sustainable and effective approach for protecting natural antioxidants and adding value to Brazilian native fruits. (iii) Workplan for the next period - The next stage will involve the optimization of spray-drying parameters for the selected antioxidant combinations using a central composite rotational design (CCRD). Finally, the optimized microparticles will be incorporated into food lipid systems to evaluate their antioxidant effectiveness in real applications and reinforce the contribution of this project to the circular economy. The carbon-flow assessment will be implemented, comparing the optimized process to the use of conventional synthetic antioxidants in the food sector and taking into account the valorization of an agro-industrial residue.

Team members: Thais M. F. S. Vieira, PI (Esalq/USP); Camila M. Gonzales, PhD (Esalq/USP), Scholarship funded by CCARBON/USP - 2024/10211-3; Gabrielle C. Vacchi, MSc (Esalq/USP), Scholarship funded by CCARBON/USP - 2024/21792-7; Luis Felipe F. Freitas, Technical support (Esalq/USP)

Results:

PRESENZA, L., TEIXEIRA, B., DE FREITAS FABRÍCIO, L., GRIMALDI, R., GALVÃO, J. A., VIEIRA, T. M. F. S. Optimizing Byproduct Processing for Clean Label Foods: Avocado and MSM-Tambaqui with a Focus on Zero Waste. *J Food Saf*, 44: e13160. 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfs.13160>

Oral presentation at international conference (abstract accepted): Cashew Juice Microencapsulation: A Technological Solution to Valorize and Preserve Brazilian Fruits, European Federation of Food Science and Technology (EFFoST) 2025 – Fostering the Transition to Sustainable Food Systems: Embracing Novelty and Overcoming Challenges, November 2025.

(G) Associate Research: Aline Silva Mello Cesar

Technology: Nutrigenomics Approach to Reducing Environmental Footprint

Key questions addressed/Research area: Nutrigenomics Approach to Reducing Environmental Footprint - Proposal submitted to Fapesp as Regular Project

Summary of achievements: Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are a leading contributor to global warming. In monogastric animals such as pigs, nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) excretion are significant environmental factors impacting the GHG effect. Strategies to mitigate N and P excretion are critical for reducing the environmental footprint of global food production, and one promising approach lies in modulating the gut microbiota through dietary interventions. Nutrigenomics, an emerging field in animal science, has gained attention for its potential to mitigate environmental impacts. Probiotics, non-pathogenic microbes with health benefits for the host, when administered in adequate quantities, are one such intervention. Among them, direct-fed microbials (DFMs) are used in animal diets to enhance performance, nutrition, and health. DFMs have also been associated with mitigating the carbon footprint in animal production, although their specific effects on pigs remain underexplored. This study hypothesizes that supplementing multi-strain DFMs to pigs' diets will reduce N and P excretion, improve fermentation characteristics, enhance feed efficiency and growth performance, and promote animal health, contributing to more sustainable livestock production. The objectives are to (1) compare and characterize N and P excretion, fermentation characteristics, feed efficiency, growth performance, digestibility profiles, and carcass and meat quality in pigs fed a DFM-supplemented diet; (2) compare and understand the gut microbiota profile, including key bacteria, protozoa, fungi, and others; (3) use omics approaches to analyze and characterize changes in transcriptome (single-cell sequencing), metabolome, and methylome (epigenomics) in response to DFM-supplemented diet; (4) explore underlying biological processes by correlating omics data with N and P excretion, production performance, feed efficiency, animal health, and microbiota profile; (5) evaluate the impact of in vitro digestion on gastrointestinal fate in response to DFM-supplemented diet. In this study, a total of 96 male commercial paternal lineage pigs will be divided into two dietary groups (N = 48) (one without supplementation and one with probiotic supplementation). The total number of animals used in the omics analyses will be 12 for each treatment. The experimental period will include the growth and finishing phases, with consumption measurements per pen, individual weekly weight of the

animals, and water and food ad libitum. The in vitro test to be applied will be INFOGEST 2.0 with three biological replicates. With a focus on training professionals, providing crucial insights for sustainable pig production, and revealing the potential of the nutrigenomics approach in reducing environmental impact and food insecurity, this project actively contributes to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially SDG 2, SDG 3, and SDG 13.

Team members: Aline Silva Mello Cesar, PI, Esalq/USP, Andrezza Maria Felicio Ament, Post-doc, Esalq/USP, Alan Giovanini de Oliveira Sartori, PA, Esalq/USP, Albino Luchiari Filho, PA, Esalq/USP, Bruna Pereira Martins da Silva, PhD, Esalq/USP, Bruna Petry, PA, USDA/US, Bárbara Silva Vignato, Post-doc, Esalq/USP, Cesar Augusto Pospissil Garbossa, PA, FMVZ/USP, Cristina Tschorny Moncau Gadbem, Post-doc, FMVZ/USP, Felipe André Oliveira Freitas, PhD, Esalq/USP, Fernanda Nery Ciconello, PhD, Esalq/USP, Gabriel Costa Monteiro Moreira, PA, INRAe, Heidge Fukumasu, PA, Fzea/USP, Hinayah Rojas de Oliveira, PA, Purdue University, Izally Carvalho Gervásio, Post-doc, Esalq/USP, Jiachao Zhang, PA, Hainan University, Luciana Correia de Almeida Regitano, PA, Embrapa, Luiz Fernando Brito, PA, Purdue University, Maria Antonia Calori, PA, Esalq/USP, Mônica Corrêa Ledur, PA, Embrapa, Priscila Silva Neubern de Oliveira, PA, Embrapa, Severino Matias de Alencar, PA, Esalq/USP, Simara Larissa Fanalli, PhD, Fzea/USP, Vivian Vezzoni de Almeida, PA, UFG, Yajing Fang, PA, Hainan University, Adriana Mércia Guaratini Ibelli, PA, Embrapa. The students presented above are collaborators of this proposal, so they don't have a scholarship funded by CCARBON/USP or linked to this proposal, yet.

(H) Associate Research: Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega

Technology: Enteric fermentation, Animal management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Greenhouse gas emissions in South American beef cattle farming and the effect of including tannin-containing forage legumes in native pastures as a mitigation strategy

Summary of achievements: South America holds a large portion of the global cattle herd, with livestock farming primarily developed on native or planted pastures under various edaphoclimatic conditions. This activity is essential to the regional economy, generating jobs and income while also contributing to the trade balance. However, it is associated with greenhouse gas (GHGs) emissions, such as methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O), especially in systems with inadequate management. Enteric CH₄ emissions and N₂O emissions from excreta deposited in the soil are significant GHGs sources. This project aimed to evaluate the impact of beef cattle farming on GHGs emissions in pasture systems, analyzing nutrient use efficiency and potential mitigation strategies. Strategies such as the recovery of degraded pastures and the introduction of leguminous forages can improve animal diets, increase productivity, and reduce GHGs emissions while also increasing soil carbon stocks. The results highlight the variability in emission factors under different pasture conditions and reinforce the importance of management strategies to reduce the environmental impacts of livestock farming in South America.

Team members: Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega (UFC), PI Renato de Aragão Ribeiro Rodrigues (UFF), Assistant Investigator - AI Fabiano Barbosa Alecrim (MSc, UFF), CAPES grant, no support letter

Results: 1 DSc thesis

Alecrim, F. B., Devincenzi, T., Reyno, R., Mederos, A., Simón Zinno, C., Mariotta, J., ... & Ciganda, V. S. (2024). Addition of Tannin-Containing Legumes to Native Grasslands: Effects on Enteric Methane Emissions, Nitrogen Losses and Animal Performance of Beef Cattle. *Sustainability*, 16(20), 9135.

(I) Associate Research: Iraê Amaral Guerrini and Bruno Rossini

Technology: Crop management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Integrated Systems

Summary of achievements: The present study was to evaluate the influence of an agroforestry system on soil fertility and biology, planted with native tree species and pasture/crops. The experiment was conducted in a 12-hectare area in the municipality of São Carlos, São Paulo state, Brazil, under Embrapa Southeast Livestock area. Research is ongoing.

Team members: PIs: Iraê Amaral Guerrini and Bruno Rossini (FCA-UNESP-Botucatu), Celso Marino and José Raimundo Sousa Passos (IB-UNESP-Botucatu); José Ricardo Macedo Pezzopane (Embrapa Southeast Livestock, São Carlos); Gian Franco Capra and Antonio Ganga (UNISS-Università degli Studi di Sassari, Sardinia, Italy); PAS: Rafael Barroca da Silva (FCA-UNESP-Botucatu); Ludmila Ribeiro Roder (UNISS-Università degli Studi di Sassari, Sardinia, Italy); Students: I.C.: Maria Fernanda Vieira Mendes, Pietro Brown (all FCA-UNESP-Botucatu, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a support letter);

(J) Associate Research: Severino Matias de Alencar

Technology: Reduce food loss and waste, and shift to sustainable healthy food

Key questions addressed/Research area: Value-added potential of brewer's spent grains byproduct from the beer industry: development of process for elaboration of functional bars and juices

Summary of achievements: Brewers' spent grain (BSG) is the major by-product of the brewing industry which remains largely unutilized despite its nutritional quality. It is estimated that the total annual production worldwide of this by-product is 39 million tons, and Brazil and Chile are also major generators of BSG. This lignocellulosic material is traditionally used as cattle feed and sold at a low retail price. However, efforts for the revalorization of this by-product are emerging since research has established that it can be used as a low-cost source of bioactive molecules and commodity chemicals that can bring value to integral biorefinery ventures. We will apply cutting edge analytical technology in Brazil and Chile to evaluate in vivo toxicity, bioaccessibility, cellular absorption, anti-inflammatory antioxidant activities, and bioactive composition, as well as develop a process for elaboration of functional bars and juices with BSG. Thus, our collaborative research will establish a foundation for future development of a commercial

market for creation of novel functional foods and nutraceuticals with this by-product. In the next phase of the project, after completing the initial analyses, we will evaluate the functional bars and beverages developed from the solid and liquid fractions, respectively.

Team members: Severino Matias de Alencar, PA, (ESALQ/USP); Erick Scheuermann, PA, (UFRO/Chile); Priscilla Siqueira Melo, Post-doc (ESALQ/USP); Carolina de Souza Moreira, PhD (ESALQ/USP)

Results: Ruíz Suarez, C. B., Schalchli Sáez, H. L., Melo, P. S., Moreira, C. D. S., Sartori, A. G. D. O., de Alencar, S. M., & Scheuermann Salinas, E. S. (2024). Effect of Physical Separation with Ultrasound Application on Brewers' Spent Grain to Obtain Powders for Potential Application in Foodstuffs. *Foods*, 13(18), 3000.

Unlocking the potential of brewer's spent grain: a systematic review of its prebiotic and antimicrobial applications in the food industry (submitted to Journal of Cereal Science).

(K) Associate Research: Suzana Caetano da Silva Lannes

Technology: Reduce food loss and waste, and shift to sustainable healthy food / Human health

Key questions addressed/Research area: Upcycling Food; Food and Materials Development.

Summary of achievements: Application of the upcycling concept in agriculture and processing industry for the development of powder mixtures

This project focuses on obtaining materials with functional characteristics for application in food formulations, with better nutritional and physical functionality, aiming at sustainability, functionality and health. The upcycling concept will be used to obtain waste that will be treated and processed to obtain products with bioactive functionality and application for health and well-being. They will be used in the solid phase of formulating nutraceutical supplements, as industrial food raw materials, as substitutes for cocoa and part of wheat flour in formulations, for example. The exploitation of agricultural and food processing materials is suitable for food development and reinforces sustainability. 3 formulations of mixtures are proposed (food industry residues + nutritional components). Materials will be used from fermentative processing or not. We will use microencapsulation to add nutritional oils, obtained from extracting the peels, as well as zinc, Fe, vitamins A, D, E. The physical analyzes (rheology, texture, thermal) will show us the structure of the food systems obtained and the chemical ones (HPLC, gas chromatography, nutritional composition, antioxidants) the nutritional potential of each one. The mixtures will be applied in two types of food products such as powdered drink and bread, with further analysis.

FAPESP: [2023/03702-8](#) (FCF/USP)

Team members: Suzana Caetano da Silva Lannes

Students: Cristina Karori Suzuki/Antonio Domenico Alves Monteiro/Gabriel Matavelli Ferreira.

Results:

Publications:

LANNES, S. C. S.; MONTEIRO, A. D. A. ; Suzuki, C. K. ; TEIXEIRA, G. M. N. ; SANTOS, P. H. S. ; ROSA, R. S. . FORMULAÇÃO EM PÓ DE RESÍDUOS INDUSTRIAIS, COMPOSIÇÃO ALIMENTÍCIA DE CHOCOLATE COMPREENDENDO A FORMULAÇÃO, E PROCESSOS DE PREPARAÇÃO RELACIONADOS. 2024, Brasil.

Patente: Privilégio de Inovação. Número do registro: BR10202402205, título: "FORMULAÇÃO EM PÓ DE RESÍDUOS INDUSTRIAIS, COMPOSIÇÃO ALIMENTÍCIA DE CHOCOLATE COMPREENDENDO A FORMULAÇÃO, E PROCESSOS DE PREPARAÇÃO RELACIONADOS" , Instituição de registro: INPI - Instituto Nacional da Propriedade Industrial. Depósito: 23/10/2024 Instituição(ões) financiadora(s): FAPESP USP.

Conferences:

LANNES, S. C. S.. Application of the Upcycling Concept in Agriculture and Processing Industry to Develop Functional Food Formulations. 2024. 30th ICFOST 2024- Indian Convention of Food Scientists & Technologists. the upcycling concept in the agriculture and processing industry to develop Nutritional food formulations. 2024. (Congresso).

LANNES, S. C. S.. Patente e Inovação: Pesquisas e tecnologias aplicadas aos biomas brasileiros,. 2024. VI Semana de Engenharia de Alimentos-SEALIM.Cultura da qualidade nos diversos setores produtivos. 2024.

LANNES, S. C. S.; QUISPE, E. E. H. ; MUJICA, J. A. Y. . Formulaciones en polvo para productos alimenticios y farmacéuticos. 2024. (Apresentação de Trabalho/Conferência ou palestra).

LANNES, S. C. S.. the upcycling concept in the agriculture and processing industry to develop Nutritional food formulations. 2024. 22o.World Congress of Food Science and Technology-IUFoST. Nutrition and Health, Alternative Proteins 2. 2024.

LANNES, S.C.S. Sustainability in Food Technology and its Relationship with Health. 17 Feb 2025. 2nd Global Virtual Meet on Food Science and Technology. London.

3.5 Sectorial chain: Bioenergy

Research Sector Chain Coordinator: João Luís Nunes Carvalho

3.5.1 Part 1: General

Summary of achievements: Bioenergy production is recognized as an important ally in the fight against climate change. It contributes by replacing fossil fuels with bio renewables and by increasing carbon sequestration through appropriate land use and management practices in bioenergy crops. Over the past year, CCARBON/USP's bioenergy chain has organized a variety of activities related to carbon removal strategies, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions mitigation, and soil health assessments. Regarding carbon removal, the main activities were: i) assessing the impact of land use and management changes on soil carbon stocks under sugarcane cultivation; ii) assessing the impact of biochar use on soil carbon sequestration through measurement and biogeochemical modeling; iii) using genetic tools to increase the photosynthetic efficiency and stress tolerance of energy crops; iv) evaluating the impact of cover crops on carbon sequestration and sugarcane production. Activities aimed at reducing GHG emissions included: i) developing regional N₂O emission factors for bioenergy crops in Brazil; ii) assessing the potential of biochar as a mitigation strategy for N₂O emissions; iii) composting and producing biofertilizers; and iv) calculating the environmental footprint of energy crops. Implications for residue recycling on soil health were also evaluated. The bioenergy group conducts multidisciplinary research and has dozens of students. Five of them have FAPESP fellowships approved: three postdoctoral fellows, one PhD student, and one technical trainee. Additionally, two postdoctoral fellows received BEPE scholarships to conduct part of the research abroad. Between September 2024 and August 2025, the group published 11 scientific papers: five on carbon removal, five on GHG emissions, and one on soil health. Two PhD theses and one master's dissertation were finalized in this period. Most of the research conducted in the bioenergy

chain was associated with bioethanol crops, sugarcane, and corn (to a lesser extent). Overall, our main findings indicated that the adoption of best management practices (like straw retention, cover crops, reduced tillage, and biochar) are feasible strategies to increase soil carbon sequestration in sugarcane fields. The addition of different types of biochar to soil was a feasible strategy to mitigate N₂O emissions. The research highlighted that the values of N₂O emissions obtained in Brazilian bioethanol crops are significantly lower than the values proposed by IPCC for tropical and subtropical regions. The use of these regional N₂O emission factors obtained here will substantially reduce the carbon footprint of sugarcane- and corn-based bioenergy. Finally, the group emphasized that recycling bioethanol residues is crucial for improving soil health. For the next period, the group intends to continue most of the activities reported here and will expand its research on corn, carinata, macaúba, and other bioenergy crops. The group will devote more effort to elucidating the role of carbon removal technologies in bioenergy systems, such as BECCS and biochar.

3.5.2 Part 2: Carbon removal

(A) Principal Investigator: Maurício Roberto Cherubin

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: How is the impact of sugarcane management (including straw removal) on soil carbon and soil-related ecosystem services?

Summary of achievements: In this research line we published to papers in *Global Change Biology Bioenergy*, where we synthesized the effects of sugarcane management (including straw removal) on soil carbon, and over other key ecosystem services, as described below: In the 2000s, sugarcane acreage boomed in Brazil due to increased bioethanol consumption by flex-fuel vehicles, raising sustainability concerns about soil organic carbon (SOC) losses from land-use changes and management practices. The industrial use of straw for 2G ethanol and electricity also sparked worries. Despite numerous studies, information remains scattered. Our study summarized the literature and derived regional factors of SOC stock changes for sugarcane cultivation in Brazil. This represents a step forward in understanding the impact of sugarcane on soil carbon and can aid scientists and policymakers. For the next period, we will advance on: 1) to start studies with carinata in Brazil, to understand its potential to produce feedstock to sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) and also capture C and improve soil health as a cover crop. We established a partnership with SLC company. A PD scholarship (João Leonardo Corte Baptistella) was submitted to FAPESP with support to CCARBON/USP (2025/12516-9)

Team members: Mauricio Roberto Cherubin, PI (ESALQ/USP); João Carvalho (CNPEM); Carlos Roberto Pinheiro Junior (ESALQ/USP); Carlos Eduardo Cerri (ESALQ/USP); Lucas Canisares (ESALQ/USP); João Leonardo Corte Baptistella (ESALQ/USP).

Post-doc Carlos Roberto Pinheiro Junior (FAPESP # 23/11337-8 24/23520-4) - CCARBON/USP supporting letter

Results:

Pinheiro Junior, C. R., Carvalho, J. L. N., Canisares, L. P., Cerri, C. E. P., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Soil carbon stocks in sugarcane cultivation: An evidence synthesis associated with land use and management practices. *GCB Bioenergy*, 16(9), e13188.

(B) Principal Investigator: João Luis Nunes Carvalho

Technology: Soil carbon, Biochar

Key questions addressed/Research area: How suitable are biogeochemical models to simulate soil carbon changes induced by biochar application?

Team members: João Luís Nunes Carvalho – PI (CNPq); Amanda Ronix Pereira (CNPq, ESALQ/USP); Carlos Eduardo Cerri (ESALQ/USP)

Post-doc Amanda Ronix Pereira (FAPESP # 2025/01169-6; 2025/14148-7)

Summary of achievements: In this research line, we performed a literature review focusing on biogeochemical models used to simulate soil carbon stocks, considering the application of biochar. The objective was to identify the main advances as well as the gaps that limit the accurate representation of the interactions between biochar and soil in the simulation models. The research indicated that the development of studies on the topic of “biochar” is widely explored, with 4259 papers being identified using the first search filter. Specifically, searching for studies that mentioned terms related to biogeochemical models for estimating soil carbon stock, it was observed that a small number of studies (N = 46) considered the entry of biochar into the models. Although most studies have used the RothC model to simulate biochar within biogeochemical models, biochar inputs have also been implemented in APSIM, EPIC, Century, DNDC, and other models, including those not primarily focused on soil carbon stock estimation. Among the reviewed studies, only a small fraction reported the calibration and validation of biogeochemical models, which are essential steps to ensure their credibility and predictive reliability. To address this gap, our subsequent efforts will focus on collecting soil samples from long-term experiments under biochar application and organizing empirical datasets that enable robust calibration and validation of biogeochemical models to estimate soil carbon stocks in tropical environments with biochar application. To achieve this objective, a BEPE scholarship (Amanda Ronix Pereira) was approved by FAPESP with the support of CCARBON/USP (2025/14148-7).

Results: Ronix, A., da Silva Neto, E. C., Cerri, C. E. P., Latawiec, A. E., & Carvalho, J. L. N. (2025). Incorporating Biochar Into Biogeochemical Models: Achievements and Challenges. In *GCB Bioenergy* (Vol. 17, Issue 5). <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.70037>

(C) Principal Investigator: Leidivan Almeida Frazão

Key questions addressed/Research area: Application of biochar and biochar-based organomineral fertilizers: Impacts on bioenergy crop production and soil carbon sequestration

Summary of achievements: The use of biochar in agriculture has been suggested as an alternative to improve soil properties, particularly through the addition of more stable forms of carbon. Additionally, a sustainable alternative for utilizing charcoal fines—by-products of plant wood pyrolysis—is their use in the production of granulated

organomineral fertilizers. The quality and stability of the granules, which are closely linked to the choice of binders, are essential to prevent losses during agricultural application. However, specific binders may increase production costs, potentially making fertilizer use economically unfeasible and negatively impacting soil microbial activity. Despite the relatively large number of scientific publications on biochar, long-term field studies remain scarce. In this context, we hypothesize that, over time, biochar can enhance soil fertility, increase and sustain high soil carbon levels, and improve the yield of bioenergy crops such as sugarcane and macaúba. This study aims to evaluate the effects of biochar and biochar-based organomineral fertilizers on soil properties and the productivity of bioenergy crops. Our preliminary results indicate that biochar improves soil properties and enhances sugarcane yield. It contributed to increased cation exchange capacity, soil organic carbon content, the number of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungal spores, and glomalin levels—regardless of mineral fertilizer application. However, biochar did not affect the population of diazotrophic bacteria. The next steps include evaluating the potential application of organomineral fertilizers and biochar in macaúba cultivation, as well as assessing the crop's initial growth and soil carbon storage.

Team members: Leidivan Almeida Frazão, PI, (UFMG) César Florentino Puma Vega, PhD (CAPES/UFMG) José Mendes Santos Junior, PhD (CAPES/UFMG) Alfredo Nápoli (CIRAD) Luiz Arnaldo Fernandes (UFMG).

Results:

Vega, Cesar Florentino Puma; Mota, Mauro Franco Castro; Lopes, Erika Manuela Gonçalves; Santos Júnior, José Mendes; Colen, Fernando; Frazão, Leidivan Almeida; Pegoraro, Rodinei Facco; Parra-Serrano, Luisa Julieth.; Napoli, Alfredo; Fernandes, Luiz Arnaldo. Biochar from eucalyptus waste improves the chemical and biological properties of an Inceptisol and sugarcane yield over time under tropical conditions. *Pedosphere*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedsph.2025.08.002>

(D) Principal Investigator: Helaine Carrer

Technology: Crop breeding/physiology

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Carbon Removal: Point mutations in the *rbcL* gene in the chloroplast genome aiming the improvement of photosynthesis efficiency.

Summary of achievements: Ribulose-1,5-Bisphosphate (RuBP) carboxylase/ oxygenase (RuBisCO) is the key enzyme for the fixation of atmospheric carbon and productivity of plants. At the moment, no single solution to optimize the CO₂ fixing process has been shown in higher plants. The availability of chloroplast transformation protocol allows the manipulation of the large subunit of RuBisCO (Whitney et al., 2011). We are proposing to test the point mutation of an alanine (Ala) 378 substituting a valine (Val) (A378V) in the tobacco chloroplast based on the results on *Synechococcus* (Satagopan et al., 2009). We used two *rbcL*-synthetic vectors, pTT633 with the amino acid alanine changed to a valine (A378V) and another one without the replacement (pTT632). The transgenic plants obtained with both vectors had a phenotype of yellowish leaves and slow growth under tissue culture. Considering that these vectors had some additional nucleotide changes beside the point mutation, new vectors were prepared using pTT632 as a backbone only replacing the *rbcL* sequence by a new synthesized sequence of the original tobacco *rbcL*

and the mutant (A378V), pFSWt e pFS378V, respectively. After chloroplast transformation, 20 transgenic plants were obtained, 12 with the mutant *rbcL* and 8 with the control *rbcL*. The plants are being subcultured for 4 to 5 generations in order to be homoplasmic. The fact that it is homoplasmic is essential to determine if this point mutation is effective to decrease photorespiration. Also, plants will grow in the greenhouse to allow photosynthesis rate measurement.

Team members: Helaine Carrer - PI Pedro Boscariol Ferreira (post-doc Fapesp 2022/09094-7) Felipe Georgete Scola (MSc student-Capes) . Pedro and Felipe do not have scholarship from the CCARBON/USP

Technology: Crop breeding/physiology

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Biomass Production: Genetic Pathways from extremophile plants to improve abiotic stress tolerance and photosynthesis efficiency in cultivated plants

Summary of achievements: In modern agriculture, high-yield crop cultivars often exhibit a significant tradeoff between productivity and stress tolerance. Extremophytes are non-crop plant species, which manage to maintain high productivity while thriving in adverse conditions. The Chilean species *Strombocarpa tamarugo*, and Antarctic species *Deschampsia antarctica*, and *Colobanthus quitensis* ecotype Antarctica fall into this category. They are promising models for discovering stress tolerance mechanisms. De Novo transcriptome assembly was accomplished, and differential expression analysis identified genes associated to outlier traits such as five genes from *P. tamarugo* (PtPIF3, PtPLGG1, PtHB7, PtANR, and PtBBX32), three from *Deschampsia* (DaBT2, DaCIPK4, and DaHIPP1) and four from *Colobanthus* (CqUF3GT, CqROF1, CqERF27, and CqSGS1). These genes were cloned into *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* vectors and are under genetic transformation in *Nicotiana tabacum*. Although seven genes were successfully transformed, only four were selected to continue the functional analysis for drought based on RT-qPCR (expression analysis). Tobacco plants expressing the genes: Phytochrome interacting factor 3 (StPIF3), Homeobox 7 (StHB7), B-box domain protein 32 (StBBX32), de *Strombocarpa tamarugo*, e Ethylene response factor (CqERF27), de *Colobanthus quitensis* were grown in greenhouse to produce seeds for two generations in order to obtain homozygous plants. At the moment, seeds are germinating on culture media with kanamycin antibiotic to select homozygous plants to water deficit experiment in the greenhouse.

Team members: Helaine Carrer PI Pedro Boscariol Ferreira (post-doc Fapesp 2022/09094-7) Giovana Carolyn Domingues Saito MSc student-Capes- Giovana had a letter from CCARBON/USP to Fapesp but the scholarship was not approved.

(F) Associate Research: Antonio Augusto Franco Garcia

Technology: Crop breeding/physiology

Key questions addressed/Research area: Evaluation of national germplasm regarding its potential for genetic improvement for carbon sequestration. Crops: soybean, pastures, sugarcane.

Summary of achievements: In this initial stage, we are still assessing the methods to be employed for evaluating the genetic potential of the selected crops, given that the methods need to be implemented on a large scale, involving the assessment of hundreds of genotypes. We have been discussing alternatives, and so far, the main emphasis has been on pastures. However, the strategies have not yet been defined.

Team members: Antonio Augusto Franco Garcia, José Baldin Pinheiro, Helaine Carrer, Fábio Marin

(G) Associate Research: Thiago Romanelli

Technology: Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS)

Key questions addressed/Research area: Carbon mitigation routes on the energy content

(H) Principal Investigator: Denizart Bolonhezi

Research Sector Chain: Bioenergy

Technology: Cover crops for improved C management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Use of Cover Crops in Sugarcane and Grain Production Systems

Summary of achievements: Two experiments were developed on sugarcane field renovation using cover crop mixes, two experiments on intercropping legumes in unburned ratoon cane fields, and the maintenance of one long-term trial on no-tillage and liming in unburned sugarcane renovation with soybean (initiated in 1998), as well as one experiment on sugarcane renovation under different soil management practices in the MEIOSI system with peanut (MITOSI Project – *Simultaneous Intercropping Transplanting Method*). The trials using cover crop mixes were installed in partnership with *Usina da Pedra*, and during the reporting period, soil sampling and sugarcane planting were carried out after biomass management. Among the preliminary results, a highlight was the quantification of four-times more root biomass in treatments with a higher percentage of grass species in the mix, within the first 40 cm of the studied *Quartzarenic Neosol*, when compared to *Crotalaria spectabilis* and pearl millet standards. Additionally, root colonization by arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) was 30% higher in the mix treatments compared to the isolated cultivation of millet or *Crotalaria spectabilis*. Regarding the MITOSI project, it is noteworthy that the harvest was conducted in July, and the treatment combining direct seeding of peanut with direct furrowing for sugarcane did not differ statistically (84.7 TCH) from the conventional tillage treatment (86 TCH). This is an important result considering diesel savings (due to reduced tillage) and the preservation of soil organic matter (samples are yet to be collected). Regarding the long-term trial is installed at the IAC Sugarcane Center in Ribeirão Preto, agronomic evaluations were carried out, and final samplings are scheduled for the next period with the goal of quantifying carbon stocks under each management system. For the upcoming period, soil sampling is planned for the two experiments involving species mixes in sugarcane renovation, installed in two production environments (A2 and E1) at *Usina da Pedra*, as well as root sampling and sugarcane productivity assessments. The trial known as the MITOSI system, which involved peanut during renovation, is expected to continue for one more harvest cycle before renovation

in the 2026/27 season, while the long-term trial will be renovated with soybean in this semester. A project proposal is under preparation for submission to FAPESP for funding

Team members: Felipe Martins do Rêgo Barros, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP). Fernando Dini Andreote, PI, Brazilian Supervisor, (ESALQ/USP). Andre Luiz Custodio Franco, Supervisor abroad, (Indiana University).

Results:

BETIOL, O.; DE MARIA, I.C.; RUIZ, F.F.; ALMEIDA, P.L.; MASSAROLLO, L.; ORNELLA, T.; GRUENER, C.E.; FURLANI, C.A. Soil Health and soybean yield responses to strategic tillage and cover-crops in long-term no-tillage. In: WORLD CONGRESS ON CONSERVATION AGRICULTURE, IX. Proceedings...Western Cape Department of Agriculture, Cape Town, South Africa, p. 57-59, 2024. ISBN: 978-1-0370-5134-0

BOLONHEZI, D.; CORDEIRO Jr., P.S.; BETIOL, O.; RUIZ, F.F.; FINOTO, E.; ZERBATO, C. How to improve the soybean grain yield and root system in a long-term trial of no-tillage under sugarcane straw. In: WORLD CONGRESS ON CONSERVATION AGRICULTURE, IX. Proceedings...Western Cape Department of Agriculture, Cape Town, South Africa, p. 57-59, 2024. ISBN: 978-1-0370-5134-0

GRANDE, L. H. Q.; SANTOS, J. K. ; PEREIRA, M.B. N. ; SILVA, L. H. A. ; MUNIZ, L. F. ; BOLONHEZI, D. ; UMBURANAS, R. C. ; MORAES, M. T. Modelling sugarcane root elongation in response to mechanical stress as an indicator of soil physical quality. EXPERIMENTAL AGRICULTURE , v. 61, p. 1-14, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0014479725000018>

OLIVEIRA, I. N. DE ; SOUZA, Z. M. DE ; BOLONHEZI, D. ; TAVARES, R. L. M. ; LIMA, R. P. ; SILVA, R. B. DA ; ARAÚJO, F. S. ; LOVERA, L. H. ; LIMA, E. DE S. . Effect of Conservation Management on Oxisol in a Sugarcane Area Under a Pre-Sprouted Seedling System. AGRICULTURE , v. 14, p. 1965, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture14111965>

Co-supervised Theses and Dissertations:

BETIOL, O. Impactos do Preparo Ocasional Após 26 Anos em Plantio Direto com Diferentes Rotações de Culturas sobre a Produtividade da Soja e Alguns Atributos do Solo. UNESP, FCAVJ, Jaboticabal, 2025, 68 p. Tese de Doutorado

RUIZ, F.F. Consórcio de Feijoeiros e Leguminosas Adubos verdes em Soqueira de Cana Crua. UNESP, FCAVJ, Jaboticabal, 2025, 48 p. Dissertação de Mestrado

3.5.3 Part 3: GHG emission reduction

(A) Principal Investigator: Maurício Roberto Cherubin

Technology: Fertilizer management

Key questions addressed/Research area: What are the impacts of the move from IPCC Tier 1 to Tier 2 for N₂O emission factors for biofuel crops (corn and sugarcane) in Brazil?

Summary of achievements: In this research line, we performed a literature review to establish regional Tier 2 for N₂O emission factors (EF) for corn and sugarcane in Brazil. A paper was generated and published, as described below: The recognition of bioethanol as a key strategy for mitigating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is closely linked to the accuracy of N₂O EF used in life cycle assessments. However, previous studies have shown that the default N₂O EF values recommended by the IPCC do not accurately reflect the diverse edaphoclimatic conditions found in Brazil, leading to uncertainties in GHG inventories. Therefore, establishing regional N₂O EF is essential for improving the precision of bioethanol GHG emission estimates. In this study, we conducted a systematic literature review compiling 300 measurements from 46 field studies on sugarcane and corn, the main crops used for ethanol production in Brazil. Our findings indicate that the average N₂O EF for these crops is 0.7% (0.58–0.75%), lower than the value reported for the tropics and sub-tropics (1.6%). When analyzed separately, sugarcane showed an average N₂O EF of 0.65%, with higher emissions from the combined use of mineral and organic fertilizers (0.79%) compared to mineral (0.55%) or organic fertilizers alone (0.77%). For corn, the average N₂O EF was 0.84%, with mineral fertilizers presenting the lowest EF (0.48%), while emissions increased with the combination of mineral and organic sources (0.82%), reaching the highest levels with pig slurry application (1.72%). Our results reinforce the need for Tier 2 methodologies incorporating region-specific data to enhance GHG inventory accuracy and support targeted mitigation strategies. This study represents a significant step toward refining N₂O EF estimates for bioethanol crops, contributing to more precise assessments of the sector's climate impact. For the next period, we will advance on: i) to elaborate a LCA for corn ethanol produced under different management system in Brazilian Cerrado; ii) develop scenario to study the land costs and externalities associated with sugarcane expansion in Brazil

Team members: Mauricio Roberto Cherubin PI; Graciela Angnes - Pos-doc (Bolsa FUSP – cota de projeto) Projeto - Project – Definition of regional N₂O emission factors for bioenergy-relevant crops in Brazil

Results:

Angnes, G.; Carvalho, J.L.N.; Cerri, C.E.P.; Cherubin, M.R. Establishing regional N₂O emission factors for bioethanol crops in Brazil. *Global Change Biology – Bioenergy*, v.17, e70071, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.70071>

(B) Principal Investigator: João Luis Nunes Carvalho

Technology 1: Biochar for greenhouse gas emissions mitigation of the bioenergy sector

Key questions addressed: What are the environmental benefits of converting sugarcane biomass (straw, bagasse, and lignin) into biochar for use as a soil amendment?

Team members:

João Luís Nunes Carvalho - PI

PhD Student Fernanda Palmeira Gabetto (FAPESP # 2024/13225-5; # 2021/11995-0);
Team members: João Luís Nunes Carvalho (CNPEN); Luiza Cordeiro Boff (TT-3 – FAPESP #2023/08012-0)

Summary of achievements:

To address our research questions, we conducted three experiments to evaluate the impact of applying residue-derived biochar on greenhouse gas fluxes in tropical soils. In the first experiment, we compared the effects of sugarcane straw and its biochar on soil N₂O emissions and their interaction with functional genes associated with N₂O production and consumption. Studies indicate that biochar reduces N₂O emissions by changing chemical, physical, and biological soil attributes; however, the understanding of how biochar influences N₂O emissions remains limited. Our results have shown that biochar application resulted in 73% lower N₂O emissions compared with the soils with sugarcane straw. We also observed that in sugarcane soils, N₂O emissions were closely linked to the presence of genes associated with nitrification, suggesting that this was the primary N₂O-producing pathway. In the second experiment, we tested different types of biochar produced from the main lignocellulosic residues available in Brazil (sugarcane straw and bagasse, pine and eucalyptus residues). Since feedstock type influences biochar properties, we hypothesized that these differences would affect soil N₂O emissions and microbial diversity. Here, we observed that regardless of the origin of the feedstock, all biochar treatments reduced the cumulative N₂O emissions by 25% to 50% in comparison with the nitrogen-fertilized treatment. Only the biochar derived from eucalyptus residue showed a lower capacity to decrease N₂O emissions compared to the one derived from sugarcane straw. Emissions were negatively correlated with the presence of oxidized functional groups in the biochars. However, these chemical variations did not significantly alter bacterial or fungal diversity. The third experiment evaluated the effects of conventional and aged sugarcane-based biochar on soil N₂O emissions. We observed that biochar application in soil is an efficient material for GHG sequestration. When compared with soil without biochar and under nitrogen fertilization, the soil N₂O emissions from treatment with conventional biochar application were reduced by 48%, while the aged biochar reduced by 30%. We conclude that biochar application in tropical soil represents a nature-based solution to decrease N₂O emissions without changing microbial diversity. These studies also highlighted that the effects of biochar on N₂O emissions should be observed in a long-term perspective. These results were the initial efforts to shed light on the environmental responses caused by biochar addition. For the following steps, we aim to further explore the underlying mechanisms by which biochar can affect the soil organic matter dynamics under tropical climate conditions.

Gabetto, F. P., Tenelli, S., Netto-Ferreira, J. B., Gonzaga, L. C., Isidório, M. A. S., & Carvalho, J. L. N. (2024). Exploring the potential of sugarcane straw biochar: Insights into N₂O emissions and microbial functional genes. *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 182(January). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2024.107070>

Gabetto, F. P., Tenelli, S., Netto-Ferreira, J. B., Martins Junior, J., Almeida, O. A. C., Cosenza, M. L., Strauss, M., & Carvalho, J. L. N. (2025). Biochar from crop residues mitigate N₂O emissions and increase carbon content in tropical soils. *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.2734>

(C) Principal Investigator: Heitor Cantarella

Technology: *Residue recycling for greenhouse gas mitigation*

Key questions addressed/Research area: Recycling C and nutrients from urban waste and sewage sludge

Summary of achievements: Urban waste is usually discarded in landfills, where nutrients are wasted, in addition to causing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, especially CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O. Recycling waste by aerobic composting is a way of properly promoting the circular economy. A partnership involving Campinas municipal administration, the city water and sewage treatment agency (SANASA) and the Agronomic Institute in Campinas (IAC), representing the State of São Paulo Agriculture Secretary, put together a project to recycle approximately 100 t/day of green material from the city parks, and 70 t/day of sewage sludge. The residues are aerobically composted for approximately 60 to 90 days, resulting in organic fertilizer, registered at MAPA as Class B fertilizer. The project has been in operation since 2020, yielding approximately 70 t/day fertilizer. The organic fertilizer generated in just 1 year is estimated to recycle 4,000 t C, 184 t N, 74 t P, and 57 t K, enough to fertilize 1,000 to 2,000 hectares of corn. If added to soils, the compost will recycle 14,290 t CO₂e. Such C and nutrients would otherwise be dumped in landfills. In the next period, emissions of N₂O and CH₄ from the composting piles will be measured to assess the greenhouse gas balance of the composting process. In the coming year, biogas from sewage sludge anaerobic digestion will be considered, further improving the project's environmental benefits by producing bioenergy.

Team members: Heitor Cantarella, PI (IAC) and Leonardo Souza (MS student)

(D) Associate Research: Thiago Romanelli

Technology: Crop management

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Environmental footprints of energy crops

Summary of achievements: A paper out of the PhD Dissertation was published.

Team members: T.L.Romanelli, PA (ESALQ/USP); Flavio Eduardo Fava/PhD candidate/PPGESA; Graciele Angnes, Post-doc (USP/Esalq); M.R. Cherubin, PI (USP/Esalq).

Results:

Fava, F. E., Alves, L. R. A., & Romanelli, T. L. (2025). Economic Feasibility and Decarbonization Incentives of Sugarcane Biogas Production Pathways. *Agriculture*, 15(4), 380.

Angnes, G., Denny, D. M. T., Grenz, J., Romanelli, T. L., & Cherubin, M. R. (2025). Voluntary sustainability standards and soil health: insights from a case study in soybean production in Brazilian Savannah. *Experimental Agriculture*, 61, e13.

3.5.4 Part 4: Soil Health

(A) Principal Investigator: João Luis Nunes Carvalho

Technology: Residue recycling

Key questions addressed/Research area: How vinasse application affects the long-term soil health of sugarcane fields?

Summary of achievements: Vinasse is the main residue generated in sugarcane ethanol production, and its efficient use is essential for the economic and environmental sustainability of the sugarcane industry. We used the Soil Management Assessment Framework (SMAF) to assess the long-term effects of vinasse application on integrated soil health response in soils with contrasting textures. Overall, vinasse application improved soil health components in both soils. Vinasse application showed increased soil organic carbon content, nutrient recycling, and soil physical quality. The long-term application of vinasse increased the soil health from 49 to 62% in the clayey soil and from 43 to 61% in the sandy clay soil. Therefore, the findings revealed the potential of vinasse application to reduce the need for synthetic fertilizer and promote the circular economy and soil health regardless of soil type. This study verifies that long-term vinasse application to sandy- and clay-textures soils in Brazil has both economic and environmental benefits because it recycles an important ethanol byproduct and enhances soil health.

Team members: João Luis Nunes Carvalho – PI (CNPEN); Maurício Roberto Cherubin; Felipe Bonini da Luz (UFPR); Leandro Carolino Gonzaga (CNPEN); Guilherme Ferreira Castioni (CTC)

Results:

Luz, F.B.; Gonzaga, L.C.; Cherubin, M.R.; Castioni, G.A.F.; Carvalho, J.L.N. Soil health impact of long-term sugarcane vinasse recycling. *Biofuels Bioproducts & Biorefining-Biofpr*. v. 1, p. 1-14, 2024.

3.6 Sectorial chain: Sustainable Livestock

Research Sector Chain Coordinator: Luiz Lehmann Coutinho

3.6.1 Part 1: General

Summary of achievements: Substantial progress was made in this second year. Several in vitro and in vivo experiments were conducted to achieve GHG emission reduction by manipulation of rumen fermentation using innovative dietary strategies. Multiple in vitro and in vivo trials were conducted across participating institutions. The in vitro Rumiflow System (IVRFS) was developed to simulate rumen fermentation semi-continuously. Several projects used this system to evaluate methane production, fermentation parameters, and rumen microbiota using diverse forage combinations. Promising dietary treatments were identified that reduce methane emissions without compromising digestibility, supporting climate-smart feeding strategies. An important byproduct of the ethanol industry was evaluated. Researchers conducted three experiments assessing the use of corn dried distiller's grains with solubles (DDGS) in feedlot cattle diets. Results showed that DDGS improved nutrient digestibility and nitrogen retention without increasing methane emissions or disrupting rumen function. Specifically, a 30% DDGS inclusion provided optimal carcass weight, while high DDGS levels enhanced nutrient utilization. Substituting 40% DDGS for soybean meals, cottonseed, and part of the corn did not negatively impact performance, digestibility, or methane output. Ongoing studies are exploring additional DDGS inclusion strategies with different corn processing methods to optimize cattle nutrition and environmental sustainability further. Important studies also investigated the use of bioactive compounds and the interaction between gastrointestinal nematodes and ruminal microbiota in sheep, aiming to develop microbiota manipulation strategies to control endoparasites and reduce methane emissions. Integrated studies considering land use change, afforestation, reforestation, forest management, crop management, fertilizer management, enteric fermentation, and

animal management are being conducted. Initial evidence suggests that regenerative agriculture can increase soil carbon stocks, particularly in degraded pasture areas, contributing to GHG emissions reduction. The results will support strategies to expand the adoption of regenerative practices, strengthening the sustainability of Brazilian agriculture and supporting national climate targets. A meta-analysis study regarding changes in SOC stocks following the conversion of low-productivity pastures in Brazil indicated an average increase in SOC stock of 15.3% (95% CI: 10.4–20.5%) across all interventions relative to low-productivity baselines. Management factors (MF) were derived for specific systems, ranging from 1.12 for Crop-Livestock Systems (CLS) to 1.40 for Crop-Livestock-Forestry Systems (CLFS) after 20 years of management in the 0-100 cm soil profile. Consequently, estimated annual SOC change rates (ΔC) for this scenario ranged from 0.75 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in CLS to 2.42 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in CLFS. The activities resulted in 10 summaries presented at Scientific Meetings and eight publications in journals. The upcoming period will focus on expanding the applications of the In vitro Rumiflow System (IVRFS) to a broader range of tropical forages and seaweed. Efforts will be made to complete gas quantification, microbial sequencing, and isotopic analyses to enhance model validation. Integration of various datasets, including in vitro, in vivo, and isotopic data, will be prioritized. There will be a strong emphasis on manuscript submission, data consolidation, and dissemination to support sustainable livestock systems in tropical environments. The evaluation of inclusion levels of DDGS in diets with both ground and rehydrated flint corn will continue. The next stage will involve integrating into MRV systems, expanding predictive models to different regions, using climate time series in prospective analyses, and developing technical protocols for national agricultural emissions mitigation programs. Controlled grazing and data collection will be implemented during the 2025/2026 tropical growing season, with soil, plant, and animal data being collected. Soil and forage sampling will be conducted to analyze fertility, microbial biomass, greenhouse gas emissions, and the impact of tree traits on pasture productivity and nutritional value. Finally, a database will be organized and converted for application in the DSSAT model, with estimations of animal intake and nitrogen cycling through feces and urine. New climate change scenarios will be simulated using DSSAT, and preparations will be made for an oral presentation at the Modelling Nutrient Digestion and Utilization in Farm Animals 2025 conference

3.6.2 Part 2: Carbon removal

(A) Principal Investigator: Adibe Luiz Abdalla

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area: How can the impact of silvopastoral systems in reducing greenhouse gas emissions (such as CH₄), improving feed efficiency and animal welfare, and their integration with managed and regenerative pasture systems contribute to carbon removal?

Summary of achievements: During the initial nine months of the project “Effect of the pattern of distribution, density, and diversity of native trees in silvopastoral systems in the Amazon biome” (FAPESP Grant No. 2024/07657-0), the research team successfully completed the georeferencing of 120 paddocks containing native Amazonian trees, along with the quantification of tree density and spatial distribution. A comprehensive botanical

survey identified 2,457 trees representing 96 species, enabling the calculation of a diversity index for each paddock. These foundational data support the ecological characterization of tree components within the silvopastoral system and are essential for evaluating the effects of arboreal configurations on ecosystem services. A major accomplishment during this period was the establishment of a robust ecological baseline for the experimental area, providing a valuable dataset on native tree composition and structure in managed livestock systems. This achievement sets the stage for interdisciplinary assessments of soil quality, carbon sequestration, and ruminant productivity. The project directly supports the goals of the CCARBON/USP -Animal research line under the CCARBON/USP program (Grant No. 2021/10573-4), advancing climate-smart strategies for tropical livestock systems. Additionally, Dr. Lumena Souza Takahashi's complementary postdoctoral project explores the integration of *Tithonia diversifolia* and *Moringa oleifera* in silvopastoral systems, targeting improved animal performance and reduced methane emissions. Upcoming activities include soil sampling in all paddocks for fertility, microbial biomass, and greenhouse gas emission analysis. Forage sampling will also be conducted to determine the impact of tree traits on pasture productivity and nutritional value. Subsequently, *in vitro* rumen fermentation assays will evaluate the relationship between forage composition and methane (CH₄) production. These efforts aim to generate integrated data on the multifunctionality of silvopastoral systems, supporting the development of low-emission, resilient livestock production strategies in the Amazon biome.

Team members: Adibe Luiz Abdalla PI (CENA/USP), Vagner Ovani PD (CENA/USP), Lumena Souza Takahashi PD (CENA/USP). Adibe Luiz Abdalla PI (CENA/USP), PD Vagner Ovani (CENA/USP), PD Lumena Souza Takahashi (CENA/USP) PD Vagner Ovani (i) scholarship not directly funded by CCARBON/USP (ii) FAPESP 2021/10573-4 "Effect of the pattern of distribution, density and diversity of native trees in a silvopastoral system in the Amazon biome." (iii) Yes, we received CCARBON/USP supporting letter PD Lumena Souza Takahashi (i) scholarship not directly funded by CCARBON/USP (ii) CENA PD Supporting Edital 2025 - "Innovation and Sustainability in Brazilian Livestock: The Use of *Tithonia diversifolia* and *Moringa oleifera* in Silvopastoral Systems." (iii) Yes, we received CCARBON/USP supporting letter

Results:

Ovani, V., de Almeida, E., Pérez-Márquez, S., Lima, P. D. M. T., Louvandini, H., de Carvalho, H. W. P., & Abdalla, A. L. (2025). Use of energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence (EDXRF) spectrometry to determine external markers in animal intake estimation trials. *Microchemical Journal*, 212, 113582. Ovani, V. et al. 20224. <https://doi.org/10.1071/cp24148>

Ovani, V., Pérez-Márquez, S., Monteiro, A., Kruger, A. M., de Mello Tavares Lima, P., Bizzuti, B. E., ... & Abdalla, A. L. (2024). Understanding the impacts of intensity and harvest frequency on *Tithonia diversifolia* for use in tropical silvopastoral systems. *Grassland Science*.

Pérez-Márquez, S., Ovani, V., Meira, V. E., de Azevedo Olival, A., Louvandini, H., de Morais, J. P. G., ... & Abdalla, A. L. (2025). Assessing the impact of *Samanea tubulosa*

trees on methane emissions and its potential as a feed supplement for ruminants in silvopastoral systems. *Agroforestry Systems*, 99(6), 135.

(B) Principal Investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Improving pasture management as a “nature-based solution” for soil carbon sequestration in Brazil

Summary of achievements: (i) Summary of Main Activities Conducted During the Period: The project investigates the impacts of converting pastures into regenerative agricultural systems on the quantity and quality of soil organic matter (SOM) in tropical and subtropical regions of Brazil, also assessing the potential for carbon sequestration and mitigation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The study areas encompass different treatments, including conventional pasture, managed pasture, regenerative agricultural systems, crop-livestock integration, agroforestry systems, and no-tillage. Soil sampling was carried out using a grid (1 ha, nine points every 50 m), collecting disturbed, semi-disturbed, and undisturbed samples (up to 1 m depth) for chemical, physical, and microbiological analyses. Measurements included carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) contents and stocks, soil bulk density, aggregate stability, and enzymatic activity (arylsulfatase and β -glucosidase). Analyses of bulk density, chemical and enzymatic properties, as well as the final determination of C and N stocks, were completed for all areas, with only the interpretation and FTIR analyses remaining. (ii) Highlights: Carbon Sequestration and GHG Mitigation: Initial evidence suggests that regenerative agriculture can increase soil carbon stocks, particularly in degraded pasture areas, contributing to GHG emissions reduction. Changes in SOM: The study demonstrates the potential of land-use change to modify SOM composition and stability, enhancing soil health and resilience. Sustainable Strategies: The results will support strategies to expand the adoption of regenerative practices, strengthening the sustainability of Brazilian agriculture and supporting national climate targets. (iii) Work Plan for the Next Period: Manuscript preparation activities will be coordinated, and the results will be published. The insights gained from these data will enable the identification of management practices and system intensification levels most suitable for soil carbon storage, aiming to minimize global warming potential. Based on this information, it will be possible to more accurately recommend mitigation-oriented management practices in cultivated areas, contributing to reducing the negative impacts of agriculture on GHG emissions and promoting sustainable production systems.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI (ESALQ/USP), Daniel Aquino De Borba, PhD (ESALQ/USP)

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Carbon sequestration in Brazilian pasturelands and integrated systems

Summary of achievements: i) The objective of this study was to systematically synthesize evidence regarding changes in SOC stocks following the conversion of low-productivity pastures in Brazil, and to derive system-specific SOC management factors that would assist in national carbon inventories. A systematic search of peer-reviewed

literature published up to December 2024 was conducted. Following a comprehensive screening and data extraction process adhering to an established protocol, 50 studies detailing 57 experimental sites in Brazil were incorporated. The log response ratio (lnRR) was employed as the effect size metric to measure the proportional change in SOC stocks. A linear mixed-effects model was developed to evaluate the effects of management system, implementation duration, and soil depth, incorporating study identity as a random effect. ii) The model was validated for publication bias and residual normality. The meta-analysis indicated an average increase in SOC stock of 15.3 % (95 % CI: 10.4–20.5 %) across all interventions relative to low-productivity baselines. Management factors (MF) were derived for specific systems, ranging from 1.12 for Crop-Livestock Systems (CLS) to 1.40 for Crop-Livestock-Forestry Systems (CLFS) after 20 years of management in the 0-100 cm soil profile. Consequently, estimated annual SOC change rates (ΔC) for this scenario ranged from 0.75 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in CLS to 2.42 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in CLFS. Although total carbon stocks increased with management duration, the average annual accumulation rate decreased over long-term scenarios. The restoration of low-yield pasturelands in Brazil represents an achievable strategy for mitigating climate change. The findings extend beyond merely verifying whether these systems sequester carbon to identify which systems are most effective and the duration of their efficacy. The incorporation of trees is a key factor in the rate of carbon sequestration, and a long-term perspective is crucial for achieving the complete potential of these restored agroecosystems. iii) Compare the estimated MF to with the national greenhouse gas inventories to suggest new methodologies that could include each integrated production system as different factors for C sequestration account. Apply the meta-analysis results to carbon sequestration modeling on scenarios simulations of management systems and climate horizons.

Team members: Carlos E. P. Cerri, PI, (CCARBON/ USP); Stocicio M. F. Maia, PI, (IFAL); Leidivan A. Frazão, PI, (UFMG); José I. A. Castro, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) i)No ii)- iii)No

Results: Submitted Doctoral Thesis - Sustainable intensification of Brazilian pastures: soil health assessment and carbon sequestration / Jose Igor Almeida Castro.

(C) Principal Investigator: Joaquim Bento de Souza Ferreira Filho

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Second harvest modelling and soil carbon in Brazil

Summary of achievements: The model is under development. Data collection on second harvest concluded.

Team members: Joaquim Bento de Souza Ferreira Filho (PI, ESALQ/USP), Fernanda Sigainky Lisbinski (PhD. No scholarship so far). No letter from CCARBON/USP yet.

(D) Principal Investigator: Leidivan Almeida Frazão

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Enhancing soil carbon sequestration and stabilization through regenerative pasture systems

Summary of achievements: Livestock production systems employing regenerative soil health practices play a key role in mitigating the impacts of climate change and restoring degraded pastures. These systems drive increased agricultural productivity and promote the accumulation of organic soil carbon, thereby making a significant contribution to environmental sustainability. Thus, the objective is to analyze soil health and the productivity of pasture systems following the adoption of regenerative practices in livestock production systems established in the semi-arid region of Minas Gerais, combining field and laboratory analyses with data compilation using soil health diagnostic tools. The first project in this research line is in its initial development phase, and during the first three months, two sites were selected for evaluation. The next steps consist of: i) assessment of soil quality attributes (physical, chemical, and biological); ii) evaluation of forage production potential using cover crops; iii) assessment of soil carbon sequestration potential.

Team members: Leidivan Almeida Frazão, PI, (UFMG) Alex José Silva Couto, MSc (CAPES), (UFMG) Aline Araujo Reis, MSc (CAPES), (UFMG) Igor Costa de Freitas, Post-doc (CNPq), (UFMG)

(E) Associate Research: Carlos Guilherme Silveira Pedreira

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Animal

Summary of achievements: A poster was presented at the 2024 ASA, CSSA, SSSA International Annual Meeting to share initial project results. Forage production data were calibrated for use in the APSIM model for crop-livestock and crop-livestock-forestry systems. Simulations of future scenarios were carried out for livestock and livestock-forestry systems under different climate projections. The BEPE research internship began at the Department of Agricultural and Biological Engineering at the University of Florida, in Gainesville, enhancing international collaboration and methodological integration. Next steps include organizing and converting the database for application in the DSSAT model, estimating animal intake and nitrogen cycling through feces and urine, simulating new climate change scenarios using DSSAT, and preparing for an oral presentation at the Modelling Nutrient Digestion and Utilization in Farm Animals 2025 conference.

Team members: Carlos Guilherme Silveira Pedreira - PI Post-doc Alyce Raiana Monteiro dos Santos (FAPESP # 24/00033-0 25/00477-9). 1- Resilience of integrated crop-livestock-forestry systems to climate change in the Amazon Biome. 2- Using CROPGRO-Perennial Forage model to assess the resilience of integrated crop-livestock-forestry systems to climate change. YES, we received a CCARBON/USP supporting letter.

(F) Associate Research: Rogerio Martins Mauricio

Technology: Aforestation, reforestation and forest management

Key questions addressed/Research area: cattle nutrition, silvopastoral systems Associate professor at the Federal University of São João del-Rei (UFSJ) and member of the Global Agenda for Sustainable Livestock (GASL – FAO). Researcher in ruminant nutrition, silvopastoral systems, and natural regeneration of native trees. Works on forage evaluation, GHG reduction, measuring the efficiency of natural resource use in livestock systems, sustainable techniques for ruminant production, and addressing climate change in the tropics.

Summary of achievements: Scientific publications, projects (International atomic energy agency and Global Agenda for Sustainable Livestock), congress (ASAS-CSAS), meetings (IAEA Asutria, GASL Rome). Strong scientific collaboration with Prof Adibe (CENA).

Team members: Rogerio Martins Mauricio, Laura Bertolaso De Vecchi (doutoranda), Scholarship from FAPESP, no support from CCABON

Results: Ovani, V., Pérez-Márquez, S., Monteiro, A., Kruger, A. M., de Mello Tavares Lima, P., Bizzuti, B. E., ... & Abdalla, A. L. (2024). Understanding the impacts of intensity and harvest frequency on *Tithonia diversifolia* for use in tropical silvopastoral systems. *Grassland Science*.

Pérez-Márquez, S., Ovani, V., Meira, V. E., de Azevedo Olival, A., Louvandini, H., de Morais, J. P. G., ... & Abdalla, A. L. (2025). Assessing the impact of *Samanea tubulosa* trees on methane emissions and its potential as a feed supplement for ruminants in silvopastoral systems. *Agroforestry Systems*, 99(6), 135.

(G) Associate Research: Stoécio Malta Ferreira Maia

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil carbon sequestration in integrated systems and pastures in the Brazilian semiarid region

Summary of achievements: Fieldwork was conducted in four locations in Brazil's semiarid region, encompassing various livestock-forest integration systems. The focus was to assess the dynamics of soil C and organic matter.

Team members: Stoécio M.F. Maia, Adviser (IFAL). Crislâny Canuto dos Santos (PhD. UFAL). Thamirys Suelle da Silva (PhD. UFAL). Handerson Brandão Melo de Lima (MsC. UFAL). José Marcone da Silva (MsC. UFAL). None of them were scholarship holders or received direct support from CCARBON//USP.

Results:

Two doctoral and two master's degree papers have been completed. Five articles have been submitted so far. One has been accepted but has not yet been published; the others are under review. In addition, three other papers are being finalized and should be submitted by the end of August.

3.6.3 Part 3: GHG emission reduction

(A) Principal Investigator: Adibe Luiz Abdalla

Technology: Enteric fermentation

Key questions addressed/Research area: How manipulating the microbiome profile in the rumen through feed biomass can mitigate enteric methane in grazing ruminants under tropical conditions?

Summary of achievements: The objective of research line is to evaluate the potential of innovative strategies involving the use of biomass, tropical algae, and biochar in reducing the environmental impact of ruminant livestock production by mitigating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, enhancing feed efficiency, conserving ecosystems, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices. (i) Main activities performed during the period: The research initiatives carried out under the CCARBON/USP -Animal program focused on evaluating innovative dietary strategies—using forage biomass, tropical algae, and biochar—for mitigating enteric methane (CH₄) emissions in ruminants. Multiple in vitro and in vivo trials were conducted across participating institutions. At the University of Alexandria, three trials tested natural and nano-formulated plant extracts (red seaweed, turnip leaves, Arabic gum) for antimethanogenic potential. The University of Wyoming applied Green Feed and precision tools to assess methane emissions and optimize sheep grazing with virtual fencing. At CENA/USP, the In vitro Rumiflow System (IVRFS) was developed to simulate rumen fermentation semi-continuously. Several projects used this system to evaluate methane production, fermentation parameters, and rumen microbiota using diverse forage combinations. Additional efforts include the application of *Hermetia illucens* frass in intercropped pastures and assessments of *Tithonia diversifolia* with agro-industrial by-products in sheep feeding systems. (ii) Highlights: Key achievements include the development and operation of the IVRFS at LANA/CENA, approval and execution of field trials with CEUA/CENA and CEUA/IZ, submission of abstracts to major international conferences (GGAA, ASAS-CSAS, SilvoPast), and the preparation of multiple manuscripts. Promising dietary treatments were identified that reduce methane emissions without compromising digestibility, supporting climate-smart feeding strategies. Research outcomes directly align with Brazil's ABC+ Plan and Net Zero 2050 targets. (iii) Workplan for the next period: The next phase will involve expanding IVRFS applications to a wider range of tropical forages and seaweeds, completing gas quantification, microbial sequencing, and isotopic analyses. Integration of in vitro, in vivo, and isotopic datasets will enhance model validation. Emphasis will also be placed on manuscript submission, data consolidation, and the dissemination of findings to support CCARBON/USP's mission for sustainable livestock systems in tropical environments.

Team members: Adibe Luiz Abdalla PI (CENA/USP), Yosra A. Soltan, PA (University of Alexandria Egypt, Paulo Tavares Lima PA, (University of Wyoming/USA); Thaynã Gonçalves Timm, PD (CENA/USP); Theyson Duarte Maranhão, PD (CENA/USP), Laura Bertolaso de Vecchi, PhD (CENA/USP); Vivian Evangelista, MSc (CENA/USP). PD Thaynã Gonçalves Timm (i) scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP (quota) (ii) FAPESP 2024/06301-7 “Comprehensive investigation of forage-induced enteric

methane emissions: a multifaceted approach integrating short-term batch culture and long-term RUSITEC incubations with emphasis on isotopic signatures and rumen microbiome functionality.” PD Theyson Duarte Maranhão (i) scholarship not directly funded by CCARBON/USP (ii) PIPD/CAPES: 88887.125425/2025 - “Application of *Hermetia illucens* L. excreta in tropical pastures intercropped with legumes as a strategy to achieve the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals”, (iii) Yes, we received CCARBON/USP supporting letter PhD Laura Bertolaso de Vecchi (i) scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP (quota) (ii) FAPESP 2024/03777-0 “Forage biomass of *Tithonia diversifolia* associated with different agro-industrial co-products in sheep feed: potential for reducing greenhouse gas emissions.” MSc Vivian Evangelista (iv) scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP (v) FAPESP: 2024/23553-0 - “Evaluation of biomasses from integrated systems as an alternative for greenhouse gas mitigation: an in vitro approach”,

Results:

Timm, T.G., Bastidas Vasconez, J.J., Ovani, V. & Abdalla, A.L. Design and implementation of a modified semi-continuous simulation technique to assess enteric methane mitigation in ruminants. RAMIRAN 2025 – 19th international conference, 15–17 October 2025, Wageningen, NL

Timm, T.G., Maranhão, T.D., Ovani, V., Amâncio, B. R., Lopes, L.S., Araújo, P.C.R., Machado, R.S., Abdalla, A.L. Quantification of enteric methane in cattle fed with high-grain, low-grain, and pure-grain diets. RAMIRAN 2025 – 19th international conference, 15–17 October 2025, Wageningen, NL

Timm, T.G. et al. Rumiflow: An Adapted Semi-Continuous In Vitro Fermentation System for Assessing Methane Mitigation in Ruminant Nutrition. II Congresso de Pós-Doutorandos da USP – São Paulo

Laura Bertolaso De Vecchi; Vagner Ovani; Simón Pérez-Márquez; Marya Fernanda Santos da Silva; Helder Louvandini; Rogério Martins Mauricio; Adibe Luiz Abdalla. Intake, digestibility, and gas emissions in Santa Inês sheep fed *Tithonia diversifolia*-based diets with agro-Industrial by-products. XIII Congresso Internacional de Sistemas Silvopastoris (SilvoPast) – Cuba, 2025

M. F. S da Silva, L.B.D. Vecchi, V. S. Ovani, H. Louvandini, A. L. Abdalla, R. M. Maurício. In vivo evaluation of enteric methane production in sheep fed diets composed of agro-industrial by-products. ASAS-CSAS Annual Meeting – Hollywood, Florida, EUA, 2025 (Diplomat Beach Resort)

Laura Bertolaso De Vecchi; Simón Pérez-Márquez; Vagner Ovani; Jeraldine Bastidas; Rogério Martins Mauricio; Helder Louvandini; Adibe Luiz Abdalla. 9th International Greenhouse Gas and Animal Agriculture Conference (GGAA 2025) – Nairobi, Kenya, organizado pelo ILRI e NIBIO;

(B) Principal Investigator: Flávio Augusto Portela Santos

Technology: Enteric fermentation, Animal management

Key questions addressed/Research area: What are the impacts of the inclusion of flint corn ethanol byproducts available in Brazil in diets containing flint corn for feedlot cattle on beef production and GHG emissions?

Summary of achievements: Three studies were conducted to evaluate corn DDGS (dry distillers grains with solubles) for feedlot cattle. In Exp. 1a 391 Nellore bulls were fed diets containing 0, 150, 300, 450, or 600 g/kg DM of DDGS. In Exp. 1b. 20 rumen-cannulated Nellore bulls were fed the same diets of Exp. 1a. In Exp. 1a inclusion of DDGS in the diet decreased dry matter intake linearly and had a quadratic effect on hot carcass weight, with the best result at 30% inclusion. In Exp. 1b DDGS inclusion linearly improved the digestibility of dry matter, organic matter, crude protein, ether extract, and neutral detergent fiber. Nitrogen retention increased without affecting nitrogen excretion. In the rumen, higher DDGS levels decreased propionate, affected quadratically ammoniacal nitrogen with the lowest concentration observed at 300 g/kg DDGS, and did not affect methane production. In summary, high levels of DDGS improved nutrient utilization and nitrogen retention without compromising ruminal stability or increasing methane emissions, highlighting its potential as a sustainable dietary strategy for finishing beef cattle. In this experiment, fecal samples were collected for microbioma analysis. In Exp. 2a 361 Nellore bulls were fed finishing diets containing 0 x 40% DDGS. . In Exp. 2b 16 rumen cannulated F1 Angus x Nellore steers were fed the same diets from the performance trial. The inclusion of 40% DDGS, fully replacing soybean meal and whole cottonseed and partially replacing ground flint corn in the diet during the final third of the finishing period, did not affect feedlot cattle performance, ruminal fermentation, methane production, diet dry matter digestibility and diet net energy concentration. In Exp. 3a 289 Nellore bulls were fed finishing diets containing 0 x 20 x 40% DDGS. In Exp. 3b 24 rumen cannulated F1 Angus x Nellore heifers were fed the same diets from the performance trial. The experiment is not finished yet. The work plan for the next year is to continue evaluating inclusion levels of DDGS not only in diets with ground flint corn, but also with rehydrated flint corn.

Team members: Flávio A. Portela Santos, PI (ESALQ/USP); Diogo F. Costa PA (ESALQ/USP); Larissa de Melo Coelho (PhD, FAPESP # 2023/00518-1); Pedro Souto Lamas (MS, CAPES); Artur Marques Nardi (MS, CAPES).

Results: The Exp 1,2 and 3 will result in 1 Thesis and 2 Dissertations respectively. Abstracts of Exp. 1 and 2 were presented in the American Animal Science Annual Meeting 2024 and 2025

(C) Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Technology: Fertilizer management, Residue management, Land use change, Crop management, Water management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Emission mitigation through soil management, land use, and sustainable practices supported by data and modeling

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, research on reducing agricultural GHG emissions advanced in assessing land management and use practices to mitigate soil- and crop-related fluxes. Remote sensing, predictive modeling, and agro-environmental indicators were integrated to identify critical areas and guide strategies that increase input use efficiency, reduce carbon losses, and maintain soil cover. Methods were developed to monitor the frequency of bare soil — associated with degradation and emissions — alongside improvements in soil physical characterization and the integration of digital mapping with crop growth models. These approaches provided support for conservation practices and more efficient fertilizer management, reducing nitrous oxide emissions and promoting sustainable agricultural systems. Highlights: The research line consolidated a framework linking soil attributes, agricultural management, and GHG emissions, with potential applications in low-carbon agriculture policies and monitoring platforms. Next period plan: The next stage will prioritize integration into MRV systems, expansion of predictive models to different regions, use of climate time series in prospective analyses, and development of technical protocols for national agricultural emissions mitigation programs.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Kabindra Adhikari, PA, (Texas Tech University) Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17876-8 Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2024/11100-0 Borges Marfrann Dias Melo, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00 Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES Miguel Palacio Pelaez Carvalho Neto, IC, (ESALQ/USP) – Projeto IC Mapeamento Calcário/Carbono (FAPESP submetido) Students: Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/17876-8; (iii) Não Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Não Borges Marfrann Dias Melo, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00; (iii) Não Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES; (iii) Não Miguel Palacio Pelaez Carvalho Neto, IC, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP submetido; (iii) Não

Results:

DI RAIMO, L.A.D.L. et al. Sand subfractions by proximal and satellite sensing: Optimizing agricultural expansion in tropical sandy soils. *Catena*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.catena.2023.107604

DOS SANTOS, N.V. et al. Digital soil mapping and crop modeling to define the spatially-explicit influence of soils on water-limited sugarcane yield. *Plant and Soil*, 2024. DOI: 10.1007/s11104-024-06587-w

PELEGRINO, M.H.P. et al. Optimizing soil texture spatial prediction in the Brazilian Cerrado: Insights from random forest and spectral data. *Geoderma Regional*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.geodrs.2025.e00922

SOUSA, G.P.B. et al. Assessing soil degradation in Brazilian agriculture by a remote sensing approach to monitor bare soil frequency: impact on soil carbon. *Soil Advances*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.soilad.2024.100011

(D) Associate Research: Carlos Guilherme Silveira Pedreira

Technology: Fertilizer management, Land use change, Crop management, Enteric fermentation, Animal management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Animal

Summary of achievements: Mitigation Strategies for Greenhouse Gas Emissions in Grazing Systems - The project of postdoctoral researcher Solange Garcia Holschuch, which began on April 1, 2025, falls within the scope of reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, addressing the following categories: fertilizer management, land-use change, crop management, enteric fermentation (via *in vitro* evaluation), and animal management. During this period, the activities focused on structuring the experimental area, including the installation of electric fences, drinking troughs, and other infrastructure required to conduct grazing trials using non-lactating dairy cows as defoliating agents. Soil sampling was also conducted to obtain the initial (baseline) characterization of the experimental units. Samples were analyzed for chemical fertility, physical attributes, total soil carbon, and total nitrogen content, both for project monitoring purposes and to support liming and fertility corrections, ensuring optimal conditions for the establishment and development of the forage crops. (ii) Highlights The main highlight of the period was the preparation of the experimental infrastructure and the initial soil characterization, a critical step to ensure the scientific quality and comparability of future data. The chemical soil analyses also enabled corrective actions to optimize the establishment of the forage species. (iii) Work plan for the next period The next phase of the project will begin during the 2025/2026 tropical growing season, with the implementation of controlled grazing and the collection of soil, plant, and animal data. GHG emissions will be evaluated through *in vitro* methane production assays of the harvested forage samples. The data obtained will be used to quantify the effects of different management practices on GHG emission dynamics in tropical forage systems managed under continuous stocking.

Team members: Carlos Guilherme Silveira Pedreira – PI, ESALQ/USP. Solange Garcia Holschuch, Post-doc, ESALQ/USP – Yes, the scholarship is directly funded by CCARBON/USP. FAPESP 2025/01492-1: Mitigation Strategies for Greenhouse Gas Emissions in Grazing Systems.

(E) Associate Research: Helder Louvadini

Technology: Animal management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Function food in ruminants

Summary of achievements: Bioactive compounds in ruminant as a functional feed will be investigated, integrating different areas of knowledge (inter and multidisciplinary) such as chemistry, microbiology and animal sciences (nutrology, parasitology, genetics, reproduction and immunology) using advances of the "Omics.

Results:

1. Corrêa, P. S., Silva, B. L. A., Duarte, J. P., Presuto, L. M., Guedes, Abdalla, A. L., Louvandini, H. Maternal zinc oxide nanoparticle supplementation during pregnancy and lactation shapes lamb ruminal microbiota. ACAS-CSAS Annual Meeting. Hollywood, Florida, USA. 2025.

2. Alves B.L.S, Saccaro A.S. , Duarte J. P., Jimenez C. R., Abdalla A. L., Louvandini H., Correa P. S. The Influence of zinc oxide nanoparticle supplementation on the composition of rumen microbiota and mcrA gene abundance in Santa Inês ewes. In: 14th International Gut Microbiology Symposium; 2025 Jun 3–5; Clermont-Ferrand, France. Clermont-Ferrand: INRAE; 2025. p. 50.

3. Ferarezi V. S., Silva, B. L. A. Jimenez C. R. , Abdalla A. L., Gerdes L., Louvandini H., Correa, P. S. Influence of different production systems on the archaeal community in beef cattle feces. In: 14th International Gut Microbiology Symposium; 2025 Jun 3–5; Clermont-Ferrand, France. Clermont-Ferrand: INRAE; 2025. p. 50.

(F) Associate Research: Patricia Louvandini

Technology: Enteric fermentation, Animal management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Interaction between gastrointestinal microbiota, ruminants and endoparasites

Summary of achievements: Sheep production represents an opportunity for expansion within Brazilian agribusiness, with the feeding of the herd, as well as reproduction, being key points for the development of this sector. One of the biggest concerns still faced by sheep farming in Brazil is a parasitic infection by gastrointestinal nematodes such as *Haemonchus contortus* (HC), which has been aggravated by the overuse of anthelmintic drugs, causing serious disease problems such as drugs available on the market. Despite the importance of the gastrointestinal microbiota for the health and development of ruminants, little is known about the effects of endoparasite infections on this microbiota. Therefore, the objective of this study is to evaluate the effects on the gastrointestinal microbiota of sheep infected with HC in order to better understand the interaction between parasite and host for the development of a gastrointestinal microbiota manipulation strategy and control of endoparasites in animal production.

Team members: Adibe Luiz Abdalla (CENA/USP), Helder Louvandini (CENA/USP)

Results:

Corrêa, P. S., Fernandes, M. A., Jimenez, C. R., Mendes, L. W., Lima, P. D. M. T., Abdalla, A. L., & Louvandini, H. (2024). Interaction between methanotrophy and gastrointestinal nematodes infection on the rumen microbiome of lambs. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, *100*(6), fiae083.

Corrêa, P. S., Mendes, L. W., Lemos, L. N., Sampaio, A. C. K., Issakowicz, J., McManus, C. M., ... & Louvandini, H. (2021). The effect of *Haemonchus contortus* and *Trichostrongylus colubriformis* infection on the ruminal microbiome of lambs. *Experimental Parasitology*, *231*, 108175.

Correa, P. S., Mendes, L. W., Lemos, L. N., Cruzoulon, P., Niderkorn, V., Hoste, H., ... & Louvandini, H. (2020). Tannin supplementation modulates the composition and function of ruminal microbiome in lambs infected with gastrointestinal nematodes. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, *96*(3), fiae024.

3.7 Sectorial chain: Annual Crops

Research Sector Chain Coordinator: Fábio Ricardo Marin

3.7.1 Part 1: General

Summary of achievements: The Annual Crops research chain has demonstrated significant progress over the past year, with a strong focus on enhancing soil health, mitigating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and improving carbon sequestration in tropical agricultural systems. The research activities, supported by FAPESP and CAPES, involved a comprehensive blend of literature reviews, field studies, and advanced modeling to provide a robust understanding of sustainable management practices. A key achievement was the completion of a project on the impacts of crop diversification strategies in the Brazilian Cerrado. This project, which included a systematic review of 236 studies, revealed a lack of GHG measurements in the biome. It showed that systems incorporating cover crops significantly increased soil aggregate stability, leading to higher carbon content within aggregates (up to 48% more in large macroaggregates) compared to traditional double-cropping systems. Modeling with DayCent indicated that while soybean-cotton succession could decrease soil carbon stocks, diversified systems with cover crops like millet and sunn hemp showed a high potential for soil carbon accrual, estimated at approximately $0.71 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$. Research also advanced on the use of inoculations and cover crops. Findings suggest that inoculations reinforce the positive effects of cover crops on soil enzymatic activity and physical attributes like compaction and porosity. The long-term impact on carbon accumulation is slower but measurable. In a study on GHG emissions, the effects of organic (cover crop residues) and inorganic nitrogen sources on N_2O emissions were assessed in tropical soils. The results highlighted that cover crop residues, particularly from legumes, regulate microbial processes and N_2O emissions by altering soil pH. Furthermore, a long-term field experiment was initiated to evaluate the effectiveness of lime and calcium/magnesium silicate in tropical no-till systems with soybean-maize rotations intercropped with *Urochloa ruziziensis*. This study has established GHG monitoring infrastructure and

initiated systematic measurements of CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O fluxes, with the goal of determining carbon balance and GHG efficiency per kilogram of crop production. Other projects are focused on quantifying carbon input from cover crop biomass and evaluating the decomposition rate in clay soils, and assessing soil health through a multi-indicator approach that includes organic matter fractionation and glomalin-related protein. The upcoming year will focus on finalizing laboratory analyses and data integration from ongoing field experiments to comprehensively evaluate carbon sequestration, soil health, and GHG emissions. The workplan includes completing field campaigns for soybean and maize rotations, maintaining GHG flux measurements, and analyzing soil physical, biochemical, and microbiological indicators. The data will be used to refine and publish scientific manuscripts and technical reports, ensuring the research translates into practical recommendations for sustainable and climate-resilient agricultural practices. We will also continue to investigate how abiotic changes modulate the structure and function of soil microbial communities and study gas emission dynamics under different crop successions and inoculations. Finally, a significant effort will be directed toward a synthesis of the results related to biological and physical soil attributes to provide a holistic view of soil quality.

List of publications obtained throughout the year:

Dias, T.S., Brunetti, H.B., Marin, F.R. (2025). Mitigating Agricultural Risk under Future Climate: Assessing Maize Cycle and Yield in Brazil. *Theoretical and applied climatology*.

Ferreira, J. H. S. et al. Boosting carbon sequestration by using forage grass in tropical deep soil with no-tillage. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, v. 381, p. 109451, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.agee.2025.109750.

Locatelli, J. L. et al. A comprehensive assessment of greenhouse gas emissions research in the Cerrado region, Brazil. *Catena*, v. 247, p. 108538, 2024.

Locatelli, J. L. et al. Modeling soil organic matter changes under crop diversification strategies and climate change scenarios in the Brazilian Cerrado. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, v. 379, p. 109334, 2025.

Locatelli, J. L. et al. Soil carbon allocation, composition, and sequestration changes induced by cropping diversification in tropical systems. *Soil and Tillage Research*, v. 248, p. 106464, 2025.

Locatelli, J. L., & Cerri, C. E. P. (2024). Crop diversification strategies' effects on soil organic matter dynamics in the Brazilian Cerrado region. *Tese de Doutorado*.

Popin, G. V. et al. Land-use change and deep-soil carbon distribution on the Brazilian Amazon-Cerrado agricultural frontier. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, v. 381, p. 109451, 2025.

Popin, G. V., & Cerri, C. E. P. (2024). Land-use change and agricultural intensification: impacts on carbon and nitrogen distribution in soil profiles of the Amazon-Cerrado frontier. *Tese de Doutorado*.

Souza, V. S. et al. Cover crops enhance soil health, crop yield and resilience of tropical agroecosystem. *Field Crops Research*, v. 322, p. 109755, 2025.

Souza, V. S. et al. Trade offs of tropical cover crops: enhanced carbon inputs and soybean yield offset higher N₂O emissions. *Frontiers in Soil Science*, 5, 2025.

3.7.2 Part 2: Carbon removal

(A) Principal Investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Impacts of Crop Diversification Strategies on Soil Carbon Dynamics in the Brazilian Cerrado

Summary of achievements: In this project, we conducted a systematic literature review and a field study to evaluate the current state-of-the-art on the assessment of GHG emissions in agricultural systems and the impact of crop diversification on SOM dynamics in the Cerrado. Specifically, we i) performed a comprehensive literature review to synthesize the information about GHG emissions data; ii) assessed how crop diversification associated with cover crops and no-tillage affect SOM and aggregation in a field experiment conducted in Itiquira – MT; iii) used the DayCent model to simulate the long-term impact of crop diversification and no-tillage on SOM dynamics considering three field experiments located in Costa Rica – MS, Itiquira – MT, and Diamantino – MT. The subject of “GHG” has been poorly investigated in the Cerrado biome. Most studies (30% of 236) only mentioned GHG-related terms but did not measure them. The studies that measured GHG were conducted mainly in the south-central part of the region and were mostly limited to short-term experiments or monitoring periods. The systems including cover crops increased soil aggregate stability, doubling large macroaggregation in the 5-10 and 10-20 cm depths. Increased aggregation under cover crops enhanced C contents within aggregates, i.e., ~48%, 32%, and 34% higher for large macroaggregates, macroaggregates, and microaggregates, respectively, compared to soybean-maize double cropping. Simulations using DayCent indicate that soil C stocks would decrease under the long-term soybean-cotton succession, regardless of soil management (-0.04 to -0.17 Mg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹). Crop diversification with cover crops (i.e., millet, ruzigrass, sunn hemp) had the highest soil C accrual potential (~0.71 Mg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹). The current project was already concluded

Team members: Carlos E. P. Cerri, PI, (ESALQ/USP), Jorge Luiz Locatelli, PhD (ESALQ/USP) - (i) The scholarship was not directly funded by CCARBON/USP; (ii) Process: Fapesp n. 2021/14989-0; (iii) The scholarship did not receive a support letter from CCARBON/USP.

Results:

Thesis:

Locatelli, Jorge Luiz; Cerri, Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino. Crop diversification strategies' effects on soil organic matter dynamics in the Brazilian Cerrado region. 2024.

Publications:

Locatelli, J. L., Popin, G. V., Santos, R. S., Bieluczyk, W., Cipriani, L. T., Cherubin, M. R., & Cerri, C. E. P. (2024). A comprehensive assessment of greenhouse gas emissions research in the Cerrado region, Brazil. *Catena*, 247, 108538.

Locatelli, J. L., Santos, R. S., Tenelli, S., Soares, M. B., Del Grosso, S., Stewart, C. E., ... & Cerri, C. E. P. (2025). Soil carbon allocation, composition, and sequestration changes induced by cropping diversification in tropical systems. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 248, 106464.

Locatelli, J. L., Del Grosso, S., Santos, R. S., Hong, M., Gurung, R., Stewart, C. E., ... & Cerri, C. E. P. (2025). Modeling soil organic matter changes under crop diversification strategies and climate change scenarios in the Brazilian Cerrado. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 379, 109334.

Technology: Soil carbon/ Inoculation with microorganisms

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Cover crop and inoculation with microorganisms in production systems involving grains, especially soybeans.

Summary of achievements: (i) synthesis of the main activities performed during the period> Research on isolated and interacting effects of inoculation and co-inoculation of soybeans in the summer, and intercropping of corn with *Urochloa ruziziensis* in succession, as well as inoculation of intercropped corn and brachiaria with growth-promoting microorganisms on soil quality, especially parameters related to carbon. (ii) highlights: • inoculations reinforce the action of cover crops in promoting enzymatic activity in the soil; • successive crops with balanced inputs facilitate soil enzymatic activity; • enzymatic activity under inoculations with nitrogen-fixing microorganisms is affected by nitrogen input into the system; • cover crops and inoculations influence soil compaction and porosity; • the effect of inoculations and cover crops on carbon accumulation in the soil is slower than that of other attributes such as enzymatic activity and physical attributes (iii) work plan for the next period: Study of gas emission dynamics under successions involving soybeans, inoculated or co-inoculated in the summer, and cover crops or inoculated cover crops in the winter. Synthesis study of the results of biological, including soil carbon, and physical attributes on soil quality.

Team members: Carlos E. P. Cerri, PI, (ESALQ/USP), Arnold Barbosa de Oliveira, MSc, (ESALQ/USP, Embrapa).

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 3: Improving pasture management as a “nature-based solution” for soil carbon sequestration in Brazil

Summary of achievements: (i) Summary of Main Activities Conducted During the Period: The project investigates the impacts of converting pastures into regenerative agricultural systems on the quantity and quality of soil organic matter (SOM) in tropical and subtropical regions of Brazil, also assessing the potential for carbon sequestration and mitigation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The study areas encompass different treatments, including conventional pasture, managed pasture, regenerative agricultural systems, crop-livestock integration, agroforestry systems, and no-tillage. Soil sampling was carried out using a grid (1 ha, nine points every 50 m), collecting disturbed, semi-

disturbed, and undisturbed samples (up to 1 m depth) for chemical, physical, and microbiological analyses. Measurements included carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) contents and stocks, soil bulk density, aggregate stability, and enzymatic activity (arylsulfatase and β -glucosidase). Analyses of bulk density, chemical and enzymatic properties, as well as the final determination of C and N stocks, were completed for all areas, with only the interpretation and FTIR analyses remaining. (ii) Highlights: Carbon Sequestration and GHG Mitigation: Initial evidence suggests that regenerative agriculture can increase soil carbon stocks, particularly in degraded pasture areas, contributing to GHG emissions reduction. Changes in SOM: The study demonstrates the potential of land-use change to modify SOM composition and stability, enhancing soil health and resilience. Sustainable Strategies: The results will support strategies to expand the adoption of regenerative practices, strengthening the sustainability of Brazilian agriculture and supporting national climate targets. (iii) Work Plan for the Next Period: Manuscript preparation activities will be coordinated, and the results will be published. The insights gained from these data will enable the identification of management practices and system intensification levels most suitable for soil carbon storage, aiming to minimize global warming potential. Based on this information, it will be possible to more accurately recommend mitigation-oriented management practices in cultivated areas, contributing to reducing the negative impacts of agriculture on GHG emissions and promoting sustainable production systems.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI (ESALQ/USP), Daniel Aquino De Borba, PhD (ESALQ/USP)

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 4: Impacts on integrated organic matter, glomalina, and soil health in diversified agricultural systems

Summary of achievements: During the period, field samples were collected in an experiment in Lucas do Rio Verde, Mato Grosso. The samples were prepared and analyzed for physical, chemical, and biological indicators. Wet sieving of the samples was performed to obtain three aggregate size classes (large macroaggregates, small macroaggregates, and microaggregates). Physical fractionation of soil organic matter was performed to obtain particulate organic matter (POM) and mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM) in bulk soil samples for each aggregate class. Additionally, glomalin-related soil protein (GRSP) was extracted, purified, and prepared for future analysis. In the next period, an audit of the data in preparation for the BEPE will be conducted at Indiana University (starting November 1st), where the student will work on structural equation modeling and writing scientific papers. In Brazil, interns will be conducting additional evaluations with glomalin, mycorrhizal fungal spores, and carbon.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI (ESALQ/USP); Marcelo Trybek, MSs (ESALQ/USP); Vanessa Mandro Baesteiro, IC (ESALQ/USP).

Results: Article called "Use the slakes application to assess the stability of soil aggregates in tropical conservation agriculture" was submitted to Soil & Tillage Research. But still not accepted to publication. (Submitted)

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 5: Intensified management in regenerative agriculture: impacts on intra-aggregated organic matter

Summary of achievements: During this period, samples were prepared and analyzed for physical, chemical, and biological indicators. Wet sieving of the samples was performed to obtain three aggregate size classes (large macroaggregates, small macroaggregates, and microaggregates). In the soil macroaggregates, physical fractionation of soil organic matter was performed to obtain particulate organic matter (POM) and mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM). In addition, glomalin-related soil protein (GRSP) was extracted from bulk soil samples. In the next period, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) will be performed on POM and MAOM samples in soil aggregates. In addition, mycorrhizal fungal spores will be counted. Furthermore, the data will be processed and used to produce a scientific report for FAPESP.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI (ESALQ/USP); Marcelo Trybek, MSs (ESALQ/USP); Vanessa Mandro Baesteiro, IC (ESALQ/USP).

(B) Principal Investigator: Fernando Dini Andreote

Technology 1: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Cover cropping under no-tillage (NT)

Summary of achievements: In the pursuit of reconciling high-yield agriculture with reduced environmental impact, advancing research on management systems that improve the soil microbiome and its interactions with crops is essential. In this context, we are conducting studies aimed at evaluating the structure, diversity, composition, and complexity of bacterial and fungal communities in the soil, as well as the metabolic versatility in the soybean rhizosphere under the influence of a grass species, a legume species, their combination, and a fallow condition without plants as off-season cover in a no-tillage (NT) system. To this end, our study was conducted in a long-term experimental area (over 20 years) cultivated under no-tillage with cover crops during the off-season and soybean during the growing season. From this site, we collected soil and soybean rhizosphere samples, along with soil for greenhouse experiments. As main findings, we observed that the structure, composition, and connectivity of the soil microbial community are shaped and enhanced by the use of cover crops during the off-season, with direct effects evident in the subsequent soybean season. Additionally, we found that structuring the soil microbiome through off-season cover crops under no-tillage played an important role in modulating the metabolic compounds in the soybean rhizosphere, which resulted in increased carbon stocks in the treatments with off-season cover crops. Overall, our results emphasize that the soil microbial community structured under conservation practices, such as no-tillage with cover cropping during the off-season, can promote unique ecological interactions among soil-microorganisms-rhizosphere-plant in soybean cultivation. For the upcoming period, our plans include publishing the articles derived from this research, which will be presented in the Doctoral Thesis to be defended on August 15, 2025.

Team members: Fernando D. Andreote, PI, (ESALQ/USP). Caio C. G. Freitas, PhD, (ESALQ/USP). Caio César Gomes Freitas/PhD/(ESALQ/USP) (i): No (ii): CAPES (88887.612699/2021-00) (iii): No

Results: Thesis to be defended on August 15, 2025, and manuscripts to be submitted in the upcoming semester.

(C) Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Modeling and monitoring of soil carbon using remote sensing and AI for removal and MRV

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, the research line on Soil Carbon advanced in the quantification and monitoring of soil organic carbon (SOC) in tropical regions by integrating geospatial data, spectroscopy, proximal sensing, and machine learning. Scalable approaches were developed to link field measurements with remote sensing, enabling high-resolution mapping and MRV systems for climate mitigation. Actions included the consolidation of spectral libraries, improvement of predictive models, and the association of mineralogy, microbiology, and carbon stabilization. This made it possible to identify areas with higher sequestration potential and to align national monitoring protocols with international standards. Highlights: Progress was made in operationalizing SOC monitoring, reducing uncertainties, and supporting carbon removal policies. Tools integrating spectroscopy, remote sensing, and modeling were applied at regional and national scales, impacting agriculture, forests, and restoration areas. Next period plan: The focus will be on expanding uncertainty-based assessments, integrating microbial data into sequestration models, improving spectral transferability, and incorporating results into national MRV and carbon credit platforms.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Nikolaos Tziolas, PA, (University of Florida) Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2022/14935-0 Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17508-9 (CCARBON/USP) Nicolás Augusto Rosin, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2021/10063-6 e BEPE 2023/11467-9 Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/11350-4 Marcos Guedes de Lana, MSc, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES Victoria Sato Pedral, IC, (ESALQ/USP) – Projeto Fosfato e Mineralogia Students: Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2022/14935-0; (iii) Não Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Sim (CCARBON/USP); (ii) FAPESP 2023/17508-9; (iii) Sim Nicolás Augusto Rosin, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2021/10063-6 e BEPE 2023/11467-9; (iii) Não Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/11350-4; (iii) Não Marcos Guedes de Lana, MSc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES; (iii) Não Victoria Sato Pedral, IC, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) –; (iii) Não

Results:

BARTSCH, B.A. et al. Space-time mapping of soil organic carbon through remote sensing and machine learning. *Soil & Tillage Research*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.still.2024.106428

RODRÍGUEZ-ALBARRACÍN, H.S. et al. Soil organic carbon sequestration potential explained by mineralogical and microbiological activity using spectral transfer functions. *Science of the Total Environment*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174652

VAN WESEMAEL, B. et al. A European soil organic carbon monitoring system leveraging Sentinel 2 imagery and the LUCAS soil data base. *Geoderma*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.geoderma.2024.117113

ROSIN, N.A. et al. Spatializing soil elemental concentration as measured by X-ray fluorescence analysis using remote sensing data. *Catena*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.catena.2024.107988

(D) Principal Investigator: Maurício Roberto Cherubin

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Biodiversification of agricultural systems as a strategy for soil carbon removal

Summary of achievements: During this period, the project advanced significantly in its goal to evaluate the impacts of regenerative agricultural practices on soil health, carbon storage, and ecosystem sustainability. Activities combined field sampling, laboratory analysis, literature review, and modeling to generate a comprehensive understanding of how diversified systems influence key soil functions. Fieldwork was carried out across multiple sites representing different regions and management histories. Soil samples were collected at various depths and processed to assess physical, chemical, and biological indicators of soil health. Laboratory efforts focused on analyzing soil structure, nutrient availability, organic carbon content, and biological activity. Enzymatic assays and fractionation techniques helped characterize organic matter quality and its role in supporting soil function. Preliminary findings suggest that systems incorporating cover crops and crop rotation tend to enhance soil physical condition, increase biological activity, and contribute to carbon accumulation compared to more simplified systems. Modeling efforts complemented experimental work by projecting the long-term impacts of regenerative practices under different climate and management scenarios. These simulations support the idea that increasing biodiversity and reducing soil disturbance can improve resilience and sustainability in tropical agricultural systems. Knowledge exchange and international collaboration further strengthened methodological approaches and data interpretation. Key highlights of the period include the completion of extensive field and laboratory activities, strong initial results supporting the benefits of regenerative practices, and progress in scientific writing and publication. Collaborative work also led to invited contributions and the development of manuscripts for peer-reviewed journals. In the next phase, remaining analyses will be finalized, and all data will be integrated to evaluate soil carbon sequestration and soil health comprehensively. Modeling outputs will be refined, and a synthesis of results will support the preparation of scientific publications and technical reports. Continued collaboration and dissemination will ensure the broader relevance and application of the project's findings. This research line is also supported by three CCARBON/USP project funded by private sector and coordinated by prof. Maurício Cherubin 1 - BALANÇO DE CARBONO EM SISTEMAS AGRÍCOLAS: revelando o impacto da adoção de práticas de manejo sustentáveis nos estoques de carbono do solo e nas emissões de gases de efeito estufa, from 2023-2025 (Bayer) - finished 2 - FAZENDAS REGENERATIVAS: uma abordagem integrando práticas de manejo e métricas de saúde de solo, from 2025-2027 (Bayer) - in execution

3- Exploring the multifunctionality of cover crops for regenerative agriculture: carbon, soil health, crop yield and resilience, from 2025-2028 (Cargill) - in execution

Team members: Maurício Roberto Cherubin - PI (ESALQ/USP) Lucas Pecci Canisares, Post-doc (ESALQ/USP) - Pos Doc FAPESP - 2023/08814-9 – CCARBON/USP support letter Leonardo Aro Galera, Post-doc (ESALQ/USP) - Bolsa FEALQ (ABC) Carlos Alcides Villalba Algarin, PhD (ESALQ/USP) - Bolsa Paraguai Victoria Santos Souza, PhD (ESALQ/USP) - Doutorado FAPESP - 2022/16368-6 Luis Perissoto, Master (ESALQ/USP) - Mestrado CAPES Mateus Abitante, Master (ESALQ/USP) – Mestrado FAPESP - 2025/02244-1 CCARBON/USP scholarship Eloísa Honorato Rocha, IC (ESALQ/USP) - Graduação FEALQ - Bayer Pedro Chudzik, IC (ESALQ/USP) - Graduação FAPESP 2025/00292-9– CCARBON/USP scholarship Gabriela Ferreira Codling, IC (ESALQ/USP) - Graduação FAPESP 2024/17979-4- CCARBON/USP scholarship Julia Molina, IC (ESALQ/USP) - Graduação FUSP - Ag4C– CCARBON/USP support letter Giovani Viecelli, IC (ESALQ/USP) - Graduação FEALQ - Agrisus

Results:

SOUZA, VICTORIA SANTOS; CANISARES, LUCAS PECCI; SCHIEBELBEIN, BRUNA EMANUELE; SANTOS, DARLIANE DE CASTRO; MENILLO, RAFAEL BRAGHIERI; JUNIOR, C. ROBERTO PINHEIRO; CHERUBIN, MAURICIO ROBERTO. Cover crops enhance soil health, crop yield and resilience of tropical agroecosystem. *FIELD CROPS RESEARCH*, v. 322, p. 12-pg., 2025-01-18. (24/06095-8, 22/16368-6, 23/11337-8, 23/08814-9, 23/10897-0, 24/08419-5, 21/10573-4) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2025.109755>

PINHEIRO JUNIOR, C. ROBERTO; CANISARES, LUCAS PECCI; ABREU, MARCEL CARVALHO; LYRA, GUSTAVO BASTOS; DE OLIVEIRA, ALINE PACOBAHYBA; GRESCHUK, LUCAS TADEU; FERREIRA, TIAGO OSORIO; PEREIRA, MARCOS GERVASIO; DOS ANJOS, LUCIA HELENA CUNHA; CHERUBIN, MAURICIO ROBERTO. Drivers of carbon stabilization and sequestration in Brazil's black soils. *CATENA*, v. 246, p. 8-pg., 2024-10-05. (21/10573-4, 23/11337-8, 23/00438-8, 23/08814-9)

SOUZA, VICTORIA SANTOS; SANTOS, DARLIANE DE CASTRO; FERREIRA, JAQUELINE GOMES; DE SOUZA, STEFANY OLIVEIRA; GONCALO, TULIO PORTO; DE SOUSA, JOAO VITOR ALVES; CRUVINEL, ALINE GUIMARAES; VILELA, LOURIVAL; PAIM, TIAGO DO PRADO; DE ALMEIDA, RODRIGO ESTEVAM MUNHOZ; et al. Cover crop diversity for sustainable agriculture: Insights from the Cerrado biome. *SOIL USE AND MANAGEMENT*, v. 40, n. 1, p. 15-pg., 2024-01-08. (22/16368-6) <https://doi.org/10.1111/sum.13014>

PINHEIRO JUNIOR, C. ROBERTO; FERREIRA, TIAGO OSORIO; OLIVEIRA FILHO, JOSE DE SOUZA; QUEIROZ, HERMANO MELO; CANISARES, LUCAS PECCI; GRESCHUK, LUCAS T.; CERRI, CARLOS EDUARDO PELLEGRINO; PEREIRA, MARCOS GERVASIO; PEREIRA, GONCALO AMARANTE GUIMARAES; CHERUBIN, MAURICIO ROBERTO. Shallow soils in dryland ecosystems: Drivers of C accumulation and land management implications.

GEODERMA REGIONAL, v. 38, p. 9-pg., 2024-08-14. (23/11337-8, 23/08814-9, 23/00438-8, 21/10573-4)

Canisares, L. P., Joris, H. W., Teixeira, S. A., Junior, C. K., Souza, L. F., Junior, C. R. P., ... & Cherubin, M. R. (2025). Exploring high-intensity cropping rotations for improved yield and economic returns. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 169, 127679. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2025.127679>

Souza, V. S.; Ferreira, J. B. G.; Santos, D. C.; Greschuk, L. T.; Schiebelbein, B. E.; Bortolo, L. S.; Gonçalo, T. P.; Fialho, A. R.; Souza, S. O.; Paim, T. P.; Almeida, R. E. M.; Vilela, L.; Cherubin, M. R. Maize-Urochloa grass intercropping: an option for improving sustainable agriculture in the Brazilian Savannah. *Experimental Agriculture*, 61, e17, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0014479725100070>

Souza, V. S.; Vanolli, B. S.; Schiebelbein, B. E.; Bortolo, L. S.; Carvalho, M. L.; Mendes, I. C.; Cherubin, M. R. Cover crops and soil health in Brazilian agricultural systems. In: Mendes, I. C.; Cherubin, M. R. (Eds.) *Soil health and sustainable agriculture in Brazil*. Soil Health Series: Volume 3. ASA, CSSA, and SSSA Books, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780891187448.ch4>

Carvalho, M.L., Galera, L.A., Siepmann Scholten, R.S.,... Cherubin, M.R. Biomass production and nutrient uptake from cover crops in Brazilian agriculture, 17 June 2025, PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square [<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-6787742/v1>]

(E) Associate Research: Carlos Alexandre Costa Crusciol

Technology: Soil carbon, Crop breeding/physiology, Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS)

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil carbon, Crop breeding/physiology and BECCS (This line evaluates lime and calcium/magnesium silicate as tools to enhance soil carbon sequestration and reduce GHG emissions in tropical no-till systems, combining field and greenhouse experiments to assess carbon inputs, stabilization, and emission dynamics).

Summary of achievements: Substantial progress was achieved in implementing the long-term field experiment focused on the mitigation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions using lime and calcium/magnesium silicate under tropical no-till systems. The experimental setup was successfully established with soybean–maize rotations (2024–2026) intercropped with *Urochloa ruziziensis*. Soil sampling and installation of GHG monitoring infrastructure, including PVC collars and LI-COR IRGA systems, were completed. Protocols for collecting above- and belowground biomass, root C and N, and plant biochemical components were initiated. Systematic measurements of CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O fluxes during crop cycles began, alongside soil moisture and temperature monitoring. Key achievements during this period include: (i) calibration and reliable operation of the LI-COR IRGA system for high-resolution GHG flux data; (ii) detailed destructive sampling for dry matter and root C and N using LECO elemental analysis; (iii) execution of soil analyses, including total C and N, pH, and organic matter fractionation into particulate (POM) and mineral-associated (MAOM) pools; and (iv)

initiation of a controlled greenhouse trial to compare the direct CO₂ release from lime versus silicate reactions in previously unamended soils. For the next phase, the workplan includes completing field campaigns for soybean and maize (2025/2026), maintaining GHG flux measurements, and calculating cumulative emissions and CO₂-equivalent values. Comprehensive evaluations of soil physical, biochemical, and microbiological indicators (e.g., microbial biomass, basal respiration, qCO₂) will be conducted. The carbon balance and conservation index will be estimated based on inputs and losses, and results will be linked to grain yield to determine GHG efficiency per kilogram of production.

Team members: Carlos Alexandre Costa Crusciol, PI (FCA/UNESP); João Henrique dos Santos Ferreira, PhD Fellow (FCA/UNESP); Laura Tarrafel da Silva, IC Fellow (FCA/UNESP); Marcela Pacola Oliveira, Post-doc applicant (FCA/UNESP); Juliano Carlos Calonego, Faculty Member (FCA/UNESP); José Roberto Portugal, Collaborator (FCA/UNESP, not funded by CCARBON/USP). Students: João Henrique dos Santos Ferreira / PhD Fellow / FCA–UNESP (Department of Crop Production) (i) Is the scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP? No (ii) Funding agency and process number: FAPESP – Process n° 2023/18096-6 (iii) Did the scholarship receive a support letter from CCARBON? Yes Laura Tarrafel da Silva / IC Fellow / FCA–UNESP (Department of Crop Production) (i) Is the scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP? No (ii) Funding agency and process number: FAPESP – Process n° 2024/08385-3 (iii) Did the scholarship receive a support letter from CCARBON/USP? Yes

Results:

This research line is linked to two approved FAPESP projects:

- PhD – FAPESP Process n° 2023/18096-6: Potencial mitigador de gases de efeito estufa com uso de calcário e silicato de cálcio e magnésio em sistema de semeadura direta de longa duração
- IC – FAPESP Process n° 2024/08385-3: Calcário e silicato de cálcio e magnésio no balanço de carbono em semeadura direta de longa duração

Published article: Ferreira, J. H. S., Portugal, J. R., Fróes, M., Bossolani, J. W., Calonego, J. C., Crusciol, C. A. C. (2025). Boosting carbon sequestration by using forage grass in tropical deep soil with no-tillage. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 109750. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2025.109750> No thesis or dissertation has been defended yet under this research line, and additional manuscripts are currently under preparation.

3.7.3 Part 3: GHG emission reduction

(A) Principal Investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri

Technology: Land use change/Crop management/ Soil Carbon and Nitrogen Biogeochemistry

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Use of different land-uses and soil management to soil carbon and nitrogen

Summary of achievements: During the reporting period, two major studies advanced understanding of deep-soil biogeochemistry in the southeastern Amazon. The first examined deep soil nitrogen (N) dynamics across forest, recently deforested, single-crop soybean, and double-crop soybean–corn systems to 8 m depth. We found that deforestation alone—without fertilization—drove significant redistribution of N from surface to deep layers, likely via mineralization and leaching following slash-and-burn. Croplands exhibited similar total N stocks to forests but with distinct nitrate enrichment at 3–6 m depth, suggesting combined effects of land conversion and fertilization. These results clarify initial mechanisms of deep nitrate formation and highlight the long-term legacy of deforestation on N cycling. The second paper investigated deep-soil carbon (C) distribution under native forest, pasture, recently deforested, single-cropped soybean, and double-cropped soybean–maize. Across land uses, 30–40% of C to 8 m was stored in the top metre, with ~50% in the upper 3 m. Forest-to-cropland conversion reduced mineral-associated organic matter C to 1 m depth, while intensification (double cropping) partially restored surface C pools. Pasture promoted particulate organic matter accrual at depth. These findings emphasize the need to sample beyond the conventional 1 m profile to capture full C dynamics under tropical land-use change. In the coming period, we will finalize and submit the manuscript “Short-term deforestation and conversion to cropland systems drive shifts of soil bacterial and fungal communities in the southeastern Amazon” to *Soil Biology & Biochemistry*. This work links land-use change, microbial community composition, and C and N fractions, adding a mechanistic, biological dimension to our previous geochemical findings.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo P. Cerri, Gustavo Vicentini Popin (PhD) Gustavo Vicentini Popin/ former PhD student/"Luiz de Queiroz" College of Agriculture - University of São Paulo FAPESP, Process number 2019/25988-5, No support letter from CCARBON/USP.

Results:

Thesis:

Popin, G. V., & Cerri, C. E. P. (2024). Land-use change and agricultural intensification: impacts on carbon and nitrogen distribution in soil profiles of the Amazon-Cerrado frontier.

Publications:

Popin, G. V., de Resende, M. E. B., Locatelli, J. L., Santos, R. S., Siqueira-Neto, M., Brando, P. M., ... & Cerri, C. E. (2025). Land-use change and deep-soil carbon distribution on the Brazilian Amazon-Cerrado agricultural frontier. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 381, 109451.

Technology: Land use change/ Crop management/
Inoculation with microorganisms

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Elimination or reduction of nitrogen fertilization through the inoculation of soybeans or other grain crops with nitrogen-fixing microorganisms or plant growth promoters.

Summary of achievements: The adoption of new soybean genotypes raises questions about the need for supplemental mineral nitrogen (N), despite its potential to suppress biological nitrogen fixation (BNF). In Brazil, many producers rely on endemic rhizobium populations, yet our results show that mineral N consistently impairs BNF without increasing yields. Reinoculation with *Bradyrhizobium* prevents yield losses even in areas with native populations, while co-inoculation with *Azospirillum* enhances crop performance. Extending these biologically based, environmentally friendly technologies to other crops such as maize and brachiaria offers a sustainable path to higher productivity with reduced dependence on resource-intensive inputs.

Team members: Carlos E. P. Cerri, PI, (ESALQ/USP), Arnold Barbosa de Oliveira, MSc, (ESALQ/USP, Embrapa).

Technology: Crop management

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Quantification of organic carbon input from the total biomass of cover crops and evaluation of the decomposition rate in production systems in clay soils of tropical climates.

Summary of achievements: In recent decades, the concentration of greenhouse gases (GHG), particularly CO₂, has increased significantly, largely due to agricultural activities and changes in land use. Conventional agricultural operations, which involve intensive soil tillage, cause carbon loss through the release of CO₂ into the atmosphere, worsening the problem. However, sustainable agricultural practices, such as the use of cover crops and no-till farming, can mitigate this impact by reducing emissions and increasing carbon storage in the soil. The overall goal of this project is to quantify carbon storage in the aboveground biomass and root system of cover crops up to a depth of 50 cm (0-10, 10-20, 20-30, 30-40, and 40-50 cm), as well as to evaluate the decomposition rate (0 and 90 days) of these plants in clay soils in the tropical region of Brazil. The study will be conducted in Sorriso, MT. Field samples will be collected to analyze the carbon content in the aboveground and root parts of the plants using an elemental analyzer. Additionally, the decomposition rate of the biomass will be determined, evaluating carbon and nitrogen content. The data will be analyzed using ANOVA, and Tukey's test will be applied with a significance level of 5%. It is expected that the results obtained will guide national public policies aimed at reducing GHGs in agriculture, as well as serve as a valuable tool for producers and technicians in improving the management of production systems. Thus, the project will contribute to promoting more sustainable and environmentally responsible agriculture.

Team members: María Celina Villagra Luraschi/Master's degree student/CCARBON/USP Carlos Eduard Pellegrino Cerri/Advisor, Prof. Dr./CCARBON/USP

(B) Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Technology: Fertilizer management, Residue management, Land use change, Crop management, Water management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Emission mitigation through soil management, land use, and sustainable practices supported by data and modeling

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, research on reducing agricultural GHG emissions advanced in assessing land management and use practices to mitigate soil- and crop-related fluxes. Remote sensing, predictive modeling, and agro-environmental indicators were integrated to identify critical areas and guide strategies that increase input use efficiency, reduce carbon losses, and maintain soil cover. Methods were developed to monitor the frequency of bare soil—associated with degradation and emissions—alongside improvements in soil physical characterization and the integration of digital mapping with crop growth models. These approaches provided support for conservation practices and more efficient fertilizer management, reducing nitrous oxide emissions and promoting sustainable agricultural systems. Highlights: The research line consolidated a framework linking soil attributes, agricultural management, and GHG emissions, with potential applications in low-carbon agriculture policies and monitoring platforms. Next period plan: The next stage will prioritize integration into MRV systems, expansion of predictive models to different regions, use of climate time series in prospective analyses, and development of technical protocols for national agricultural emissions mitigation programs.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Kabindra Adhikari, PA, (Texas Tech University) Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17876-8 Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2024/11100-0 Borges Marfrann Dias Melo, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00 Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES Miguel Palacio Pelaez Carvalho Neto, IC, (ESALQ/USP) – Projeto IC Mapeamento Calcário/Carbono (FAPESP submetido) Students: Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/17876-8; (iii) Não Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Não Borges Marfrann Dias Melo, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00; (iii) Não Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES; (iii) Não Miguel Palacio Pelaez Carvalho Neto, IC, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP submetido; (iii) Não

Results:

DI RAIMO, L.A.D.L. et al. Sand subfractions by proximal and satellite sensing: Optimizing agricultural expansion in tropical sandy soils. *Catena*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.catena.2023.107604

DOS SANTOS, N.V. et al. Digital soil mapping and crop modeling to define the spatially-explicit influence of soils on water-limited sugarcane yield. *Plant and Soil*, 2024. DOI: 10.1007/s11104-024-06587-w

PELEGRINO, M.H.P. et al. Optimizing soil texture spatial prediction in the Brazilian Cerrado: Insights from random forest and spectral data. *Geoderma Regional*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.geodrs.2025.e00922

SOUSA, G.P.B. et al. Assessing soil degradation in Brazilian agriculture by a remote sensing approach to monitor bare soil frequency: impact on soil carbon. *Soil Advances*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.soilad.2024.100011

(C) Principal Investigator: Maurício Roberto Cherubin

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed: Mechanisms and mitigation of greenhouse gases emissions in diversified tropical agroecosystems

Summary of achievements: During the reporting period, significant progress was made toward understanding how diversified management practices influence greenhouse gas emissions (GHG), and carbon and nitrogen dynamics in agroecosystems across Brazil. Activities included soil sampling from incubation to long-term field experiments under varying cropping systems, laboratory analysis and greenhouse gas monitoring under different treatments. Multiple experimental sites were assessed across key agricultural regions (e.g., Carambei - PR, Rio Verde - GO, Rondonópolis MT). Controlled incubations and in-field gas monitoring campaigns were conducted to assess GHG emissions, particularly nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions under contrasting treatments, including rotation system, organic residues and mineral fertilizers. In the field, studies are being finalized, but first results are showing that diversified systems, including cover crops, emit more, but the carbon intensity (emissions/crop yield) is lower, reducing C footprint of soybean grains. Also, incubation studies provided insights into the temporal dynamics of emissions and the role of soil pH and residue quality in regulating nitrogen losses. Highlights of the period include evidence that diversified cropping systems, particularly those integrating cover crops, improve soil structure and carbon stabilization, while potentially mitigating greenhouse gas emissions or reducing C intensity. Preliminarily, systems with greater plant diversity showed enhanced biological activity and better aggregation, though some treatments increased short-term N₂O emissions depending on soil type and input quality. For the next period, work will focus on finalizing pending laboratory analyses, including gas chromatography of remaining samples, and processing of organic matter fractions. Integrated data analysis will be conducted to link soil properties, crop productivity, and emissions. Emphasis will be placed on comparing systems based on both environmental performance and productivity, using metrics such as emissions per unit of biomass produced. This will support the identification of sustainable and climate-resilient agricultural practices suitable for tropical regions.

Team members: Maurício Roberto Cherubin - PI (ESALQ/USP) Leonardo Aro Galera, Post-doc (ESALQ/USP) - Bolsa FEALQ (ABC) Lucas Pecci Canisares, Post-doc (ESALQ/USP) - Pos Doc FAPESP - 2023/08814-9 – CCARBON/USP support letter Martha Lustosa Carvalho, PhD (ESALQ/USP) - Doutorado FAPESP - 2022/13531-3 Victoria Santos Souza, PhD (ESALQ/USP) - Doutorado FAPESP - 2022/16368-6 Camile Padovese, IC (ESALQ/USP) - Graduação FAPESP - Ag4C Pedro Chudzik, IC (ESALQ/USP) - Graduação FAPESP 2025/00292-9– CCARBON/USP scholarship Gabriela Ferreira Codling, IC (ESALQ/USP) - Graduação FAPESP 2024/17979-4 CCARBON/USP scholarship Giovani Viecelli, IC (ESALQ/USP) - Graduação FEALQ - Agrisus

Results:

Locatelli, J. L. et al. A comprehensive assessment of greenhouse gas emissions research in the Cerrado region, Brazil, *Catena*, 247, 108538, 2024 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2024.108538>

Souza, V. S.; Borges, M. T.; Schiebelbein, B. E.; Canisares, L. P.; Locatelli, J. L.; Bortolo, L. S.; Santos, D. C.; Pacheco, L. P.; Cerri, C. E. P.; Cherubin, M. R. Trade offs of tropical cover crops: enhanced carbon inputs and soybean yield offset higher N₂O emissions. *Frontiers in Soil Science*, in press, 2025.

(D) Associate Research: Paulo Sergio Pavinato

Technology: Fertilizer management, Residue management, Crop management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil/Crop/Fertilizer Management to Improve P and S Efficiency in Annual Crops for improving C sequestration

Summary of achievements: This project includes both short-term and long-term experiments. Short-term experiments will evaluate the effectiveness of crop species, as well as the most promising P and S management strategies and bio-based fertilizers aiming at sustainable cash crop production and active C allocation in soil. Long-term field experiments (LTE) will assess the impact of cover crops on soil profile quality and health within crop rotations. LTEs trials are already established in some regions of Brazil, with additional experiments to be established in collaboration with institutions and partners. This project provides an opportunity to introduce innovative P and S solutions (e.g., new cover crops, bio-based fertilizers, fertilizer placement) to enhance nutrient use efficiency and assess soil C protection and accumulation, contributing to improved soil health. **Methodology:** Soil samples will be collected from field studies conducted in collaboration with research institutions and universities across Brazil. Specific experiments include: 1. Dois Vizinhos-PR (UTFPR): Ongoing since 2009, evaluating cover crop effects on P dynamics, P speciation, and crop yield. 2. Arapiraca-AL (UFAL): Established in 2022, focusing on P solubility in semi-arid conditions with maize as the cash crop. 3. Paraguay: Field P calibration experiments in collaboration with UFRGS, evaluating yield and P availability. 4. Fundação ABC, PR: Evaluating chemical-biological changes from crop/soil management in LTEs. 5. Fundação MS: Trials assessing microorganism effects on P solubilization and nutrient availability. 6. Fundação MT: LTEs in Itiquira-MT since 2010, studying P levels in depth and comparing furrow vs. broadcast fertilization. In all field studies, crop yield, shoot growth, and P/S uptake will be evaluated, along with soil P speciation. In select studies, rhizosphere soil will be analyzed for organic acids, enzymes, and effective species exudation. **Deliverables:** The results will deepen our understanding of how different P sources affect availability over time and how annual crops absorb these forms of P, linking these mechanisms to biogeochemical and geochemical nutrient cycles. Technical recommendations for improved nutrient management practices will be disseminated through WP7.

Team members: Paulo Sergio Pavinato – PI, (Esalq/USP) Lucas W. Mendes – PA, Cena/USP Maria Carolina Quecine – Esalq/USP Jose Leonardo Gonçalves - Esalq/USP Tiago Tezotto – Esalq/USP Carlos Antônio C. Nascimento – Esalq/USP Hudson Wallace Carvalho – Cena/USP Laercio R. Sartor – UTFPR, Dois Vizinhos PR Tales Tiecher – UFRGS, Porto Alegre RS Valdevan R. dos Santos – UFAL, Arapiraca AL Douglas Gitti

– Fundação MS, Dourados MS Gabriel Barth – Fundação ABC, Castro PR Larissa Bortolo – Fundação MT, Rondonópolis MT Students: Millena Raquel Queiroz – MS, Esalq/USP – scholarship CAPES Wellington Rosa Soares – MS, Esalq/USP – no scholarship Andre L. de F. Espinoza – DR, Esalq/USP - scholarship CAPES Fernanda Miotti – DR, Esalq/USP - scholarship CAPES Matheus B. N. Pereira – DR, Esalq/USP - scholarship CAPES Mikaella Meira Monteiro – DR, Esalq/USP

(E) Associate Research: Simone Raposo Cotta

Technology 2: Crop management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Mechanisms of diversified cropping systems in reducing greenhouse gas emissions through changes in microbial communities.

Summary of achievements: Mitigating climate change requires a better understanding of greenhouse gas emissions from agroecosystems, particularly the trade-off between soil organic carbon sequestration and nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions. This study assessed the effects of organic (cover crop residues) and inorganic (ammonium sulfate, AS) nitrogen sources on N₂O emissions in tropical soils with contrasting pH (5.6 and 7.0), focusing on microbial mechanisms driving nitrification over a 30-day microcosm incubation. Cover crop residues, particularly legumes, have a significant influence on nitrogen dynamics and soil pH. In acidic soil, legumes mineralized ~20 µg NH₄⁺-N g⁻¹ more than grasses and increased pH by up to 1.5 units within 10 days. N₂O emissions varied according to nitrogen source and soil pH. In acidic soil, residues initially produced more N₂O than AS; however, emissions from AS surpassed those from residues after 13 days, resulting in 45% higher cumulative emissions. In near-neutral soil, both AS and legume residues generated up to 10.7 times more N₂O than grasses or control treatments. Emission factors showed that AS contributed 0.48% of the applied N to N₂O emissions in acidic soil, while grass and legume residues emitted 0.54% and 0.44% of the mineralized N, respectively. Ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB) were more abundant in N-amended soils, particularly with organic inputs under low pH. In contrast, ammonia-oxidizing archaea (AOA) predominated under near-neutral pH with organic amendments. These findings highlight the role of cover crop residues in regulating microbial processes and N₂O emissions by altering soil pH and NH₄⁺ availability. We are now investigating how these abiotic changes modulate the structure and function of soil microbial communities.

Team members: Simone R Cotta, PA, (ESALQ/USP). Caio Simões dos Santos Nicolau, MsC student (ESALQ/USP). (i) No (ii) CAPES (iii) Not yet. We are currently finalizing the proposal to submit it to FAPESP, with a support letter from CCARBON/USP. The regular project was approved at FAPESP (2024/15399-0) with a support letter from CCARBON/USP

3.8 Transversal research areas

3.8.1 Measurement, Reporting and Verification (MRV) Technologies

Research Sector Chain Coordinator: José Alexandre M. Demattê

Summary of achievements: i) During the period we worked with projects from farm to global scale. Two farm scales were evaluated regarding soil carbon degradation. After, a deep preparation of big data reaching about 150.000 analysis from Brazil and 1.500.000 soil analysis of the globe. Data are with geolocation and soil analysis carbon included. We organized, evaluated consistency and harmonized data. The data started to be used on two projects, the Brazilian soil spectral service, an online service of soil carbon analysis and the world soil spectral service at global scale. Both algorithms are finalized and will start validation. A quantification of soil water retention was performed as well. Satellite sensing on carbon quantification was performed. Carbon flux at the Brazilian scale is ongoing.

ii) quantify carbon using sensors at distance for Brazil and Global scales are absolutely novel. The soil carbon flux of CO₂ and its balance is in development using proximal and remote sensing as well. We generated an algorithm to quantify carbon with sensors located 800 km from the target with 30 and 20 m spatial resolution. Dissemination is being done by submission in congress, events and workshops. Lectures given in Brazilian events and overseas (Belgium) were performed as well.

iii) Next steps are to finalize these ongoing works and go to a next level such as relating soil health by soil sensing by online platforms. We also intend to determine the Brazilian soil's detailed mineralogy and relate it with carbon sequestration.

Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

(A) Principal Investigator 1: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Technology: Fertilizer management, Residue management, Land use change, Crop management, Water management

Key questions addressed/Research area: Emission mitigation through soil management, land use, and sustainable practices supported by data and modeling

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, research on reducing agricultural GHG emissions advanced in assessing land management and use practices to mitigate soil- and crop-related fluxes. Remote sensing, predictive modeling, and agro-environmental indicators were integrated to identify critical areas and guide strategies that increase input use efficiency, reduce carbon losses, and maintain soil cover. Methods were developed to monitor the frequency of bare soil—associated with degradation and emissions—alongside improvements in soil physical characterization and the integration of digital mapping with crop growth models. These approaches provided support for conservation practices and more efficient fertilizer management, reducing nitrous oxide emissions and promoting sustainable agricultural systems. Highlights: The research line consolidated a framework linking soil attributes, agricultural management, and GHG emissions, with potential applications in low-carbon agriculture policies and monitoring platforms. Next period plan: The next stage will prioritize integration into MRV systems, expansion of predictive models to different regions, use of climate time series in prospective analyses, and development of technical protocols for national agricultural emissions mitigation programs.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Kabindra Adhikari, PA, (Texas Tech University) Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17876-8 Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2024/11100-0 Borges Marfrann Dias Melo, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00 Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES Miguel Palacio Pelaez Carvalho Neto, IC, (ESALQ/USP) – Projeto IC Mapeamento Calcário/Carbono (FAPESP submetido) Students: Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/17876-8; (iii) Não Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Não Borges Marfrann Dias Melo, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES 88887.840324/2023-00; (iii) Não Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES; (iii) Não Miguel Palacio Pelaez Carvalho Neto, IC, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP submetido; (iii) Não

Results:

DI RAIMO, L.A.D.L. et al. Sand subfractions by proximal and satellite sensing: Optimizing agricultural expansion in tropical sandy soils. *Catena*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.catena.2023.107604

DOS SANTOS, N.V. et al. Digital soil mapping and crop modeling to define the spatially-explicit influence of soils on water-limited sugarcane yield. *Plant and Soil*, 2024. DOI: 10.1007/s11104-024-06587-w

PELEGRINO, M.H.P. et al. Optimizing soil texture spatial prediction in the Brazilian Cerrado: Insights from random forest and spectral data. *Geoderma Regional*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.geodrs.2025.e00922

SOUSA, G.P.B. et al. Assessing soil degradation in Brazilian agriculture by a remote sensing approach to monitor bare soil frequency: impact on soil carbon. *Soil Advances*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.soilad.2024.100011

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: MRV, climate modeling, and data governance for policies and sustainable land use

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, the transversal research line focused on the development of MRV technologies, climate modeling, and data governance for sustainable land use. Global databases, remote sensing, spectroscopy, and artificial intelligence were integrated to create scalable monitoring and analysis tools applicable in different contexts. Advances were made in consolidating spectral libraries and data networks, essential for closing information gaps and supporting MRV systems. Automated analysis methods and models integrating edaphoclimatic, socioeconomic, and land use variables enabled climate impact assessments and supported mitigation and adaptation policies. The research also strengthened the connection between science and governance, aligning technical data with green finance, carbon markets, and low-carbon agriculture programs. This integration fostered innovation and the development of sustainable economic models. Highlights: Development of MRV systems based on spectroscopy and orbital data, interoperability between national and international platforms, and the use of cloud-based analysis for fast and low-cost diagnostics. Next period plan: (i) Integrate future climate models and land use scenarios; (ii) Expand MRV systems to include carbon credits; (iii) Promote adoption of tools by public and private institutions; (iv) Develop standardized protocols for governance and environmental traceability.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Nikolaos Tziolas, PA, (University of Florida) Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2022/14935-0 Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17508-9 (CCARBON/USP) Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2022/11034-2 Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/11350-4 Students: Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2022/14935-0; (iii) Não Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Sim (CCARBON/USP); (ii) FAPESP 2023/17508-9; (iii) Sim Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2022/11034-2; (iii) Não Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/11350-4; (iii) Não

Results:

DEMATTE, J.A.M. et al. *Frontiers in earth observation for global soil properties assessment linked to environmental and socio-economic factors. The Innovation*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.xinn.2025.100985

DEMATTE, J.A.M. et al. A global soil spectral grid based on space sensing. *Science of the Total Environment*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.178791

NOVAIS, J.J.M. et al. Online analysis of Amazon's soils through reflectance spectroscopy and cloud computing. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.124155

NOVAIS, J.J.M. et al. Brazilian Soil Spectral Library (VIS-NIR-SWIR-MIR) data opening. Dokuchaev Soil Bulletin, 2024. DOI: 10.19047/0136-1694-2024-119-92-116

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 3: Modeling and monitoring of soil carbon using remote sensing and AI for removal and MRV

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, the research line on Soil Carbon advanced in the quantification and monitoring of soil organic carbon (SOC) in tropical regions by integrating geospatial data, spectroscopy, proximal sensing, and machine learning. Scalable approaches were developed to link field measurements with remote sensing, enabling high-resolution mapping and MRV systems for climate mitigation. Actions included the consolidation of spectral libraries, improvement of predictive models, and the association of mineralogy, microbiology, and carbon stabilization. This made it possible to identify areas with higher sequestration potential and to align national monitoring protocols with international standards. Highlights: Progress was made in operationalizing SOC monitoring, reducing uncertainties, and supporting carbon removal policies. Tools integrating spectroscopy, remote sensing, and modeling were applied at regional and national scales, impacting agriculture, forests, and restoration areas. Next period plan: The focus will be on expanding uncertainty-based assessments, integrating microbial data into sequestration models, improving spectral transferability, and incorporating results into national MRV and carbon credit platforms.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Nikolaos Tziolas, PA, (University of Florida) Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2022/14935-0 Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17508-9 (CCARBON/USP) Nicolás Augusto Rosin, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2021/10063-6 e BEPE 2023/11467-9 Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/11350-4 Marcos Guedes de Lana, MSc, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES Victoria Sato Pedral, IC, (ESALQ/USP) – Projeto Fosfato e Mineralogia Students: Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2022/14935-0; (iii) Não Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Sim (CCARBON/USP); (ii) FAPESP 2023/17508-9; (iii) Sim Nicolás Augusto Rosin, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2021/10063-6 e BEPE 2023/11467-9; (iii) Não Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/11350-4; (iii) Não Marcos Guedes de Lana, MSc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES; (iii) Não Victoria Sato Pedral, IC, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) –; (iii) Não

Results:

BARTSCH, B.A. et al. Space-time mapping of soil organic carbon through remote sensing and machine learning. Soil & Tillage Research, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.still.2024.106428

RODRÍGUEZ-ALBARRACÍN, H.S. et al. Soil organic carbon sequestration potential explained by mineralogical and microbiological activity using spectral transfer functions. Science of the Total Environment, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174652

VAN WESEMAEL, B. et al. A European soil organic carbon monitoring system leveraging Sentinel 2 imagery and the LUCAS soil data base. *Geoderma*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.geoderma.2024.117113

ROSIN, N.A. et al. Spatializing soil elemental concentration as measured by X-ray fluorescence analysis using remote sensing data. *Catena*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.catena.2024.107988

(B) Principal Investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri

Key questions addressed/Research area 3: MRV technologies and modeling of climate impacts on soil attributes

Summary of achievements: During the reporting period, transversal research activities advanced in two main directions: (i) the development and application of MRV-compatible methodologies for soil and land surface monitoring, and (ii) modeling the impacts of climate change on soil and ecosystem processes. The study by Siqueira et al. (2023), published in *Geoderma*, applied machine learning to predict soil texture in Maritime Antarctica and the Northern Antarctic Peninsula using remote sensing and environmental covariates. This work contributed to improving the accuracy of spatial soil information in data-scarce regions, directly supporting MRV systems by providing standardized, reproducible methods for soil property estimation. Complementing this, De Mello et al. (2023) in *Geoderma* investigated chemical weathering detection in periglacial landscapes of Maritime Antarctica through the integration of geophysical sensors, topographic data, and machine learning. The findings provided insights into how climate-induced changes in these environments affect soil formation processes and carbon cycling, reinforcing the link between climate change and soil dynamics. Additionally, contributions to the BRASPECS2 platform enhanced national capacity for spectral soil analysis, enabling standardized large-scale SOC and soil property mapping aligned with MRV protocols. Highlights Implementation of ML-based approaches for soil property mapping in remote and climate-sensitive regions. Integration of geophysical, spectral, and environmental datasets to assess climate change impacts on soil processes. Contribution to a national spectral database (BRASPECS2) with direct applications for MRV frameworks. Workplan for the next period: the next steps include expanding MRV-compatible spectral libraries, applying uncertainty mapping to prioritize sampling in underrepresented areas, and integrating climate change projections into soil carbon and property models. Special focus will be placed on improving temporal monitoring capabilities for dynamic environments.

Team members: Equipe: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI, (ESALQ/USP) José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Cássio Marques Moquedace dos Santos, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2025/00139-6 Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2024/11100-0 Students: Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/17876-8; (iii) Não Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Não Cássio Marques Moquedace dos Santos, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Sim

Results:

Siqueira, R. G., Moquedace, C. M., Francelino, M. R., Schaefer, C. E. G. R., Fernandes Filho, E. I. (2023). Machine learning applied for Antarctic soil mapping: Spatial prediction of soil texture for Maritime Antarctica and Northern Antarctic Peninsula. *Geoderma*, 432, 116405. doi:10.1016/j.geoderma.2023.116405

De Mello, D. C., Veloso, G. V., Moquedace, C. M., et al. (2023). Chemical weathering detection in the periglacial landscapes of Maritime Antarctica: New approach using geophysical sensors, topographic variables and machine learning algorithms. *Geoderma*, 438, 116615. doi:10.1016/j.geoderma.2023.116615

(C) Principal Investigator: Maurício Roberto Cherubin

Technology: MRV technologies

Key questions addressed/Research area: STRATIFICATION OF SOIL SAMPLING THROUGH SOIL AND PLANT SPACE-TIME MAPPING TECHNOLOGIES: bases for defining the uncertainties and scalability of the assessment (baseline and monitoring) of soil carbon stocks

Summary of achievements:

In this research line, we have a FAPESP/CNPq project and one post-doc involved. We are starting the second year of the project, and up to now, two main activities were developed:

a. Literature review on the main data (terrain, soil or plant attributes) most commonly used to generate homogeneous management zones (HMZs)- A systematic literature review was carried out of 118 scientific articles focusing on the generation of homogeneous management zones (HMZ). The studies analyzed showed a predominance of the use of soil attributes such as texture, apparent electrical conductivity (ECa) and organic matter, followed by plant data such as NDVI and yield maps, and terrain attributes such as elevation and slope. The most recurrent combinations involved soil and plant data, reinforcing the importance of integrating multiple sources of spatial variability. The most commonly used clustering methods were fuzzy c-means and k-means, highlighting the preference for statistical approaches in the delimitation of MHZs. The full article is under final preparation.

b. Stratification of an experimental area using ZHM design to characterize carbon stocks

At this stage of the project, data was collected from different sources in the experimental area (~67 ha), with a view to future stratification by homogeneous management zones. Soil samples were collected at different depths for physico-chemical analyses and determination of total carbon. Apparent electrical conductivity (ECa) data was also obtained using an electromagnetic induction sensor, as well as soil magnetic susceptibility (MS) data. In addition, images of exposed soil were generated with a drone and yield images collected by a harvester with a duly calibrated yield monitor were processed. This data will be used in the next stage of the project, which involves applying clustering algorithms to delineate the MHZs and then quantifying the soil carbon stocks in each zone. The data collected and the maps generated are in the next sections of this report.

Finally, we expect to make progress in this area with a new CCARBON/USP project, which is funded by Shell, Earthoptics and Bayer. This project will expand the scope to cover more areas and provide more in-depth evaluations.

Team members: Mauricio Cherubin - PI FAPESP project 2024/01979-5 with CCARBON/USP support letter Guilherme Sanches FAPESP 2024/11109-8 (scholarship associated to this project)

(D) Principal Investigator: Pedro Henrique Santin Brancalion

Key questions addressed/Research area: 1. How can biomass estimation approaches be enhanced to support more accurate and credible carbon assessments in forest restoration initiatives? 2. What is the role of locally calibrated allometric models in improving the robustness of carbon accounting across diverse tropical restoration contexts? 3. How can improved allometric models support the integration of field data and remote sensing technologies to enable robust large-scale monitoring? 4. How does the choice of biomass estimation models influence the transparency and credibility of carbon reporting in nature-based solutions?

Summary of achievements: (i) We completed the third campaign of destructive sampling with 176 trees from native species in a 20-year-old restoration plantation at the Anhembi Experimental Station (ESALQ/USP). This complements two previous sampling campaigns at 6 and 12 years of age. Together, the three campaigns provided a comprehensive dataset of 324 trees from 26 species, stratified by diameter classes and functional types. Aboveground biomass (stem, branches, leaves) and wood density were measured for all individuals, and coarse root biomass was sampled for a subset of 40 trees, through complete root excavation. Biomass dry weights were obtained after oven-drying to constant weight, ensuring high-precision quantification. (ii) This dataset represents one of the most complete destructive biomass assessments for native Atlantic Forest plantations to date, and it constitutes the empirical foundation for novel additive and system-based modeling approaches (e.g., Weighted Nonlinear Seemingly Unrelated Regression - WNSUR). These models provide biologically consistent partitioning of biomass among tree components, supporting more robust carbon accounting and improved calibration of remote sensing estimates. Preliminary results demonstrate improved accuracy compared to pantropical models, particularly for multi-strata, mixed-species plantings. (iii) Next steps include the validation of model fitting and error propagation analyses, submission of scientific papers based on the results, and integration of the new allometric equations into LiDAR-based and long-term carbon modeling frameworks in ongoing restoration projects.

Team members: • PIs: Pedro H. S. Brancalion (ESALQ/USP), Otávio Campoe (UFLA), Joannès Guillemot (CIRAD), Ricardo Viani (CCA/UFSCAR), Matheus Ferreira (ESALQ/USP), • PA: Jonathan W. Trautenmüller (ESALQ/USP), Isáira Leite Lopes (UFLA), Matheus S. Luz (UFLA) • PhD: Ana Paula C. Ferez (currently CAPES, transitioning to FAPESP/NBS–RCGI next month)

(E) Associate Research: Iraê Amaral Guerrini

Key questions addressed/Research area: MRV Technologies

Summary of achievements: This research line is about the use of remote sensing. We have developed different approaches to quantify forest carbon through different remote sensing approaches, including Lidar, multi- and hyper-spectral data and RGB images. We have had some success quantifying aboveground carbon stocks in natural forests with satellites and we are now using the same objective with Lidar. Results will be published next year.

Team members: PIs: Iraê Amaral Guerrini (FCA-UNESP-Botucatu); Matheus Ferreira (ESALQ-USP); José Raimundo Sousa Passos (IB-UNESP-Botucatu); Gian Franco Capra and Antonio Ganga (UNISS-Università degli Studi di Sassari, Sardinia, Italy); Students: PhD: Leonardo José Silva Costa (FCA-UNESP, CAPES, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a support letter); MSc: Felipe Góes de Moraes (FCA-UNESP, CAPES, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a support letter);

Results:

JUSTINO, SÉRVIO TÚLIO PEREIRA ; SILVA, RAFAEL BARROCA ; GUERRINI, IRAÊ AMARAL ; DA SILVA, RICHARDSON BARBOSA GOMES ; SIMÕES, DANILO . Monitoring Environmental Degradation and Spatial Changes in Vegetation and Water Resources in the Brazilian Pantanal. Sustainability, v. 17, p. 51, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17010051>

Moraes, Felipe Góes; Sivisaca, Deicy Carolina Lozano; Passos, José Raimundo de Souza; Silva, Rafael Barroca; Roder, Ludmila Ribeiro; Ganga, Antonio; Capra, Gian Franco; Guerrini, Iraê Amaral. The Use of Vegetation Indices as Methods Applied to Predict Aboveground Biomass in Tropical Forests of Brazil. Remote Sensing, 2025 (Submitted)

MSc dissertations defended:

Felipe Góes de Moraes (FCA-UNESP);

(F) Associate Research: Mateus Cecílio Gerolamo

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: A Multicriteria Framework for Selecting Low-Carbon Livestock Practices in the Brazilian Context

Summary of achievements: This research project aims to develop a multicriteria decision-making framework to support the selection of sustainable livestock management practices in the tropical agricultural context of Brazil. The framework emphasizes the integration of economic, environmental, and social criteria, with special attention to mitigating negative social rebound effects. The methodology begins with a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) focused on sustainable practices in livestock production in tropical climates. This review prioritizes academic and technical publications from Brazilian and international tropical contexts. The next steps of the research involve: • The definition and structuring of decision criteria, including indicators related to costs, emissions reduction and social effects (climate justice). • The assignment of relative weights to these criteria, to reflect their importance in the Brazilian livestock context. •

And the validation of the model with experts and producers, ensuring that it reflects practical realities and regional priorities. Data for evaluating the alternatives will be drawn primarily from official Brazilian institutions such as Embrapa, ABC+ Plan, and Brazil's Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC). Validation of the framework will be conducted through consultations with experts and producers, incorporating their perspectives to refine the structure and weights of the decision criteria.

Team members: Murilo Neves Mourarias (EESC/USP), Professor Dr. Mateus Cecílio Gerolamo (ESALQ/USP)

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Mapping Livestock Management Practices for Carbon Sequestration in Brazil.

Summary of achievements: This research project aims to identify and map sustainable livestock management practices that contribute to carbon sequestration in Brazil, while also assessing the current stage of scientific research related to these practices. The methodology began with the identification of agricultural practices that promote carbon sequestration within Brazilian livestock systems, conducted through a systematic review of the relevant scientific literature. The next steps of the research involve: • Create a Map the main sustainable livestock practices currently used in Brazil that present potential for CO₂ sequestration, considering regional variation. • Investigating the state of scientific research on these practices, with the goal of identifying knowledge gaps and opportunities for technical and scientific advancement.

Team members: Felipe Baso Lestido (ESALQ/USP), Professor Dr. Mateus Cecílio Gerolamo (ESALQ/USP)

Key questions addressed/Research area 3: The Power of Data Analytics in Transforming the Agribusiness Industry through Digital Product Passport

Summary of achievements: The main objective is to understand and explain the relationship between Digital Product Passport (DPP) and Data Analytics, explaining how data influences DPP and how this fact can be used to implement and optimize it. With this research project we hope to carry out the Systematic Literature Review methodology on the following topics: Digital Product Passport, Data, Data-Driven, followed by the application of the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) topic model technique, aiming to ensure that there is no bias in the results obtained during the bibliographic research. After data collection, a case study will be carried out with a company in the agricultural sector to elucidate the operation of the DPP in practice. The expected results are, in the academic focus, the theoretical basis for the implementation of the DPP through a data-driven approach and, in the business context, the study of this occurrence in a practical way, demonstrating sustainable economic and environmental implications, enabling the development of public policies. In this way, we seek to determine what already exists on the subject in the academic sector, list the challenges founded in relation to data (privacy, security, sharing, etc.) in contributing to the DPP and prepare a case study focused on the agricultural sector to determine what needs to be done so that data and its technologies enable the use of the DPP by organizations in this important area for Brazil. Regarding deliveries, the execution of two reports is planned, one partial and one final, to monitor the progress of the project, the use of the LDA technique and, finally, the preparation of

a scientific article as a conclusion of the results, including both the theoretical academic part and the practical part of the case study focused on agribusiness. It is worth mentioning that the article aims to be published in journals and approved for presentation at conferences. However, as the project has not yet been approved, it has not been defined how many and which publication processes the article will be submitted to. Observation: the execution of the activities listed here depends on the approval of the Fapesp Scientific Initiation project number 2025/08887-1, already submitted and which is “In Qualification”, with validity scheduled from 06/01/2025 to 05/31/2026. There are no main results yet because the project has not been approved.

Team members: Paulo Vinícius Carneiro Perazolli (EESC/USP), Professor Dr. Mateus Cecílio Gerolamo (ESALQ/USP)

(G) Associate Research: Lucie Zinger

Technology: Biomonitoring with environmental DNA

Key questions addressed/Research area: Improvement of eDNA-based technologies for the monitoring of natural tropical ecosystems, land use change impacts, and restoration success

Summary of achievements: The escalating threats to tropical ecosystems require developing efficient and non-invasive monitoring tools for effective conservation and restoration efforts. This research line focuses on improving eDNA-based technologies for the monitoring of natural tropical ecosystems, land use impacts, and restoration success. (i) Synthesis of Main Activities Performed (Current Period): As I have joined CCARBON/USP only recently on the project, there have been no main activities performed by me during this initial period. (ii) Highlights (New Approaches): A key highlight of our on-going work that could be applied in CCARBON/USP involves pioneering new approaches to study canopy biodiversity. Specifically, we developed an approach in Amazonian forests and tree plantations utilizing DNA contained in canopy throughfalls (i.e. DNA washed from forest canopy by rain). This innovative method holds significant promise for non-invasively assessing the diverse life forms inhabiting the often-inaccessible tropical forest canopy, including plants, vertebrates, and invertebrates. (iii) Workplan for the Next Period: Our immediate workplan is multifaceted. We will focus on the deployment and rigorous validation of the rain eDNA approach across various habitats in French Guiana and Brazil natural and disturbed environments. This will involve field work and comparison with traditional biodiversity monitoring methods to assess its efficacy and reliability of the approach to both quantify biodiversity and detect species of high interest for conservation or human/ecosystem health. Concurrently, we aim to develop a more quantitative and multitrophic eDNA-based method to describe full food-webs. Finally, a last crucial aspect of our work will be the development of portable eDNA-based approaches, enabling rapid and on-site analysis in remote tropical environments, which is essential for timely conservation and management decisions.

Team members: Lucie Zinger, PI (CNRS) Jérémy Raynaud, PhD student (Toulouse University/CNRS), not funded by CCARBON/USP, thesis funded and project funded by LabEx TULIP (ANR-10-LABX-0041) and LabEx CEBA (ANR-10-LABX-25-01), letter

from CCARBON/USP not requested as the work started independently from CCARBON/USP, but we are happy to include it within this framework.

Results:

Zinger L. et al. (in press) Elusive tropical forest canopy diversity revealed through environmental DNA contained in rainwater. *Science Advances*. Preprint: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.02.26.640397>

(H) Associate Research: Matheus Pinheiro Ferreira

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Biomass estimation using LiDAR technology

Summary of achievements: Team of the recently approved FAPESP Project led by Prof. Rodrigo Hakamada (Demonstrative Multifunctional Forests to support the ReflorestaSP Program – DemonstrataSP, FAPESP process no. 2024/15282-6)

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: LiDAR Technology for Forest Monitoring

Summary of achievements: Recently approved FAPESP project (currently under contract) titled "LiDAR Technology for Forest Monitoring in São Paulo: Support for Public Policies on Climate Change Mitigation," under the FAPESP Research Program on Public Policies (PPPP).

(I) Associate Research: Raul Roberto Poppiel

Key questions addressed/Research area: Remote sensing, modelling, mapping soil attributes and spatial soil health assessment

Summary of achievements: During the reporting period, I co-authored and published two high-impact scientific articles. The first addressed the spatial assessment of soil health across Latin America and the Caribbean, while the second focused on the global mapping of soil attributes in relation to socioeconomic indicators. Additionally, I edited a Special Issue on "Soil Organic Carbon Mapping and Monitoring" in collaboration with a U.S.-based researcher, aiming to advance the global discussion on SOC MRV. ii) Key findings and highlights - An estimated 38% of soils in Latin America and the Caribbean are classified as unhealthy, 28% as moderately healthy, and 34% as healthy, based on integrated soil health indicators. - Approximately 64% of the world's topsoil has a sandy texture, making it highly susceptible to degradation and carbon loss under inappropriate land management. iii) Work plan for the next period Two undergraduate theses (TCC) and one scientific initiation (IC) will be supervised: 1. Assessment of Soil Health Index in the Piracicaba Region: Analyzing its agricultural, environmental, and socioeconomic implications. 2. Spatiotemporal analysis of soil organic carbon stocks in relation to land use and land cover change in Brazil. 3. Mapping of soil organic carbon and plant-available water across São Paulo State. Research proposal submission: I will prepare and submit a proposal to the FAPESP First Research Grant – 2025 Call (Primeiros Projetos), focused on soil monitoring systems and carbon modeling. Scientific outreach and participation: I will participate in the 2025 Brazilian Congress of Soil Science (CBCS 2025), where I will deliver a lecture on alternative methodologies for soil health assessment, emphasizing low-cost, scalable approaches. Soil health assessment Perform a global assessment of soil health using the soil attribute maps elaborated for the globe.

Team members: Prof. José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, LSO/ESALQ/USP -Prof. Raul Roberto Poppiel, LSO/ESALQ/USP Students: - Victória Sato Pedral, TCC, LSO/ESALQ/USP Advisor: Raul R. Poppiel Scholarship: None - Augusto Resende Vilarinho Prudêncio, TCC, LSO/ESALQ/USP Advisor: Raul R. Poppiel Scholarship: None - Matheus Fatori, IC, LSO/ESALQ/USP Advisor: Raul R. Poppiel Scholarship: PUB/USP

Results:

DEMATTÊ, JOSÉ A.M.; POPPIEL, RAUL R.; NOVAIS, JEAN J.M.; ROSIN, NÍCOLAS AUGUSTO; MINASNY, BUDIMAN; SAVIN, IGOR Y.; GRUNWALD, SABINE; CHEN, SONGCHAO; HONG, YONGSHENG; HUANG, JINGYI; CHABRILLAT, SABINE; DE JONG VAN LIER, QUIRIJN; BEN-DOR, EYAL; GOMEZ, CECILE; GANLIN, ZHANG; ACCORSI AMORIM, MERILYN TAYNARA; VOGEL, LETÍCIA GUADAGNIN; FIM ROSAS, JORGE TADEU; MILEWSKI, ROBERT; GHOLIZADEH, ASA; ZHOGOLEV, ARSENIY V.; CAMPUSANO, JOSE PADARIAN; MA, YUXIN; JANG, HO JUN; RUDIYANTO; WANG, CHANGKUN; RIZZO, RODNEI; TZIOLAS, NIKOLAOS; TSAKIRIDIS, NIKOLAOS; KODAIRA, MASAKAZU; KUMAR, D. NAGESH; DHARUMARAJAN, SUBRAMANIAN; GE, YUFENG; VAUDOUR, EMMANUELLE; AYOUBI, SHAMSOLLAH; MENSAH BINEY, JAMES KOBINA; BELAL, ABDELAZIZ; MARANDI, SALMAN NAIMI; HAFSHEJANI, NAJMEH ASGARI; KALOPESA, ELENI; MELLO, DANILO CESAR; FRANCELINO, MARCIO ROCHA; MOHAMED SALAMA, ELSAYED SAID; ABDELBAKI, ASMAA. *Frontiers in earth observation for global soil properties assessment linked to environmental and socio-economic factors. The Innovation.* Fator de Impacto: 33,2, v.1, p.100985, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xinn.2025.100985>

POPPIEL, RAUL R.; CHERUBIN, MAURÍCIO R.; NOVAIS, JEAN J. M.; DEMATTÊ, JOSÉ A. M. *Soil health in Latin America and the Caribbean. Communications Earth & Environment.* Fator de Impacto: 8,1, v.6, p.1 - 1, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-025-02021-w>

Special Issue in Agronomy (MDPI)

Advancing Soil Organic Carbon Stock Prediction with Digital Mapping https://www.mdpi.com/journal/agriculture/special_issues/3AE5881A7F Editors: - Prof. Dr. Raul R. Poppiel (ESALQ/USP) - Prof. Dr. Nikolaos Tziolas (University of Florida)

3.8.2 Modeling impact assessment due climate change

Research Sector Chain Coordinator: Fábio Ricardo Marin

Summary of achievements: Over the past year, the research on "Modeling Impact Assessment due to Climate Change" chain has been productive, demonstrating significant advancements in developing and applying models to evaluate climate change impacts on Brazilian agricultural systems. This success is a testament to the dedicated work of a talented team of graduate and postdoctoral researchers, whose projects, supported by FAPESP scholarships, are directly contributing to the center's scientific output and its mission to train skilled professionals.

The team is actively engaged in several key projects focused on major agricultural sectors across Brazil. Master's student Tharsos Hister Giovanella is assessing the impact of climate change on rice cultivation. In a related project, Gustavo Angelo de Luca is working on evaluating the effects of climate change on Asian soybean rust. Pietra Putarov is investigating the impact of climate change on the maize-brachiaria intercropping system, while Ulysses Chaves Netto is studying its effects on cassava cultivation. These projects provide crucial insights into the vulnerabilities of Brazil's food and bioenergy crops and are essential for developing adaptive strategies.

In addition, postdoctoral researcher Henrique Baubab Brunetti is conducting a vital project to evaluate climate change impacts on Brazilian pastures. These diverse research efforts contribute to a comprehensive and multidisciplinary agenda that integrates data across various scales, from specific crop vulnerabilities to broader ecosystem responses.

The team's work has led to significant publications and submissions, reinforcing CCARBON/USP leadership in this field. One article, focusing on maize yield in Brazil, was published in 2025:

- Dias, T.S., Brunetti, H.B., Marin, F.R. (2025). Mitigating Agricultural Risk under Future Climate: Assessing Maize Cycle and Yield in Brazil. Theoretical and applied climatology.

Furthermore, two manuscripts have been submitted to the journal *Agricultural Systems* for consideration, extending the research to other important crops and systems:

- Leite, E., Silva, E.H.F.S., Marin, F.R. Modeling sugarcane yield, crop water productivity, and nitrous oxide emissions across Brazil's bioenergy frontiers under climate change. *Agricultural Systems* (submitted).
- Brunetti, H.B., Marin, F.R. Assessing Climate Risk and Adaptive Strategies for Forage Production in Brazilian Pasture-Based Livestock under Future Climate Scenarios. *Agricultural Systems* (submitted).

Workplan for the Next Period:

In the upcoming period, the team will continue to advance these projects, finalizing analyses and preparing additional manuscripts for publication. The focus will be on expanding our modeling efforts to incorporate a wider range of climate and socioeconomic variables, with the aim of developing more complex and integrated assessments. We also plan to actively disseminate our findings through scientific conferences, workshops, and technical reports to inform policymakers and industry stakeholders. Our goal is to translate scientific knowledge into practical, actionable solutions that enhance the resilience of tropical agricultural systems to climate change.

(A) Principal Investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Impacts of Crop Diversification Strategies on Soil Carbon Dynamics in the Brazilian Cerrado

Summary of achievements: In this project, we conducted a systematic literature review and a field study to evaluate the current state-of-the-art on the assessment of GHG emissions in agricultural systems and the impact of crop diversification on SOM dynamics in the Cerrado. Specifically, we i) performed a comprehensive literature review to synthesize the information about GHG emissions data; ii) assessed how crop diversification associated with cover crops and no-tillage affect SOM and aggregation in a field experiment conducted in Itiquira – MT; iii) used the DayCent model to simulate the long-term impact of crop diversification and no-tillage on SOM dynamics considering three field experiments located in Costa Rica – MS, Itiquira – MT, and Diamantino – MT. The subject of “GHG” has been poorly investigated in the Cerrado biome. Most studies (30% of 236) only mentioned GHG-related terms but did not measure them. The studies that measured GHG were conducted mainly in the south-central part of the region and were mostly limited to short-term experiments or monitoring periods. The systems including cover crops increased soil aggregate stability, doubling large macroaggregation in the 5-10 and 10-20 cm depths. Increased aggregation under cover crops enhanced C contents within aggregates, i.e., ~48%, 32%, and 34% higher for large macroaggregates, macroaggregates, and microaggregates, respectively, compared to soybean-maize double cropping. Simulations using DayCent indicate that soil C stocks would decrease under the long-term soybean-cotton succession, regardless of soil management (-0.04 to -0.17 Mg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹). Crop diversification with cover crops (i.e., millet, ruzigrass, sunn

hemp) had the highest soil C accrual potential ($\sim 0.71 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$). The current project was already concluded

Team members: Carlos E. P. Cerri, PI, (ESALQ/USP), Jorge Luiz Locatelli, PhD (ESALQ/USP) - (i) The scholarship was not directly funded by CCARBON/USP; (ii) Process: Fapesp n. 2021/14989-0; (iii) The scholarship did not receive a support letter from CCARBON/USP

Results:

Thesis:

Locatelli, Jorge Luiz; Cerri, Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino. Crop diversification strategies' effects on soil organic matter dynamics in the Brazilian Cerrado region. 2024.

Publications:

Locatelli, J. L., Popin, G. V., Santos, R. S., Bieluczyk, W., Cipriani, L. T., Cherubin, M. R., & Cerri, C. E. P. (2024). A comprehensive assessment of greenhouse gas emissions research in the Cerrado region, Brazil. *Catena*, 247, 108538.

Locatelli, J. L., Santos, R. S., Tenelli, S., Soares, M. B., Del Grosso, S., Stewart, C. E., ... & Cerri, C. E. P. (2025). Soil carbon allocation, composition, and sequestration changes induced by cropping diversification in tropical systems. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 248, 106464.

Locatelli, J. L., Del Grosso, S., Santos, R. S., Hong, M., Gurung, R., Stewart, C. E., ... & Cerri, C. E. P. (2025). Modeling soil organic matter changes under crop diversification strategies and climate change scenarios in the Brazilian Cerrado. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 379, 109334. (afiliação correta)

Technology: Soil carbon (Carbon Removal)

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Mapping and modeling soil carbon using spectroscopy and AI

Summary of achievements: During the reporting period, research efforts focused on soil organic carbon (SOC) mapping and modeling at different spatial scales, with two major scientific outputs. The first, published in *Geoderma Regional* (2024), produced high-resolution SOC stock maps for the western Amazon using dry combustion data as a reference, complemented with Walkley–Black converted values. This work integrated spectral data from VNIR and MIR analyses with environmental covariates to train Random Forest models, improving SOC spatial prediction in a tropical context with strong land use variability. The second, published in *Communications Earth & Environment* (2025), extended the SOC research to extreme environments, assessing the potential of ice-free areas of Maritime and Peninsular Antarctica to act as carbon sinks under climate change. This study combined field-collected SOC measurements with spatial modeling, highlighting the role of emerging ecosystems in global carbon dynamics. Beyond publications, activities included the organization and harmonization of SOC datasets, contributions to the BRASPECS2 spectral platform, and the application of spatial modeling techniques consistent with the SCORPAN framework. These steps directly support Measurement, Reporting and Verification (MRV) requirements for

carbon accounting. Highlights High-resolution SOC mapping in the western Amazon (Geoderma Regional, 2024). First assessment of SOC sink potential in Antarctic ice-free areas (Communications Earth & Environment, 2025). Integration of analytical, spectral, and environmental data for improved SOC prediction. Contribution to national spectral databases for MRV applications. Workplan for the next period The next phase will expand SOC mapping to broader regions in Brazil, increasing coverage of dry combustion measurements and incorporating additional MIR spectra. Advanced machine learning approaches will be tested to refine model accuracy. The Antarctic SOC dataset will be updated with new sampling campaigns, enabling temporal analysis of carbon accumulation. These actions aim to deliver robust SOC maps and uncertainty layers aligned with national and global MRV systems, supporting targeted carbon sequestration strategies.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI, (ESALQ/USP) José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Cássio Marques Moquedace dos Santos, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2025/00139-6 Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2024/11100-0 Students: Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/17876-8; (iii) Não Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Não Cássio Marques Moquedace dos Santos, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Sim

Results:

Moquedace, C. M., Baldi, C. G. O., Siqueira, R. G., Cardoso, I. M., de Souza, E. F. M., Fontes, R. L. F., Francelino, M. R., Gomes, L. C., Fernandes-Filho, E. I. (2024). High-resolution mapping of soil carbon stocks in the western Amazon. *Geoderma Regional*, 31, e00889. doi: 10.1016/j.geodrs.2024.e00773

De Mello, D. C., Francelino, M. R., Moquedace, C. M., Baldi, C. G. O., et al. (2025). Global warming may turn ice-free areas of Maritime and Peninsular Antarctica into potential soil organic carbon sinks. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 6, 143. doi:10.1038/s43247-024-01937-z

Technology: Land use change/ Crop management (GHG emission reduction)

Key questions addressed/Research area 3: Monitoring land-use changes and environmental disturbances for GHG emissions mitigation

Summary of achievements: During the reporting period, activities under this research line focused on quantifying and monitoring processes related to GHG emission reduction through land use change assessment and management practices. The first key study, published in *Journal of Environmental Management* (Imbaná et al., 2024), evaluated the quality of constructed technosols in ecological restoration areas. The research integrated soil property measurements with spatial analysis to assess the effectiveness of restoration in improving soil function and contributing to long-term carbon retention. This approach demonstrated how well-designed restoration projects can serve as a tool for both ecosystem recovery and GHG mitigation. The second, published in *International Journal of Remote Sensing* (Siqueira et al., 2025), investigated the capacity of high-resolution satellite sensors to detect burnt areas in the Pantanal wetlands during the 2020 wildfire

event. By comparing MODIS, Landsat-8, and Sentinel-2 data, the study improved the detection accuracy of fire-affected zones, enabling better quantification of biomass loss and associated carbon emissions. These findings directly support strategies to monitor and reduce emissions from wildfires, which are a major source of GHG in tropical regions. Highlights Demonstration of ecological restoration's role in carbon retention through constructed technosols monitoring. Enhanced accuracy in detecting burnt areas using finer-resolution satellite imagery, improving fire-related GHG emission estimates. Integration of field data, laboratory analyses, and geospatial technologies to support MRV frameworks for emission reduction. Workplan for the next period Next steps include expanding restoration site monitoring to capture temporal trends in soil carbon recovery, applying similar methodologies in different biomes. Additionally, wildfire detection algorithms will be further refined using multi-sensor data fusion, aiming to provide rapid, high-precision assessments of GHG emissions from fire events. Both lines of work will contribute to robust MRV-compatible datasets supporting emission reduction strategies in Brazil.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI, (ESALQ/USP) José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Cássio Marques Moquedace dos Santos, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2025/00139-6 Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2024/11100-0 Students: Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/17876-8; (iii) Não Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Não Cássio Marques Moquedace dos Santos, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Sim

Results:

Imbaná, R., Valente, F. D. A., Siqueira, R. G., Moquedace, C. M., Assis, I. R. (2024). Assessing the quality of constructed technosols enabled holistic monitoring of ecological restoration. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 353, 120237. doi:10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.120237

Siqueira, R. G., Moquedace, C. M., Silva, L. V., Oliveira, M. S., Cruz, G. B., Francelino, M. R., Schaefer, C. E. G. R., Fernandes-Filho, E. I. (2025). Do finer-resolution sensors better discriminate burnt areas? A case study with MODIS, Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2 spectral indices for the Pantanal 2020 wildfire detection. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 47, 1–24. doi:10.1080/01431161.2025.2496000

Key questions addressed/Research area 4: MRV technologies and modeling of climate impacts on soil attributes

Summary of achievements: During the reporting period, transversal research activities advanced in two main directions: (i) the development and application of MRV-compatible methodologies for soil and land surface monitoring, and (ii) modeling the impacts of climate change on soil and ecosystem processes. The study by Siqueira et al. (2023), published in *Geoderma*, applied machine learning to predict soil texture in Maritime Antarctica and the Northern Antarctic Peninsula using remote sensing and environmental covariates. This work contributed to improving the accuracy of spatial soil information in data-scarce regions, directly supporting MRV systems by providing

standardized, reproducible methods for soil property estimation. Complementing this, De Mello et al. (2023) in *Geoderma* investigated chemical weathering detection in periglacial landscapes of Maritime Antarctica through the integration of geophysical sensors, topographic data, and machine learning. The findings provided insights into how climate-induced changes in these environments affect soil formation processes and carbon cycling, reinforcing the link between climate change and soil dynamics. Additionally, contributions to the BRASPECS2 platform enhanced national capacity for spectral soil analysis, enabling standardized large-scale SOC and soil property mapping aligned with MRV protocols. Highlights Implementation of ML-based approaches for soil property mapping in remote and climate-sensitive regions. Integration of geophysical, spectral, and environmental datasets to assess climate change impacts on soil processes. Contribution to a national spectral database (BRASPECS2) with direct applications for MRV frameworks. Workplan for the next period The next steps include expanding MRV-compatible spectral libraries, applying uncertainty mapping to prioritize sampling in underrepresented areas, and integrating climate change projections into soil carbon and property models. Special focus will be placed on improving temporal monitoring capabilities for dynamic environments.

Team members: Equipe: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI, (ESALQ/USP) José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Cássio Marques Moquedace dos Santos, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2025/00139-6 Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2024/11100-0 Students: Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/17876-8; (iii) Não Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Não Cássio Marques Moquedace dos Santos, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Sim

Results:

Siqueira, R. G., Moquedace, C. M., Francelino, M. R., Schaefer, C. E. G. R., Fernandes Filho, E. I. (2023). Machine learning applied for Antarctic soil mapping: Spatial prediction of soil texture for Maritime Antarctica and Northern Antarctic Peninsula. *Geoderma*, 432, 116405. doi:10.1016/j.geoderma.2023.116405

De Mello, D. C., Veloso, G. V., Moquedace, C. M., et al. (2023). Chemical weathering detection in the periglacial landscapes of Maritime Antarctica: New approach using geophysical sensors, topographic variables and machine learning algorithms. *Geoderma*, 438, 116615. doi:10.1016/j.geoderma.2023.116615

Key questions addressed/Research area 5: Digital Soil Mapping and Soil Organic Carbon Modeling Using Remote Sensing Tools and Machine Learning Techniques.

Summary of achievements: i) Submission and acceptance of an abstract at an international conference; completion of courses offered by the ESALQ graduate program, ii) active participation in courses provided by the GeoCiS group and field sample collection, and iii) database organization, as well as theoretical and bibliographic deepening.

Team members: Prof. Dr. Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri (ESALQ/USP), Prof. Dr. José Alexandre Melo Demattê (ESALQ/USP). MSc Matheus Carraco Cardoso (ESALQ/USP). i) Sim, ii) FAPESP (2025/00502-3) e iii) Não.

Technology: Modeling impact assessment due climate change

Key questions addressed/Research area 6: Develop an algorithm to quantify available water using remote sensing techniques and relate it to changes in carbon.

Summary of achievements: i) Submission and acceptance of abstracts at international conferences; completion of courses offered by the ESALQ/USP graduate program; literature review; ii) active participation in training/courses provided by the research group; iii) writing of thesis/article chapter; correlating available soil water data with carbon dynamics; study and testing of the relationship between available water, microorganisms, and soil mineralogy; presentation of the first chapter at the conference.

Team members: Prof. Dr. Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, (ESALQ, USP); Prof. Dr. José Alexandre Melo Demattê, (ESALQ/USP). Leticia Guadagnin Vogel, PhD, (ESALQ/USP), i) Sim, ii) FAPESP (2025/00597-4) iii) Não.

(B) Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Key questions addressed/Research area: MRV, climate modeling, and data governance for policies and sustainable land use

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, the transversal research line focused on the development of MRV technologies, climate modeling, and data governance for sustainable land use. Global databases, remote sensing, spectroscopy, and artificial intelligence were integrated to create scalable monitoring and analysis tools applicable in different contexts. Advances were made in consolidating spectral libraries and data networks, essential for closing information gaps and supporting MRV systems. Automated analysis methods and models integrating edaphoclimatic, socioeconomic, and land use variables enabled climate impact assessments and supported mitigation and adaptation policies. The research also strengthened the connection between science and governance, aligning technical data with green finance, carbon markets, and low-carbon agriculture programs. This integration fostered innovation and the development of sustainable economic models. Highlights: Development of MRV systems based on spectroscopy and orbital data, interoperability between national and international platforms, and the use of cloud-based analysis for fast and low-cost diagnostics. Next period plan: (i) Integrate future climate models and land use scenarios; (ii) Expand MRV systems to include carbon credits; (iii) Promote adoption of tools by public and private institutions; (iv) Develop standardized protocols for governance and environmental traceability.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Nikolaos Tziolas, PA, (University of Florida) Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2022/14935-0 Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17508-9 (CCARBON/USP) Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2022/11034-2 Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP)

– FAPESP 2023/11350-4 Students: Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2022/14935-0; (iii) Não Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Sim (CCARBON/USP); (ii) FAPESP 2023/17508-9; (iii) Sim Merylyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2022/11034-2; (iii) Não Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/11350-4; (iii) Não

Results:

DEMATTÊ, J.A.M. et al. Frontiers in earth observation for global soil properties assessment linked to environmental and socio-economic factors. *The Innovation*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.xinn.2025.100985

DEMATTÊ, J.A.M. et al. A global soil spectral grid based on space sensing. *Science of the Total Environment*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.178791

NOVAIS, J.J.M. et al. Online analysis of Amazon's soils through reflectance spectroscopy and cloud computing. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.124155

NOVAIS, J.J.M. et al. Brazilian Soil Spectral Library (VIS-NIR-SWIR-MIR) data opening. *Dokuchaev Soil Bulletin*, 2024. DOI: 10.19047/0136-1694-2024-119-92-116

(C) Associate Research: Ernani Pinto Júnior

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil Health

Summary of achievements: Although my direct collaboration in transversal research within CCARBON/USP has not yet begun, my submitted Thematic Project (FAPESP Process nº 2023/11082-0) aligns strongly with these themes. The project proposes the integration of stable isotope tracing and metabolomic data into modeling frameworks for evaluating carbon sequestration efficiency under different agroforestry management practices.

These methodologies can contribute to CCARBON/USP's transversal goals by generating high-resolution biochemical and isotopic datasets to feed into predictive models of carbon cycling, soil health, and resilience to climate change. In the period, two publications cited CCARBON/USP:

1. Campos TGV et al. New records on toxic cyanobacteria from Brazil: Exploring their occurrence and geography, *Science of The Total Environment*, Volume 931, 2024, 172689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172689>

2. Jacinavicius et al. A rapid LC-MS/MS method for multi-class identification and quantification of cyanotoxins, *Toxicon*, Volume 234, October 2023, 107282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxicon.2023.107282>

Work plan for the next period: If the project is approved, initiate experimental trials in agroforestry systems, generating isotopic and metabolomic datasets to be integrated with CCARBON/USP's modeling activities and soil health assessments.

Team members: Ernani Pinto, PI (CENA/USP) and other members of CCARBON/USP

Results:

Campos TGV et al. New records on toxic cyanobacteria from Brazil: Exploring their occurrence and geography, *Science of The Total Environment*, Volume 931, 2024, 172689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172689>

Jacinavicius et al. A rapid LC-MS/MS method for multi-class identification and quantification of cyanotoxins, *Toxicon*, Volume 234, October 2023, 107282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxicon.2023.107282>

(D) Associate Research: Stoécio Malta Ferreira Maia

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil carbon sequestration in integrated systems and pastures in the Brazilian semiarid region

Summary of achievements: Fieldwork was conducted in four locations in Brazil's semiarid region, encompassing various livestock-forest integration systems. The focus was to assess the dynamics of soil C and organic matter.

Team members: Stoécio M.F. Maia, Adviser (IFAL). Crislâny Canuto dos Santos (PhD. UFAL). Thamirys Suelle da Silva (PhD. UFAL). Handerson Brandão Melo de Lima (MSC. UFAL). José Marcone da Silva (MsC. UFAL). None of them were scholarship holders or received direct support from CCARBON/USP.

Results:

Two doctoral and two master's degree papers have been completed. Five articles have been submitted so far. One has been accepted but has not yet been published; the others are under review. In addition, three other papers are being finalized and should be submitted by the end of August.

(E) Associate Research: Tsai Siu Mui

Technology: Soil carbon, Crop breeding/physiology, Biochar, Methanotrophy stimulation through use of composed inoculants

Key questions addressed/Research area: This project aims to investigate the role of methanotrophy in carbon sequestration at different stages of ecological succession in restoration areas, pastures, and native forests in the Amazon. The central hypothesis postulates that the increase in methanotrophic bacteria and the reduction in methanogenic archaea promote greater carbon sequestration, favoring the ecological balance throughout forest succession. Another hypothesis tested in this study suggests that model plants will have a positive effect on modulating the microbial community, favoring carbon sequestration. To attend the main goal, soil and litter samples will be collected at different depths (0-10 cm, 10-20 cm, and 20-40 cm) during two seasons (dry and rainy) and two subsequent years. The functional characterization of the microbiota will be conducted through the quantification of functional genes associated with methanotrophy (pmoA and mmoX) and analysis of CH₄ isotopic composition. In parallel, CH₄ emission measurements will be performed using gas chromatography and soil physicochemical analyses will be conducted to assess their influence on microbial processes. The study will be conducted in areas surrounding pastures, forests, and secondary forests in southern

Rondônia. The results of this project will enable an understanding of how ecological succession modulates the microbial communities involved in the methane cycle, contributing to the development of forest management and conservation strategies. The findings are also expected to reinforce the role of secondary forests as potential carbon sinks, with direct implications for climate change mitigation. Furthermore, the potential of Ipê (*Handroanthus* spp.), Jatobá (*Hymenaea courbaril*), and Copaíba (*Copaifera* spp.) species in modulating microbial communities will be evaluated to determine their abilities to stimulate methanotrophy and promote nutrient cycling, thus favoring carbon sequestration.

Team members: Tsai Siu Mui, PI (CENA/USP), Juan Andrés de Domini (PhD student), Rafael Barti Dextro (Post-doc) (ii) A PhD fellowship from CAPES, but the PhD proposal will also be submitted to FAPESP (iii) It will be submitted with a support letter from CCARBON/USP.

Summary of achievements: The project has just started.

3.8.3 Green finances, economic models, public policies, innovations and governance

Research Sector Chain Coordinator: Mateus Cecílio Gerolamo

Summary of achievements: The research sector chain, “Green finances, economic models, public policies, innovations and governance,” integrates interdisciplinary projects aimed at promoting sustainability in Brazilian agriculture. This report spans six key areas: (1) soil carbon sequestration via regenerative agriculture; (2) developing advanced MRV technologies using remote sensing and AI for climate assessments and green finance; (3) analyzing digital transformation and AgTechs to reconfigure value chains for small producers; (4) examining governance challenges of sustainable pasture recovery; (5) designing models for Green Open Innovation; and (6) evaluating Circular Economy strategies for sustainable development. The work plan focuses on publishing results, expanding MRV systems for carbon credits, integrating climate models, promoting institutional adoption of new tools, and further evaluating circular economy practices. These interconnected areas combine technological and governance innovations to build a framework that links scientific discovery, finance, and practical implementation for a low-carbon agricultural economy.

(i) **Synthesis of Main Activities:** The period's work established scientific and technological foundations for a low-carbon economy. This involved field research on soil carbon, developing MRV systems with remote sensing and AI, and policy analysis for sustainable pasture management and green finance. Research also began exploring the role of digital AgTechs and circular economy models in decarbonizing value chains.

(ii) **Highlights:**

- * **Research:** Progress was made in MRV capabilities, with four papers published on soil property assessment and spectral analysis. Initial evidence was gathered on regenerative agriculture's potential to boost soil carbon and mitigate emissions.

- * **Innovation:** Projects initiated the development of innovative, scalable tools, including cloud-based spectral analysis and data platform interoperability. Work began on designing governance models for Green Open Innovation and mapping AgTech solutions.

- * **Dissemination:** Knowledge was shared through the mentioned publications, with further dissemination planned for upcoming periods.

(iii) **Workplan for the Next Period:** The primary goals are to finalize data interpretation and publish results from ongoing soil carbon studies. The plan includes expanding MRV systems for carbon credit certification, integrating future climate and land-use scenarios, and promoting tool adoption by institutions. Future work will also evaluate circular economy practices and develop standardized protocols for environmental governance. New projects submitted to funding agencies are planned to start soon.

Analysis of Research Maturity:

This research line is predominantly in the "Plan of Execution" stage, with its foundational ideas firmly established and now being actively implemented.

- * **Plan of Ideas (Conceptualization):** The core concepts for all research areas are almost fully defined and have moved beyond mere ideation. The projects have clear key questions and structured methodologies.

- * **Plan of Execution (Active Research and Development):** This is the current and dominant phase. The synthesis of activities confirms that extensive field research, technological development, data collection, and policy analysis are actively underway across most teams. The submission of new project proposals to funding agencies further confirms this active, executing state.

- * **Plan of Results/Outcomes/Impact (Long-Term Goal):** While there are early outputs (e.g., four published papers in one sub-area), the overall initiative has not yet produced a comprehensive set of publications, theses, patents, or measurable societal impacts. These higher-order results are recognized as long-term goals, as indicated by the workplan's focus on future publication, tool adoption, and policy development. The impact on society remains a central objective for the future.

(A) Principal Investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Technology transfer

Summary of achievements: Collaborator in technology transfer initiatives aimed at promoting the sustainability of soybean production systems, with a focus on bio-inputs (inoculants) and Integrated Pest and Disease Management. These efforts support the reduction of chemical interventions to levels compatible with plant–microorganism symbiosis and promote pest and disease control strategies based on population thresholds informed by the ecology of insects and microorganisms.

Team members: Carlos E. P. Cerri, PI, (ESALQ/USP), Arnold Barbosa de Oliveira, MSc, (ESALQ/USP, Embrapa).

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Improving pasture management as a “nature-based solution” for soil carbon sequestration in Brazil

Summary of achievements: (i) Summary of Main Activities Conducted During the Period: The project investigates the impacts of converting pastures into regenerative agricultural systems on the quantity and quality of soil organic matter (SOM) in tropical and subtropical regions of Brazil, also assessing the potential for carbon sequestration and mitigation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The study areas encompass different treatments, including conventional pasture, managed pasture, regenerative agricultural systems, crop-livestock integration, agroforestry systems, and no-tillage. Soil sampling was carried out using a grid (1 ha, nine points every 50 m), collecting disturbed, semi-disturbed, and undisturbed samples (up to 1 m depth) for chemical, physical, and microbiological analyses. Measurements included carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) contents and stocks, soil bulk density, aggregate stability, and enzymatic activity (arylsulfatase and β -glucosidase). Analyses of bulk density, chemical and enzymatic properties, as well as the final determination of C and N stocks, were completed for all areas, with only the interpretation and FTIR analyses remaining. (ii) Highlights: Carbon Sequestration and GHG Mitigation: Initial evidence suggests that regenerative agriculture can increase soil carbon stocks, particularly in degraded pasture areas, contributing to GHG emissions reduction. Changes in SOM: The study demonstrates the potential of land-use change to modify SOM composition and stability, enhancing soil health and resilience. Sustainable Strategies: The results will support strategies to expand the adoption of regenerative practices, strengthening the sustainability of Brazilian agriculture and supporting national climate targets. (iii) Work Plan for the Next Period: Manuscript preparation activities will be coordinated, and the results will be published. The insights gained from these data will enable the identification of management practices and system intensification levels most suitable for soil carbon storage, aiming to minimize global warming potential. Based on this information, it will be possible to more accurately recommend mitigation-oriented management practices in cultivated areas, contributing to reducing the negative impacts of agriculture on GHG emissions and promoting sustainable production systems.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI (ESALQ/USP), Daniel Aquino De Borba, PhD (ESALQ/USP)

(B) Principal Investigator: Joaquim Bento de Souza Ferreira Filho

Key questions addressed/Research area: Second harvest modelling and soil carbon in Brazil

Team members: Joaquim Bento de Souza Ferreira Filho (PI, ESALQ/USP), Fernanda Sigainisky Lisbinski (PhD. No scholarship so far). No letter from CCARBON/USP yet.

Summary of achievements: Model under development, no result yet.

(C) Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Key questions addressed/Research area: MRV, climate modeling, and data governance for policies and sustainable land use

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, the transversal research line focused on the development of MRV technologies, climate modeling, and data governance for sustainable land use. Global databases, remote sensing, spectroscopy, and artificial intelligence were integrated to create scalable monitoring and analysis tools applicable in different contexts. Advances were made in consolidating spectral libraries and data networks, essential for closing information gaps and supporting MRV systems. Automated analysis methods and models integrating edaphoclimatic, socioeconomic, and land use variables enabled climate impact assessments and supported mitigation and adaptation policies. The research also strengthened the connection between science and governance, aligning technical data with green finance, carbon markets, and low-carbon agriculture programs. This integration fostered innovation and the development of sustainable economic models. Highlights: Development of MRV systems based on spectroscopy and orbital data, interoperability between national and international platforms, and the use of cloud-based analysis for fast and low-cost diagnostics. Next period plan: (i) Integrate future climate models and land use scenarios; (ii) Expand MRV systems to include carbon credits; (iii) Promote adoption of tools by public and private institutions; (iv) Develop standardized protocols for governance and environmental traceability.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Nikolaos Tziolas, PA, (University of Florida) Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2022/14935-0 Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17508-9 (CCARBON/USP) Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2022/11034-2 Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/11350-4 Students: Jean de Jesus Macedo Novais, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2022/14935-0; (iii) Não Heidy Soledad Rodríguez Albarracín, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Sim (CCARBON/USP); (ii) FAPESP 2023/17508-9; (iii) Sim Merilyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2022/11034-2; (iii) Não Bruno dos Anjos Bartsch, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/11350-4; (iii) Não

Results:

DEMATTE, J.A.M. et al. Frontiers in earth observation for global soil properties assessment linked to environmental and socio-economic factors. The Innovation, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.xinn.2025.100985

DEMATTE, J.A.M. et al. A global soil spectral grid based on space sensing. *Science of the Total Environment*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.178791

NOVAIS, J.J.M. et al. Online analysis of Amazon's soils through reflectance spectroscopy and cloud computing. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.124155

NOVAIS, J.J.M. et al. Brazilian Soil Spectral Library (VIS-NIR-SWIR-MIR) data opening. *Dokuchaev Soil Bulletin*, 2024. DOI: 10.19047/0136-1694-2024-119-92-116

(D) Associate Research: Catarina Barbosa Careta

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Redesign of Value Chains and Innovation Processes — The Digital Transformation of Small Producers in Brazil

Team members: Catarina Barbosa Careta

Summary of achievements: Highlight: This research line investigates how digital transformation can reconfigure agri-food value chains in Brazil, fostering the productive inclusion of small producers while aligning economic efficiency with decarbonization goals. The focus is on analyzing how digital technologies (such as agricultural platforms, IoT sensors, and traceability systems) reshape innovation processes, promoting collaborative governance, new green economic models, and access to sustainable finance. The research directly contributes to CCARBON/USP's mission by integrating sustainability, innovation, and socio-environmental justice. Workplan: (1) Nationwide mapping of digital platforms aimed at small-scale farming and their potential integration with green finance instruments. (2) Case studies in strategic territories to identify inclusive innovation networks and governance models. (3) Development of indicators to assess the socio-environmental impacts of digital technologies applied to value chains.

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: AgTechs as Drivers of Innovation and Green Finance in Brazilian Agribusiness

Team members: Catarina Barbosa Careta

Summary of achievements: Highlights: This research line examines the strategic role of agribusiness startups (AgTechs) in advancing the transition to a low-carbon and inclusive economy. It explores how these disruptive companies foster new green business models, facilitate access to sustainable finance mechanisms, and strengthen collaborative governance in rural value chains. Workplan: (1) Mapping of Brazilian AgTechs offering solutions for emission mitigation, water efficiency, carbon traceability, and smallholder inclusion. (2) Analysis of business models and the connection of these startups with green finance instruments (e.g., carbon credits, ESG funds). (3) Case studies of selected AgTechs to assess their performance in governance, collaborative innovation, and socio-environmental impact.

(E) Associate Research: Danielle Mendes Thame Denny

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Pasture recovery as a nature-based solution to climate change: legal, political, and governance challenges

Summary of achievements: A comprehensive literature review and legal-document analysis is being conducted, covering international, national, and subnational frameworks related to environmental governance, food security, land-use policies, and the integration of climate, biodiversity, and agricultural production. A preliminary analytical framework was developed to assess regulatory instruments and governance arrangements involved in the implementation of sustainable pasture recovery in Brazil. Special attention was given to the National Program for the Conversion of Degraded Pastures (PNCPD) established by Decree No. 11,815/2023, and its alignment with Brazil's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, and the objectives of the UNCCD and the Sharm El-Sheikh Joint Work. In addition, qualitative fieldwork was initiated, including stakeholder mapping and interviews with key actors from public institutions, the private sector, civil society, and research institutions involved in sustainable livestock initiatives and climate-smart agriculture. These activities helped identify barriers and opportunities for scaling NbS through pasture restoration in Brazil, especially in terms of financing, technical assistance, and legal enforcement. Workplan for the next period Empirical Fieldwork – Finalize and expand stakeholder interviews, particularly with actors involved in carbon markets, traceability systems, and financial institutions supporting sustainable livestock in Brazil. Prepare publications and participation in academic events.

Team members: Danielle Mendes Thame Denny, post-doc, ESALQ, RCGI (i) no (ii)2024/10451-4 - Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Public Policy Research Project: Promoting Geographical Indications for Sustainable Rural Development – Geographical indications, cost-benefit analysis for agri-food products, and dissemination of the practice as a means to add value to Brazilian agricultural systems.

Summary of achievements: Technical visit to Canastra region. A comprehensive mapping of existing Brazilian GIs focusing on agro-food products, and identifying key actors, territorial dynamics, regulatory frameworks, and institutional arrangements. Field data were gathered through semi-structured interviews and document analysis, emphasizing the value chains and governance structures of selected GIs.

Team members: PI: Eduardo Eugênio Spers; PA: Lucilio Rogerio Aparecido Alves ; Maurício Roberto Cherubin ; Odaléia Telles Marcondes Machado Queiroz ; Rosebelly Nunes Marques; PD: Danielle Mendes Thame Denny, Rubmara Ketzer Oliveira, Renata Forato, Marcel D'Alexandria; 23/10119-7 - Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo

(F) Associate Research: Jamil Ramsi Farkat Diogenes

Key questions addressed/Research area: Innovation Management; Green Open Innovation; Green Open Innovation Governance

Team members: Mateus Cecilio Gerolamo (AR CCARBON/USP & LES/ESALQ-USP), Post-doc Jamil Ramsi Farkat Diogenes. The postdoctoral project has received the support letter from CCARBON/USP.

Summary of achievements:

(i) Synthesis of the main activities performed during the period: The main achievement was the formal submission of the postdoctoral research proposal to FAPESP titled “Governance Model for Green Open Innovation in Research, Development and Innovation (RD&I) Centers: Advancing Sustainability through the Quintuple Helix Framework.” All activities were developed in partnership with Professor Mateus Cecilio Gerolamo, supervisor of the project. In addition, two scientific initiation proposals were submitted to FAPESP, aiming to engage undergraduate students through scholarship support and to strengthen the empirical basis of the research. (ii) Highlights: A significant highlight is the strategic collaboration with CCARBON/USP, where I act as a technical advisor in a project conducted with the innovation consultancy Numerik. Funded by a donation from Fundo Vale, this initiative aims to design the first institutional innovation strategy of CCARBON/USP. My contribution involves technical-scientific alignment, methodological planning, and stakeholder engagement design — directly aligned with the objectives of the postdoctoral research and contributing to the positioning of CCARBON/USP as a national reference in climate innovation. (iii) Work plan for the next period: The work plan for the next period strongly depends on the outcome of the FAPESP evaluation process for the postdoctoral fellowship and on the results of the scientific initiation scholarship applications. In parallel, I will continue supporting the strategic development of the CCARBON/USP innovation agenda, ensuring synergy between academic research and institutional transformation.

(G) Associate Research: Jessica Suarez Campoli

Technology: Economic models

Key questions addressed: Can circular economy practices support the achievement of the SDGs?

Team members: Jessica Suarez Campoli

Summary of achievements:

(i) Synthesis of activities: During this period, two main research activities were carried out. The first resulted in the publication of the article: Campoli, J. S., Nagano, M. S., Kodama, T. K., & Burnquist, H. L. (2025). Advancing the 15th SDG: G20 Nations' Progress in Protecting Life on Land Through Circular Economy Strategies. *Business Strategy & Development*, 8(2), e70141. The second activity involves the development of a new article titled “Efficiency and Productivity of G20 Countries in the Context of the Paris Agreement”, which is currently in progress. (ii) Highlights: The published article represents a contribution by evaluating how G20 countries are advancing Sustainable Development Goal 15 (Life on Land) through Circular Economy (CE) strategies. It employed Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) with the Slacks-Based Measure (SBM) and the Malmquist Productivity Index (MPI), complemented by econometric validation through Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS). Results indicated disparities in performance among developed and emerging countries and pointed to a general decline in productivity, emphasizing the need to review environmental policies. The ongoing article expands this methodological framework to analyze the effectiveness of G20 countries in meeting the climate targets set under the Paris Agreement, providing an important link between CE, efficiency analysis, and international environmental

commitments. (iii) Workplan for the next period: The next stage of the project will focus on evaluating Circular Economy practices in sustainable agriculture within G20 nations, and their contribution to the advancement of SDGs 2 (Zero Hunger), 13 (Climate Action), and 15 (Life on Land). This research will involve the development of new efficiency and productivity indicators using DEA-SBM and MPI methodologies, with FGLS validation, aiming to provide macro-level insights that support public policies and promote sustainable development transitions aligned with the global SDG agenda.

Results: Campoli, J. S., Nagano, M. S., Kodama, T. K., & Burnquist, H. L. (2025). Advancing the 15th SDG: G20 Nations' Progress in Protecting Life on Land Through Circular Economy Strategies. *Business Strategy & Development*, 8(2), e70141.

3.9 Co-benefits

The projects developed within the carbon removal line not only contribute to carbon sequestration and climate change mitigation but also generate a range of environmental, social, and economic co-benefits. Among them, the following stand out:

Soil health (7 projects): practices such as crop-livestock-forest integration, regenerative pasture management, and the use of biochar promote greater fertility, increased organic matter, and microbiological balance, ensuring more resilient agricultural systems.

Biodiversity (5 projects): integrated arrangements and agroforestry systems restore degraded areas, increase plant diversity, and support associated fauna, creating more sustainable landscape mosaics.

Human health (3 projects): by promoting more sustainable production systems, reducing dependence on chemical inputs, and adding value to agro-industrial residues, the research generates indirect positive impacts on public health, whether through healthier foods or improved environmental quality.

Thus, the co-benefits reinforce the strategic role of CCARBON/USP in aligning technological innovation, environmental conservation, and social well-being, demonstrating that low-carbon solutions can simultaneously contribute to meeting climate targets and advancing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The following are the projects that generate such co-benefits.

(A) Principal Investigator: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri

Technology: Soil health/Biodiversity

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Assessment of co-benefits for soil health and biodiversity in restored and managed systems

Summary of achievements: During the reporting period, co-benefit research activities emphasized soil health improvement and biodiversity support through restoration and sustainable land management practices. The work by Imbaná et al. (2024) in *Journal of Environmental Management* assessed the quality of constructed technosols in restoration areas, providing a holistic framework for monitoring ecological recovery. By evaluating physical and chemical soil properties, the study demonstrated how restoration interventions not only increase soil carbon retention but also enhance soil structure, nutrient availability, and overall health, fostering conditions favorable to biodiversity. These findings support integrated strategies where soil health management aligns with biodiversity protection, strengthening ecosystem services that go beyond carbon storage. Highlights Demonstrated soil health improvements through ecological restoration and constructed technosols monitoring. Quantified benefits of tree-based agricultural systems for maintaining soil quality and ecological functions. Provided data supporting the integration of soil health indicators into biodiversity and ecosystem service assessments. Workplan for the next period The upcoming period will involve expanding soil health monitoring to restoration projects in other biomes, applying standardized indicator frameworks. Further research will integrate biodiversity metrics into soil surveys, allowing joint reporting of carbon, soil health, and biodiversity outcomes in MRV-compatible formats.

Team members: Equipe: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI, (ESALQ/USP) José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Cássio Marques Moquedace dos Santos, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2025/00139-6 Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2024/11100-0 Students: Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/17876-8; (iii) Não Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Não Cássio Marques Moquedace dos Santos, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Sim

Results:

Imbaná, R., Valente, F. D. A., Siqueira, R. G., Moquedace, C. M., Assis, I. R. (2024). Assessing the quality of constructed technosols enabled holistic monitoring of ecological restoration. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 353, 120237. doi:10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.120237

Technology: Soil health

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Soil health

Summary of achievements: During the period, research focused on understanding the individual and combined effects of soybean inoculation and co-inoculation in summer crops, as well as corn–*Urochloa ruziziensis* intercropping in succession. Additional studies examined the inoculation of intercropped corn and brachiaria with growth-promoting microorganisms and their influence on soil quality, with particular attention to carbon-related parameters. Results consistently showed that inoculation enhances the benefits of cover crops in stimulating soil enzymatic activity, while balanced input management in successive cropping systems further supports this process. Nitrogen inputs were found to influence enzymatic activity under inoculation with nitrogen-fixing microorganisms, and both inoculation and cover crops affected soil compaction and porosity. Notably, improvements in soil carbon accumulation occurred more slowly than changes in enzymatic and physical attributes. In the next period, research will focus on synthesizing results linking biological and physical soil attributes to overall soil quality.

Team members: Carlos E. P. Cerri, PI, (ESALQ/USP), Arnold Barbosa de Oliveira, MSc, (ESALQ/USP, Embrapa).

Research Sector Chain: Annual Crops

Technology: Crop management

Key questions addressed/Research area 3: Quantification of organic carbon input from the total biomass of cover crops and evaluation of the decomposition rate in production systems in clay soils of tropical climates.

Summary of achievements: In recent decades, the concentration of greenhouse gases (GHG), particularly CO₂, has increased significantly, largely due to agricultural activities and changes in land use. Conventional agricultural operations, which involve intensive soil tillage, cause carbon loss through the release of CO₂ into the atmosphere, worsening the problem. However, sustainable agricultural practices, such as the use of cover crops and no-till farming, can mitigate this impact by reducing emissions and increasing carbon storage in the soil. The overall goal of this project is to quantify carbon storage in the aboveground biomass and root system of cover crops up to a depth of 50 cm (0-10, 10-20, 20-30, 30-40, and 40-50 cm), as well as to evaluate the decomposition rate (0 and 90 days) of these plants in clay soils in the tropical region of Brazil. The study will be conducted in Sorriso, MT. Field samples will be collected to analyze the carbon content in the aboveground and root parts of the plants using an elemental analyzer. Additionally, the decomposition rate of the biomass will be determined, evaluating carbon and nitrogen content. The data will be analyzed using ANOVA, and Tukey's test will be applied with a significance level of 5%. It is expected that the results obtained will guide national public policies aimed at reducing GHGs in agriculture, as well as serve as a valuable tool for producers and technicians in improving the management of production systems. Thus, the project will contribute to promoting more sustainable and environmentally responsible agriculture.

Team members: María Celina Villagra Luraschi/Master's degree student/CCARBON/USP Carlos Eduard Pellegrino Cerri/Advisor, Prof. Dr./CCARBON/USP

Research Sector Chain: Integrated Systems

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 4: Spectroscopic Techniques and Modeling Applied to Soil Organic Matter Dynamics in Pasture Systems under Different Brazilian Biomes

Summary of achievements: Soil organic matter (SOM) is a key indicator of soil quality, influencing edaphic properties and playing a crucial role in climate change mitigation. Quantifying and understanding the stabilization mechanisms of SOM is essential for the development of sustainable agricultural systems. Pasture management, combined with soil characteristics and edaphoclimatic conditions of different Brazilian biomes, directly affects SOM dynamics, though these effects remain underexplored. In addition to quantification, assessing the chemical quality of SOM—focusing on functional groups and carbon protection within aggregates—is necessary. Non-destructive techniques, such as laser-induced fluorescence spectroscopy, have proven effective in this context. Integrating these data with existing surveys through modeling allows the simulation of management scenarios in terms of carbon stocks, SOM quality, and soil health. This project aims to understand how different pasture conditions (native, managed, degraded, and integrated) affect SOM and its chemical properties. The association of modeling with functional SOM characterization is strategic to advance the understanding of SOM dynamics in pasture systems and to support Brazil in achieving its Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) goals.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri/Advisor/ESALQ/USP and CCARBON/USP / Kelly Tamires Urbano Daboit/PhD Student/ ESALQ/USP. and CCARBON (i) Is the scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP? Yes (ii) Funding agency and process number : 2025/11644-3 (iii) Did the scholarship receive a support letter from CCARBON/USP? Yes

Technology: Soil health

Key questions addressed/Research area 5: Evaluation of Soil Health due to the adoption of cover crops in a soybean production system in the state of Mato Grosso.

Summary of achievements: The evaluation and monitoring of the impacts of agricultural systems on soil quality are essential to establish best management practices and promote the sustainable use of land, in order to mitigate climate change, conserve biodiversity, and achieve food and energy security. The Soil Management Assessment Framework (SMAF) has been successfully tested as an objective tool to quantify the effects of land use and management on soil health, even under Brazilian edaphic conditions. Therefore, the aim of this study is to evaluate soil health due to the adoption of cover crops in a soybean production system in Mato Grosso. Five treatments with three replications in a randomized complete block design, combining cover crops in the soybean off-season, will be evaluated in a four-year experiment at the Learning and Dissemination Center (CAD-Norte), Sorriso – MT. The treatments are: (1) corn; (2) corn + brachiaria; and (3) corn + brachiaria + crotalaria. Disturbed and undisturbed soil samples will be collected at depths of 0–10, 10–20, and 20–30 cm from one point per experimental unit for the evaluation of chemical (pH, P, K), physical (porosity, bulk density, and penetration

resistance), and biological (organic carbon and enzymatic activity) indicators. The SMAF scoring curves will be applied, the measured values will be transformed (scale from 0 to 1), and an overall Soil Health Index (SHI) will be calculated. Data will be subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA), and if significant differences are found ($p < 0.05$), means will be compared using Tukey's test ($p < 0.05$).

Team members: Caroline Andreatto Zanoli/Graduation's degree student, IC/CCARBON/USP Carlos Eduard Pellegrino Cerri/Advisor, Prof. Dr./CCARBON/USP

Results: Tese de Doutorado defendida em Maio de 2025: Sistemas Integrados de Produção Agropecuária: Estoque e estabilização do carbono e sua relação com os microrganismos. Somente a versão simplificada foi disponibilizada no repositório da ESALQ/USP. Versão final será disponibilizada após dois anos. <https://www.teses.usp.br/teses/disponiveis/11/11140/tde-04082025-145555/pt-br.php>

Research Sector Chain: Integrated Systems/ Sustainable Livestock

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area 6: SOIL HEALTH ASSESSMENT IN MANAGED PASTURES

Summary of achievements: i) We conducted a systematic review of 64 studies published between 2014 and 2024 to map the intellectual structure of soil health assessment in managed Brazilian pastures, identifying research trends, methodological approaches, and knowledge gaps.

ii) Our analysis reveals a geographical concentration of research in the Cerrado and Atlantic Forest biomes. Methodologically, soil health assessments have matured from qualitative towards quantitative integration frameworks and are constantly built upon a foundational triad of indicators: soil organic carbon, pH, and bulk density. Network analysis showed these indicators act as hubs connecting distinct research themes focused on soil structure, chemical fertility, and microbial activity. This review provides evidence for sustainable intensification while also revealing critical gaps in underrepresented regions and topics.

iii) To develop a practical roadmap for future research aimed at enhancing the productivity and environmental resilience of Brazil's pasturelands.

To synthesize qualitatively and quantitatively the outcomes of the included studies in the systematic review and assess how the reported "good management" practices affected soil health.

Team members: Team members: Carlos E. P. Cerri, PI, (CCARBON/ USP); Maurício R. Cherubin, PI, (CCARBON/ USP); Wanderlei Bieluczyk, Post-doc, (CENA/USP) Students: José I. A. Castro, PhD, (ESALQ/USP), Victória S. Souza, PhD, (ESALQ/USP), Lucas T. Greschuk, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) i) No ii) No iii) No

Results: Submitted Doctoral Thesis - Sustainable intensification of Brazilian pastures: soil health assessment and carbon sequestration / Jose Igor Almeida Castro.

Submitted Article - Soil health assessments across pasture management systems in Brazil: a comprehensive review - Soil Security Journal - Manuscript Number: SOISEC-D-25-00073.

Research Sector Chain: Annual Crops

Technology: Soil carbon/ Biodiversity

Key questions addressed/Research area 7: Impacts on integrated organic matter, glomalina, and soil health in diversified agricultural systems

Summary of achievements: During the period, field samples were collected in an experiment in Lucas do Rio Verde, Mato Grosso. The samples were prepared and analyzed for physical, chemical, and biological indicators. Wet sieving of the samples was performed to obtain three aggregate size classes (large macroaggregates, small macroaggregates, and microaggregates). Physical fractionation of soil organic matter was performed to obtain particulate organic matter (POM) and mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM) in bulk soil samples for each aggregate class. Additionally, glomalin-related soil protein (GRSP) was extracted, purified, and prepared for future analysis. In the next period, an audit of the data in preparation for the BEPE will be conducted at Indiana University (starting November 1st), where the student will work on structural equation modeling and writing scientific papers. In Brazil, interns will be conducting additional evaluations with glomalin, mycorrhizal fungal spores, and carbon.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI (ESALQ/USP); Marcelo Trybek, MSs (ESALQ/USP); Vanessa Mandro Baesteiro, IC (ESALQ/USP).

Results: Article called "Use the slakes application to assess the stability of soil aggregates in tropical conservation agriculture" was submitted to Soil & Tillage Research. But still not accepted to publication. (Submitted)

Technology: Soil carbon/ Biodiversity

Key questions addressed/Research area 8: Intensified management in regenerative agriculture: impacts on integrated organic matter

Summary of achievements: During this period, samples were prepared and analyzed for physical, chemical, and biological indicators. Wet sieving of the samples was performed to obtain three aggregate size classes (large macroaggregates, small macroaggregates, and microaggregates). In the soil macroaggregates, physical fractionation of soil organic matter was performed to obtain particulate organic matter (POM) and mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM). In addition, glomalin-related soil protein (GRSP) was extracted from bulk soil samples. In the next period, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) will be performed on POM and MAOM samples in soil aggregates. In addition, mycorrhizal fungal spores will be counted. Furthermore, the data will be processed and used to produce a scientific report for FAPESP.

Team members: Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI (ESALQ/USP); Marcelo Trybek, MSs (ESALQ/USP); Vanessa Mandro Baesteiro, IC (ESALQ/USP).

(B) Principal Investigator: Fernando Dini Andreote**Research Sector Chain: Integrated Systems****Technology:** Biodiversity**Key questions addressed/Research area:** Soil Biology

Summary of achievements: Activities performed during the period: Research internship abroad (Process: 24/07113-0) – Soil Ecology Laboratory, Indiana University: 1. Field visits to establish and maintain experiments involving the introduction of nematodes into forest systems. 2. Implementation of an experiment to manipulate soil fauna, aiming to eliminate nematodes from soil samples while preserving their physical structure. Work plan for the next period: Resumption of activities related to the project in Brazil (Process: 23/04352-0), including the writing of the first articles. The results of the evaluation of nematode, bacterial, and fungal communities in integrated agricultural production systems are now ready.

Team members: Felipe Martins do Rêgo Barros, Post-doc, (ESLAQ/USP). Fernando Dini Andreote, PI, Brazilian Supervisor, (ESALQ/USP). Andre Luiz Custodio Franco, Supervisor abroad, (Indiana University).

Research Sector Chain: Integrated Systems**Technology:** Biodiversity**Key questions addressed/Research area:** Soil Biology

Summary of achievements: Activities performed during the period: Research internship abroad (Process: 2024/01300-2) - Molecular Microbial Ecology Group, Rothamsted Research, Harpenden, UK: 1. Soil sampling in long-term experiments and in agroforestry systems. 2. Determination of the functional potential of microorganisms for the construction of synthetic bacterial communities (SynCom). 3. Implementation of a greenhouse experiment to evaluate the introduction and persistence of SynCom in soils from different uses. 4. Training in bioinformatics for sequencing data analysis. Work plan for the next period: Resumption of project-related activities in Brazil (Process: 2022/09977-6), data analysis, and writing of articles related to the project (the first was submitted during the BEPE period and is still under review).

Team members: Nariane de Andrade, PhD candidate, FAPESP, (ESALQ/USP) (The scholarship is not directly funded by CCARBON/USP and has not received a letter of support from CCARBON/USP.) Fernando Dini Andreote, PI, Brazilian Supervisor, (ESALQ/USP). Tim Mauchline, PI, Supervisor abroad, (Rothamsted Research) Rodrigo Gouvêa Taketani, Post doc, (Rothamsted Research)

Research Sector Chain: Annual Crops**Technology 1:** Soil carbon**Key questions addressed/Research area:** Cover cropping under no-tillage (NT)

Summary of achievements: In the pursuit of reconciling high-yield agriculture with reduced environmental impact, advancing research on management systems that improve

the soil microbiome and its interactions with crops is essential. In this context, we are conducting studies aimed at evaluating the structure, diversity, composition, and complexity of bacterial and fungal communities in the soil, as well as the metabolic versatility in the soybean rhizosphere under the influence of a grass species, a legume species, their combination, and a fallow condition without plants as off-season cover in a no-tillage (NT) system. To this end, our study was conducted in a long-term experimental area (over 20 years) cultivated under no-tillage with cover crops during the off-season and soybean during the growing season. From this site, we collected soil and soybean rhizosphere samples, along with soil for greenhouse experiments. As main findings, we observed that the structure, composition, and connectivity of the soil microbial community are shaped and enhanced by the use of cover crops during the off-season, with direct effects evident in the subsequent soybean season. Additionally, we found that structuring the soil microbiome through off-season cover crops under no-tillage played an important role in modulating the metabolic compounds in the soybean rhizosphere, which resulted in increased carbon stocks in the treatments with off-season cover crops. Overall, our results emphasize that the soil microbial community structured under conservation practices, such as no-tillage with cover cropping during the off-season, can promote unique ecological interactions among soil-microorganisms-rhizosphere-plant in soybean cultivation. For the upcoming period, our plans include publishing the articles derived from this research, which will be presented in the Doctoral Thesis to be defended on August 15, 2025.

Team members: Fernando D. Andreote, PI, (ESALQ/USP). Caio C. G. Freitas, PhD, (ESALQ/USP). Caio César Gomes Freitas/PhD/(ESALQ/USP) (i): No (ii): CAPES (88887.612699/2021-00) (iii): No

Results: Thesis to be defended on August 15, 2025, and manuscripts to be submitted in the upcoming semester.

Research Sector Chain: Ecosystem Restoration and Conservation, Integrated systems, Annual crops, MRV technologies, Modeling impact assessment due climate change

Technology: Biodiversity

Key questions addressed/Research area: The research line is focused on enhancing the value of microbial biodiversity from semiarid soils, particularly from the Caatinga biome, and its application in agricultural resilience strategies. The project investigates how microbiomes adapted to extreme conditions (such as drought and desertification) can modulate gene expression and metabolite production in soybean, promoting greater tolerance to water deficit. By comparing microbiomes from conserved, degrading, and recovering soils, the research explores the effects of soil functional biodiversity on plant health and the sustainability of agroecosystems. In addition, it conducts the bioprospecting of promising microorganisms aimed at forming synthetic communities capable of restoring ecological processes and promoting plant growth under adverse conditions, thereby reinforcing the importance of conserving and strategically using microbial diversity.

Summary of achievements: Between 2024 and 2025, fundamental activities for the development of the project were carried out, including a literature review and the selection of target genes related to water stress in *Glycine max.* Specific primers were designed, and standard curves were constructed for quantification by RT-qPCR. Soil samples were collected from two contrasting biomes, Caatinga (semiarid) and Atlantic Forest (humid tropical), and chemically characterized. Two experiments were conducted: the first with 13 distinct microbiomes (13 treatments) and the second with a factorial design involving 4 microbiomes, 2 soybean genotypes (susceptible and tolerant to water stress), and 3 levels of water availability, totaling 24 treatments. Agronomic and physiological measurements were performed (plant height, fresh and dry biomass, number of trifoliolate leaves, stem diameter, and chlorophyll index), as well as RNA extraction from leaves and roots, cDNA synthesis, and storage of samples for later extractions. The activities of the enzymes β -glucosidase and phosphatase in the soils were also quantified, and DNA was extracted from all soil samples for microbial community taxonomy analyses.

The project remains on schedule and is currently in its intermediate phase. The next steps include quantifying metabolites in leaves stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (ABA, proline, trehalose) and continuing gene expression analyses by RT-qPCR, with the completion of standard curves in progress. DNA samples are expected to be sent for sequencing (Illumina platform) of bacterial, fungal, and mycorrhizal communities by the company Novogene. After receiving the data, taxonomic and multivariate analyses will be conducted to integrate the agronomic, physiological, and microbiological data, aiming to understand plant–microbiome interactions under water stress.

Team members: Research line 1 – Team members: • Fernando Dini Andreote, PI, (ESALQ/USP) • Antonio Marcos Miranda Silva, PhD, (SDU/Denmark) • Arthur Prudencio de Araujo Pereira, PhD, (UFC) • Danilo Ferreira da Silva, MsC, (ESALQ/USP) Students: Danilo Ferreira da Silva / PhD Student / ESALQ-USP (i) Is the scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP? → No (ii) Funding agency and process number → FAPESP, 2023/16775-3 (iii) Did the scholarship receive a support letter from CCARBON/USP? → No Gabriel Moreno Castilho / IC / ESALQ-USP (i) Is the scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP? → No (ii) Funding agency and process number → FAPESP, 2024/05748-8 (iii) Did the scholarship receive a support letter from CCARBON/USP? → No

(C) Principal Investigator: José Alexandre Melo Demattê

Technology: Soil health, Biodiversity

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil health and biodiversity assessed through geotechnologies and modeling for sustainable management

Summary of achievements: During 2024–2025, the co-benefits research line focused on the integrated assessment of soil health, functional biodiversity, and their connections with agricultural productivity and ecosystem resilience. Geotechnologies, spectroscopy, and modeling were applied to quantify soil attributes, understand ecosystem functions, and support management practices that combine environmental conservation and climate

mitigation. Actions included high-resolution characterization of physical and chemical soil properties, modeling of soil thickness and profiles, and the use of sensors to monitor plant physiological parameters. This approach enabled linking edaphic attributes to microbial biodiversity and agronomic performance, strengthening sustainable management strategies. Methods were also improved to assess soil health using spectral and geophysical indicators, enabling rapid diagnostics and supporting regenerative practices. Studies integrating edaphoclimatic data and plant responses reinforced the importance of maintaining healthy soils as a foundation for productivity and ecosystem services. Highlights: Consolidation of protocols to measure soil health attributes and ecosystem services, with emphasis on scalable and non-destructive spectral and sensing tools. Next period plan: (i) Integrate soil health indicators with biodiversity data; (ii) Expand in-field spectral diagnostics; (iii) Assess the effects of regenerative practices on ecosystem functions; (iv) Translate results into recommendations for conservation and sustainable intensification policies.

Team members: José Alexandre Melo Demattê, PI, (ESALQ/USP) Kabindra Adhikari, PA, (Texas Tech University) Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2023/17876-8 Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2024/11100-0 Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES Merylyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim, PhD, (ESALQ/USP) – FAPESP 2022/11034-2 Marcos Guedes de Lana, MSc, (ESALQ/USP) – CAPES Students: Jorge Tadeu Fim Rosas, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2023/17876-8; (iii) Não Marcelo Henrique Procópio Pelegrino, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2024/11100-0; (iii) Não Isadora Ribeiro Uruga, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES; (iii) Não Merylyn Taynara Accorsi Amorim, PhD, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) FAPESP 2022/11034-2; (iii) Não Marcos Guedes de Lana, MSc, (ESALQ/USP): (i) Não; (ii) CAPES; (iii) Não

Results:

ROSAS, J.T.F. et al. Geotechnologies on the phosphorus stocks determination in tropical soils: General impacts on society. *Science of the Total Environment*, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.173537

MELLO, D.C. et al. Integrating proximal geophysical sensing and machine learning for digital soil mapping. *Soil Advances*, 2025. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.soilad.2024.100024>

GOZUKARA, G. et al. Prediction accuracy of pXRF, MIR, and Vis-NIR spectra for soil properties – A review. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 2025. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/saj2.70028>

ROSIN, N.A. et al. Mapping soil thickness using a mechanistic model and machine learning approaches. *Catena*, 2025. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2024.108621>

FALCIONI, R. et al. Decreased Photosynthetic Efficiency in *Nicotiana tabacum* under Transient Heat Stress. *Plants*, 2024. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/plants13030395>

FIORIO, P.R. et al. Prediction of leaf nitrogen in sugarcane by Vis-NIR-SWIR spectroradiometry. *Heliyon*, 2024. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e26819>

(D) Principal Investigator: Leidivan Almeida Frazão**Research Sector Chain: Annual crops**

Technology: Soil health

Key questions addressed/Research area: Adaptation of cover crops for the semi-arid region: potential for increased biomass production in autumn/winter and improvement of soil quality

Summary of achievements: The state of Minas Gerais exhibits great climatic diversity across its regions during the autumn and winter periods, which are invariably dry and associated with low relative humidity. These climatic factors are critical and limiting for the reduction of native vegetation growth, the absence of annual crop cultivation without irrigation, and the degradation of pastures throughout all regions of the state. This project aims to evaluate and validate the adaptation of cover crops with the potential to increase biomass production during autumn/winter in the semi-arid region of Minas Gerais. This project is funded by FAPEMIG (APQ-05959-24) and is currently in its initial development phase. During the first three months, cover crops were cultivated (both monocultures and various mixes), and the next steps will be: i) to evaluate the soil quality indicators (physical, chemical, and biological); ii) to assess the productivity increase of the subsequent crop (corn); iii) to determine the soil carbon sequestration potential following the adoption of no-tillage practices.

Team members: Leidivan Almeida Frazão, PI, (UFMG); Maria Nilfa Almeida Neta (Post-doc; FAPEMIG)

(E) Principal Investigator: Maurício Roberto Cherubin**Research Sector Chain: Blue Carbon**

Key questions addressed/Research area: Assessment and quantification of the ecosystem services provided by mangrove forests

Technology: Soil health

Summary of achievements: In this research line, we started the research on soil health for mangrove forests analyzing the scientific production about soil health in mangroves through a bibliometric review. The data showed many scientific articles exploring mangroves and soil (8289), while only 321 articles included the soil health concept, and 39 analyzed soil health with ecosystem services. The data included articles from 1958 to 2024 and showed that most research is concentrated in China, India, USA, Brazil and Australia. The conclusion pointed to a great research gap and opportunity to apply the soil health concept to evaluate mangroves, considering its potential to characterize these environments and the low number of scientific research considering the two topics. The review article was published in the Water Journal (Mello et al. 2024 - <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/16/24/3626>)

Afterwards, we adapted soil health index methods and applied them to evaluate mangroves under land use change in the Amazon coast. The soil health index worked as a proxy to evaluate the delivery of ecosystem services in mangrove forests. The manuscript is expected to be submitted to an international journal in August 2024. The next step is to test other soil health index methods in mangroves under different

conservation scenarios and at different positions in the Brazilian coast. We will evaluate the following scenarios: i) reforestation in mangroves in the states of Ceará and Rio de Janeiro; ii) soil organic carbon patterns in multiple mangroves across the Brazilian coast; iii) soil health evaluation in mangroves dead over natural events; iv) Soil health modeling in Brazilian mangroves. Our activities are basically associated with the BLUSHORE project, adding new students with scholarships from PUB/USP and FAPESP.

Team members: Maurício Roberto Cherubin, PI, (ESALQ/USP), Fellipe Alcantara de Oliveira Mello, Post-doc, (ESALQ/USP) - Projeto BLUSHORE, Lorena Manoel Barbosa, IC, (ESALQ/USP) – PUB, Livia Odorisi Pavan, IC, (ESALQ/USP) - Graduação FAPESP 2025/08259-0 (Carta CCARBON/USP), Isabella Simão de Carvalho, IC (ESALQ/USP)- Graduação FAPESP (em submissão) (Carta CCARBON/USP)

Results: Mello, F. A., Ferreira, T. O., Bernardino, A. F., Queiroz, H. M., Mello, D. C., Menillo, R. B., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Soil Health and Ecosystem Services in Mangrove Forests: A Global Overview. *Water*, 16(24), 3626. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16243626>

Research Sector Chain: Ecosystem Restoration and Conservation

Technology: Soil health, Biodiversity

Key questions addressed/Research area: How does desertification and ecological restoration affect soil health and the taxonomic composition and functional potential of soil microbial communities in the Brazilian drylands (Caatinga biome)?

Summary of achievements: In this research line we presented scientific contributions published in a paper and national and international conferences, highlighting preliminary findings on the impacts of desertification and restoration on soil health in Brazilian drylands. These presentations addressed key themes such as the effects of grazing exclusion on carbon stocks and microbial activity, the influence of soil density and salinity on degradation, and the role of biological indicators and nature-based solutions in ecosystem recovery. Together, these studies emphasize the relevance of soil microbiology and carbon dynamics in understanding and reversing dryland degradation. As part of the thesis entitled “Soil health assessment in desertified drylands in Brazil” (FAPESP # 2024/03722-1), we conducted fieldwork in four Desertification Nuclei of the Brazilian Semiarid (Irauçuba-CE, Cabrobó-PE, Gilbués-PI, and Cariris Velhos-PB), collecting 108 soil samples (0–10 cm depth) across native vegetation, degraded, and restored areas. Laboratory analyses of biological indicators were completed, including microbial biomass, enzymatic activities, and total organic carbon. For the next period, activities will focus on the advanced integration of microbial and environmental datasets during a BEPE research internship at the University of Colorado Boulder (FAPESP #2025/04487-9), under the supervision of Dr. Noah Fierer. Metagenomic sequencing will be used to assess microbial taxonomic and functional diversity across different land-use scenarios. The bioinformatics pipeline (FastQC, Trimmomatic, MEGAHIT, Kraken2, MetaPhlan, KEGG, EggNOG, Pfam) will be applied, followed by multivariate statistical analyses, network analysis, and machine learning approaches. Analyses will include co-occurrence network construction (CoNet/Cytoscape), redundancy analysis, and predictive modeling (e.g., Random Forest) to identify key microbial traits and metabolic

pathways associated with restoration success. Expected outcomes will include a deeper understanding of how microbial communities respond to land degradation and restoration, providing scientific support for evidence-based strategies to combat desertification and promote sustainable land management in the Brazilian Semiarid.

Team members: Mauricio Roberto Cherubin - PI PhD Antonio Yan Viana Lima (FAPESP # 2024/03722-1 2025/04487-9) 1- Avaliação da saúde do solo em drylands desertificadas no Brasil 2- Da degradação à restauração: mudanças microbianas e ciclagem de carbono em terras secas brasileiras | YES - We received CCARBON/USP supporting letter.

Results:

Lima, A. Y. V., Cherubin, M. R., Greschuk, L. T., Muniz, G. de A. M., Cavalcante, D. M., & Pereira, A. P. de A. (2024). Mapping soil health research in the Brazilian Semiarid region: a bibliometric approach. *Experimental Agriculture*, 60, e29. doi:10.1017/S0014479724000243

Lima, A. Y. V., Cherubin, M. R., & Pereira, A. P. A. (2024). Grazing exclusion effects on carbon stocks in Brazilian drylands. In *Anais do I Carbon Soil Health Symposium. Carbon Soil Health Symposium: From the Field to the Socioeconomic & Political Perspectives*, Piracicaba.

Lima, A. Y. V., Pereira, A. P. A., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Effects of soil density and salinity on soil degradation in desertified areas in Brazil. In *Anais do XXI Congresso Colombiano de la Ciencia del Suelo. XXI Congresso Colombiano de la Ciencia del Suelo*, Medellín.

Lima, A. Y. V., Pereira, A. P. A., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). "Chemical and physical effects of grazing exclusion on the recovery of degraded soils in Semiarid areas. In *Anais da Energy Transition Research & Innovation Conference (ETRI 2024). Energy Transition Research & Innovation Conference*, São Paulo.

Lima, A. Y. V., Greschuk, L. T., Pereira, A. P. A., & Cherubin, M. R. (2023). Grazing exclusion: A nature-based solution to increase soil organic carbon in Brazilian desertified drylands. In *I Seminar on Nature-Based Solutions in Agriculture and Forestry. I Seminar on Nature-Based Solutions in Agriculture and Forestry*, Piracicaba.

Lima, A. Y. V., Greschuk, L. T., Pereira, A. P. A., Vanolli, B. S., Carvalho, M. L., Rodrigues, A. M. S., & Cherubin, M. R. (2023). Biological indicators of soil health in desertified drylands in Brazil. In *Anais do XXIII Congresso Latino-Americano de Ciência do Solo e XXXVIII Congresso Brasileiro de Ciência do Solo. XXIII Congresso Latino-Americano de Ciência do Solo e XXXVIII Congresso Brasileiro de Ciência do Solo*, Florianópolis.

Lima, A. Y. V., Pereira, A. P. A., & Cherubin, M. R. (2023). Grazing exclusion: A nature-based solution to increase microbial activity in Brazilian desertified drylands. In *Anais da Energy Transition Research & Innovation Conference (ETRI 2023). Energy Transition Research & Innovation Conference*, São Paulo.

Lima, A. Y. V., Pereira, A. P. A., Vanolli, B. S., Rodrigues, N. F., Rodrigues, A. M. S., Carvalho, M. L., & Cherubin, M. R. (2023). The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index in the evaluation of desertified areas in the Brazilian drylands. In *Anais do XXIII Congresso Latino-Americano de Ciência do Solo e XXXVIII Congresso Brasileiro de Ciência do Solo*. XXIII Congresso Latino-Americano de Ciência do Solo e XXXVIII Congresso Brasileiro de Ciência do Solo, Florianópolis.

Research Sector Chain: Integrated Systems

Technology: Soil health

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil health in integrated systems

Summary of achievements: In this research line, we addressed soil health using literature review and also field experimentation approaches. Globally, IAS is considered a key 21st-century nature-based solution for addressing food, energy, and environmental challenges (<https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.agron.2024.02.003>). In Brazil, our studies are distributed in different regions, SP, MS, GO, PE, PI e CE. Activities focused on the co-benefits of IAS, particularly regarding soil health and biodiversity. For example, one study evaluated pasture restoration through crop-livestock integration (CLI) in sandy soils, finding it improved subsurface indicators but had limited surface impact. A critical analysis of soil health research in Brazil further identified national challenges and priorities, revealing that research is concentrated in specific biomes, leaving large, vulnerable areas understudied. These findings show that CLI systems can partially restore soil health in degraded sandy pastures. Future activities will include a multifunctional soil assessment across four integrated systems in contrasting Brazilian regions, as well, its role in the circular economy. Building on the recent national-level analysis, a key future goal is to conduct a similar critical analysis on a global scale to identify worldwide challenges and opportunities in soil health research.

Team members: Mauricio Roberto Cherubin, PI, ESALQ/USP Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PI, ESALQ/USP Stoécio M. F. Maia, PA, Instituto Federal de Alagoas/IFAL Arthur Prudêncio de Araujo Pereira, PA, Universidade Federal do Ceará/UFC Chukwudi Nwaogu, Post-doc, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FAPESP – 2021/11757-1; (iii) No. Lucas Freitas Nogueira Souza, Post-doc, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No. Beatriz da Silva Vanolli, PhD, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FAPESP – 2022/14212-9; (iii) No. Lucas Tadeu Greschuk, PhD, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FAPESP 2023/00438-8; (iii) Yes. Luan Aparecido Ferreira de Campos, IC, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No.

Results:

Publications:

Cherubin, M. R., Pinheiro Junior, C. R., Souza, L. N., Canisares, L. P., & Cerri, C. E. P. (2025). Exploring soil health research in Brazil: A critical analysis of national challenges, opportunities, and priorities. *Land Use Policy*, 157, 107677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2025.107677>

Nwaogu, C., Minasny, B., Field, D. J., & Cherubin, M. R. (2025). Conceptualizing core aspects of circular economy in soil: A critical review and analysis. *Critical Reviews in*

Environmental Science and Technology, 55(11), 805–835.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10643389.2025.2454689>

Vanolli, B. S., Dias, H. B., Da Luz, F. B., Lamparelli, R. A. C., Magalhães, P. S. G., & Cherubin, M. R. (2025). Crop–livestock integrated systems improve soil health in tropical sandy soils. *Agronomy-Basel*, 15, 378. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy15020378>

Book

Cherubin, M. R.; Vanolli, B. S. ; Souza, L. F. N. ; Canisares, L. P. ; Pinheiro Junior, C. R. ; Schiebelbein, B. E. ; Cardoso, G. M. ; Lima, A. Y. V. ; Luz, F. B. ; Souza, V. S. ; Bortolo, L. S. ; Menillo, R. B. ; Meneghini, V. ; Greschuk, L. T. ; Carvalho, M. L. ; Borba, D. A. ; Rodrigues, A. M. S. ; Marostica, M. E. M. . Guia prático de plantas de cobertura: espécies, manejo e impacto na saúde do solo. 2. ed. Piracicaba-SP: SOHMA-ESALQ, 2024. v. 1. 175p. <https://doi.org/10.11606/9786587391618>

Book Chapters

Canisares, L. P., Pinheiro Júnior, C. R., Vanolli, B. S., Carvalho, M. L., Nwaogu, C., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Enhancing Soil Health in Brazilian Agroecosystems: Indicators and Management Practices. In *Sustainable Soil Systems in Global South*. Springer Nature Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-5276-8_23 (Book chapter).

Nwaogu, C., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Integrated agricultural systems: the 21st century nature-based solution for resolving the global FEEES challenges. *Advances in Agronomy*, 185, 1-73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.agron.2024.02.003> (Book chapter).

Vanolli, B. S., Souza, L. F. N., Canisares, L. P., Pinheiro Junior, C. R., Schiebelbein, B. E., Cardoso, G. M., Lima, A. Y. V., Luz, F. B., Souza, V. S., Bortolo, L. S., Menillo, R. B., Meneghini, V., Greschuk, L. T., Carvalho, M. L., Borba, D. A., Rodrigues, A. M. S., & Marostica, M. E. M. (2024). Guia prático de plantas de cobertura: espécies, manejo e impacto na saúde do solo. 2. ed. Piracicaba: ESALQ/SOHMA. <https://doi.org/10.11606/9786587391618> (Book chapter).

Conference Papers

Greschuk, L. T.; Souza, V. S.; Ferreira, J. B. G.; Santos, D. C.; Schiebelbein, B. E.; Santos, A. M.; Cherubin, M. R. Grasses intercropping in succession agricultural system in the Brazilian savanna. In: CCARBON/USP SOIL HEALTH SYMPOSIUM: FROM THE FIELD TO THE SOCIOECONOMICAL AND POLITICAL PERSPECTIVES, 2024, Piracicaba. CCARBON/USP soil health symposium, 2024.

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Agri-PV system: combining solar energy production with food production and climate change adaptation (“AgriPV_Brazil”)

Summary of achievements: This research line investigates the co-benefits of agrivoltaic (Agri-PV) systems on soil health by assessing short-term impacts on physical, chemical, and biological indicators. A pilot experiment was implemented on a Nitisol in Piracicaba (SP), with four land-use treatments: (i) Conventional Photovoltaic System without crops; (ii) Cropping under Pre-existing PV Panels; (iii) Conventional Cropping under full sun; and (iv) Agrivoltaic System implemented from the beginning. Physical assessments (0–10 cm) included bulk density, macroporosity, water aggregate stability, and penetration

resistance. The conventional cropping treatment showed better structural indicators, while all treatments involving PV installation exhibited signs of compaction and reduced aggregation—likely caused by machinery traffic. Microbial biomass carbon (SMB-C) was used as a biological indicator, revealing lower values under PV (259 mg kg⁻¹) and Agri-PV (312 mg kg⁻¹) compared to the control with undisturbed ruzigrass cover (539 mg kg⁻¹). In addition, soil enzyme activities (arilsulfatase, β-glucosidase, and acid phosphatase) and complete chemical analyses (pH, CEC, nutrients) have already been performed and are currently under processing. These data will be integrated into a comprehensive soil health evaluation using the Soil Management Assessment Framework (SMAF), allowing a multi-indicator diagnosis of the effects of Agri-PV on soil functioning. Future work includes seasonal monitoring under soybean–maize rotation and the development of a tailored soil health index for agrivoltaic systems. This effort will contribute to sustainable land-use recommendations that balance renewable energy production with the preservation and enhancement of soil ecosystem services.

Team members: Maurício Roberto Cherubin, PI, ESALQ/USP Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, PA, ESALQ/USP Moacir Tuzzin De Moraes, PA, ESALQ/USP Angelo Tiago Azevedo, Post-doc, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No. George Rodrigues Lambais; Post-doc, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No. Rafael Braghieri Menillo, PhD, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No. Anaila Amaral de Alencar, MSc, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No. João Victor Muller Antigo, IC, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No. Matheus Viana Lopes, IC, ESALQ/USP: (i) No; (ii) FUSP; (iii) No.

Technology: Soil health

Key questions addressed/Research area: How is the impact of sugarcane management (including straw removal) on soil carbon and soil-related ecosystem services?

Summary of achievements: Sugarcane straw removal for bioenergy production is a promising pathway for decarbonization. However, its indiscriminate removal may negatively impact soil-related ecosystem services (SES) and compromise the sustainability of bioenergy production. Our study evaluated 1024 pairwise comparisons to determine the effect and confidence level of three straw removal levels on eight SES (C storage, water regulation and erosion control, nutrient cycling, soil biodiversity, pest control, weed control, GHG mitigation, and food and bioenergy provision). Our impact matrix associated with straw removal should be useful in guiding decision-makers toward sustainable bioenergy production and contributing to a low-carbon economy and climate change mitigation.

Team members: Mauricio Roberto Cherubin - PI
Post-doc Carlos Roberto Pinheiro Junior (FAPESP # 23/11337-8 24/23520-4) –
CCARBON/USP supporting letter - 1 Effect of land use change and sugarcane management practices on soil carbon, soil health, and associated ecosystem services: a synthesis of evidence, 2 - Land cost for sugarcane ethanol production in Brazil
YES - We received CCARBON//USP supporting letter

Results:

Pinheiro Junior, C. R., Carvalho, J. L. N., Canisares, L. P., Bordonal, R. D. O., Cerri, C. E. P., & Cherubin, M. R. (2025). Bioenergy Production From Sugarcane Straw: Implications for Soil-Related Ecosystem Services. *GCB Bioenergy*, 17(5), e70032.

Research Sector Chain: Annual crops

Technology: Soil health

Key questions addressed/Research area: Soil health, regenerative agriculture, and ecosystem services in diversified production systems

Summary of achievements: This period was marked by significant advances in the assessment of soil health across contrasting Brazilian agroecosystems. Field activities included soil sampling from long-term experiments established in key agricultural regions, with a focus on evaluating how management practices, particularly those involving cover crops and crop diversification, affect soil physical, chemical, and biological properties. Samples were collected at multiple depths and analyzed for indicators related to soil structure, organic matter fractions, enzymatic activity, and compaction. Fractionation techniques were applied to quantify particulate and mineral-associated organic matter, providing insights into carbon stabilization mechanisms. In parallel, a national-scale effort compiled over 14,000 georeferenced soil samples to generate predictive soil health maps. These maps integrate indicators such as aggregate stability, bulk density, carbon content, and biological activity. The digital soil mapping approach, developed with international collaboration, offers new tools for evaluating the spatial variability of soil health and the influence of regenerative practices. A notable highlight was the development and validation of the SOHMA KIT®, an accessible toolkit for on-farm soil health diagnosis, now with patent deposited and paper published. Additionally, a systematic review consolidated over 1,000 observations on cover crop performance, linking functional diversity to improvements in biomass production, nutrient cycling, and potential benefits to soil health. Moving forward, the next steps include refining interpretation curves for key soil health indicators and deploying them through an interactive platform. Additional manuscripts are in preparation to communicate findings on biological activity, structural quality, and organic matter dynamics. Ongoing field trials will continue to monitor the response of soil health to diversified management, contributing to scalable indicators and recommendations for more sustainable and resilient farming systems in Brazil. The project's overall trajectory strengthens the scientific basis for regenerative practices as a driver of improved soil function and ecosystem services.

Team members: Maurício Roberto Cherubin - PI (ESALQ/USP) Leonardo Aro Galera, Post-doc (ESALQ/USP) – Bolsa FEALQ (ABC) Lucas Freitas Nogueira Souza, Post-doc (ESALQ/USP) – Bolsa FUSP (Ag4C - SHELL) Martha Lustosa Carvalho, PhD (ESALQ/USP) – Doutorado FAPESP – 2022/13531-3 Victoria Santos Souza, PhD (ESALQ/USP) – Doutorado FAPESP – 2022/16368-6 Carlos Alcides Villalba Algarin, PhD (ESALQ/USP) – Bolsa Paraguai Bruna Emanuele Schiebelbein, PhD (ESALQ/USP) – Doutorado FAPESP - 2023/10897-0 CCARBON/USP supporting letter Mateus Abitante, MSc (ESALQ/USP) – Mestrado FAPESP – 2025/02244-1 CCARBON/USP

scholarship Viviana Meneghini, MSc (ESALQ/USP) – Mestrado FAPESP 2024/02508-6 CCARBON/USP supporting letter Luis Perissoto, MSc (ESALQ/USP) – Mestrado CAPES Giovani Viecelli, IC (ESALQ/USP) – Graduação FEALQ – Agrisus

Results:

Schiebelbein. B.E.; Cherubin, M. R. Patent deposition number BR 10 2024 015629 3, MÉTODO PARA AVALIAÇÃO DA SAÚDE DO SOLO E SEU USO;

Schiebelbein. B.E.; Souza , V.S., Cherubin, M. R. 2025 Soil Health and Management Assessment Kit (SOHMA KIT®): Development and validation for on-farm applications” Environmental and Sustainability Indicators. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indic.2025.100802>

Schiebelbein. B.E.; Cherubin, M. R. Guia do usuário de campo do Kit SOHMA de saúde do solo, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11606/9786587391557>.

Dissertação: Crop diversification mediates soil health and crop resilience in Southern Brazil. Viviana Meneghini (Orientador: Mauricio Cherubin),- defendida 28/07/2025

(F) Principal Investigator: Tiago Osório Ferreira

Technology: Soil health

Key questions addressed/Research area: How does blue carbon soil health support the provision of soil functions, ecosystem services, and SDGs in the face of a climate change scenario?

Summary of achievements: (i) for the evaluation period in this initiative, we have conducted the publication of 1 scientific paper (Water) on a Global Overview of the Soil Health and Ecosystem Services in Mangrove Forests. This study conducted a comprehensive analysis of the integration of soil health (SH) and ecosystem services (ESs) within global mangrove research literature published between 1958 and 2024. The research underscores the importance of considering soil health as a framework for evaluating mangroves’ capacity to provide ecosystem services. Despite this relevance, the systematic review of the Scopus database revealed a significant gap: out of 8,289 scientific articles addressing mangrove soils or sediments, only 321 discussed aspects related to soil health, and a mere 39 addressed both soil health and ecosystem services together. This indicates that most mangrove research neglects to directly address soil health and its connection to ecosystem functions and benefits. The review also found a prevalent historical use of the term “sediment,” reflecting a marine science focus in the literature. Carbon dynamics emerged as the most frequently studied topic within mangrove soil research. Geographically, six out of the fifteen most research-productive countries are also among those with the largest mangrove forest areas, highlighting a correlation between research focus and mangrove distribution. Overall, the primary finding is the pronounced lack of integration between soil health evaluation and ecosystem services in mangrove research, representing a clear scientific shortfall. The authors recommend the development of a soil health index specifically designed for mangrove ecosystems, which would account for their unique physical, geochemical, and climatic characteristics, as well as their social and economic importance. Addressing this research gap is essential not only for advancing scientific understanding but also for supporting the management and conservation of mangroves and the vital ecosystem

services they provide. An additional product of this initiative we also highlight the writing of the book Chapter entitled “Ecosystem services and soil health in mangroves” as part of the Brazilian Soil Health Partnership. The chapter addresses how mangrove forests provide multiple ecosystem services, such as pollutant retention, coastal protection, biodiversity support, and notably, carbon sequestration—making them important allies in climate change mitigation. These services are closely tied to soil health, which reflects the soil's capacity to respond to environmental pressures and sustain biogeochemical processes. This chapter examines soil functioning, ecosystem service provision, and mangrove soil health across different land-use and climatic contexts, highlighting soil formation processes and key biogeochemical roles. It also discusses approaches for assessing soil health, emphasizing indices as tools for restoration, conservation, and policymaking. The lack of integrated studies on soil health and ecosystem services in mangroves is identified as a major challenge for effective management, especially in the face of climate change and increasing human impact. In addition, a new project was approved by FAPESP (2025-08259-0). This project will be conducted by the undergraduate student Livia Odorisi Pavan and aims to develop a quantitative Soil Health Index tailored for Amazonian mangroves under different land-use scenarios, integrating physical, chemical, and biological indicators to assess ecosystem functionality and carbon dynamics. (iii) For the next evaluation period, this initiative will focus on advancing research dissemination and applying soil health assessments in mangrove ecosystems. The main objective is to publish four scientific articles addressing soil health in mangroves affected by distinct anthropogenic and natural disturbances: (I) Land use change in Amazonian mangroves: soil health as a proxy for ecosystem services trade-offs; (II) natural disasters and their impact on soil health; (III) contamination from urban waste; and (IV) the conversion of mangrove forests into shrimp farms. In addition, (V) the mapping and classification of Brazilian coastal mangroves using a soil health index will be carried out to provide a spatial overview of ecosystem conditions. Lastly, (VI) a book chapter will be published, focusing on soil health in mangroves and its relevance to ecosystem service provision.

Team members:

PI: Tiago O Ferreira (ESALQ/USP), Maurício Cherubin (USP/ESALQ), PA: Hermano Melo Queiroz (USP/FFLCH), Angelo Bernardino (UFES), Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega (UFC) Post-doc: Dr. Fellipe Alcantara de Oliveira Mello (USP/ESALQ) - funded by FUSP (Project 107 - RCGI) IC: Livia Odorisi Pavan (USP/ESALQ) - funded by FAPESP (2025-08259-0) and received a support letter from CCARBON/USP.

Results:

Mello, F. A., Ferreira, T. O., Bernardino, A. F., Queiroz, H. M., Mello, D. C., Menillo, R. B., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Soil Health and Ecosystem Services in Mangrove Forests: A Global Overview. *Water*, 16(24), 3626.

(G) Associate Research: Angelo Fraga Bernardino

Technology: Human health

Key questions addressed/Research area: Assessment and quantification of the ecosystem services provided by mangrove forests

Summary of achievements: In this line of research, we have sought to identify, qualify, and measure the value of the ecosystem services provided by mangrove forests to coastal communities living nearby. Initially, we identified how mangroves directly benefit the lives of traditional communities along the Amazonian coast, mapping the flow of services to these communities. Our studies show that these communities directly use and benefit from these ecosystems, making intensive use of provisioning, supporting, regulating, and cultural services. These studies were the first to demonstrate the wide range of services provided to these communities and are now being replicated along the coast of Espírito Santo. In the coming years, we will also carry out the monetary valuation of these services for these communities, providing support for their inclusion in payment for ecosystem services schemes.

Team members: Angelo Bernardino, PI, UFES, Margaret Owuor, Co-PI, Wyss Academy for Nature, Tiago O. Ferreira, ESALQ/USP, Gabriel C. Coppo, Post-doc, UFES Students Vitor Leonardo Rodrigues/PhD student/UFES, BlueShore scholarship Carla F. Pacheco/PhD student/UFES, CNPq scholarship Lethicia Pinto/Master student/UFES, CAPES scholarship

Results: Owuor, M., Santos, T. M., Otieno, P., Mazzuco, A. C. A., Iheaturu, C., & Bernardino, A. F. (2024). Flow of mangrove ecosystem services to coastal communities in the Brazilian Amazon. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 12, 1329006.

(H) Principal Investigator: Denizart Bolonhezi

Research Sector Chain: Bioenergy

Technology: Biodiversity

Key questions addressed/Research area: Use of Cover Crops in Sugarcane and Grain Production Systems

Summary of achievements: Two experiments were developed on sugarcane field renovation using cover crop mixes, two experiments on intercropping legumes in unburned ratoon cane fields, and the maintenance of one long-term trial on no-tillage and liming in unburned sugarcane renovation with soybean (initiated in 1998), as well as one experiment on sugarcane renovation under different soil management practices in the MEIOSI system with peanut (MITOSI Project – *Simultaneous Intercropping Transplanting Method*). The trials using cover crop mixes were installed in partnership with *Usina da Pedra*, and during the reporting period, soil sampling and sugarcane planting were carried out after biomass management. Among the preliminary results, a highlight was the quantification of four times more dry root biomass in treatments with a higher percentage of grass species in the mix, within the first 40 cm of the studied *Quartzarenic Neosol*, when compared to *Crotalaria spectabilis* and pearl millet standards. Additionally, root colonization by arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) was 30% higher in the mix treatments compared to the isolated cultivation of millet or *Crotalaria spectabilis*. Regarding the MITOSI project, it is noteworthy that the harvest was conducted in July, and the treatment combining direct seeding of peanut with direct furrowing for sugarcane did not differ statistically (84.7 TCH) from the conventional tillage treatment (86 TCH). This is an important result considering diesel savings (due to reduced tillage) and the preservation of soil organic matter (samples are yet to be

collected). The long-term trial is installed at the IAC Sugarcane Center in Ribeirão Preto. During the reported period, agronomic evaluations were carried out, and final samplings are scheduled for the next period with the goal of quantifying carbon stocks under each management system. For the upcoming period, soil sampling is planned for the two experiments involving species mixes in sugarcane renovation, installed in two production environments (A2 and E1) at *Usina da Pedra*, as well as root sampling and sugarcane productivity assessments. The trial known as the MITOSI system, which involved peanut during renovation, is expected to continue for one more harvest cycle before renovation in the 2026/27 season, while the long-term trial will be renovated with soybean in this semester. A project proposal is under preparation for submission to FAPESP for funding

Team members: Felipe Martins do Rêgo Barros, Post-doc, (ESLAQ/USP). Fernando Dini Andreote, PI, Brazilian Supervisor, (ESALQ/USP). Andre Luiz Custodio Franco, Supervisor abroad, (Indiana University).

Results:

BETIOL, O.; DE MARIA, I.C.; RUIZ, F.F.; ALMEIDA, P.L.; MASSAROLLO, L.; ORNELLA, T.; GRUENER, C.E.; FURLANI, C.A. Soil Helath and soybena yield responses to strategic tillage and cover-crops in long-term no-tillage. In: WORLD CONGRESS ON CONSERVATION AGRICULTURE, IX. Proceedings...Western Cape Department of Agriculture, Cape Town, South Africa, p. 57-59, 2024. ISBN: 978-1-0370-5134-0

BOLONHEZI, D.; CORDEIRO Jr., P.S.; BETIOL, O.; RUIZ, F.F.; FINOTO, E.; ZERBATTO, C. How to improve the soybean grain yield and root system in a long-term trial of no-tillage under sugarcane straw. In: WORLD CONGRESS ON CONSERVATION AGRICULTURE, IX. Proceedings...Western Cape Department of Agriculture, Cape Town, South Africa, p. 57-59, 2024. ISBN: 978-1-0370-5134-0

GRANDE, L. H. Q.; SANTOS, J. K. ; PEREIRA, M.B. N. ; SILVA, L. H. A. ; MUNIZ, L. F. ; BOLONHEZI, D. ; UMBURANAS, R. C. ; MORAES, M. T. Modelling sugarcane root elongation in response to mechanical stress as an indicator of soil physical quality. EXPERIMENTAL AGRICULTURE , v. 61, p. 1-14, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0014479725000018>

AUGUSTO, J. G.; DE PAZ, C. C. P.; MENDONÇA, G. G.; MOITINHO, M. R. ; MENEGATTO, L. S.; BOLONHEZI, D. ; SALLES, M. S.V. ; SIMILI, F.F Integrated crop-livestock versus conventional systems: Effects on the chemical and physical characteristics of an Oxisol. GRASS AND FORAGE SCIENCE , v. 1, p. 1-11, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gfs.12664>

OLIVEIRA, I. N. DE ; SOUZA, Z. M. DE ; BOLONHEZI, D. ; TAVARES, R. L. M. ; LIMA, R. P. ; SILVA, R. B. DA ; ARAÚJO, F. S. ; LOVERA, L. H. ; LIMA, E. DE S. . Effect of Conservation Management on Oxisol in a Sugarcane Area Under a Pre-Sprouted Seedling System. AGRICULTURE , v. 14, p. 1965, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture14111965>

Co-supervised Theses and Dissertations:

BETIOL, O. Impactos do Preparo Ocasional Após 26 Anos em Plantio Direto com Diferentes Rotações de Culturas sobre a Produtividade da Soja e Alguns Atributos do Solo. UNESP, FCAVJ, Jaboticabal, 2025, 68 p. Tese de Doutorado

RUIZ, F.F. Consórcio de Feijoeiros e Leguminosas Adubos verdes em Soqueira de Cana Crua. UNESP, FCAVJ, Jaboticabal, 2025, 48 p. Dissertação de Mestrado

Associate Research: Ernani Pinto Júnior

Technology: Biodiversity / Human Health

Key questions addressed/Research area: indirect contribution through water quality and cyanobacteria monitoring

Summary of achievements: While no direct co-benefits project within CCARBON/USP has been initiated in this period, my ongoing research and submitted Thematic Project (FAPESP Process nº 2023/11082-0) can generate co-benefits for biodiversity conservation and human health. By applying stable isotope tracing and metabolomics to agroforestry systems, the project can identify management practices that enhance biodiversity through improved soil-plant-microorganism interactions. In addition, my research on cyanobacteria occurrence and toxin monitoring directly relates to human health protection, especially in the context of water quality in agricultural landscapes. In the period, two publications cited CCARBON/USP:

1. Campos TGV et al. New records on toxic cyanobacteria from Brazil: Exploring their occurrence and geography, *Science of The Total Environment*, Volume 931, 2024, 172689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172689>
2. Jacinavicius et al. A rapid LC-MS/MS method for multi-class identification and quantification of cyanotoxins, *Toxicon*, Volume 234, October 2023, 107282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxicon.2023.107282>

Work plan for the next period: Integrate biodiversity indicators and water quality monitoring into CCARBON/USP co-benefits assessments, in collaboration with other researchers focusing on ecosystem services.

Team members: Ernani Pinto, PI (CENA/USP) and other CCARBON/USP participants

Results:

Campos TGV et al. New records on toxic cyanobacteria from Brazil: Exploring their occurrence and geography, *Science of The Total Environment*, Volume 931, 2024, 172689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172689>

Jacinavicius et al. A rapid LC-MS/MS method for multi-class identification and quantification of cyanotoxins, *Toxicon*, Volume 234, October 2023, 107282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxicon.2023.107282>

Work plan for the next period: Integrate biodiversity indicators and water quality monitoring into CCARBON/USP co-benefits assessments, in collaboration with other researchers focusing on ecosystem services.

(I) Associate Research: Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega

Key questions addressed/Research area: Impact of shrimp farming production on mangrove soil health

Technology: Soil health

Summary of achievements: Mangroves are tropical coastal ecosystems recognized as globally important carbon (C) sinks. However, despite their importance, these ecosystems face increasing anthropogenic pressures, such as the expansion of shrimp farming. This activity, although economically significant, alters the dynamics of organic matter (OM), phosphorus (P) and soil health in mangrove soils, negatively impacting their ability to mitigate climate change and increasing the risk of eutrophication. Therefore, this project aims to deepen the understanding of these impacts by characterizing the soil health, P and OM dynamics of mangrove areas directly impacted by shrimp farming and adjacent unimpacted areas. To this end, soil samples will be collected from three mangroves located in the Acaraú River, Ceará, in pairs (impacted and unimpacted areas). In addition to the physical and chemical characterization of the soils (redox potential, pH, and particle size), the levels of organic C, total and organic P, and different geochemical fractions will be quantified, as well as enzymatic activities related to C and P dynamics, seeking to identify possible feedback mechanisms. To deepen understanding, physical fractionation of OM will be performed to quantify the forms of C and P associated with particulate organic matter (MOP) and associated with minerals (MOAM). The results of this study are expected to provide crucial information on the mechanisms that control C loss in mangroves under the influence of shrimp farming, promoting support for the conservation and sustainable use of these coastal ecosystems of great ecological and socioeconomic importance.

Team members: Gabriel Nuto Nóbrega (UFC), PI Tiago Osório Ferreira (ESALQ/USP), Associate Investigator (AI) Arthur Prudêncio de Araújo Pereira (UFC), AI Luis Ernesto de Arruda Bezerra (UFC), AI Lorena Maria Gomes da Silva (MSc/UFC), CAPES grant, no support letter Israel Oliveira Gomes (MSc/UFC), FUNCAP grant, no support letter

Results: 2 MSc dissertations ongoing 1 Undergraduate monograph ongoing

(J) Associate Research: Iraê Amaral Guerrini

Technology: Soil health, Biodiversity

Key questions addressed/Research area 1: Evaluation of soil health in different fragments under restoration of Atlantic Forest

Summary of achievements: The project is about the natural recovery of different Semideciduous Seasonal Atlantic Forest fragments, at UNESP Campus in Botucatu, comparing soil characteristics as indicators of preservation degree of soil health. Results are under analysis and will be published next year.

Team members: PIs: Iraê Amaral Guerrini (FCA-UNESP-Botucatu), José Raimundo Sousa Passos (IB-UNESP-Botucatu); Gian Franco Capra and Antonio Ganga (UNISS-Università degli Studi di Sassari, Sardinia, Italy); Students: MSc: Matheus Fontes Souza (FCA-UNESP, CAPES, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a

support letter); I.C.: Giulia Frizzo Puccetti (FCA-UNESP-Botucatu, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a support letter);

Technology: Soil health, Biodiversity

Key questions addressed/Research area 2: Evaluation of biodiversity and ecosystem services in different fragments under restoration of Atlantic Forest

Summary of achievements: The project is about the natural recovery of different Semideciduous Seasonal Atlantic Forest fragments, at UNESP Campus in Botucatu, comparing different biodiversity and ecosystem services indicators of preservation degree in a natural forest. Results are under analysis and will be published next year.

Team members: PIs: Iraê Amaral Guerrini and Maria José Zackia (FCA-UNESP-Botucatu), José Raimundo Sousa Passos (IB-UNESP-Botucatu); Gian Franco Capra and Antonio Ganga (UNISS-Università degli Studi di Sassari, Sardinia, Italy); Students: PhD: Gabriel Fratta Fritz (FCA-UNESP; Capes, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a support letter); I.C.: Giulia Frizzo Puccetti, Magda Santos, Pietro Brown (FCA-UNESP-Botucatu, not directly funded by CCARBON/USP or benefited by a support letter).

(K) Associate Research: Jessica Suarez Campoli

Technology: Biodiversity

Key questions addressed: Can circular economy practices support the achievement of the SDGs?

Team members: Jessica Suarez Campoli

Summary of achievements:

(i) Synthesis of activities: During this period, two main research activities were carried out. The first resulted in the publication of the article: Campoli, J. S., Nagano, M. S., Kodama, T. K., & Burnquist, H. L. (2025). Advancing the 15th SDG: G20 Nations' Progress in Protecting Life on Land Through Circular Economy Strategies. *Business Strategy & Development*, 8(2), e70141. The second activity involves the development of a new article titled "Efficiency and Productivity of G20 Countries in the Context of the Paris Agreement", which is currently in progress. (ii) Highlights: The published article represents a contribution by evaluating how G20 countries are advancing Sustainable Development Goal 15 (Life on Land) through Circular Economy (CE) strategies. It employed Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) with the Slacks-Based Measure (SBM) and the Malmquist Productivity Index (MPI), complemented by econometric validation through Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS). Results indicated disparities in performance among developed and emerging countries and pointed to a general decline in productivity, emphasizing the need to review environmental policies. The ongoing article expands this methodological framework to analyze the effectiveness of G20 countries in meeting the climate targets set under the Paris Agreement, providing an important link between CE, efficiency analysis, and international environmental commitments. (iii) Workplan for the next period: The next stage of the project will focus on evaluating Circular Economy practices in sustainable agriculture within G20 nations,

and their contribution to the advancement of SDGs 2 (Zero Hunger), 13 (Climate Action), and 15 (Life on Land). This research will involve the development of new efficiency and productivity indicators using DEA-SBM and MPI methodologies, with FGLS validation, aiming to provide macro-level insights that support public policies and promote sustainable development transitions aligned with the global SDG agenda.

Results: Campoli, J. S., Nagano, M. S., Kodama, T. K., & Burnquist, H. L. (2025). Advancing the 15th SDG: G20 Nations' Progress in Protecting Life on Land Through Circular Economy Strategies. *Business Strategy & Development*, 8(2), e70141.

(L) Associate Research: Lucas William Mendes

Research Sector Chain: Integrated Systems

Technology: Soil carbon

Key questions addressed/Research area: Impact of Cover Crops on Soil Health: Microbial Diversity and Phosphorus Dynamics in Sustainable Agricultural Systems

Summary of achievements: This project aims to determine how cover crops alter C and P cycling processes, the soil microbiota, and related ecosystem services through complementary studies. To this end, two short- and long-term field experiments and one controlled pot experiment will be evaluated. The first study will investigate the contribution of cover crops to agricultural sustainability, focusing on soil carbon reservoirs and impacts on soil health and multifunctionality. More specifically, the second study will explore the microbial (soil–plant) feedbacks left by cover crops for a subsequent commercial crop, assessing how cover crops modulate microbial community networks and P-cycling genes such as *pqqC* and *phoC* to enhance P availability. The third study will evaluate how cover crops associated with arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi affect soil P dynamics, shifting P reservoirs in no-till systems managed with these plants over short and long periods. Additionally, a greenhouse experiment will be conducted during an international research stay to analyze microbial recruitment in the rhizosphere of cover crops through metabolite exudation under conditions of high and low P limitation. This project is expected to generate insights into how cover crops modulate the soil microbiome and C and P dynamics, contributing to the development of more sustainable agricultural practices. The PhD candidate Luana do Nascimento Silva Barbosa is developing this research with FAPESP scholarship (2024/17838-1).

Team members: Lucas William Mendes, PI (CENA-USP). Student: Luana Nascimento Silva Barbosa. Project: Impacto de plantas de cobertura na saúde do solo: diversidade microbiana e dinâmica do fósforo em sistemas agrícolas sustentáveis (FAPESP 2024/17838-1). YES - We received CCARBON/USP supporting letter.

(M) Associate Research: Lucie Zinger

Research Sector Chain: Ecosystem Restoration and Conservation

Technology: Soil health, Biodiversity

Key questions addressed/Research area: Impact of pastoralism, forestry, and restoration strategies on soil food webs structure and biodiversity across habitats.

Summary of achievements: In the face of escalating threats to tropical ecosystems, such as deforestation and climate change, understanding the ecological consequences of various land management practices across habitats is crucial. This research line investigates the impacts of pastoralism, forestry, and restoration strategies on soil food webs structure and biodiversity. (i) Synthesis of Main Activities Performed (Current Period): As I have only recently joined the project, there have been no main activities performed by me during this initial period, except fieldwork. (ii) Highlights: As this research line has just commenced, there are no specific highlights to report from previous activities. (iii) Workplan for the Next Period: Our workplan for the upcoming period centers on the analysis, interpretation and valorisation of samples obtained in field expedition conducted in March 2025, at the Itatinga Research Station in collaboration with M. Cooper (ESALQ), Jérôme Mathieu (Sorbonne University), and George Brown (EMBRAPA). My student and I are responsible for the characterization of how soil and litter food webs structure and biodiversity vary across habitats (clayish Mata Atlantica soils vs. sandy Cerrado soils), across land use types (i.e. old-growth forests, pastures, eucalyptus plantations, passive restoration, and active restoration). This comprehensive sampling will allow us to assess the differential impacts of various land-use practices and restoration strategies on the intricate belowground biodiversity. The project can be also included in the Cadeira "Forestry". This project can serve as a foundation for other projects at larger spatial scales that I intend to develop with other members of CCARBON/USP, for example Simone Cotta, Lucas Mendes, as well as with another French institution, the CIRAD (with Agnès Robin and Daniel Poultney).

Team members: Lucie Zinger, PI (CNRS) Jérémy Raynaud, PhD student (Toulouse University/CNRS), not funded by CCARBON/USP, thesis funded and project funded by LabEx TULIP (ANR-10-LABX-0041), letter from CCARBON/USP not requested as the work started independently from CCARBON/USP, but we are happy to include it within the CCARBON/USP framework.

(N) Associate Research: Moacir Tuzzin de Moraes

Technology: Soil health

Key questions addressed/Research area: Modeling sugarcane root growth as a function of mechanical and water stresses in the soil

Summary of achievements: (i) Synthesis of the main activities performed during the period: The objective of the study is to parameterize the root system growth of sugarcane in soil samples derived from areas under regenerative agriculture and conventional farming systems, as a function of mechanical and water stresses, as well as the effect of biopores in mitigating these stresses. (ii) Highlights: Soil samples were collected, and the root elongation rate of sugarcane was quantified. Two articles were developed: one was published in the journal *Experimental Agriculture*, and another is under review in *Soil and Tillage Research*. (iii) Work plan for the next period: Data analysis and preparation of a scientific article on the sugarcane root growth model.

Team members: Moacir Tuzzin de Moraes Student: Luiz Henrique Quecine Grande/Mestrando/PPGSNP ESALQ/USP (i) Is the scholarship directly funded by CCARBON/USP? Não (ii) Funding agency and process number and, (iii) Did the

scholarship receive a support letter from CCARBON/USP? Sim, bolsa de Mestrado [Programas Regulares / Bolsas / No País / Mestrado - Fluxo Contínuo, Processo FAPESP 2024/05953-0]

Results: GRANDE, LUIZ HENRIQUE QUECINE; DOS SANTOS, JOHN KENNEDY; PEREIRA, MATHEUS BATISTA NERI; DA SILVA, LUCAS HENRIQUE AMARO; MUNIZ, LARISSA FERNANDA; BOLONHEZI, DENIZART; UMBURANAS, RENAN CALDAS; DE MORAES, MOACIR TUZZIN. Modelling sugarcane root elongation in response to mechanical stress as an indicator of soil physical quality. EXPERIMENTAL AGRICULTURE, v. 61, p. 14-pg., 2025-02-20. (24/05953-0, 23/11945-8) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0014479725000018>

(O) Associate Research: Renato A. Ferreira de Lima

Research Sector Chain: Ecosystem Restoration and Conservation

Technology: Biodiversity

Key questions addressed/Research area: Expanding the TreeCo database to cover vegetation types across all Brazil

Team members: PIs: Renato A. Ferreira de Lima, (ESALQ/USP), Pedro H. S. Brancalion (ESALQ/USP), Ricardo Ribeiro Rodrigues (ESALQ/USP), Alexandre Adalardo de Oliveira (IB/USP) and Paulo I. K. L. Prado (IB/USP). No students with direct CCARBON/USP funding or support.

Summary of achievements: (i) In this research line, we started to review and compile information regarding the recovery of carbon stocks in areas undergoing restoration in the Atlantic Forest, consolidating existing information and aiming to support large-scale forest restoration strategies. A systematic literature search was conducted, which uncovered approximately 4,000 potentially relevant studies that had their titles and abstracts reviewed. At the end of this preliminary screening, a list of 2,200 relevant studies were selected for full inspection to extract the minimum variables (e.g., forest age, forest biomass estimate, restoration method, and geographic coordinates) and additional variables (e.g., inclusion criteria, sampling effort, forest formation, altitude, and previous land use) from each study. (ii) We found a total of 2016 inventories of forests undergoing restoration, 506 in secondary forests and 1510 in forests undergoing restoration, with different methods and contexts, including abandoned commercial plantations. Among planted forests, 43% corresponded to active restorations (i.e., plantings, direct seeding, topsoil transposition, nucleation) that spanned between 0.2 and 94 years of age at the time of the inventory. (iii) In the next period, we will apply for funding for scholarships (CNPq, FAPESP) for having PhD students or Post-docs to fully incorporate the new information found to the TreeCo database and to analyze these results and provide recommendations regarding the best restoration methods for the Atlantic Forest

Results:

Brouwer, Rens, Marielos Peña-Claros, Frans Bongers, Lourens Poorter, Joannès Guillemot, Danilo R. A. Almeida, Catherine Torres de Almeida, Angélica F. Resende, Laura H. P. Simões, Natália M. Ivanauskas, Renato A. Ferreira de Lima, Vinicius Castro Souza, Cássio A. P. Toledo, Miguel Cooper, José Guedes Fernandes Neto, Mathieu

Decuyper, Paulo G. Molin, Ricardo R. Rodrigues, and Pedro H. S. Brancalion. "Functional Recovery of Tropical Forests: The Role of Restoration Methods and Environmental Conditions." *Biological Conservation* 309 (2025/09/01/ 2025): 111269. <http://dx.doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111269>. 4

Simões, Laura H. P., Marielos Peña-Claros, Joannès Guillemot, Rens Brouwer, Frans Bongers, Lourens Poorter, Catherine T. de Almeida, Danilo R. A. Almeida, Miguel Cooper, Mathieu Decuyper, José G. Fernandes Neto, Matheus S. Fuza, Renato A. F. Lima, Juliano van Melis, Paulo G. Molin, Angélica F. Resende, Ricardo R. Rodrigues, Vinicius C. Souza, Ari F. de Toledo, Cássio A. P. Toledo, and Pedro H. S. Brancalion. "Recovery of Tree Species Functional Composition in Eucalypt Plantations with Natural Regeneration Differs among Canopy Strata." *Forest Ecology and Management* 594 (2025/10/15/ 2025): 122952.

<http://dx.doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2025.122952>

(P) Associate Research: Ricardo de Oliveira Bordonal

Technology: Soil health, Biodiversity

Key questions addressed/Research area: Impacts of land use and soil management practices on biological indicators and soil health

Summary of achievements: The Amazon region, a critical global carbon sink, is increasingly threatened by agricultural expansion, leading to soil disturbances that affect microbial activity and carbon dynamics. In the southern Amazon, Brazil, the potential of agricultural systems to sequester carbon and improve soil health through microbial necromass remains largely unexplored. The scarcity of studies on the dynamics, contribution, and response of microbial necromass in tropical systems highlights a critical gap, limiting not only the advancement of sustainable soil management strategies but also the Amazon region's contribution to mitigating the adverse effects of global climate change. This year, we concluded important studies addressing the role of biological activity in carbon storage in tropical agroecosystems. Our goal for the next period is to apply the Soil Management Assessment Framework (SMAF) to evaluate soil health under integrated agricultural systems in the Amazon biome.

Team members: 1. Carlos Eduardo Pelegrino Cerri (PI) – ESALQ/USP. 2. Maurício Roberto Cherubin (PI) – ESALQ/USP. 3. João Luís Nunes Carvalho (PI) – LNBR/CNPEN. 4. Ricardo de Oliveira Bordonal (PA) – LNBR/CNPEN. 5. Marcelo Laranjeira Pimentel (PhD) – LNBR/CNPEN. Bolsa FAPESP (#23/00183-0). 6. Gabriel dos Santos Rocha (MSc) – UNESP/Jaboticabal. Bolsa CAPES.

Results:

PIMENTEL, M.L.; TENELLI, S.; ANDRADE, N.; NASCIMENTO, A.F.; ANDREOTE, F.D.; CHERUBIN, M.R.; CERRI, C.E.P.; CARVALHO, J.L.N.; BORDONAL, R.O. Interactions among biological indicators, aggregation, and soil carbon in response to agricultural intensification in southern Amazon, Brazil. *CATENA*. 2025. [Submetido/Em revisão].

PIMENTEL, M.L.; ROCHA, A.V.S.; NASCIMENTO, A.F.; ANDREOTE, F.D.; CHERUBIN, M.R.; CERRI, C.E.P.; MEDEIROS, E.V.; CARVALHO, J.L.N.; BORDONAL, R.O. Microbial necromass contributes to soil carbon accumulation under agricultural intensification in the Southern Amazon. *SOIL BIOLOGY AND BIOCHEMISTRY*. 2025. [Submetido/Em revisão].

Marcelo Laranjeira Pimentel. Agricultural intensification systems enhance microbial activity and necromass contribution to soil carbon sequestration in tropical agroecosystems. Tese (doutorado) – Universidade Estadual Paulista (UNESP), Faculdade de Ciências Agrárias e Veterinárias, Jaboticabal, 2025. 110 p. / Orientador: Ricardo de Oliveira Bordonal. <https://repositorio.unesp.br/bitstreams/2d08379a-8590-4273-954a-c934124215af/download>

(Q) Associate Research: Severino Matias de Alencar

Technology: Human health

Key questions addressed/Research area: Effects of UVB Radiation and Tropical/Subtropical Climate on the Phenolic Composition, Bioaccessibility, and Biological Activity of a Wine Grape Variety and Brazilian Wines

Summary of achievements: In this line of research, we have submitted a funding request to FAPESP, which is currently under review. Additionally, Vinícola Biagi has been supporting the implementation of field experiments. We do not yet have any published results, as I joined CCARBON/USP this year and the trials also began this year. For the upcoming period, our goals are to: 1) Characterize grape and wine extracts exposed to different intensities of UV radiation in terms of total phenolics, total tannins, anthocyanins, and volatile compounds; 2) Perform in vitro gastrointestinal digestion of the samples; 3) Assess the bioaccessibility of phenolics using Caco-2 cells; 4) Evaluate the phenolic composition and biological activity of Brazilian wines made from the Cabernet Sauvignon, Tempranillo, Chardonnay, and Sauvignon Blanc varieties grown in tropical and subtropical regions.

Team members: Severino Matias de Alencar, PA, (ESALQ/USP); Daniel Saraiva Lopes, PhD (ESALQ/USP)

(R) Associate Research: Suzana Caetano da Silva Lannes

Technology: Biodiversity, Human health - Reduce food loss and waste, and shift to sustainable healthy food / Human health

Key questions addressed/Research area: Upcycling Food; Food and Materials Development.

Summary of achievements: Application of the upcycling concept in agriculture and processing industry for the development of powder mixtures

This project focuses on obtaining materials with functional characteristics for application in food formulations, with better nutritional and physical functionality, aiming at sustainability, functionality and health. The upcycling concept will be used to obtain waste that will be treated and processed to obtain products with bioactive functionality

and application for health and well-being. They will be used in the solid phase of formulating nutraceutical supplements, as industrial food raw materials, as substitutes for cocoa and part of wheat flour in formulations, for example. The exploitation of agricultural and food processing materials is suitable for food development and reinforces sustainability. 3 formulations of mixtures are proposed (food industry residues + nutritional components). Materials will be used from fermentative processing or not. We will use microencapsulation to add nutritional oils, obtained from extracting the peels, as well as zinc, Fe, vitamins A, D, E. The physical analyzes (rheology, texture, thermal) will show us the structure of the food systems obtained and the chemical ones (HPLC, gas chromatography, nutritional composition, antioxidants) the nutritional potential of each one. The mixtures will be applied in two types of food products such as powdered drink and bread, with further analysis.

FAPESP: [2023/03702-8](#) (FCF/USP)

Team members: Suzana Caetano da Silva Lannes

Students: Cristina Karori Suzuki/Antonio Domenico Alves Monteiro/Gabriel Matavelli Ferreira.

Results:

Publications:

LANNES, S. C. S.; MONTEIRO, A. D. A. ; Suzuki, C. K. ; TEIXEIRA, G. M. N. ; SANTOS, P. H. S. ; ROSA, R. S. . FORMULAÇÃO EM PÓ DE RESÍDUOS INDUSTRIAIS, COMPOSIÇÃO ALIMENTÍCIA DE CHOCOLATE COMPREENDENDO A FORMULAÇÃO, E PROCESSOS DE PREPARAÇÃO RELACIONADOS. 2024, Brasil.

Patente: Privilégio de Inovação. Número do registro: BR10202402205, título: "FORMULAÇÃO EM PÓ DE RESÍDUOS INDUSTRIAIS, COMPOSIÇÃO ALIMENTÍCIA DE CHOCOLATE COMPREENDENDO A FORMULAÇÃO, E PROCESSOS DE PREPARAÇÃO RELACIONADOS" , Instituição de registro: INPI - Instituto Nacional da Propriedade Industrial. Depósito: 23/10/2024 Instituição(ões) financiadora(s): FAPESP USP.

Conferences:

LANNES, S. C. S.. Application of the Upcycling Concept in Agriculture and Processing Industry to Develop Functional Food Formulations. 2024. 30th ICFOST 2024- Indian Convention of Food Scientists & Technologists. the upcycling concept in the agriculture and processing industry to develop Nutritional food formulations. 2024. (Congresso).

LANNES, S. C. S.. Patente e Inovação: Pesquisas e tecnologias aplicadas aos biomas brasileiros,. 2024. VI Semana de Engenharia de Alimentos-SEALIM.Cultura da qualidade nos diversos setores produtivos. 2024.

LANNES, S. C. S.; QUISPE, E. E. H. ; MUJICA, J. A. Y. . Formulaciones en polvo para productos alimenticios y farmacéuticos. 2024. (Apresentação de Trabalho/Conferência ou palestra).

LANNES, S. C. S.. the upcycling concept in the agriculture and processing industry to develop Nutritional food formulations. 2024. 22o. World Congress of Food Science and Technology-IUFoST. Nutrition and Health, Alternative Proteins 2. 2024.

LANNES, S.C.S. Sustainability in Food Technology and its Relationship with Health. 17 Feb 2025. 2nd Global Virtual Meet on Food Science and Technology. London.

4. INNOVATION

4.1 Innovation Strategic Plan

This second year of activities of CCARBON/USP was dedicated to structure the pillar of Innovation of the center, which is one of the most challenging given the less pronounced experience of university researchers – most CCARBON/USP members – in this field, at least compared to Research and Dissemination. Given this limitation, we chose the strategy to develop a strategic plan as a basis for the activities of Innovation, to be prepared with the support of leading companies in the field. This type of consultancy was not, however, covered by the CEPID grant, so we had to approach CCARBON/USP partners to support it. We then succeeded in obtaining a R\$ 200,000.00 grant from Fundo Vale to finance the hiring of a specialized consultancy in innovation to prepare our strategic plan. We signed a MoU with Fundo Vale – which has an outstanding experience in innovation –, and with their guidance we hired Numerik – a leading consultancy on innovation – to support the development of the innovation strategic plan.

Our main goal with this consultancy is to develop goals and tools for implementing and monitoring the plan, connecting research with the private sector and expanding CCARBON/USP's role in the innovation ecosystem. The consultancy will play a key role in providing strategic support and defining pathways to strengthen CCARBON/USP's innovation ecosystem. Its role will include developing and managing the innovation strategy, coordinating with various market players, and connecting with startups, investors, companies, and research centers. By closely monitoring this process, the consultancy will ensure alignment with institutional objectives and provide strategic directions to maximize impact. This support aims to accelerate the transformation of research into practical applications, expand fundraising, and attract talent, strengthening the sustainable innovation ecosystem for tropical agriculture and low-carbon agriculture. The workplan is structured as follows:

Figure 15. Workplan for the development of CCARBON/USP strategic plan.

The strategic plan will be developed by the following team: (i) one part-time expert on innovation to be hired by Numerik, who will be supervised by a senior consultant of the company dedicated to the project; (ii) two post-doc researchers, to be hired with CEPID's grant; (iii) Marcelo Lima de Melo, administrative staff of CCARBON/USP; and (iv) a working group, lead by prof. Pedro Brancalion, CCARBON/USP Innovation Director, and composed by other CCARBON/USP researchers and key players of the sector, including representatives of startup hubs, companies, and R&D centers. The project is expected to start in September 2025 and last for 12 months.

4.2 Interactions with startups and innovation hubs

Another important front of activities in the Innovation pillar of CCARBON/USP has been the interaction with startups and innovation hubs, in order to consolidate CCARBON/USP as a leading player in the field and maximize positive interactions for the center. The expectation is that CCARBON/USP will soon become a great supplier of startups and technologies to the innovation ecosystem of tropical agriculture, so we decided that the connection with these groups would be strategic. We have three main achievements to highlight on this issue:

- The signing, in July 2025, of a MoU with Hub Cerrado - the largest innovation and business ecosystem in the Midwest. Established in 2019 in Goiânia-GO, this startup hub has a prominent role in agriculture, integrating some of the leading agribusiness companies and startups. Based on this collaboration, CCARBON/USP will provide research expertise and tutorship for entrepreneurship in initiatives related to carbon in agriculture;
- The recognition, in March 2025, of CCARBON/USP as tutor, in the topic of carbon and climate change, of startups incubated at PwC Agtech Innovation, in Piracicaba-SP. Based on this partnership, CCARBON/USP has participated in several programs, such as the Game Changer – Climate and Carbon, in which startups were evaluated in a hackathon event, and has received several visits from companies engaged in this ecosystem environment;
- The co-organization of an innovation event – the AgTech Day – with ESALQ Tec, to be held in Piracicaba, in November 2025. This will be the 12th edition of this event, this time with the theme “Innovations for low carbon agriculture”, and will have nearly 250 participants. The first phase of this event consists of a hackathon with 20 startups, to be selected based on dozens of proposals to be received by the coordination of the event. The second consists of three panels, with one moderator and three lecturers, who will cover the topics (i) accumulating soil carbon, (ii) integrated farming systems for carbon removal, and (iii) landscape approaches for low carbon agriculture. On the day after the event, we will promote a technical visit to the CCARBON/USP administrative office and some strategic laboratories with interested participants of the event, in order to foster new collaborations and strengthen partnerships.

4.3 Mapping innovation in CCARBON/USP ecosystem

One of the key missions of CCARBON/USP is to promote novel technologies to help transform tropical agriculture from a main carbon source to a major carbon sink. To achieve this goal, the coordination of the center will have to develop the capacity to

identify research with innovative potential and foster their transformation into usable innovations, which may be achieved through novel products and processes, as well as emerging companies. We will perform a major screening of the innovation potential of the several research projects being developed as part of CCARBON/USP as part of the development of the Innovation Strategic Plan, with the support of experts in the field. However, we have already done a preliminary assessment of it, and present here some initiatives to illustrate how this process will be developed.

(A) Innovation Report

- **Title:** Selection of carbon-enhancing native species: an innovative approach to forest restoration
- **Institution:** ESALQ/USP & CCARBON/USP
- **Country:** Brazil
- **Nature:** Methodological Innovation (under development)
- **Team:** Gabriela Albuquerque Lucio da Silva, Pedro Henrique Santin Brancalion, Joannès Guillemot, Juliano van Melis

Abstract: This innovation presents a method for selecting native tree species with high carbon accumulation potential, designed for application in ecological restoration projects with a focus on carbon credit generation. The approach includes: a) analysis of 14,158 individual trees across 202 restoration plots in five Brazilian states; b) quantification of aboveground biomass per tree; c) estimation of aboveground carbon stock; d) identification of carbon-enhancing species, considering structural traits, environmental conditions, and land-use history; and e) development of a regionalized map for the Atlantic Forest indicating the most suitable carbon-enhancing species for each area. The methodology aims to support professionals working in forest restoration and the carbon market by providing technical guidance to align restoration practices with climate goals, making them both economically viable and scalable.

Sector pain that innovation aims to solve: Although climate finance in Brazil moves approximately R\$ 23.5 billion annually, only 25% is allocated to forest-related initiatives. Ecological restoration still faces significant barriers to becoming a competitive activity in the carbon market, especially due to the difficulty in offsetting operational costs through credit sales. Most restoration projects are designed to meet legal requirements, with little focus on carbon sequestration outcomes. This methodology addresses that gap by introducing technical criteria to maximize carbon accumulation per restored hectare. This approach enhances the efficiency of credit generation and strengthens the economic viability of restoration as a nature-based solution.

Connection of private sector: This methodology is being developed as part of a doctoral project at ESALQ/USP, in collaboration with the FAPESP Thematic Project NewFor (grant no. 2018/18416-2). This novel restoration approach has attracted increasing interest from forestry companies, environmental consultancies, corporate restoration

programs, and organizations working toward ESG targets. Its implementation can improve the technical planning of restoration projects, increase profitability per restored hectare, and support public policies related to climate mitigation and sustainable land use.

Intellectual property protection actions: The methodology will be published in an open-access scientific journal to ensure wide dissemination and adoption by public and private institutions. This strategy aims to accelerate the adoption of this restoration approach by stakeholders already active in the field, as well as emerging companies that face challenges in integrating reforestation goals into the sustainability of their business models.

(B) Innovation Report

- **Title:** Allometric Modeling Framework for Carbon Estimation in Tropical Forest Restoration
- **Institution:** ESALQ/USP & CCARBON/USP
- **Country:** Brazil
- **Nature:** Methodological Innovation (under development)

Abstract: This innovation refers to the development of a locally calibrated and biologically consistent allometric modeling framework for estimating tree biomass and carbon stocks in restoration plantations. The methodology is grounded in one of the most comprehensive destructive sampling datasets for tropical forest restoration in the Atlantic Forest, comprising 324 trees from 26 native species across three age classes (6, 12, and 20 years). It includes additive and system-based nonlinear models (e.g., Weighted Nonlinear Seemingly Unrelated Regression – WNSUR) that enable logical partitioning of biomass among tree components (stem, branches, leaves, and roots). These models outperform pantropical equations in terms of accuracy, particularly in mixed-species systems, and are being calibrated to support large-scale carbon monitoring through LiDAR and remote sensing integration.

Sector Pain that the Innovation Aims to Solve: Reliable carbon estimates are essential for the credibility of forest restoration projects and Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). However, most current carbon accounting relies on generic models that are poorly suited for restoration contexts. This innovation addresses this gap by providing locally calibrated equations tailored to restoration plantations with native species, reducing significantly the uncertainty in biomass estimates. It helps overcome key barriers to credible Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) in carbon markets and climate mechanisms.

Connection with the Private Sector: This innovation responds to the growing demand from carbon project developers and private programs involved in large-scale ecological restoration. It is directly aligned with the needs of projects focused on forest carbon certification, ecosystem restoration, and environmental asset management. It supports initiatives aiming to quantify restoration outcomes and generate carbon credits. The

methodological framework is currently being integrated into restoration monitoring protocols in collaboration with CCARBON/USP.

Intellectual Property Protection Actions: The methodological approach is intended for publication in high-impact scientific journals and is being incorporated into technical reports and carbon estimation protocols. Model calibration routines and integration procedures with remote sensing tools are currently under evaluation.

(C) Innovation Report

- **Title:** Multi-functional forests: an alternative use of the Legal Reserve area in rural properties
- **Applicant:** Rodrigo K. Hakamada
- **Institution:** ESALQ/USP, in partnership with the Environment Secretariat from the Sao Paulo state government
- **Country:** Brazil

Abstract: The Brazilian “Forest Code” requires that a portion of rural properties – ranging from 20% to 80% depending on the biome – must be designated as a “Legal Reserve,” maintained with forest species to both conserve nature and provide forest products for farmers. These areas may contain up to 50% exotic species and be managed without clearcut (only by thinning or partial cuttings). We propose an innovative approach that mixes native and fast-growing exotic species to fulfill both conservation and production goals.

Sector Pain that the Innovation Aims to Solve: Legal Reserve restoration is seen by farmers as a cost, and an area that is just set aside that is “lost” within the property. This new model of doing forest restoration and producing forest products is an innovative way to conciliate objectives.

Connection with the Private Sector: This mixed plantation model can be used for all companies and private landowners, generating cash while generating ecosystem services. In the near future, Legal Reserve areas could be used to stock carbon and generate incomes and wood and non-wood products to be used in the farm.

(D) Innovation Report

- **Title:** Satellite-based monitoring of forest regrowth in plantations
- **Applicant:** Matheus Pinheiro Ferreira and Paulo Guilherme Molin
- **Institution:** Centre for Carbon Studies in Tropical Agriculture - USP, Luiz de Queiroz College of Agriculture.
- **Country:** Brazil

Abstract: This research aims to develop deep learning regression models for satellite-based monitoring of forest regrowth in plantation and restoration areas. Convolutional

neural networks (CNNs) will be trained using canopy height models (CHM) derived from multi-temporal airborne laser scanning (ALS) data as reference, enabling the estimation of tree height solely from high-resolution optical satellite imagery. By applying this approach over multiple acquisition dates, it becomes possible to track growth dynamics and assess spatial variability in forest development. The method offers a scalable and cost-effective solution for continuous monitoring and decision-making in sustainable forest management.

Sector Pain that the Innovation Aims to Solve: The forestry sector faces significant challenges in cost-effective and scalable monitoring of tree growth, especially in large plantation and restoration areas. Traditional field inventories are expensive, time-consuming, and spatially limited, while airborne LiDAR acquisitions, although accurate, are costly and infrequent. This limits the ability to monitor regrowth dynamics continuously and at scale. The proposed innovation addresses this gap by enabling accurate estimation of tree height from readily available satellite optical imagery, reducing dependency on frequent LiDAR acquisitions and expanding monitoring capabilities.

Connection with the Private Sector: The proposed innovation has strong potential for integration with the private forestry sector, particularly companies managing large-scale plantations and restoration projects. By providing an affordable and scalable tool for monitoring tree height and growth dynamics from satellite imagery, the solution can enhance operational planning, optimize harvest cycles, and support certification processes. Partnerships with private enterprises can also facilitate access to reference data and accelerate the adoption of advanced monitoring technologies in commercial forestry.

(E) Innovation Report

- KITSOHMA (“*Método para avaliação da saúde do solo e seu uso*”)
- Institution where it was filed: INPI - National Institute of Industrial Property.
- Country: Brazil.
- Nature: Invention Patent.
- Registration number: BR10202401562.
- Filing date: 30/07/2024.
- Applicant: Bruna Emanuele Schiebelbein, Maurício Roberto Cherubin.
- Principal: Centre for Carbon Studies in Tropical Agriculture - USP, Luiz de Queiroz College of Agriculture.

Abstract: The present invention relates to a method for directly assessing soil health comprising the following stages: a) Selection of Assessment Zones; b) Assessment of monitoring indicators; c) Interpretation of measured results and generation of a soil health index; and d) Planning of management practices. This method is aimed at farmers, agronomists and other professionals involved in soil management and analysis, and makes it possible to carry out chemical, physical and biological assessments in a practical and accessible way.

Sector Pain that the Innovation Aims to Solve: This patent application is the result of more than three years of research into this technology. KIT SOHMA® is a portable, inexpensive and user-friendly tool that enables the sector to have a straightforward and rapid evaluation and interpretation of chemical, physical and biological indicators directly in the field. It can be useful for public and private initiatives, from small- to large-scale, of regenerative agriculture, pasture reclamation, forest restoration that are ongoing or planned across the country. KIT SOHMA® has been tested in different regions of Brazil, and has the potential to be scaled up in other countries. Further details at <https://www.livrosabertos.abcd.usp.br/portaldelivrosUSP/catalog/book/1311>.

Connection with the Private Sector: KIT SOHMA® was developed at the university with the support of public-private projects (FAPESP, Fundação Agrisus and Bayer). We are now determining how to commercialise it, as private companies, research institutions, cooperatives, public agencies and governments are highly interested in using the kit in their initiatives.

Intellectual property protection actions: A patent deposit was done in INPI - Instituto Nacional da Propriedade Industrial (BR 10 2024 015629 3).

5. DISSEMINATION

The Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture (CCARBON/USP), through its Dissemination Division, consolidated during the reporting period a significant set of actions aimed at scientific communication, capacity building for strategic audiences, and the strengthening of national and international partnerships. Acting as a hub that integrates science, public policy, and society, CCARBON/USP seeks to amplify the impact of its research through the publication of scientific articles, books, and technical materials; engagement in strategic networks and alliances; the organization and participation in relevant events; and the promotion of educational and public awareness initiatives.

Currently, the structure of the Dissemination team includes Director Professor Tiago Osório Ferreira, the researcher MSc. Rodolfo Fagundes Costa, and the Scientific Journalism scholar Dr. Juliana Ramiro, Dr. Nayana Pereira Alves and MSc. Mariana Pezzatte Pollo works in an integrated manner to develop and implement strategies across five main areas: Publications, Advocacy, Training, Social Media, and Public Awareness. Results achieved during this period include the publication of dozens of articles in high-impact journals, books, and book chapters; the formalization of technical-scientific cooperation agreements; the organization of national and international events; and the coordination of educational programs such as Educarbon.

In the field of publications, noteworthy outputs include works that advance knowledge on low-carbon agriculture, soil health, carbon sequestration, and the sustainable management of tropical ecosystems. In advocacy, highlights include the creation of the Brazilian Soil Health Partnership, the agreement with the São Paulo State Forest Foundation to strengthen integrated mangrove management, and participation in the EMBRAPA–FGV–CCARBON/USP Alliance. In training, the Center organized and supported symposia, workshops, and courses, expanding the reach of its technical and scientific expertise.

In addition to scientific dissemination activities, the Division strengthened its institutional and international presence through strategic participation in conferences and forums, contributing to the formulation of public policies and positioning Brazil as a reference in nature-based solutions for tropical agriculture. The combination of robust scientific output, multisectoral engagement, and educational initiatives reflects CCARBON/USP's commitment to fostering more sustainable and resilient agriculture aligned with global challenges in climate change mitigation and adaptation.

5.1 Publications

Scientific Papers

Since the center's establishment, 60 scientific papers have been published in internationally recognized, peer-reviewed journals indexed in major academic databases. The full list of publications is presented below in alphabetical order:

1. Carvalho, M. L., Maciel, V. F., Bordonal, R. D. O., Carvalho, J. L. N., Ferreira, T. O., Cerri, C. E. P., & Cherubin, M. R. (2023). Stabilization of organic matter in soils: drivers, mechanisms, and analytical tools—a literature review. *Revista Brasileira de Ciência do Solo*, *47*, e0230130.
2. Bieluczyk, W., Cherubin, M. R., Cerri, C. E. P., Siqueira-Neto, M., Abdalla-Filho, A. L., Castro, J. I. A., ... & de Camargo, P. B. (2024). Greenhouse gas fluxes in Brazilian climate-smart agricultural and livestock systems: A systematic and critical overview. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, *464*, 142782.
3. Pereira, A. P., Cherubin, M. R., de Araujo, A. S., Santana, M. C., de Medeiros, E. V., da Costa, D. P., ... & Cardoso, E. J. (2024). Soil quality evaluation in mono and mixed eucalypt plantation. *Sustainability*, *16*(6), 2534.
4. Pinheiro Junior, C. R., Carvalho, J. L. N., Canisares, L. P., Cerri, C. E. P., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Soil carbon stocks in sugarcane cultivation: An evidence synthesis associated with land use and management practices. *GCB Bioenergy*, *16*(9), e13188.
5. Queiroz, H. M., Ferreira, T. O., Cerri, C. E. P., Pereira, G. A. G., & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Advancing the agave-soil nexus approach: A systematic review. *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining*, *18*(5), 1306-1320.
6. Soares, M. B., Rodrigues, R. R., Péres, L. O., Cerri, C. E. P., & Alleoni, L. R. F. (2024). Impact of climatic seasons on the dynamics of carbon, nitrogen and mercury in soils of Brazilian biomes affected by gold mining. *Science of the Total Environment*, *954*, 176279.
7. da Luz, F. B., Gonzaga, L. C., Cherubin, M. R., Castioni, G. A. F., & Carvalho, J. L. N. (2024). Soil health impact of long-term sugarcane vinasse recycling. *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining*, *18*(6), 2064-2077.
8. Pinheiro Junior, C. R., Canisares, L. P., Abreu, M. C., Lyra, G. B., de Oliveira, A. P., Greschuk, L. T., ... & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Drivers of carbon stabilization and sequestration in Brazil's black soils. *Catena*, *246*, 108451.
9. Pinheiro Junior, C. R., Ferreira, T. O., Oliveira Filho, J. D. S., Queiroz, H. M., Canisares, L. P., Greschuk, L. T., ... & Cherubin, M. R. (2024). Shallow soils in dryland ecosystem: Drivers of C accumulation and land management implications. *Geoderma Regional*, *38*, 1-9.
10. Bernardino, A. F., Queiroz, H. M., Nobrega, G. N., Coppo, G. C., Sanders, C. J., Silva, A. E., ... & Ferreira, T. O. (2024). Soil greenhouse gas fluxes partially reduce the net gains in carbon sequestration in mangroves of the Brazilian Amazon. *Environmental research*, *263*, 120102.
11. Locatelli, J. L., Del Grosso, S., Santos, R. S., Hong, M., Gurung, R., Stewart, C. E., ... & Cerri, C. E. P. (2025). Modeling soil organic matter changes under crop diversification strategies and climate change scenarios in the Brazilian Cerrado. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, *379*, 109334.
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Book chapters:

Since the establishment of CCARBON/USP, six book chapters have been published by associate researchers. These contributions address topics related to sustainable agricultural practices, aiming to enhance soil health, increase carbon sequestration, and improve resilience to climate change. Below is the list of book chapters published by CCARBON/USP researchers.

1. CERRI, C.E.P.; MELLO, F.F.D.C.; RENTERIA, N.B.; CHERUBIN, M.R. (2024). Public Policies and Initiatives to Promote Soil Health and Carbon Sequestration in Brazil. In Soil Health Series: Volume 3 Soil Health and Sustainable Agriculture in Brazil (eds I.C. Mendes and M.R. Cherubin). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780891187448.ch12>
2. CHERUBIN, M.R.; DA LUZ, F.B.; DE LIMA, R.P.; TENELLI, S.; BORDONAL, R.O.; DE OLIVEIRA, B.G.; GONZAGA, L.C.; CERRI, C.E.P.; CARVALHO, J.L.N. (2024). Soil Health in Sugarcane Production Systems. In Soil Health Series: Volume 3 Soil Health and Sustainable Agriculture in Brazil (eds I.C. Mendes and M.R. Cherubin). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780891187448.ch5>
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Books

In addition to the book chapters, two books authored by CCARBON/USP researchers were published in 2024, both focusing on soil health and sustainability. These publications contribute to the dissemination of practical and scientific knowledge in the field. Details of each book are provided below:

1. MENDES, I.C.; CHERUBIN, M.R. (2024) Soil Health and Sustainable Agriculture in Brazil. ISBN: 978-0-891-18743-1. March 2024. 432 pages <https://www.wiley.com/enus/Soil+Health+and+Sustainable+Agriculture+in+Brazil-p-9780891187431>
2. CHERUBIN, M.R. Guia prático de plantas de cobertura: espécies, manejo e impacto na saúde do solo. Universidade de São Paulo. Escola Superior de Agricultura Luiz de Queiroz, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.11606/9786587391618>

eBook:

In order to provide guidelines for enabling soil management practices, promoting improvements in soil health and agricultural sustainability, eBooks were published as practical guides for their users. Below are the two eBooks published and their respective numbers of downloads up to the time of writing this report:

1. SCHIEBELBEIN, B.E.; CHERUBIN, M.R. Guia do usuário de campo do Kit SOHMA de saúde do solo. Universidade de São Paulo. Escola Superior de Agricultura Luiz de Queiroz, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11606/9786587391557> Disponível em: www.livrosabertos.abcd.usp.br/portaldelivrosUSP/catalog/book/1311. Number of downloads: 3.361.
2. CHERUBIN, M.R. Guia prático de plantas de cobertura: espécies, manejo e impacto na saúde do solo. Universidade de São Paulo. Escola Superior de Agricultura Luiz de Queiroz, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11606/9786587391618> Disponível em: www.livrosabertos.abcd.usp.br/portaldelivrosUSP/catalog/book/1340. Number of downloads: 5.653.

5.2 Next steps

In addition to the continued efforts in publishing scientific papers, books and eBooks, the Dissemination Division is currently in discussions with SENAR to develop a series of educational booklets aimed at rural producers. The goal is to inform and train them in the adoption of sustainable practices, using accessible language and practical examples. This initiative also aligns with the division's broader training strategy, which seeks to translate scientific knowledge into actionable solutions for the field.

The main proposed theme is “*Nature-based solutions: accessible and sustainable practices for the field*”, allowing the combination of topics such as agroforestry systems, integration crop-livestock-forest (ICLF), soil management strategies like no-till and green

manuring, and access to public policies such as Payments for Environmental Services (PES). Additional content may include guidance on restoring degraded areas with native species, increasing soil carbon stocks, accessing green financing and sustainable certifications, and promoting climate education for rural families and workers. Final topics will be defined in collaboration with SENAR's national office.

5.3 Advocacy

Important initiatives related to the advocacy sub-area were implemented in the period: the establishment of the Brazilian Soil Health Partnership, the cooperation agreement with the Forest Foundation, participation in the EMBRAPA-FGV Alliance for Climate Action and Reduction of CO₂ Emissions and a strategic partnership between FAPESP, French research institutions, and CCARBON/USP.

Brazilian Soil Health Partnership

The Brazilian Soil Health Partnership was launched with the participation of more than 50 researchers from several Brazilian institutions. The initiative promotes a national soil health agenda and strengthens connections between scientists, rural producers, and other strategic actors. The official launch took place on April 24, 2024 during the Symposium on Soil Health held by CCARBON/USP. Since then, several actions have been implemented to consolidate the identity and visibility of the partnership, such as the creation of a visual identity, development of media materials, launch of its own website (<https://brsoilhealthpartnership.com/>) and the publication of technical and institutional articles aimed at promoting soil health in agricultural areas.

Figure 16. Home page of the Brazilian Soil Health Partnership website.

Cooperation Agreement with the Forest Foundation

The Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture at the University of São Paulo (CCARBON/USP) has [signed a technical and scientific cooperation agreement with the ‘São Paulo State Forest Foundation’](#) to strengthen the Integrated Mangrove Management Program, established by Normative Ordinance [FF 445/2024](#).

The program is structured around four thematic areas: Biodiversity; Bioeconomy; Environmental Education and Communication; and Research and Climate Change Mitigation and highlights the critical role of mangroves in preserving marine biodiversity, sequestering carbon, and addressing climate change. The initiative aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 13 (Climate Action) and SDG 14 (Life Below Water).

Coordinated by Prof. Dr. Tiago Osorio Ferreira (CCARBON/USP), the collaboration began in April 2024 and aims to evaluate blue carbon stocks and the presence of potentially toxic elements in mangrove soils along the São Paulo coastline. As part of the agreement, around 2,000 soil samples will be collected by Forest Foundation teams from various mangrove areas) and analyzed by CCARBON/USP researchers at laboratories located at the “Luiz de Queiroz” College of Agriculture (ESALQ/USP) in Piracicaba.

To support the collaboration, CCARBON/USP has offered technical training to the Forest Foundation’s team. In April 2024, Prof. Dr. Hermano Melo Queiroz and MSc. Rodolfo Fagundes Costa led a hands-on field course on internationally recognized methodologies for quantifying total ecosystem carbon, covering standardized protocols for soil sampling and vegetation measurement (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Image of the 1st Training Meeting for Mangrove Monitoring that took place at Itinguçu State Park in Peruíbe – SP (April 2024). Authorship: Douglas Silva

Follow-up training sessions focused on the consistent field application of these methods, ensuring data quality and comparability across sites are being conducted between researchers from both institutions (Figure 18). The resulting data will inform conservation strategies, ecological restoration efforts, and the development of evidence-based public policies. This partnership represents a major step forward in coastal ecosystem management, combining cutting-edge scientific research with territorial action. Periodic technical reports will be issued, providing insights into environmental quality and carbon stocks in mangrove ecosystems.

Figure 18. Image of an online Training Meeting for Mangrove Monitoring that took place in July 2025 with members from the Xixová-Japuí State Park that will be the first ones to conduct field sampling on mangroves. Authorship: Rodolfo Fagundes Costa

CCARBON/USP-EMBRAPA-FGV Alliance

On October 24, 2024, the Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture of the University of São Paulo (CCARBON/USP) formalized its participation in the [Alliance for Climate Action and Reduction of CO₂ Emissions in Agriculture](#), a strategic cooperation established with the Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation (Embrapa) and the Getulio Vargas Foundation (FGV). The agreement was signed during an official ceremony held at the Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock (MAPA), in Brasília, with the presence of high-level representatives from the three institutions and partner organizations.

Figure 19. Representatives from Embrapa, FGV, and CCARBON/USP during the official signing ceremony of the Alliance for Climate Action and Reduction of CO₂ Emissions in Agriculture, held at the Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock, in Brasília

The technical-scientific alliance aims to foster interinstitutional collaboration in the development and refinement of methodologies and indicators for assessing the impacts of adaptation and mitigation actions in the agricultural sector. The scope of the partnership includes the formulation of robust sustainability metrics, particularly for carbon balance assessment, emissions traceability, and the monitoring of agricultural systems' vulnerability and adaptive capacity in the context of climate change.

One of the key objectives of the initiative is to generate scientifically grounded data to support and improve public policies related to climate change and agriculture, including strategic contributions to the National Greenhouse Gas Emissions Inventory coordinated by the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation (MCTI). In parallel, the alliance will provide technical input for the development of a National Sustainability Taxonomy, under the leadership of the Ministry of Finance, aimed at orienting investments and financial instruments aligned with sustainable practices.

By promoting the integration of knowledge, research infrastructure, and human capital among the participating institutions, the alliance creates a platform for coordinated efforts in agroclimatic policy and innovation. It also seeks to establish a shared methodology for carbon accounting and sustainability assessment, adapted to the specificities of Brazilian agricultural production systems—thus addressing a critical gap in harmonized data and standardized tools for climate-smart agriculture in Brazil.

CCARBON/USP brings together many researchers and students working across disciplines to advance research in soil carbon dynamics, low-carbon agriculture, and sustainable land-use strategies. The alliance offers a unique opportunity to expand the impact of scientific knowledge through institutional synergies, generating relevant information to guide evidence-based decision-making and enhance the competitiveness and environmental performance of Brazilian agriculture.

The partnership leverages complementary strengths to develop metrics that are not only technically rigorous but also applicable to the diverse productive systems across the country. The involvement of FGV Agro, through its Center for Agribusiness Studies, contributes a strategic dimension in terms of economic analysis and policy design, reinforcing the multidimensional nature of the initiative.

The creation of this alliance marks a significant milestone in Brazil's agro-environmental agenda. It reflects a growing consensus among key stakeholders that multi-institutional coordination is essential for addressing the complex challenges posed by climate change to agriculture. The alliance also sets the stage for the scaling-up of research outputs, the formulation of innovative policy instruments, and the positioning of Brazil as a reference in climate-resilient agricultural practices on the global stage.

FAPESP-FRANCE Partnership

The collaboration between the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP), leading French research institutions and the Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture (CCARBON/USP) has emerged as a strategic alliance to address global challenges related to climate change, sustainable land use, and low-carbon agriculture. This international partnership seeks to strengthen joint research efforts on carbon dynamics within tropical and subtropical agroecosystems, focusing on the complex interactions among soil, plants, animals, and the atmosphere. It aims to integrate multidisciplinary approaches from agronomy, soil science, ecology, socioeconomics, and digital agriculture to generate robust, science-based solutions for climate resilience and sustainable rural development.

Together, these institutions aim to co-develop research frameworks aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly those focused on climate action (SDG 13), life on land (SDG 15), zero hunger (SDG 2), and partnerships for the goals (SDG 17). The partnership prioritizes topics such as:

- Greenhouse gas mitigation and carbon sequestration in tropical agriculture;
- Restoration and resilience of productive landscapes;
- Sustainable intensification of food systems;
- Bioeconomic transitions and social inclusion;
- Evidence-based policy development and territorial planning.

FAPESP plays a key role in enabling this scientific cooperation through funding mechanisms, coordination platforms, and support for internationalization strategies. The long-term goal is to structure high-impact joint research proposals, foster scientific mobility, and expand innovation networks that can inform public policies and enhance environmental governance in both Brazil and France. This partnership represents a model of South–North cooperation based on shared priorities, mutual scientific leadership, and the urgent need for integrated responses to the climate crisis.

Workshop FAPESP-CNRS/CIRAD/INRAE: Carbon dynamics in the soil-plant-animal-atmosphere interactions

The establishment of the Alliance for Climate Action and Reduction of CO₂ Emissions in Agriculture was preceded and strategically supported by a key international scientific exchange initiative. The partnership's initial groundwork was laid during the “[Workshop FAPESP-CNRS/CIRAD/INRAE: Carbon Dynamics in the Soil-Plant-Animal-Atmosphere Interactions](#),” held on November 4–6, 2024, at the “Luiz de Queiroz” College of Agriculture (Esalq/USP), in Piracicaba, São Paulo.

Figure 20. Workshop FAPESP-CNRS/CIRAD/INRAE: Carbon dynamics in the soil-plant-animal-atmosphere interactions

Organized by the Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture (CCARBON/USP), and supported by the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP) and the Consulate General of France in São Paulo, the workshop convened climate scientists and researchers from leading Brazilian and French institutions—including CNRS, CIRAD, and INRAE—with the objective of integrating scientific expertise and infrastructure to strengthen bilateral cooperation in agricultural carbon research.

The event served as a platform for the formulation of joint research strategies on carbon dynamics across soil, plant, animal, and atmospheric interfaces. Through an interdisciplinary lens, participants discussed the interconnection between climate adaptation, greenhouse gas mitigation, carbon sequestration, and sustainable land management, while considering the socioeconomic dimensions of transitioning to climate-resilient food systems. The workshop explicitly aligned its agenda with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), emphasizing the importance of biodiversity conservation alongside agricultural productivity.

The opening session featured institutional support from Esalq's Dean, Prof. Thaís Vieira, and FAPESP's Administrative Director, Fernando Menezes de Almeida, underscoring the relevance of the initiative within both local and international research agendas. Over three days, researchers participated in focused discussions, technical presentations, and strategic planning sessions, culminating in a guided tour of Esalq's research facilities and the drafting of a joint international research proposal on sustainable landscapes.

This collaborative workshop was not only a scientific milestone but also a catalyst for the partnership of CCARBON/USP, CNRS, CIRAD, and INRAE. It demonstrated the value of transnational cooperation in advancing robust, evidence-based approaches to address the challenges of climate change in agriculture. The event reinforced the shared commitment of Brazilian and French institutions to foster innovative, scalable solutions for carbon monitoring, emissions reduction, and sustainable rural development.

Strengthening International Cooperation: CCARBON/USP at the CNRS-USP High-Level Meeting in Paris

Representing CCARBON/USP, Prof. Dr. Carlos Eduardo Cerri, General Director of the center, actively participated in the CNRS–USP High-Level Meeting, in Paris on January 9 and 10, 2025, which brought together senior leadership from the University of São Paulo, the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), and key funding agencies and diplomatic representatives.

Figure 21. Prof. Carlos Eduardo Cerri at the CNRS–USP High-Level Meeting, in Paris. During the meeting, Prof. Cerri delivered a presentation entitled “*Decarbonization in the Agricultural Sector*”, outlining current research strategies and technological innovations developed at CCARBON/USP to support the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions from agricultural systems. His presentation emphasized integrated approaches to low-carbon agriculture and the center’s contribution to advancing climate-smart solutions within tropical production systems.

In addition to the scientific agenda, Prof. Cerri also participated in an institutional gathering hosted at the Brazilian Embassy in Paris, attended by prominent figures including Prof. Carlos Carlotti Junior (Rector of USP), Prof. Marco Antonio Zago (President of FAPESP), Fernando Menezes de Almeida (FAPESP Administrative Director), André Maciel (Minister-Counselor to the Brazilian Ambassador in France), and other representatives from Brazilian and French academic institutions.

Figure 22. Prof. Cerri at the Brazilian Embassy in Paris

This mission was a key milestone in the institutional internationalization strategy of CCARBON/USP. It reaffirmed the center's role as a scientific and diplomatic bridge between Brazil and France in the areas of sustainable agriculture, carbon monitoring, and climate adaptation. The meetings provided an opportunity to review the progress made by CCARBON/USP since its foundation, highlight the relevance of its research agenda, and outline strategic pathways for long-term collaboration under joint funding schemes and academic exchange programs.

Through its continuous engagement in international dialogue and joint initiatives, CCARBON/USP reinforces its commitment to science-based climate action, contributing not only to national priorities but also to global efforts aimed at fostering resilient, productive, and low-emission agricultural systems.

Advocacy actions at the municipal, state, national, and international levels

CCARBON/USP actively engages in multi-level advocacy initiatives, from municipal to international arenas. By providing scientific evidence, technical expertise, and case studies from tropical agriculture, the center supports the design and implementation of policies that contribute to climate change mitigation, adaptation, and sustainable development. Table 1 summarizes the key initiatives and highlights how CCARBON/USP can strengthen and add value to each of them

Table 1. Advocacy actions at the municipal, state, national, and international levels

Level	Initiatives / Examples	CCARBON/USP Role
Municipal	Parliamentary Front to Combat Climate Crisis; Piracicaba Municipal Environmental Council	Provide local scientific evidence, support municipal councils, and engage stakeholders
State	São Paulo State Climate Change Council	Contribute expertise on carbon sequestration, agriculture, and sustainability policies
National	PNCPD – National Program for the Conversion of Degraded Pastures	Provide data and methodologies on pasture restoration and integrated production systems
National	Brazil's Climate Plan; Brazil's NDC; MonitorAgro; National Intelligence Agency	Support with monitoring tools, databases, and policy recommendations on agriculture and emissions
National	National strategies for resilience and/or adaptation in public policies to combat climate change	Offer technical input for resilience indicators and socio-environmental adaptation strategies
National	Agriculture as an option for adaptation and mitigation of global climate change; Ecosystem services; Forest management; Decision-making frameworks	Develop applied research and tools to measure ecosystem services and climate mitigation potential
International	IICA (Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture)	Share Brazilian case studies and collaborate in hemispheric networks of agriculture and carbon
International	CIRCASA (Coordination of International Research Cooperation on Soil Carbon Sequestration in Agriculture)	Contribute USP research on tropical soils and carbon to international soil networks
International	FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations)	Provide scientific basis for FAO global reports and agricultural sustainability frameworks
International	COP30 (UN Climate Change Conference 2025)	Advocate with scientific evidence from CCARBON/USP research to inform international negotiations
International	Estimates of soil carbon sequestration potential in agricultural soils (334 Mha in the Americas; 13.1 ± 7.1 Pg CO ₂ eq in 20 years)	Disseminate CCARBON's research data and methodologies to global assessments and IPCC-related studies

5.4 Training

The previous report presented two events organized by CCARBON/USP, the 1st CCARBON/USP Symposium: Integrating scales, expertise and scientific approaches in carbon studies ([1st Carbon Symposium | Escola Superior de Agricultura "Luiz de Queiroz"](#)) and the CCARBON/USP Soil Health Symposium: from the field to the socioeconomic and political perspectives ([CCarbon Soil health Symposium: from the field to the socioeconomical and political perspectives | Escola Superior de Agricultura "Luiz de Queiroz"](#)), in addition to the online course Low Carbon Agriculture, taught by Professors Carlos Eduardo P. Cerri and Maurício R. Cherubin ([Série de Cursos em Agricultura de Baixo Carbono](#)). Following these activities, CCARBON/USP participated in the organization of five additional events, which are listed and described below.

5.4.1 VII International Workshop on Land Use Policy and Governance and VI Seminar on Water Resources Sustainability

The VII International Workshop on Land Use Policy and Governance and the VI Seminar on Water Resources Sustainability were held jointly in Piracicaba at the "Luiz de Queiroz" College of Agriculture (Esalq), on December 5th and 6th, 2024. The event was held in the historic congregation hall of Esalq's main building and brought together researchers, policymakers, jurists, industry leaders, and public managers. The primary goal was to foster actionable proposals for the sustainable management of natural resources. Key discussions revolved around soil management practices, land use policies, and water resource governance. Participants also explored innovative research and policy solutions for integrating soil and water management with sustainability goals. The event served as a platform to connect the target audience with leading experts and stakeholders in agriculture and environmental sustainability. The event was organized by the Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture at the University of São Paulo (CCARBON/USP), the Luiz de Queiroz Foundation for Agricultural Studies (Fealq), and the Land Use Policy Research Group (PolUS). It was supported by Fealq, Esalq, USP, the Soil Health & Management Research Group (SOHMA), the Foundation for Teaching and Research in Uberaba (FUNEP), the Public Prosecutor's Office of the State of Minas Gerais (MPMG), and the São Paulo State University "Júlio de Mesquita Filho." The event had a total of 176 registered participants, with 87 attending in person. During the welcome coffee at 8:30 a.m. and the breaks between discussions, six research posters or thematic research lines from different participating institutions were presented. The opening session began at 9:30 a.m. on December 5th and was chaired by Prof. Carlos Eduardo Cerri. Representatives from various institutions formed the panel, including Carlos Alberto Valera, Ivan Carneiro Castanheiro, Alexandra Frachioli, Marília, Marcelo Fonseca, Nanci Thame, Maria de Lourdes Mendonça Santos Bredin and Maria Eugênia Escobar.

Figure 23. Opening section VII International Workshop on Land Use Policy and Governance and VI Seminar on Water Resources Sustainability

Additional information regarding this event is available in the document accessible via the following Drive link: [FAPESP Report-VII International Workshop](#)

5.4.2 International Workshop on Microbial Ecology and Biogeochemistry

The International Workshop on Microbial Ecology and Biogeochemistry was held on March 20, 2025, from 8:00 a.m. to 5:00 p.m. at Ceres Room – Central Building, ESALQ/USP, bringing together leading national and international researchers to discuss recent advances in microbial ecology, soil biogeochemical processes, and their relevance to sustainable agriculture. The event was supported by the Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture (CCARBON/USP) and provided an important platform for scientific exchange and collaboration. The opening session featured keynote presentations by renowned researchers including Prof. Carlos Eduardo P. Cerri (Director of CCARBON/USP and Professor at the Department of Soil Science – ESALQ/USP), Dr. Graeme Nicol (Director of Research at CNRS and former AXA Chair in Microbial Ecology at École Centrale de Lyon), Dr. Christina Hazard (Specialist in soil microbial community dynamics and biogeochemical cycles), and Dr. Gerd Gleixner (Group Leader at the Max Planck Institute for Biogeochemistry), among others. The morning sessions also included contributions from Dr. Lucas Pecci Canisares, Postdoctoral Researcher in the Soil Health Management Group at ESALQ/USP, whose research focuses on carbon and nitrogen cycling in agricultural systems. In the afternoon, a second session featured talks by national experts such as Prof. Maurício Cherubin (Deputy Director of CCARBON/USP), Prof. Eduardo Mariano (CENA/USP), Prof. Lucas William Mendes (CENA/USP), Prof. Tsai Siu Mui (CENA/USP), and Prof. Simone Raposo Cotta (ESALQ/USP and Associate Researcher at CCARBON/USP). These sessions highlighted ongoing research in microbial ecology, nitrogen use efficiency, and the integration of soil microbiology with agricultural sustainability strategies. The event concluded with oral presentations from researchers and students, followed by open discussions and

networking opportunities. The workshop successfully fostered interdisciplinary dialogue and opened new avenues for cooperation in the study of soil microbial communities and their role in carbon and nitrogen dynamics.

Figure 24. International Workshop on Microbial Ecology and Biogeochemistry
Additional information regarding this event is available in the document accessible via the following Drive links: [FAPESP Report-GN 1-04-2025](#) and [FAPESP Report-CH 01-04-2025](#)

5.4.3 Clima & Sustainability Chair – Seminar Series

On April 15th, 2025, the Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture (CCARBON/USP) participated in the organization and scientific programming of the seminar “*Agriculture and Climate*”, held at Sala Alfredo Bosi, University of São Paulo. This event marked the inaugural edition of the series “*Rethinking Progress: Reflections from Climate Change*”, promoted by the Clima & Sustainability Chair at the Institute of Advanced Studies (IEA-USP). The initiative forms part of the broader climate agenda of the city of São Paulo and contributes to national mobilization efforts in preparation for COP30. The seminar addressed the crucial intersection between climate change and agriculture in Brazil, a country that occupies a prominent position as one of the largest global producers and exporters of food, feed, fiber, and biofuels. While the agricultural sector is among the primary contributors to greenhouse gas emissions, it is also one of the most vulnerable to the adverse effects of global climate change — particularly in tropical regions. The event sought to promote informed discussion on the challenges and opportunities inherent to the sector’s transition toward low-carbon and climate-resilient systems.

Figure 25. Clima & Sustainability Chair – Seminar Series - *Agriculture and Climate*

CCARBON/USP played a central role in the event, with several of its researchers participating as keynote speakers and moderators. Professor Carlos Eduardo P. Cerri, Director of CCARBON/USP, took part in the opening session alongside Professors Marcos Buckeridge, Arlindo Philippi Jr., and Carlos Nobre, representing IEA-USP and the Clima & Sustainability Chair. Professor Cerri also delivered the opening lecture of the first panel, entitled “*Climate Change, International Agreements, and the Impacts on Brazilian Agriculture*”, in which he addressed the global and national implications of climate policies on the sector and emphasized the importance of integrating science and governance. In the second panel, which focused on agriculture as part of the solution to climate change, CCARBON/USP was represented by Professor Maurício Roberto Cherubin, who presented on “*Regenerative Agriculture as a Strategy for Mitigation and Adaptation to Climate Change*”. His talk explored sustainable land-use practices aimed at enhancing soil health and increasing carbon sequestration. Additionally, Professor Pedro Henrique Santin Brancalion delivered a lecture on “*Forest Restoration as a Nature-Based Solution – Brazil’s Opportunities*”, underlining the strategic role of ecological restoration in national and global climate agendas. This session was moderated by Professor Tiago Osorio Ferreira, who also joined the closing session to summarize the main conclusions and reinforce the need for cross-sectoral collaboration. CCARBON/USP’s engagement in the seminar reflects its ongoing commitment to supporting science-based public policy and advancing interdisciplinary research in tropical agricultural systems. By contributing to this high-level dialogue, the Center reaffirmed its institutional role in addressing the urgent challenges of climate change

through sustainable innovation, academic excellence, and public engagement. More information about the event, including the full program and access to recorded presentations, is available at: <https://www.iea.usp.br/eventos/agricultura-clima>

5.4.4 DecisionES 2025 Symposium

Between June 30 and July 4, 2025, the Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture (CCARBON/USP) actively contributed to the organization and institutional support of the international symposium *DecisionES 2025: Decision Analytic Framework to Explore the Ecosystem Services Space*, held in Porto Seguro, Bahia, Brazil. The event was promoted by the International Union of Forest Research Organizations (IUFRO) and brought together scientists, professionals, and policymakers engaged in ecosystem services, forest management, and sustainable land-use planning in tropical regions. As one of the institutional supporters, CCARBON/USP collaborated in the coordination and dissemination of the event, reinforcing its commitment to advancing interdisciplinary research and fostering science-based decision-making for climate and environmental governance.

Professor Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, Director of CCARBON/USP, participated as a keynote speaker, presenting the lecture “*Challenges for Soil Carbon Measurement, Reporting and Verification*”. The presentation addressed critical technical and institutional aspects related to soil carbon quantification in the context of climate mitigation. Key challenges discussed included methodological uncertainties, the scalability of MRV (Measurement, Reporting, and Verification) systems in tropical environments, and the need for integrated policies to ensure transparency and environmental integrity in carbon accounting frameworks.

Figure 26. Professor Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri, Director of CCARBON/USP and keynote speaker at the event

The symposium's scientific program included plenary sessions, oral and poster presentations, thematic roundtables, and a technical field visit. The event provided a multidisciplinary platform for dialogue on how decision-analytic frameworks can guide ecosystem management and climate action, particularly in countries with high biodiversity and carbon stock potential, such as Brazil. CCARBON/USP's involvement in DecisionES 2025 reaffirmed its institutional role as a reference center in the development of solutions for tropical agriculture and climate resilience. The center's participation contributed to strengthening international cooperation networks and disseminating scientific knowledge aligned with global sustainability agendas. More information about the event, including the full program and access to recorded presentations, is available at: <https://decisiones.github.io/en/>

5.4.5 Latin American and Caribbean Symposium on Soil Carbon Research (LAC Soil Carbon)

From June 25-28, 2025, the Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture (CCARBON/USP) actively participated in the organization and scientific coordination of the first edition of the *Latin American and Caribbean Symposium on Soil Carbon Research (LAC Soil Carbon)*. The event was held with the aim of promoting the relevance of soil carbon in the context of sustainable agriculture, soil health, food security, and

climate change mitigation across Latin America and the Caribbean. The symposium was jointly organized by the Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation (Embrapa), CCARBON/USP, the Federal University of Goiás (UFG), the ILPF Network Association, and the National Institute of Science and Technology for Low-Carbon Agriculture (INCT-ABC). The initiative was further co-organized and endorsed by the international platforms “4 per 1000” and the *International Soil Carbon Research Consortium (IRC)*, reinforcing its global scope and collaborative nature. Over the course of three days, the event gathered a diverse audience of researchers, students, policymakers, farmers, technicians, entrepreneurs, and civil society representatives. The program was designed to foster the exchange of experiences, innovative practices, and scientific advances in soil carbon management, as well as to discuss challenges and opportunities for scaling up sustainable land-use strategies throughout the region. CCARBON/USP contributed to the event both institutionally and scientifically. As a co-organizing institution, the center played a key role in curating the thematic structure of the symposium, bringing forward its expertise in tropical soil carbon dynamics, sustainable agricultural intensification, and measurement, reporting, and verification (MRV) systems for soil-based carbon sequestration. The symposium provided a multilingual environment with simultaneous interpretation in English, Spanish, and Portuguese, ensuring accessibility and inclusive participation. Through high-level plenary talks, technical sessions, and open forums, the event created a collaborative space to strengthen science-policy dialogue and regional cooperation toward climate-resilient and soil-conscious food systems. CCARBON/USP’s involvement in LAC Soil Carbon reaffirmed its mission to serve as a regional and international reference in science-based strategies for sustainable tropical agriculture. By contributing to the event’s structure and content, the center reinforced its institutional commitment to soil carbon research, environmental stewardship, and the promotion of low-carbon agricultural development. Further information about the symposium, including the full program and updates, is available at: <https://eventos.galao.com.br/scs-2025/page/5549-home>

Figure 27. Director’s Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri and Mauricio R. Cherubin at the LAC event.

5.4.6 Next events:

XII Workshop on Forest Restoration

Figure 28. Promotional image of the XII Workshop on Forest Restoration

CCARBON/USP is actively contributing to the organization of the XII Workshop on Forest Restoration, to be held from August 28 to 30, 2025, at the Engineering Auditorium of the Luiz de Queiroz College of Agriculture (Esalq/USP). This event is one of Brazil's most important scientific forums focused on ecological restoration and will bring together researchers, professionals, policymakers, and students to exchange knowledge and experiences on large-scale forest recovery.

The main focus of the workshop is to present technologies and innovations for large-scale forest restoration, with a special emphasis on the role of carbon credits as an enabling mechanism. The program will address key topics such as the carbon market, socioeconomic aspects, and public policies related to restoration. Notable invited speakers include representatives from the Verified Carbon Standard (Verra) and the Atlantic Forest Restoration Pact.

The CCARBON/USP team is supporting the development of the event by helping curate the scientific and strategic content, identifying themes that align with the center's mission, such as climate resilience, biodiversity, and carbon sequestration and coordinating dissemination efforts to ensure broad participation. By engaging in the planning of this workshop, CCARBON/USP reinforces its role in promoting dialogue

between science, policy, and society, and in advancing evidence-based solutions to environmental challenges.

Registrations are open through the Fealq website: <https://fealq.org.br/eventos/xii-workshop-sobre-restauracao-florestal>.

3rd CCARBON/USP Symposium – Sustainable and Resilient Livestock

The CCARBON/USP team is actively involved in the planning and organization of the 3rd CCARBON/USP Symposium – Sustainable and Resilient Livestock: Ecological Strategies for Climate Mitigation and Biodiversity Conservation, scheduled to take place in November 2025 at the Engineering Auditorium of ESALQ/USP in Piracicaba, Brazil. This third edition of the symposium will focus on addressing the major challenges and opportunities of livestock systems in the context of climate change, promoting resilient, regenerative, and low-carbon production models.

The event will bring together national and international experts, including Dr. Camillo DeCamillis (FAO/GASL), and is expected to host around 200 participants, including researchers, students, professionals in the agricultural sector, and representatives from public and private institutions. The program will include keynote lectures, roundtable discussions, and a scientific poster session, facilitating the integration of science, innovation, and field practices.

Key themes will cover ecological pasture management, silvopastoral systems, carbon sequestration, biodiversity conservation, ecosystem services, traceability, and public policies for emission mitigation in livestock systems. Positioned as a pre-COP30 event, the symposium also aims to enhance international dialogue and visibility, aligning with global climate commitments.

CCARBON/USP is leading the scientific coordination and communication strategy for the event and has played a key role in resource mobilization. To date, R\$ 12,112.00 has been secured through the USP Office of Research and Innovation (PRPI/USP), primarily allocated for speaker travel and accommodation. Additional sponsorships and institutional partnerships are currently being pursued to meet the estimated budget of R\$ 44,943.80, necessary to ensure the full execution of the symposium.

Beyond content planning, the CCARBON/USP team is also responsible for the design of promotional materials, social media campaigns, and institutional outreach to potential supporters, including stakeholders from the agricultural, carbon, and sustainability sectors. Through the promotion of this symposium, CCARBON/USP reaffirms its commitment to science-based outreach, collaborative networks, and nature-based solutions to address the environmental and climate challenges of tropical livestock systems.

10th International Symposium on Soil Organic Matter

CCARBON/USP is leading the organization of the 10th International Symposium on Soil Organic Matter (SOM 2026), one of the world's most important conferences focused on soil organic matter. The event will take place from May 25 to 29, 2026, at the International Diffusion Center of the University of São Paulo (CDI/USP). This will be the first edition of the symposium held in South America, marking a historic moment for global soil science and reinforcing Brazil's leadership in sustainability, soil carbon research, and climate change mitigation.

The symposium will gather hundreds of students, researchers, agricultural professionals, policymakers, and industry representatives. The scientific program includes six plenary sessions, sixteen parallel thematic sessions, two poster sessions, and a field trip day with technical visits to cutting-edge agricultural and research sites in São Paulo, Campinas, São Carlos, and Piracicaba. In addition, the event will feature the SOM Awards, which will highlight the best oral and poster presentations and encourage engagement from early-career researchers.

With the central theme "SOM: The Nexus of Healthy Soils and Sustainable Future", SOM 2026 will address critical topics such as land use and soil productivity, SOM dynamics across climates and ecosystems, monitoring technologies, SOM and food security, carbon sequestration, climate change mitigation, public-private partnerships, and the role of organic matter in building soil resilience.

The symposium will host an exceptional lineup of internationally renowned keynote speakers, including:

- Dr. Rattan Lal (The Ohio State University, USA) – Nobel Peace Prize laureate (2007, IPCC) and a leading voice in soil carbon and sustainable agriculture.
- Prof. Pete Smith (University of Aberdeen, UK) – Expert on greenhouse gas mitigation in agriculture and food systems.
- Prof. Charles Rice (Kansas State University, USA) – Leading research on SOM and ecosystem services.
- Prof. Budiman Minasny (University of Sydney, Australia) – Specialist in digital soil mapping and soil carbon modeling.
- Prof. Francesca Cotrufo (Colorado State University, USA) – Researcher on SOM formation and plant-soil interactions.
- Prof. Johane Whalen (McGill University, Canada / Mohammed VI Polytechnic University, Morocco) – Known for her work on soil biodiversity and nutrient cycling.
- Prof. Mariangela Hungria (Embrapa Soja, Brazil) – A global reference in biological nitrogen fixation and soil microbiology.
- Dr. Martial Bernoux (FAO/UN) – Expert in sustainable land use and global carbon accounting.
- Prof. Carlos Eduardo Cerri (CCARBON/USP, Brazil) – Pioneer in SOM dynamics in tropical systems and scientific leader of CCARBON/USP.

These speakers represent a diverse array of scientific perspectives and geographic regions, ensuring a rich and inclusive dialogue on the role of soil organic matter in addressing global sustainability challenges.

The CCARBON/USP team is deeply involved in every phase of the event's development, from scientific planning and speaker engagement to communication and logistics coordination. The venue reservation at CDI/USP is confirmed, and the event is currently in the sponsorship acquisition phase, offering partnership packages in Bronze, Silver, Gold, Diamond, and Platinum tiers. These tiers provide a range of visibility and engagement opportunities for supporting institutions.

So far, funding has been secured from CNPq, and additional support is being sought from FAPESP, Agrisus Foundation, and private sector sponsors. The total estimated budget is R\$ 1,000,000.00, covering venue, speaker travel and accommodation, audiovisual and interpretation services, printed materials, outreach campaigns, field trip logistics, and participant amenities.

By hosting SOM 2026, Brazil will not only elevate its visibility in the global scientific community but also strengthen international collaboration and innovation in soil and climate research. The symposium is fully aligned with the mission of CCARBON/USP as a FAPESP CEPID, supporting science-driven solutions to accelerate sustainability in tropical agriculture and beyond.

Figure 29. Flyer of the save the date and information for SOM 2026.

5.5 Educarbon

Educarbon is an educational program developed by the Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture at the University of São Paulo (CCARBON/USP), aimed at capacity building and knowledge dissemination on innovative nature-based solutions, with the goal of promoting sustainable tropical agriculture, transitioning to a low-carbon economy, and addressing the challenges posed by climate change.

The program is aligned with CCARBON/USP's dissemination strategy, which seeks to act as an agent of social transformation, based on solid and comprehensive scientific knowledge about the effects of climate change and how to reconcile the growing demand for food, fiber, and energy with environmental, economic, and social sustainability. Therefore, Educarbon seeks to establish connections with society through different fronts of action: Educarbon Schools, Training, and Innovation (Figure 30).

Figure 30. Official Educarbon logo.

Educarbon Schools: It aims to strengthen environmental education through a participatory methodology, by approaching elementary and high schools, both public and private. It also seeks the involvement of the local community, promoting interactive, playful, and participatory activities.

As an initial step, an architectural project was carried out aimed at the renovation, expansion, and modernization of the Educarbon station - formerly Ponte Solo na Escola, at ESALQ/USP(<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1qsv4259LiB-ehInGO8jxFIuJrRFImS8D?usp=sharing>).

The development of the architectural project for the Educarbon station was a process that involved:

- Mapping the needs of the environmental education program.
- Translating scientific concepts into clear guidelines for the space's design.
- Technical meetings to ensure synergy between the researchers' vision and the architectural execution.
- Monitoring and validation of all stages, from the initial sketch to the final executive project.

Among the activities planned for the Educarbon station are: the production of pedagogical support materials, promoting middle and high school visits, conducting workshops, educational and interactive games, production of didactic materials, training with public school teachers, among others. Parallel to these initiatives, there will be communication management on social networks and social impact assessment of the promoted actions.

This strategy seeks to strengthen the bond between university and society, promoting democratic access to scientific knowledge and stimulating critical reflection on contemporary environmental challenges, especially those related to climate change. Below are some activities that have already been executed and some are still under planning:

- **Teacher training course**

In July 2025, a free online course was conducted for elementary, middle, and high school teachers. In general, the objective was to instruct them about the fundamentals of Climate Change (definition, causes, and consequences); to enable them to teach about climate change in schools effectively and engagingly (through active methodologies), in addition to encouraging the implementation of sustainable projects and actions both in schools and communities. On the last day of training, the teachers were asked to develop a thematic network (an approach that organizes the curriculum around central themes,

making the topic of climate change more meaningful and contextualized in the classroom). They were also asked to create a lesson plan and an interdisciplinary project related to the theme of climate change in schools.

The course had a workload of 30 hours and 50 spots were made available, which included registrations from teachers from various states in Brazil.

- **Production of materials for environmental education**

The planning and subsequent production of materials for environmental education are underway, focusing on making scientific content more accessible and engaging for diverse audiences, especially children and adolescents. Among the materials being developed are educational games aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), board games with environmental themes, and the creation of comic books and children's/young adult books about climate change, sustainability, and nature-based solutions (NBS).

These products play a fundamental role in scientific dissemination by promoting public understanding and engagement with complex themes, using playful, visual language adapted to different age groups. By integrating science, education, and creativity, the project is expected to broaden the reach and impact of its actions, contributing to the formation of a scientific and environmental culture from the early school years, as well as strengthening the dialogue between the university, schools, and communities.

- **World Soil Day - Event**

An event open to the community will be held to celebrate World Soil Day (12/05/2025), aiming to raise community awareness about the importance of soil as an essential natural resource, encourage active community participation in sustainability and environmental conservation actions, and foster dialogue between different generations on environmental issues.

The following activities will be carried out:

Interactive Exhibitions:

- I. Soil in Our Hands: A tactile and visual exhibition on different soil types, their composition, and the microscopic life that inhabits them.
- II. Soil and Climate, a Vital Connection: Informative panels and multimedia displays explaining how soil influences climate and how climate change affects soil.
- III. Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) in Action: Visual and interactive examples of how nature can help us combat climate change, such as reforestation, sustainable agriculture, and green roofs.

Creative Workshops:

- I. Gardening in Small Spaces: A practical workshop on how to create a home garden, even in apartments, using recycled materials and explaining the importance of soil for food cultivation.

II. Home Composting: Demonstration and explanation on how to compost at home, transforming organic waste into fertilizer for the soil.

Painting with Soil Pigments:

Using natural pigments extracted from different types of soil, children will have the opportunity to explore the textures and colors of the soil. Additionally, they will be encouraged to create a connection with the soil and learn about this resource in a playful and engaging way.

Educarbon Training: This program aims to train professionals in the carbon market and Nature-Based Solutions (NbS) through specialization courses and training programs (offered both in-person and online), all with certification from the University of São Paulo (USP). The goal is to help companies develop their workforce and build highly qualified teams prepared to meet the sector's challenges and seize its opportunities. The courses will be delivered by professionals with solid expertise in Nature-Based Solutions, combining both scientific knowledge and practical experience in the development and implementation of environmental policies and practices.

In accordance with the University of São Paulo regulations, the courses will be offered in the following categories (<https://www5.usp.br/extensao/cursos-de-extensao/>):

- **Advanced Training:** minimum of 180 hours.
- **Extension Course:** 30 to 120 hours.
- **Outreach Course:** minimum of 8 hours.

More information and examples of course formats are available at the link below:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1rv17A1tKdOnVgUpEeh0WZBV-33P9ZIr0?usp=drive_link

Educarbon Innovation:

This initiative aims to stimulate innovation within CCARBON/USP by training researchers to transform scientific knowledge into impactful businesses. Through strategic training programs, it seeks to foster the creation of startups and scientific spin-offs with USP DNA, focused on delivering innovative solutions for a low-carbon economy.

To achieve this goal, strategic partnerships are being established with [SEBRAE](#) and the [USP Innovation Agency](#). In the case of SEBRAE, the collaboration aims to promote the creation of new businesses and value chains based on Nature-Based Solutions (NbS), leveraging SEBRAE's expertise in business modeling, market access, and management—complementing CCARBON/USP's strong scientific foundation. This partnership is expected to facilitate the dissemination of technologies and methodologies developed by CCARBON/USP to micro and small enterprises, promoting social innovation and enabling large-scale adoption of sustainable practices.

In addition, SEBRAE and CCARBON/USP are developing strategies to design courses and training programs focused on the practical application of NbS in the environmental management of rural and urban micro and small enterprises. Another key strategy involves the partnership between CCARBON/USP and the USP Innovation Agency. Research conducted by CCARBON/USP often generates innovative methodologies, tools, software, and processes related to NbS. In this context, the USP Innovation Agency plays a crucial role in identifying, protecting (through patents and registrations), and managing this intellectual property, ensuring that the knowledge produced is properly valued and can be licensed or strategically applied. The agency also serves as a bridge between academic research and the market, facilitating technology licensing and fostering partnerships with companies for the development and large-scale implementation of NbS.

Next Steps – Webinar Series

As part of the next steps planned by Educarbon, a series of thematic webinars will be developed to expand the center’s science communication and outreach efforts. These online events will serve as a platform to share research findings, foster dialogue among researchers, public managers, businesses, and civil society, and promote knowledge exchange on sustainable and low-carbon development.

The webinars will focus on topics such as Nature-based Solutions (NbS), climate change mitigation, sustainable land use, innovation, and public policy. They will be free and open to a broad audience, including students, professionals, and decision-makers, and will be recorded and made available online to maximize reach and impact. This initiative reinforces CCARBON/USP commitment to scaling up the dissemination of knowledge and supporting capacity-building across different sectors.

Digital medias

The first step was to align and organize the communication strategy with the team. To ensure that objectives were met, it was essential to define and plan content production, create a posting schedule for social media, and track results through engagement metrics (reach, interactions, views).

A structured plan was developed to gather relevant information—such as research updates, news, events, and other topics—to be shared via digital channels. As part of this effort, the email dissemination.ccarbon@usp.br and the WhatsApp number +55 19 99924-5577 were created and shared with CCARBON/USP researchers so they could send updates (including publications, event participation, and media mentions) directly to the dissemination team.

LinkedIn and Instagram

The social media profiles (Instagram and LinkedIn) were launched on September 17, 2024, as part of the CCARBON/USP dissemination team’s efforts. Since then, all

content has been produced and managed by the team, including bilingual posts in English and Portuguese, as well as the development of layout and illustrations.

A publication schedule was created with a goal of three to five posts per week on average, respecting the relevance and dates of the materials to be disseminated, as well as the availability of members from the writing and design teams. To assist in organizing the process and meeting the established goal, the project management tool Trello was used. For organizing and tracking posts, a board was created for the team with lists indicating the stages of preparation, progress, and completion of tasks. Additionally, each post was organized into specific cards containing checklists, deadlines, attachments, and labels, allowing for more efficient tracking and facilitating collaboration among team members. To assess the performance metrics of LinkedIn, and Instagram, tools such as mLabs, Instagram Insights, and LinkedIn Analytics are being used. These tools allow the collection of detailed data on traffic, engagement, and audience growth. So far, key performance indicators (KPIs) have been analyzed, covering the months from September 2024 to August 2025. The growth of followers and the demographic data of the audience are also being monitored to adjust content strategies. Based on these analyses, reports are being generated that compare results over time and identify behavior trends, allowing for the optimization of future actions based on solid, measurable data. On social media, LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/ccarbonusp/posts/?feedView=all>) and Instagram (<https://www.instagram.com/ccarbon.usp/>), 172 posts have been made so far on various topics related to the center, including news, paper publications, content from the website, dissemination of opportunities (competitions and scholarships), and events.

LinkedIn Performance Metrics

The main LinkedIn KPIs correspond to 1) number of followers and engagement rate, which is the sum of likes, comments, and shares divided by the total impressions; 2) reach and impressions, an important indicator to assess the visibility of posts.

Number of followers and engagement

Engagement and follower growth on LinkedIn are essential indicators for evaluating the impact of digital communication strategies. Engagement reflects the level of interaction the audience has with the posts, demonstrating the interest and relevance of the content shared, while the increase in followers shows the expanded reach of the page and the strengthening of the community around the topics discussed. Analyzing the best posts and the growth of CCARBON/USP's followers on LinkedIn allows the identification of interaction patterns and the refinement of strategies to amplify the dissemination of information about sustainability, research, and innovation in agriculture. The graph (Figure 31) shows a continuous growth in the follower base between September 2024 and August 2025, reflecting the impact of digital communication and engagement strategies.

Figure 31. Evolution of the number of followers of CCARBON/USP over time

The steady growth in the number of followers on LinkedIn (Figure 31) reflects the positive impact of the content shared on the platform. Between September 2024 and July 2025, the number of followers increased from approximately 1,200 to nearly 5,000 — a growth of over 300%. This upward trend demonstrates that the communication strategy is effectively engaging the target audience and attracting professionals interested in the topics addressed by CCARBON/USP. The significant increase in followers suggests a strong alignment between the content published and the expectations of the audience, with scientific posts, updates on research, and outreach initiatives likely contributing to this result. If maintained, this expansion can strengthen networking opportunities, partnerships, and visibility, amplifying the impact of the platform's presence. The consistent growth also highlights the importance of maintaining a strategic and regular posting schedule, and it serves as a foundation for further improving engagement and reaching new audiences in Brazil and internationally.

Figure 32. Performance of CCARBON/USP's best posts based on organic engagement

The graph (Figure 32) presents an overview of the performance of CCARBON/USP's best-performing posts based on organic engagement, considering impressions, shares, comments, and likes. The orange line representing impressions shows a pattern of peaks and drops, with several posts reaching over 200 impressions while others remain below 100. Despite the variation in visibility, likes (green bars) remain consistently high, indicating that the audience is generally receptive to the content shared. In terms of post timing, the data reveals that content published in the afternoon or early evening, especially around 15h, 17h, and 18h, tends to perform better. This suggests that these time slots are potentially optimal for engaging with CCARBON/USP's audience and could be prioritized in future content planning.

However, the overall variation in timing also indicates that the audience is responsive throughout the day, making it valuable to test different scheduling strategies to maintain or boost engagement over time. Looking at the broader trends observed in previous months, interaction peaks were also identified in September, October, and January. These periods coincided with the publication of content related to institutional themes and strategic collaborations, suggesting that these topics tend to drive higher reach and engagement. This reinforces the importance of aligning scientific communication efforts with key institutional milestones and partnerships. Another relevant aspect is the influence of post formats on engagement.

As previously analyzed, posts featuring visual elements, especially those with images of people, such as CCARBON's directors and renowned researchers, as well as carousel formats, tend to generate greater attention and engagement. In contrast, posts that include only illustrative images from papers and technical information, generally receive lower levels of interaction. This trend likely continued during the period shown in the graph and should be considered when planning future content strategies. Overall, the analysis of CCARBON/USP's top-performing posts highlights the effectiveness of visually engaging content and the value of strategic scheduling. The data also reinforces

the role of institutional relevance in boosting interaction. Ongoing monitoring of these patterns will be essential to refine communication strategies and ensure consistent public engagement with the center's scientific and institutional messages. Figure 33 presents a comparison between these formats, highlighting those that generated the highest organic engagement.

Figure 33. Performance of Different Types of CCARBON/USP Posts on LinkedIn Based on Organic Engagement

Figure 33 presents an analysis of the performance of CCARBON/USP posts on LinkedIn based on organic engagement, comparing different publication formats. Carousel posts stand out as the most effective type, with the highest average engagement rate (close to 20%) and a high average number of interactions (97), indicating a strong preference from the audience for dynamic and interactive content. Posts featuring standalone images also showed excellent performance, registering the highest average number of interactions (97), though with a lower engagement rate (7.19%) when compared to carousels. Text-based posts achieved a similar number of interactions (51) to posts with links, but with slightly better engagement (9.68% vs. 6.58%), suggesting moderate audience interest. Posts containing only links recorded the lowest engagement indicators overall, both in average interactions (51) and engagement rate (5.68%), reinforcing the trend that such formats are less appealing to the audience. These results highlight the importance of using carousels and visual elements, especially those involving people, as part of an effective strategy to enhance reach and foster interaction with CCARBON/USP's content on LinkedIn.

Reach and Impressions

In the context of LinkedIn, impressions represent the number of times a post was shown to users, while reach is related to the number of unique people who viewed the

content. In the updated impressions graph of CCARBON/USP LinkedIn posts from August 2024 to August 2025 (Figure 34), the blue line represents organic impressions, which totaled 375,683 during the period. There were no impressions from sponsored posts. The data shows a significant peak at the beginning of October, followed by fluctuations over the months, with smaller peaks observed in December, February, and June.

Figure 34. Graph of Impressions of CCARBON/USP LinkedIn Posts from September 2024 to August 2025

There is a steady increase until early October, when the number of impressions peaks close to 55,000. From this point, the impressions fluctuate: there is a noticeable drop in November, a recovery in December and January, followed by a gradual decrease until April. After that, impressions rise again in June, before dropping sharply in August. This pattern may indicate seasonal variations in audience engagement or the impact of changes in posting strategies. Additionally, all impressions were organic, with no investment in sponsored posts, which highlights the importance of consistent posting and high-quality content to maintain visibility.

Instagram performance metrics

The main Instagram KPIs are: 1) reach, which refers to the number of unique accounts that viewed the published content; 2) interactions, which include the number of likes, comments, shares, and saves.

Reach of the posts and interactions

With a total of 173 posts and 1,283 followers at the time of preparing this report, the CCARBON/USP Instagram profile has not yet achieved as significant engagement as its LinkedIn counterpart, where the organic reach of posts has been more substantial. However, the platform remains an important tool for the dissemination of scientific and institutional content. Figure 35(A) shows the reach data for CCARBON/USP's Instagram, with the main performance indicators from the last 90 days, including views, reach, and the impact of different content types.

Figure 35. (A) Reach and views data for CCARBON/USP's Instagram from May 8 to August 05 (B) Instagram interaction data for CCARBON/USP from May 8 to August 05

The total number of views was 103,344, with 70.2% from followers and 29.8% from non-followers. The number of accounts reached was 15,730, representing a 171.0% increase compared to the previous period. Regarding the type of content, feed posts were responsible for the majority of views (77.1%), while stories contributed 21.4% and reels were 1.5%. The Instagram interactions chart for CCARBON/USP, covering the period from May 8 to August 5, shows a total of 3,579 interactions, with the vast majority 93.5% coming from followers, while only 6.5% came from non-followers (Fig. 13B). The number of accounts that actually interacted with the content was 743, indicating a relatively low level of engagement compared to the overall reach. Regarding content type, posts were responsible for 79.2% of the interactions, while stories contributed 18.5% and

reels with 2.2%. These data highlight the need for strategies aimed at increasing engagement, particularly among non-followers, and diversifying content formats to boost interaction with the audience.

Final Considerations on LinkedIn and Instagram metrics

Despite not yet reaching the desired scale, the CCARBON/USP digital media platforms have been establishing themselves as effective communication channels for disseminating research, events, and institutional collaborations. Performance on LinkedIn shows significant reach, while Instagram, despite lower engagement, remains a relevant platform for increasing the center's visibility. The results presented in this report will serve as a foundation to improve communication strategies in the next steps, aiming to strengthen digital presence and expand the impact of CCARBON/USP initiatives.

Activities in Initial Implementation

A personalized communication strategy has been established with each researcher at the center to help the public learn more about their ongoing activities. For this activity, the topics that fit into the complex issues related to carbon and the impacts of climate change on agriculture, initially described in the proposal, will be broken down. Each researcher has been contacted individually by the fellow, who will present a proposal to promote their research line on the website and social media. This strategy aims to bring the researcher closer to the center's dissemination team, as well as encourage them to share their activities with the team for promotional purposes. The use of paid traffic for promoting courses is an effective strategy that is planned for the next stages of the center's outreach. By investing in social media ads and search platforms, it is possible to target communication to reach a broader and more segmented audience quickly and accurately.

Next Steps for LinkedIn and Instagram

To continue strengthening the communication of CCARBON/USP, the next steps will focus on expanding the reach and engagement of digital media, as well as developing new strategies for scientific dissemination. Planned actions include the continuous promotion of project updates and educational materials, ensuring that the center's research reaches a broader audience. Additionally, a review and optimization of social media content will be conducted, focusing on strategic editing and publishing to increase visibility. Finally, a specific communication action with CCARBON/USP researchers is planned, encouraging their active participation in production and sharing of scientific content. With the creation of CCARBONcast and the interviews it will feature a greater number of videos, including short-form content such as Reels, will also be produced and shared across CCARBON/USP's social media platforms, aiming to broaden public engagement and diversify the formats used in outreach.

With the closure of new strategic partnerships between the center and major public and private institutions, we will share the mission of promoting innovation and

sustainable development through outreach materials. Another action that will be part of the dissemination content strategies is the Educarbon project. This project is an innovative initiative aimed at raising awareness and knowledge about the importance of sustainable agricultural practices in combating climate change. Through new strategic partnerships, CCARBON/USP plans to expand its educational actions, covering various age groups and levels of learning, from elementary to continuing education at the graduate level. This initiative will require additional actions on the center's social media, with the need to expand its outreach efforts to different audiences. In addition, regular publications will continue on social media with relevant content for the target audience, utilizing strategic hashtags to increase visibility.

Podcasts

Over the reporting period, the CCARBON/USP dissemination team made significant progress in developing a science-based, narrative-driven podcast that forms a key component of the center's broader science communication strategy. While the first season has not yet been released, this stage was essential for laying the conceptual and technical foundation of the project.

The podcast is being developed collaboratively by a multidisciplinary team composed of science communicators, recording team and audio editors. This joint effort aims to offer the public a compelling new format for understanding the scientific research and environmental missions aligned with CCARBON/USP's objectives and those of the FAPESP-supported project.

The format adopted is hybrid in nature, combining elements of interview and storytelling. Rather than using a purely informative or journalistic approach, the team is constructing episodes that blend real expert interviews with creative storytelling devices. This decision enhances the emotional and cognitive engagement of the audience while ensuring factual accuracy and scientific integrity.

The structure chosen for the episodes follows the so-called "E format," a narrative structure often used in popular science and investigative podcasts. This technique begins at an advanced point in the story -often the middle or even the end- and then unfolds either chronologically or using a "sandwich" style that alternates between the main narrative and contextual digressions. This dynamic format makes room for complexity while maintaining narrative clarity and flow.

The production process itself followed a multi-stage methodology. Initially, the team conducted thorough bibliographic research and internal discussions to define the scope and tone of the series. This phase was followed by the drafting of episode "maps" or pre-scripts that guided the selection of interviewees and the formulation of interview questions.

Interviews were then recorded, transcribed, and analyzed to identify the most impactful excerpts. Parallel to this, fictional and narrative elements were developed to interweave with real scientific content.

Figure 36. Mariana Pezzatte Pollo interviewing Prof. Rodrigo Hakamada for the CCARBONCast

After completing the scripts, the team recorded the narrations, adjusting tone and pacing through several iterations. These recordings were integrated with interview content and moved into the editing phase, where sound design was used to build an engaging and immersive listening experience.

By the end of this phase, the team had completed three full scripts and recorded a substantial portion of the interview and narration content, also developed the podcast's logo and visual identity, creating a cohesive and recognizable look to support its communication strategy.

Figure 37. CCARBONCast logo

Next steps

For the next steps, the team will focus on finalizing the editing of the episodes, ensuring that narration, interviews, and sound design are fully integrated to create a cohesive and engaging listening experience. Once completed, the first season will be

published alongside visual and written materials that support and expand the content of each episode.

Table 2. Podcast execution planning

Date	Media	Title	Guests	Status
08/20/2025	Podcast	Climate change and CCARBON/USP's performance	Carlos Eduardo P. Cerri	Editing
09/17/2025	Podcast	Soil microbiome and carbon sequestration	Fernando Dini Andreote	Editing
10/08/2025	Podcast	Forest systems: allies in carbon sequestration and GHG reduction	Rodrigo Hakamada	Recording
11/19/2025	Webinar	Sustainable Livestock and Climate Change: From Pasture Management to Enteric Methane	Adibe Luiz Abdalla	
12/17/2025	Podcast	Blue Carbon	Tiago Osório Ferreira	Research
01/21/2026	Podcast	Tropical forests: multiple benefits and resilience	Pedro Brancalion	Research
02/18/2026	Podcast	Climate change scenarios and impacts on Brazilian agriculture	Fábio Marin	Script writing
03/18/2026	Podcast	Integrated Systems	Leidivan Frazão	
04/22/2026	Podcast	Carbon fixation by plants: photosynthesis, genetics and extremophile plants	Helaine Carrer	
05/20/2026	Podcast	Bioenergy (Biochar)	João Luis Nunes Carvalho	
06/17/2026	Podcast	Sustainable ingredients from agro-industrial waste	Thais Maria F. de Souza Vieira	
07/22/2026	Podcast	Reforestation and mitigation of agricultural emissions	Luiz Carlos Estraviz Rodriguez	
08/19/2026	Podcast	High-performance production with greater carbon sequestration	Antonio Augusto F. Garcia	

A strategic communication plan will guide the release schedule and promotional efforts, with regular posts on platforms such as Instagram, LinkedIn, Spotify, and YouTube. These posts will include highlights, short clips, and calls to action designed to attract and engage different audiences. The team will also monitor audience feedback and performance metrics such as number of plays, listening time, and shares to evaluate the podcast's reach and impact, and to inform improvements for future seasons.

This collaborative effort demonstrates not only the team's technical and creative capacity but also the value of integrating storytelling into science communication. The next stage will focus on finalizing editing, launching the first season, and analyzing audience engagement metrics to guide future improvements. These actions are critical for strengthening CCARBON/USP's digital presence and ensuring that the center's mission resonates with academic, technical, and general audiences alike.

5.6 Public Awareness

The CCARBON/USP website, hosted on the USP domain (<https://ccarbon.usp.br/>), was developed by the dissemination team. It features a clean, professional, and easy-to-navigate layout, and functions as a content hub, housing scientific articles, news, and accessible-language texts based on research conducted by the center's scientists. The website will also include updates on projects and educational materials. The scientific article repository is available in the 'Dissemination' section and is updated regularly through a dedicated communication channel with CCARBON/USP researchers.

To monitor traffic and visitor behavior on the website, the main KPIs used were: 1) number of visitors (users and sessions), which determine how many people access the website; 2) average time on page, which assesses the level of audience interest in the content; 3) traffic source, which shows whether visitors arrive through organic search, social media, paid ads, or direct access.

Over the past 90 days, the website recorded approximately 3.4K visitors, representing a 61.6% increase compared to the previous 90-day period. This significant growth suggests a rising interest in the platform and its content (Figure 38).

Figure 38. Variation in the Number of Visitors Over 90 Days

The traffic trend shows consistent daily fluctuations, with notable peaks around mid-June and again in late July, when visits approached 150 per day. These spikes may reflect periods of targeted outreach, publication of new content, or increased visibility through external channels (e.g., events or social media). Despite some natural variation, the overall pattern indicates a positive trajectory in audience engagement. This highlights the importance of continuing efforts in content updates, dissemination strategies, and user experience improvements to maintain and build upon this momentum.

Figure 39. Evolution of Impressions, Clicks, and Unique Visitors

Over the analyzed period (Figure 39), the website saw a significant increase in its visibility through search engines. A total of 55,000 impressions were recorded — a remarkable 244.4% increase compared to the previous period. This sharp growth suggests that the site is ranking more frequently in search results, likely due to improved content visibility, SEO efforts, or increased interest in related topics. The number of clicks rose

to 1.9K, reflecting a 47.3% increase. This indicates not only better exposure but also improved user engagement — more people are clicking through to explore the content. Similarly, the number of unique visitors via search also reached 1.9K, up by 57.9%, reinforcing the trend of growing organic traffic. The solid upward curve of the current period (solid line) compared to the previous one (dotted line) across all metrics highlights the effectiveness of recent updates or outreach strategies. It also shows a consistent performance pattern, with multiple peaks in engagement during June and July — possibly linked to specific content launches or campaigns. These results emphasize the importance of maintaining an active and optimized presence online, and they provide a strong foundation for continued improvement in both visibility and user interaction.

Título	Visualizações de páginas	Sessões	Taxa de engajamento	Duração da sessão
1. Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture at the University of São Paulo (CCARBON/USP) - University of São Paulo	1.503	1.366	86,61%	1 min 43 s
2. Centro de Estudos de Carbono em Agricultura Tropical (CCARBON/USP) - Universidade de São Paulo	1.137	980	70,21%	2 min 13 s
3. Our Mission - Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture at the University of São Paulo (CCARBON/USP)	485	352	89,7%	1 min 50 s
4. Biochar: Um Potencial Sustentável para Mitigação e Adaptação às Mudanças Climáticas na Agricultura e Pecuária - Centro de Estudos de Carbono em Agricultura Tropical (CCARBON/USP)	424	467	50,54%	2 min 42 s
5. Research - Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture at the University of São Paulo (CCARBON/USP)	424	370	85,68%	1 min 46 s
6. Dissemination - Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture at the University of São Paulo (CCARBON/USP)	344	281	86,48%	2 min 4 s
7. News - Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture at the University of São Paulo (CCARBON/USP)	313	298	94,95%	1 min 42 s
8. Nossa missão - Centro de Estudos de Carbono em Agricultura Tropical (CCARBON/USP)	255	249	81,57%	3 min
9. Pesquisa - Centro de Estudos de Carbono em Agricultura Tropical (CCARBON/USP)	224	209	89%	2 min 4 s
10. Contact Us - Center for Carbon Research in Tropical Agriculture at the University of São Paulo (CCARBON/USP)	181	146	93,15%	1 min 32 s

Figure 40. Performance of Website Pages

Figure 40 presents the website's top-performing pages in terms of page views, sessions, engagement rate, and average session duration. The homepage in English leads with 1,503 page views and 1,366 sessions, followed by the Portuguese homepage with 1,137 views and 980 sessions — highlighting a balanced interest from both international and national audiences. Pages with particularly high engagement rates include the "News" section (94.95%), "Contact Us" (93.15%), and the "Research" section (85.68%). These values suggest that users are not only visiting but interacting meaningfully with this content. The "Dissemination" and "Pesquisa" (Portuguese Research) pages also show strong engagement above 85%. Regarding session duration, users spent the most time on the "Nossa missão" page (3 minutes), followed by "Dissemination" (2 min 44 s) and "Pesquisa" (2 min 4 s). These metrics suggest users are deeply engaging with content that explains the Center's purpose and research structure. Interestingly, the biochar article, despite having relatively high page views (424) and long average duration (2 min 42 s), shows a lower engagement rate (50.54%). This may indicate the need to improve layout, interactivity, or clarity to maintain user attention. Overall, this analysis confirms that mission-driven content and dynamic updates (like news and research) are key drivers of user engagement and interest.

The traffic source of a website through different source channels can be represented based on Analytics data. It shows how users reach the page, categorizing visits into types such as organic search, direct access, social media, referrals from other websites, and other sources. Analyzing this data helps us to understand which channels

are most effective in attracting visitors and which can be improved to enhance the overall performance of the site (Figure 41)

Figure 41. Traffic distribution by channel

The traffic source of a website through different source channels can be represented based on Analytics data. It shows how users reach the page, categorizing visits into types such as organic search, direct access, social media, referrals from other websites, and other sources. Analyzing this data helps to understand which channels are most effective in attracting visitors and which can be improved to enhance the overall performance of the site (Fig. 4). The chart shown in Figure 41 presents the distribution of website traffic by channel. The majority of access (54.9%) comes from organic search, indicating strong SEO performance and effective positioning on search engines. Direct traffic accounts for 29.5% of visits, suggesting that a significant portion of users are already familiar with the site and returns directly, a sign of brand recognition and user loyalty. Referral traffic represents 8.4%, which may reflect collaborations with external websites or mentions in other platforms. Organic social traffic makes up 6.5% of visits, suggesting that there is still room to grow through improved social media engagement strategies. A very small percentage is classified as Other, indicating that the vast majority of traffic sources are clearly identified and properly categorized. These results reinforce the importance of maintaining strong search engine visibility, while also pointing to opportunities for growth through social media presence and strategic partnerships to increase referral traffic.

The evolution of website sessions over time, segmented by different traffic channels, is shown in the line graph (Figure 42). The data illustrates significant fluctuations in visits, with noticeable traffic peaks occurring from mid-June to early

August. The most pronounced spike appears in early August, indicating possible engagement related to specific content or events.

Figure 42. Evolution of sessions by channel over time

Organic Search remains the primary source of traffic, showing frequent peaks and consistent performance over time. This confirms the site’s strong SEO visibility and ongoing discovery through search engines. Direct traffic also shows a stable presence, often accompanying organic spikes, which suggests a recurring visitor base familiar with the site. Traffic from Referral and Organic Social channels continues to represent a smaller but steady portion of total sessions. The Unassigned category remains minimal, indicating that most traffic sources are correctly classified. Overall, the traffic pattern highlights the importance of maintaining strong SEO strategies and producing engaging content that aligns with key peaks. Moving forward, actions such as enhancing social media strategies and expanding partnerships to increase referral traffic could be beneficial for diversifying and growing the site’s audience.

Sessões por Origem da campanha manual da sessão

ORIGEM DA CAMPANHA MANUAL...	SESSÕES	
google	2,7 mil	↑ 189,3%
linkedin.com	395	↑ 226,4%
bing	364	↑ 230,9%
chatgpt.com	153	↑ 240,0%
linktr.ee	109	↑ 230,3%
br.search.yahoo.com	95	↑ 187,9%
statics.teams.cdn.office.net	61	↑ 144,0%

Fig. 43. Source of sessions by manual campaign

Figure 43 shows the main sources of website sessions from manually tagged campaigns. Google remains the leading source by a wide margin, with 2.7K sessions, reflecting the effectiveness of SEO strategies and/or search engine presence. In second place is LinkedIn, with 395 sessions, indicating that professional networking and targeted outreach on this platform are contributing significantly to site visibility. Bing also shows solid performance, with 364 sessions, followed by chatgpt.com with 153 sessions — a noteworthy source that may reflect AI-generated content sharing or link usage. Linktr.ee, likely associated with Instagram or other social media bios, contributed to 109 sessions, reinforcing the impact of social-driven traffic. Other sources include Yahoo Search (95 sessions) and Microsoft Teams-related links (61 sessions), suggesting sporadic yet relevant access from shared internal or organizational content. The data confirms that search engines and professional/social platforms continue to drive most of the traffic. The strong growth across all sources (over 140% increase in each) highlights the positive momentum of visibility efforts. Additionally, the increasing traffic from alternative search engines and platforms like Bing, Yahoo, and ChatGPT points to new opportunities to diversify dissemination strategies and reach wider audiences.

Figure 44. Active users by country

Figure 44 shows the distribution of active users by country. Brazil continues to be the primary source of traffic, with approximately 2.5K users and a growth of 70.3%, confirming a strong local engagement likely driven by regionally targeted strategies or content relevance. The United States ranks second, with 245 active users and a 35.4% increase, showing significant interest from North America. Other countries with notable user activity include the United Kingdom (48 users), France (46), Netherlands (36), Germany (35), and Ireland (30). Most of these countries also recorded substantial growth, especially Germany (+169%) and Ireland (+130%). This geographic diversity highlights the platform's expanding international reach, indicating the potential to further adapt communication strategies and content to engage a broader, global audience.

Figure 45. Active users by language

Figure 45 shows the distribution of active users by language. Portuguese is the predominant language, with nearly 2.5K users, reflecting the platform's strong engagement with Brazilian audiences. English appears as the second most common language, with close to 900 users, reinforcing the effectiveness of bilingual content strategies. Other languages such as Spanish, French, Chinese, German, and Dutch show lower but noteworthy activity levels, indicating growing international interest. These insights highlight the importance of maintaining strong communication in both Portuguese and English, while also identifying opportunities for audience growth through localization efforts and targeted multilingual content.

Creation of a Bilingual Website

Since its launch, the CCARBON/USP website was initially available only in English. However, since March 2025, it has been available in both English and Portuguese. This update was implemented to better serve the Brazilian audience, which represents the majority of page visitors. Additionally, with the launch of Educarbon — an initiative aimed at engaging audiences with diverse educational backgrounds, including children, youth, and rural producers — the availability of content in Portuguese became essential.

Content Production for the Website

So far, twenty-five texts produced by the CCARBON/USP dissemination team have been published on the center's website. These include a description of the center and the beginning of its dissemination activities, eight news articles featuring the center's researchers, thirteen articles presenting research results in accessible language, and four highlighting commemorative environmental dates related to CCARBON/USP's research areas (Table 3).

Table 3. Nature of the content published on the website and access link.

Nature of the content	Link for access
Description of the center	https://ccarbon.usp.br/welcome-to-the-center-for-carbon-research-in-tropical-agriculture-at-the-university-of-sao-paulo-ccarbon-usp/
News	https://ccarbon.usp.br/ccarbon-usp-and-fundacao-florestal-join-forces-to-strengthen-the-integrated-mangrove-management-program/
News	CCARBON/USP stands out in USP's Excellence Award for Emerging Research Leaders
News	https://ccarbon.usp.br/usp-inaugurates-ccarbons-administrative-center-at-esalq-with-the-presence-of-authorities-and-sector-leaders/
News	https://ccarbon.usp.br/ccarbon-usp-makes-its-presence-felt-at-cop29-with-leadership-representation-in-agricultural-sustainability/
News	https://ccarbon.usp.br/ccarbon-usp-director-receives-sustainability-award-from-abag/
News	https://ccarbon.usp.br/brazil-and-france-working-together-for-a-more-sustainable-and-climate-resilient-agriculture/
News	https://ccarbon.usp.br/ccarbon-usp-at-g20-agro-directors-discuss-climate-change-strategies-in-food-production/
Article	The Role of the Greenhouse Gas Emissions Inventory in Brazil
Article	https://ccarbon.usp.br/forest-systems-a-nature-based-solution-for-carbon-sequestration/
Article	https://ccarbon.usp.br/the-power-of-soil-microorganisms-in-carbon-sequestration/
Article	https://ccarbon.usp.br/good-practices-for-more-sustainable-livestock-farming/

Article	https://ccarbon.usp.br/biochar-a-sustainable-potential-for-climate-change-mitigation-and-adaptation-in-agriculture-and-livestock/
Article	https://ccarbon.usp.br/integrated-systems-in-agriculture-productivity-and-sustainability/
Article	https://ccarbon.usp.br/technosols-importance-and-potential-in-the-recovery-of-degraded-areas-in-brazil/
Article	https://ccarbon.usp.br/cover-crops-allies-of-climate-resilient-agriculture/
Article	https://ccarbon.usp.br/soil-health-map-of-latin-america-reveals-challenges-and-solutions-for-sustainability/
Article	https://ccarbon.usp.br/sustainable-management-for-methane-emission-reduction-in-rice-cultivation/
Article	https://ccarbon.usp.br/regenerative-agriculture-the-path-to-sustainable-production/
Article	https://ccarbon.usp.br/paris-agreement-a-global-milestone-for-climate-sustainability/
Article	https://ccarbon.usp.br/ccarbon-usp-makes-its-presence-felt-at-cop29-with-leadership-representation-in-agricultural-sustainability/
Commemorative date	Mangroves: Nature-Based Solutions Against the Climate Crisis
Commemorative date	https://ccarbon.usp.br/brazils-national-climate-change-awareness-day-how-can-agriculture-help-us/
Commemorative date	Biodiversity, Climate Change, and Sustainable Agriculture: Challenges and Solutions
Commemorative date	https://ccarbon.usp.br/soils-as-a-climate-solution-discover-the-importance-of-this-resource-in-mitigating-global-emissions/

In addition to the content produced, 60 more news articles from other websites mentioning CCARBON/USP have been shared on the site. These mentions reflect the center's relevance to society and how it has been recognized by other media as a promising institution in promoting sustainable agriculture practices and its importance in addressing global climate challenges. These news articles can be found in the "Public Awareness" section at the following link: <https://ccarbon.usp.br/news/>.

Next steps:

Update of the Dissemination Section on the Website

The creation of a Knowledge Hub on the CCARBON/USP website is strategic for expanding access to and dissemination of the knowledge produced by the center, connecting science, education, and society. The hub will bring together scientific content, educational materials, data, videos, and practical experiences in an accessible and organized manner, targeting diverse audiences — such as researchers, educators, farmers, and decision-makers. As a key innovation, the hub will be interactive, multilingual, and inclusive, also valuing local knowledge and extension outputs. This platform will strengthen knowledge networks, foster the social appropriation of science, and support sustainable actions and policies aligned with CCARBON/USP's objectives.

Update of the Research Section on the Website

The **Research** section of our website currently presents the complex and cross-cutting questions that guide the Center's research lines. However, this page is still under development and will be updated in the next phases of the restructuring of the website. As part of this process, a new layout will be defined to better organize the information from each research area — such as soils, microbiomes, forestry, livestock, among others. The section will also include detailed information about the researchers responsible for each sectoral chain, as well as for each specific research line.

Media Mentions

Between June 2024 and July 2025, CCARBON/USP and its researchers were prominently featured in 52 media appearances across a wide range of national and international outlets. These included major newspapers and news portals such as Jornal da USP, UOL, G1, Gazeta de Piracicaba, Novacana, and Le Monde, as well as specialized platforms like Pesquisa FAPESP, Canal Rural, and EMBRAPA's communication channels. The center's experts also contributed to television, radio, and podcast interviews, including Rádio Jovem Pan, Planeta Campo, and international programs such as the IICA Podcast. The coverage highlighted CCARBON/USP's scientific research, strategic partnerships, and policy engagement on topics such as biochar production, soil health, carbon sequestration, climate change mitigation, and Nature-Based Solutions. In addition, the inauguration of CCARBON/USP's administrative headquarters and the launch of collaborative projects with national and international institutions received significant attention, reinforcing the center's role as a reference in sustainable tropical agriculture and climate resilience. The complete list is below (Table 4).

Table 4. Media Mentions

Date	Media	Representative	Link
26/06/2024	Rádio Jovem Pan	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://youtu.be/nXcT4g01WNA?si=SJzH2wFmLM0VGEw2
15/08/2024	Novacana	João Nunes Carvalho e Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://www.novacana.com/noticias/brasil-pode-tornar-protagonista-producao-biocarvao-estudo-epe-150824
17/08/2024	UOL	João Nunes Carvalho e Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://economia.uol.com.br/noticias/estadao-conteudo/2024/08/17/brasil-pode-se-tornar-protagonista-na-producao-de-biocarvao-mostra-estudo-da-epe.htm
19/08/2024	InvestTakl	João Nunes Carvalho e Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://investalk.bb.com.br/noticias/sustentabilidade/brasil-pode-se-tornar-protagonista-na-producao-de-biocarvao-mostra-estudo-da-epe
04/09/2024	Pesquisa FAPESP(site)	Maurício Cherubin	https://revistapesquisa.fapesp.br/boas-praticas-produtivas-podem-reduzir-emissoes-de-carbono-no-campo/
04/09/2024	Pesquisa FAPESP(pdf)	Maurício Cherubin	https://revistapesquisa.fapesp.br/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/070-073_carbono-agric_343.pdf
11/09/2024	Informativo ESALQNET	Tiago Osório Ferreira	https://www.esalq.usp.br/boletim/note/10809
04/10/2024	Site EPE	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://www.epe.gov.br/pt/publicacoes-dados-abertos/publicacoes/biocarvao-biochar-produto-para-mitigar-as-mudancas-climaticas-e-fortalecer-a-agricultura-regenerativa-na-producao-de-biocombustiveis
11/10/2024	Pesquisa FAPESP	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	Carlos Eduardo Cerri : Revista Pesquisa Fapesp
24/10/2024	EMBRAPA	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://www.embrapa.br/busca-de-noticias/-/noticia/94344565/embrapa-usp-e-fgv-assinam-acordo-de-cooperacao-com-foco-em-adaptacao-e-mitigacao-na-agricultura
25/10/2024	Agro +	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://youtu.be/T6LOukuELoQ?si=6c4lAvBgtpj56LEI

12/11/2024	Site Esalq	Equipe CCARBON/USP	https://www.esalq.usp.br/banco-de-noticias/brasil-e-fran%C3%A7a-em-prol-de-uma-agricultura-mais-sustent%C3%A1vel-e-resiliente-%C3%A0s
19/11/2024	Site Esalq	Cerri e Cherubin	https://www.esalq.usp.br/banco-de-noticias/expans%C3%A3o-de-pr%C3%A1ticas-sustent%C3%A1veis-sequestra-carbono-e-pode-compensar-emiss%C3%A3o-de
23/11/2024	G1	Cerri e Cherubin	https://g1.globo.com/sp/piracicaba-regiao/noticia/2024/11/23/estudo-traca-potencial-da-america-para-usar-agropecuaria-sustentavel-para-reduzir-aquecimento-global.ghtml?utm_source=share-universal&utm_medium=share-bar-app&utm_campaign=materias
25/11/2024	Pesquisa FAPESP	Maurício Cherubin	https://agencia.fapesp.br/livro-apresenta-os-beneficios-das-plantas-de-cobertura-aos-sistemas-agricolas/53377
27/11/2024	Jornal Hoje - Globoplay	Maurício Cherubin	https://globoplay.globo.com/v/13134616/
03/12/2024	Esalq Notícias	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mg-riGrYwVQ
09/12/2024	Pesquisa FAPESP	Cerri e Alleoni	https://agencia.fapesp.br/garimpos-ilegais-de-ouro-podem-emitir-35-toneladas-de-carbono-por-hectare-e-concentrar-mercúrio-no-solo/53510
12/12/2024	Secretaria do Desenvolvimento Rural RS	Maurício Cherubin	https://sdr.rs.gov.br/projetos-de-inovacao-agricola-e-sustentabilidade-sao-foco-de-visita-tecnica-da-sdr-e-emater-rs-ascar-em-piracicaba
12/12/2024	Emater RS	Maurício Cherubin	https://www.emater.tche.br/site/noticias/detalhe-noticia.php?id=37188
06/01/2025	Le Monde	Maurício Cherubin	https://www.lemonde.fr/planete/article/2025/01/06/le-dereglement-climatique-fait-grimper-le-cours-du-cafe-bresilien_6484727_3244.html

09/01/2025	Capital Reset UOL	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://capitalreset.uol.com.br/agronegocio/os-cientistas-que-estao-medindo-a-real-pegada-de-carbono-do-agro/
27/01/2025	Pesquisa FAPESP	Cerri e Cherubin	https://agencia.fapesp.br/estudo-avalia-como-praticas-sustentaveis-de-manejo-agropecuaria-nas-americas-auxiliam-sequestro-de-co2/53771
29/01/2025	EBC - entrevista	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://radios.ebc.com.br/brasil-rural/2025/01/manejo-sustentavel-no-setor-agropecuaria-auxilia-o-sequestro-de-co2
05/02/2025	Planeta Campo - entrevista	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://planetacampo.canalrural.com.br/noticias/como-as-boas-praticas-agricolas-podem-aumentar-o-sequestro-de-carbono-e-combater-as-mudancas-climaticas/
12/02/2025	Rádio Jovem Pan	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://www.youtube.com/live/GeJoUiy74MI?si=PwPwZlc4Idp2m6sp&t=2419
26/02/2025	Indigo - Podcast Minuto Agro	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://creators.spotify.com/pod/show/indigo-brasil/episodes/Minuto-Agro--Ep-35-Estratgias-para-lidar-com-as-mudanas-climaticas-e2vdf2
27/02/2025	G1	Maurício Cherubin	https://g1.globo.com/sp/piracicaba-regiao/noticia/2025/02/27/com-influencia-de-desmatamento-e-mudancas-climaticas-38percent-dos-solos-da-america-latina-e-caribe-estao-degradados-diz-estudo.ghtml
26/02/2025	Site Esalq	Maurício Cherubin	https://www.esalq.usp.br/banco-de-noticias/mapa-de-sa%C3%BAde-do-solo-na-am%C3%A9rica-latina-e-caribe-alerta-para-pol%C3%ADticas-p%C3%BAblicas-e
27/02/2025	Cana Online	Maurício Cherubin	https://www.canaonline.com.br/conteudo/mapa-de-saude-do-solo-na-america-latina-e-caribe-alerta-para-politicas-publicas-e-sustentabilidade-ambiental.html

01/03/2025	Revista Plant Project - Prof. Cherubin fala do CCARBON/USP da pág. 67 a 73	Maurício Cherubin	https://plantproject.com.br/revistas-digital/
03/03/2025	Podcast IICA	Cerri e Cherubin	https://open.spotify.com/episode/7oS LbIrq0CbFAvhOZBGKmm?si=_Vto GulPRIK8p94SY4aPXg&context=spotify%3Ashow%3A7FSviiexXaycN6sKr1al1K
17/03/2025	Pesquisa FAPESP	Maurício Cherubin	https://agencia.fapesp.br/artigo-apresenta-o-primeiro-mapa-de-saude-do-solo-da-america-latina-e-caribe/54189
17/03/2025	Jornal USP	Maurício Cherubin	https://jornal.usp.br/atualidades/america-latina-e-caribe-possuem-altas-taxas-de-degradacao-do-solo/
21/03/2025	Jornal USP	Maurício Cherubin	https://jornal.usp.br/ciencias/pesquisa-pioneira-em-culturas-de-cobertura-abre-portas-para-agricultura-mais-sustentavel-no-brasil/
03/04/2025	LinkedIn EMBRAPA	Maurício Cherubin	https://www.linkedin.com/company/embrapa-meio-ambiente/posts/?feedView=all
03/04/2025	Canal Youtube Embrapa Meio Ambiente	Maurício Cherubin	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=n9tJdfHGhCw
20/05/2025	Site EMBRAPA	Maurício Cherubin	https://www.embrapa.br/busca-de-noticias/-/noticia/100598875/equipe-do-procarbono-representa-o-brasil-em-evento-sobre-agricultura-regenerativa-e-descarbonizacao-nos-eua
06/06/2025	Jornal da USP	CCARBON/USP	https://jornal.usp.br/institucional/reitoria-inaugura-nucleo-administrativo-do-centro-de-estudos-de-carbono-no-campus-de-piracicaba/
06/06/2025	Viletim	CCARBON/USP	https://www.viletim.com.br/p/centro-sediado-na-esalq-reune-pesquisa
06/06/2025	Site Esalq	CCARBON/USP	https://www.esalq.usp.br/banco-de-noticias/usp-inaugura-sede-do-ccarbon-centro-voltado-%C3%A0-

			agricultura-tropical-sustent%C3%A1vel
06/07/2025	Gazeta de Piracicaba	CCARBON/USP	Impresso
09/06/2025	Instagram TV USP	CCARBON/USP	https://www.instagram.com/reel/DKrNF7I8Jx/?igsh=MXhleTM5OWxucGI4dg==
11/06/2025	SBCS	CCARBON/USP	https://www.sbcs.org.br/2025/06/11/4683/
11/06/2025	Instagram SBCS	CCARBON/USP	https://www.instagram.com/p/DKxXVUtx_hS/?igsh=MTF5M2dtOWh0NW9xZg==
27/06/2025	Jornal USP	CCARBON/USP	https://jornal.usp.br/institucional/o-centro-foi-criado-para-ajudar-o-brasil-a-atingir-suas-metas-internacionais-em-relacao-as-mudancas-climaticas/
30/06/2025	Site Esalq	Fabio Marin	https://www.esalq.usp.br/banco-de-noticias/como-tornar-agricultura-mais-eficiente-diante-das-mudan%C3%A7as-clim%C3%A1ticas
11/06/2025	Site Fundação Florestal	CCARBON/USP	https://fflorestal.sp.gov.br/2025/06/manguezais-de-sao-paulo-serao-analisados-em-projeto-pioneiro-para-inventario-de-carbono-azul-e-elementos-toxicos/
01/07/2025	Jornal USP	Maurício Cherubin	https://jornal.usp.br/radio-usp/plantio-direto-e-rotacao-de-culturas-criam-solos-mais-resilientes-e-produtivos-frente-as-mudancas-climaticas/
07/07/2025	Fórum “Rumo à COP30: O Agronegócio e as Mudanças Climáticas”, promovido pela ABAG	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/abag-brasil_a-agropecu%C3%A1ria-pode-ser-um-agente-de-transforma%C3%A7%C3%A3o-activity-7343345111671496705-2t0c?utm_medium=ios_app&rcm=ACoAABmVqrwBPzSBQfCbqxzO9Ch2IziYTlPkCUg&utm_source=social_share_send&utm_campaign=whatsapp

24/07/2025	Pesquisa FAPESP	Tiago Osório Ferreira	https://agencia.fapesp.br/oxidos-de-ferro-em-solos-de-manguezais-impulsionam-o-sequestro-de-carbono/55382
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Scientific Representation and Public Awareness Initiatives

Over the past year, CCARBON/USP's directors and researchers have actively participated in 34 national and international events beyond those organized by the center itself. These included scientific conferences, public workshops, policy dialogues, and academic symposiums focused on climate change, sustainable agriculture, and environmental education. This active engagement has played a key role in strengthening the visibility of CCARBON/USP's mission, fostering scientific exchange, and building strategic collaborations. Moreover, participation in these external events has been fundamental for advancing public awareness, allowing researchers to share knowledge with broader audiences and contribute to critical conversations on the future of climate and land use in tropical regions (Table 5)

Table 5. CCARBON/USP Representation in Events (2024-2025)

Date	Event	Place	CCARBON/USP Representative	Link - Event
August 23-24, 2024	Workshop - Avançando no monitoramento da recuperação da vegetação nativa no Brasil	Brasília	Pedro H.S. Brancalion	
August 27-28, 2024	Workshop do Programa Mudanças climáticas globais	IG/Unicamp - Campinas, SP	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://fapesp.br/16957/workshop-do-programa-mudancas-climaticas-globais
October, 2024	Apresentação Biochar	EPE - Empresa Brasileira de Pesquisa Energética	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri/João Luiz Nunes Carvalho	https://www.epa.gov.br/pt/publicacoes-dados-abertos/publicacoes/biocarvaobiochar-produto-para-mitigar-as-

				<u>mudancas-climaticas-e-fortalecer-a-agricultura-regenerativa-na-producao-de-biocombustiveis</u>
October, 15-16, 2024	Brazilian Climate and Carbon Conference	São Paulo	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri/Tiago Osório Ferreira	<u>https://nbsbrazilalliance.org/en/bccc-2024/</u>
October, 22-24, 2024	BBEST & IEA Bioenergy Conference 2024	São Paulo	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri/João Luiz Nunes Carvalho	<u>https://bbest-ieabioenergy.org/</u>
October, 24, 2024	Assinatura do Acordo de Cooperação EMBRAPA-CCARBON/USP-FGV	Brasília	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	
November 11-17, 2024	COP29	Baku, Azerbaijão	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	<u>https://cop29.az/en/home</u>
November 26-27, 2024	3° Carbon Science Talks da Bayer	Campinas, SP, Brasil	Carlos Cerri, Cherubin, Leidvan, Cimélio Bayer	
December 02, 2024	Visit-Chinese Academy of Agricultural Science	Esalq, Piracicaba, Brasil	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	<u>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mg-riGrYwVQ</u>
December 12, 2024	Visit-Delegation from Rio Grande do Sul	Esalq, Piracicaba, Brasil	Maurício Roberto Cherubin	
December 19-21, 2024	30th Indian Convention of Food Scientists and Technologists	Centre of Excellence, Nerul, Navi Mumbai	Suzana C. S. Lannes	<u>https://www.icfst.org/</u>
January 09, 2025	International Research Center	CNRS - Paris	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	

				259702577488/ websitePage:fl d118c7-c93f- 4bf1-a42b- ffdb54281a83
May 14, 2025	Visit - Delegation from Goiás	Piracicaba, SP (ESALQ)	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	
May 20, 2025	Agro Sea Forum	Rio de Janeiro	Adibe Luiz Abdalla	https://www.agro- o- sea.com/evento s
June 3, 2025	Agrocarbon Thematic Chamber	Brasília	Heitor Cantarella	
June 4, 2025	Inter-American Development Bank (IDB) Representation in Brasília	Brasília	Eduardo Bastos	
June 6, 2025	Inauguração da Sede Administrativa do CCARBON/USP	Piracicaba, SP (ESALQ)	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	
June 6, 2025	Visit to Legislative School Council of Piracicaba	Piracicaba	Nayana Alves Pereira	
June 9- 11, 2025	2nd Workshop on the Use of Drones for Monitoring	Brasília	Paulo Guilherme Molin	
June 18, 2025	Fórum Futuro do Agro	São Paulo	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://www.yo utube.com/watc h?v=NE2- CSb5mbE
June 27,2025	Award Ceremony for USP's Excellence	São Paulo	Maurício Roberto Cherubin	https://prpi.usp. br/pesquisa/pre mios/premios- excelencia- para-novas- liderancas-em- pesquisa-na- usp/
July 7, 2025	Visit - INRAE delegation (French National Research	Piracicaba, SP (CCARBON/US P)	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	

	Institute for Agriculture)			
July 14, 2025	Visit - Delegation from China - (SDAU)	Piracicaba, SP (ESALQ)	Jessica Suarez Campoli	
August 5, 2025	XXIX Brasileiro de Fruticultura	Campinas, SP, Brasil	Carlos Eduardo Pellegrino Cerri	https://cbfruticultura.com.br/

6. CONTRIBUTION OF CCARBON/USP TO SOCIETY AND FOR ACHIEVING THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS (SDGs)

The CCARBON representatives are actively promoting and participating in actions that directly impact society on municipal, state, national and international levels. The general aim is to foster the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in the agricultural sector, adoption of sustainable management practices, and build resilience to climate impacts. CCARBON's activities involve raising awareness, educating the public and policymakers, and collaborating with organizations and governments at different levels (from local to global) to influence decision-making and accelerate the transition to a sustainable, low-carbon future agriculture (Figure 46).

Figure 46. CCARBON's actions in different levels of society.

The highlights include: i) at the municipal level (Parliamentary Front to combat the climate crisis in Piracicaba, Piracicaba Municipal Environmental Council); ii) at the state level (State Council on Climate Change); iii) at the national level (National Program for the Conversion of Degraded Pastures, Sustainable Agroculture Thematic Chamber, ABC+: Brazilian Agricultural Program for Low Carbon Emission, National Agency of Petroleum, Natural Gas, and Biofuels National Intelligence Agency, Ecosystem Services/Forest Management/Decision Making, Brazil's NDC, MonitorAgro Alliance, National Climate Plan for adaptation and mitigation) and at the international level (IICA, FAO, CIRCASA, COP30).

CCARBON's activities also play a central role in achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as it provides the knowledge, innovation, and evidence-based solutions needed to address global challenges (Figure 47). At CCARBON/USP, research on soil carbon, biodiversity, sustainable agriculture, and low-carbon technologies contributes directly to climate change mitigation while also generating social and economic benefits. By integrating cutting-edge science with practical applications, the center positions itself as a key actor in advancing the 2030 Agenda and ensuring that sustainability transitions are grounded in robust scientific evidence.

Figure 47. CCARBON/USP's contribution to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through its research, innovation, and dissemination activities.

Strong and direct links are established with environmental SDGs such as Zero Hunger (SDG 2), Quality Education (SDG 4), Affordable and Clean Energy (SDG 7), Climate Action (SDG 13), and Life on Land (SDG 15). These reflect the core mission of the center in promoting soil health, biodiversity, sustainable agricultural practices, and low-carbon development pathways.

In addition to these direct connections, CCARBON/USP also contributes indirectly to a broader set of goals. By fostering innovation in integrated production systems, advancing sustainable cities and communities, and improving responsible consumption and production, the research strengthens SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and SDG 14 (Life Below Water). These impacts extend beyond environmental gains, supporting social and economic development while reinforcing resilience in food systems and rural livelihoods.

Other SDGs, such as SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being), SDG 5 (Gender Equality), and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), currently show weaker or more indirect links, but they remain important areas for future engagement. Likewise, opportunities for broader cooperation are found in SDG 16 (Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions) and SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals), which emphasize governance and partnerships. Altogether, the figure demonstrates that CCARBON/USP's initiatives are not isolated efforts but are deeply interconnected with the 2030 Agenda, positioning the center as a catalyst for integrated solutions that combine climate mitigation, innovation, and social well-being.

7. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In its second year of operation, CCARBON/USP has consolidated its role as a reference center in tropical agriculture, advancing research, innovation, and dissemination activities. The scientific production achieved, with dozens of high-impact publications, theses and dissertations defended, and the training of new researchers, demonstrates the center's ability to generate knowledge and solutions aligned with global sustainability challenges. The inauguration of its administrative headquarters at ESALQ/USP further strengthened institutional identity and capacity to coordinate strategic initiatives.

The integration of research with innovation and dissemination has been a distinguishing feature of CCARBON/USP. Strategic partnerships with the private sector, public agencies, and international organizations have expanded the reach of its activities, ensuring that scientific results translate into technological innovations, policy support, and capacity-building actions. Dissemination efforts—ranging from documentaries and podcasts to international advocacy and teacher training programs—have contributed to amplifying CCARBON/USP's impact beyond academia, engaging society in the transition to low-carbon agriculture.

Looking ahead, the Center reaffirms its commitment to generating science-based solutions for climate change mitigation and sustainable tropical agriculture. By continuing to expand collaborative networks, strengthen innovation ecosystems, and enhance dissemination strategies, CCARBON/USP aims to maximize its scientific and societal contributions. The progress made so far provides a solid foundation for the next period, in which the Center will deepen its research, foster new partnerships, and broaden its role in influencing sustainable development agendas at national and international levels.